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Commodification and Commercialisation of the Gospel in the 21st Century Church: The Nigerian Experience

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Abstract

The contemporary Nigeria churches have become money spinning ventures among ministers of God. Churches are becoming easy sources of financial gains where unsuspecting members are often exploited by those who are responsible for their spiritual nurturing. The Church is expected to be a refuge of comfort for the Christians in time of trouble and turbulent moments. It is rather unfortunate to observe that the Church has become an avenue for buying and selling of spiritual products, where miracles are commercialized, where money are being paid before you can receive your “blessings” or be prayed for by the so-called “men of God.” It is disheartening to say the least that ministers of God have commoditized and successfully commercialized the gospel by employing various means of marketing to advertise, brand and package gospel as a consumer or spiritual product to be sold and bought before life-challenges can be tackled. Sales of books and other spiritual items are common practices in the church today. The Church has become a place where sacred objects like rosary, rings, scapular, handkerchiefs, anointing oil, holy water are being commoditized and commercialized for material gains by “the men of God.” The intention of the paper is to examine how some charismatic ministers have shaped the religious-business environment and how their actions have impacted the genuineness of Christian

teachings in the contemporary Nigerian society. The paper also adopted qualitative method of research. The work concluded that Christianity should be a source of lifting burden rather than means of exploitation as being witnessed in Nigerian churches today. The paper recommended that ministers of God should adhere strictly to the instruction stated in Matthew, “freely you received, freely shall you give.”

Keywords: Commodification, Commercialization, Gospel, Church, Church Commercialization

Introduction

Churches in the contemporary Nigerian society are becoming money spinning venture owing get-rich syndrome and unhealthy competition among them. It has become a popular saying among Nigerians that one of the easiest ways of making it apart from being a politician and footballer is to establish a church and steady flow of income is assured. Unfortunately, a good number of these churches can be regarded as centres for exploitation and manipulation of innocent and desperate church members searching for miracles and answers to prayers.

It is glaring that a lot of church leaders in modern day Nigerian churches do merchandize the gospel for economic gains. They have succeeded in presenting the gospel in a deceitful way in their attempt to defraud and manipulate their members. Nwadiolor and Umeanolue (2013:56) noted that: Materialistic gospel message entered into Nigeria through the several visiting American materialistic gospel preachers and through their books, messages, magazines, pamphlets and radio programmes.... It is pertinent to say that commercialization and commodification of the gospel in Nigeria is characterized by increased abject poverty and other social vices like unemployment, armed robbery, bad leadership, kidnapping and a few others. Members of these commercialized churches are usually the poor, who want a way out of the level and who desired instant blessings on one hand and on the other hands are members who seek way of sustaining their wealth and who are also on the look-out for protection (Clarke, 2006: 15). One of the teachings of commercial churches is that financial breakthrough is a sign of God’s favour. Such teachings emphasis that God will make everyone materially rich. Thus, the best way of claiming these riches is to give to the church. By their actions, the ministers of God have turned the free gift of God to money-spinning venture through their commercialization

of consultation fees for prayers rendered on their behalf and the collecting of brown envelopes for prophetic offering.

Further scenarios that depict commercialization and commodification of the gospel can be illustrated fully “when adherents of the Christian faith pay for spiritual objects like candles, anointing oil, spiritual pen and pencils for success, and a host of others. The so-called “men and women of God” blatantly refused to heed to Jesus’ admonition of “freely you have received, freely you must give (Calvin, 2008:45).” Judging from the foregoing, the intention of this work was to examine the impacts of commercialization and commodification of the gospel on Nigerian Christianity and how the actions of the ministers of God engaging in such practices has continued to affect its growth.

Review of Related Literature

Church Commercialization

The phrase “church commercialization” denotes two things. In the first instance, it means the application of commercial principles in the running of the church or applying business principles to church administration or run it as a business with the goal of making financial gains (Nwanganga, 2015: 24). Secondly, it denotes the manipulation of the church, its services, with implied intensions to exploit members for economic gains (Galgoto, 2014: 47). It can also be described as conducting the church core mandate of soul winning, attending to spiritual and emotional needs of members with the sole aim of benefiting financially (Nwannganga, 2015: 32). Generally, commercialization of church should be conceived as every action, activity of church leaders, pastors, prophets that have economic making connotation.

Church

In the New Testament Greek, the word “church” is referred to as *ecclesia*, meaning an “assembly” (Jegede, 2016: 45). Similarly, in the Greek version of the Old Testament, the word *ecclesia* denoted the “gathering of the people for worship” (2016: 46). In the New Testament, it refers to a local Christian community. It is generally believed among the Christians that God founded the church through the work and deeds of Jesus and this is also sustained by the continual presence and activities of the Holy Spirit. Owing to this understanding, a church is described as a group of believers, associated together, under Christ, for His purpose (Zondervan Pictorial Encyclopedia

2314). However, the New Testament offers metaphors for the church. First, it describes the church as “body of Christ.” Second, the church is related to Christ as branches of a vine. A more intricate and pervasive relationship is implied by this image than by the image of the body. More importantly, it describes the church as the people of God; a description that stresses, on one hand, the continuity of the church with Israel and on the other hand, the church’s potential universality (Barth, 2013: 67).

Commodification

The term “commodification” is defined as treating something that cannot be owned or that everyone has a right to, like a product that can be bought or sold (www.dictionary.com). It refers to the transformation of goods, services, ideas, nature, personal information or people into commodities or objects of trade (Gill, 2008: 69). Therefore, commodification of the gospel means turning all Christian-related beliefs, teachings, symbols, sacred objects into products which can be sold for commercial gains. Thus, in Christianity, a commodity is “something to meet one’s particular needs at an acceptable cost to the person concerned” (Einstein, 2006: 21). People commoditize relationship when it is view as means to satisfy personal desires and agendas. Essien (2010: 6) identifies commodification of religion in faith branding, as a concept reflected in the packaging of religion as a product for purchase mainly using sacred objects and religious artefacts. Commodification, in religious parlance, refers to religious symbols becoming products, objects of consumption readily available in the “supermarket of religion,” in economic life and the media landscape (Ornella, 2013: 13). It is the process of re-contextualization of religious symbols, language and ideas from their original religious context to the media and consumer culture. In this process, religious symbols become commodities, objects of consumption readily available in the “supermarket of religion.” Based on the above, commodification of the gospel means turning church services into money-making activities where congregants have to pay money in order to receive healing or gain favour from God.

Commercialization

According to Wikitionary (en.m.wikitionary), commercialization is defined as the application of “business methodology to something in order to profit, the organization of something in a way intended to make a profit.” In the

same vein, the Oxford Dictionary (1092) describes it as “the process of running something or managing something principally for financial gains. There are two distinct views of the commercialization of the church. The one is a more positive appreciation of the “prosperity gospel” or the gospel of wealth and health, and the other, a more negative perspective that regards it as a practice that only benefits a few and leads to the abuse of followers.

Gospel

The word “gospel” is derived from the Anglo-Saxon term “god-spell,” meaning “good story,” a rendering of the Latin *evangelium* and the Greek *evangelion*, meaning “good news” or “good telling” (Ugwueye, 2002: 34). In the New Testament, the word refers to the announcement that Jesus has brought the reign of God to the world through his life, death and resurrection from the dead. In Christianity, the term “good news” refers to the story of Jesus Christ’s birth, death and eventual resurrection. According to Adelowo (2006: 11), gospel refers to the core doctrines and practices of Christianity. In a narrower sense, gospel means the message of salvation through faith in Jesus Christ. Outside of this application to religion, the word “gospel” is used to describe an idea or rule that is accepted as undoubtedly true. The Christian world in general, readily accepts the definition of the gospel as the good news about Jesus (Agbiji, 2015: 33), while others define Jesus’ offer of salvation through his death on the cross as the good news. Although both definitions are technically correct, yet, they fail to include several important facets of the good news which Jesus revealed to his children through additional scripture. In the context of this paper, gospel is used to imply Christianity and all that it entails including the teachings and practices of the adherents.

Origin of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel

Right from the Old Testament time, prophets like Amos, Micah and Ezekiel were against commercialization of religion. Prophet Amos, in particular, raised his voice in protest against the religious and moral corruption of his day by condemning exploitation and oppression of the poor and needy, corrupt and degenerate religious practices, perversion and corruption of justice and honesty as well as excessive indulgence and flagrant disregard for the law of God (Amos 2:8;5:4;1:5;11:8;4-6;6:12). The negative attitude of prophet Amos towards commercialization and commodification of the gospel

was manifested in the clash between him and Amaziah who refused to acknowledge in any way the divine sources of Amos' prophecies. Rather, he constantly and consistently referred to him as a political agitator. In the view of Ogunkunle (2006: 52), he opined that "the fact that Amaziah and other priests in Israel had commercialized religion is indicated in his derogatory advice to Amos, that he should go to Judah and 'earn' his bread there" (Amos 7:12). In the context of this work, "earning" could simply mean "services rendered and paid for." This therefore implies that to Amaziah and his fellow "professional prophets," religion and the free spiritual gifts of God were to be used for financial gains.

Similarly, Micah in his letters spoke against his listeners for their apostate lifestyle. Among the sins committed by them were perversion of worship practices, empty religious formalism (Amos 6:6-7), oppression of the poor and defenseless (Amos 2:2, 8-9), perversion of justice through bribery and dishonest business practices, idolatry and violence. As clearly stated in Micah 3:11; 6:11, religious leaders were charged of commercialization and commodification of religion because they collected money for religious services they rendered to people. Rather than serving and shepherding the flocks, the false prophets were actively engaged in leading the people astray. They were blinded by material gains they were getting from their innocent followers. To this extent, Shimazome (1998: 181) summed up the selfish attitude of such prophets thus: These leaders were giving the people false hope by telling them they would not be punished by God, that there would be no calamity. If someone paid the false shepherds well, they would pronounce peace on him. In other words, they told a person what he wanted to hear for a price.

Without doubt, these religious leaders were only concerned with their own welfare, their personal gains and comforts at the expense of the nation's welfare. Materialism and inordinate desire to get more was their goal, master and ultimate aim.

The same thing can be said of prophet Ezekiel. He was vehemently against the prophets and prophetesses who were into the business of commodifying and commercializing the gospel of Jesus. It is rather discouraging to know that commercialization of the gospel became more prominent in the New Testament era. It got to its peak even at the time of Jesus' earthly ministry as indicated in Matthew 21:12-13; Mark 11:15-18; and Luke 19:43-46. At a point in his ministry, Jesus expressed his indignation against the people

changing money and selling Doves in the temple. The Jewish temple authorities set up small booths where pilgrims could buy doves to sacrifice and where money could be changed. Those operating the booths were cheating the people and taking large profits for themselves. For this reason, Jesus drove them out and overturned their tables and benches. William (1954: 17) gave more insights into this phenomenon of selling Doves in the temple. Usually, every Jew had to pay a temple of one-half shekel a year. He further stated that the tax had to be paid in one particular coinage which means that the Jews that came from all over the world with all kinds of currencies had their money changed with exorbitant charge. This made the festive period a busy time for the temple authorities who were involved in the business of changing money rather than leading the people in the worship (1954: 23).

It is pertinent to mention that the business of gospel commercialization did not end in the temple or with the false prophets and prophetesses' activities. During the Feast of Passover, Ogunkunle (2006: 45) submitted that selling and buying of Doves became very popular and highly profitable. The organizers of the Feast of Passover strictly advised worshippers and those in attendant to buy doves at the temple stalls, often at exorbitant prices. These Doves could have been easily and cheaply purchased outside the temple, but the temple inspectors would be sure to find-fault or something wrong with them. Judging from the above, the exploitation meted out to the pilgrims by the Jew temple authorities, for their own financial gains, indicated that the pilgrims were not considered as worshippers but as things to be exploited. Jesus condemned this attitude and rebuked the religious leaders for the desecration of God's holy place. These scenarios depict commercialization and commodification of the church, and it should be seen as a violation of religious ethics.

Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel in Nigeria

Weber (1989: 78) accentuated on the influence of religion on economic behavior. He submitted that the "spirit" preaches hard work and this produced discipline and rational pursuit of economic gains. It was believed that long before man was born, he was predestined to either salvation in heaven or condemnation in hell. This brought about anxiety. Thus, to relieve such anxiety, and resist temptation, man only has to exercise self-control and serious labour (Olawole, 2013: 21). To this extent, the church believes

that whether saved or condemned, the faithful must work hard for the glory of God. To them, hard work is a calling from God so as to establish His kingdom on earth. The purpose of hard work was to glorify God and that they should not spend their wealth on worldly pleasures, instead they invested in the preaching of the gospel.

However, in Nigeria today, the church seems to be deviating from this preaching. Churches do not preach hard work. Rather, they lay emphasis on “prosperity preaching.” Self-acclaimed ministers have turned Christianity into a huge business franchise marred by mischief. They carry out this act through various ways and forms. The commodification and manipulation of the gospel is played out in several ways by prosperity-minded gospel preachers. Instead of laying emphasis on dignity of labour and hard work, they have succeeded in twisting and upturning the concept of miracle and tithe that literally means 10% of one’s income. The innocent and unaware congregants are made to believe that once they paid 10%, their income will be doubled. They dwell on biblical portions that read thus, “he who sow sparingly will reap sparingly,” “you cannot sow maize and reap cocoyam,” “with your tithes and offerings you are robbing God,” to commercialize spiritual activities (Olawole, 2013 34). As a way of driving home manipulating intension, they often resort to the use of imprecation as threat (Achor, 2000 28). Among the churches in Nigeria, the use of divination is a common practice. Through this means, the prophets, prophetesses and pastors can predict the future, explain the present, and even uncover the past that is shrouded with mysteries for their “clients” and collect exorbitant fees for the supposedly religious services rendered. In this way, the church becomes a lucrative business venture.

More so, the prosperity preachers have been able to perfect several ways of commercializing the gospel for material gains. One of such ways is through the mounting of big billboards where they display catching and captivating themes of their supposed programmes during which special offerings and donations are collected. Captivating themes like, “*Osan Meta, Oru Meta* meaning literally “three afternoon three nights,” “Power must change hands,” “Fall and die,” and “power must change hands” are few of such themes often used to draw people’s attention to their programmes (Adewole, 2011: 72). A good number of them also print newsletters with exaggerated news and stories mainly to solicit for money. In the church today are vigorous advertisement of crusades and revivals and printed T Shirts

indicating the themes of the crusade are displayed for sales (Abogunrin, 2009: 76). However, some of these miracle healing pastors combined magical power with Christian faith. As such, quiet a lot of these miracles are mere fabrications intended to attract crowds and make money (Asaju, 1989: 91). It is disheartening to observe that commercialization of religion knows no bound in Nigeria. This is because everybody is allowed to self-licensed himself/herself as whatever and as a result, has golden opportunity to fool, deceive, lead or mislead unsuspecting members of the church (Jemiriye, 2012: 10). In the same vein, many gullible members just sink in whatever they are being fed by their religious leaders who simply take advantage of their gullibility and desperation to exploit them and amass wealth for themselves. Advance in communication and information technology have made many churches tech savvy. They use these new tools for further fund raising and managing the money, assets, records and crowds they are able to generate. As income of the church is booming so have opportunities for spending by crass commercialization and new technology (Nwanganga, 2018 28). In some churches in Nigeria, tithe payments are used as determinant factor for promotion of the pastors. The more money generated through tithe payment means the higher such pastors go in the hierarchy of the church. Pastoral visit has been turned into a clinic where people line up and pay consultation fees to see the pastor. Prayers are contracted for a fee which attracts a kind of prayer team to handle the prayer (William, 1954: 221). These materialistic tendencies of most Nigerian churches create a doubt in the minds of people concerning the real purpose of church.

Causes of Church Commercialization and Commodification on Contemporary Nigerian Churches

1. **Poverty:** Poverty has been considered as one of the major factors of church commodification and commercialization in Nigeria. Townsend (2011: 31), poverty is described as lack of opportunity to develop one's abilities and control one's own life owing to economic deprivation. Despite its abundance of human and natural resources, Nigerians still wallow in abject poverty. Speaking of poverty in Nigeria, it has been reported that 69.7% of Nigerians are living below the line of poverty. Over 80 million Nigerians based on the 120 million estimations survive on less than \$1per day. The growing rate of graduates in Nigeria as further increase the tension associated with poverty (The Punch 16). In

the attempt to suffer, many Nigerians find themselves in pastoral work even when it is obvious they did not receive any call from God. This explains the high rate of church commercialization in the contemporary Nigerian churches.

2. ***High Unemployment Rate:*** Unemployment is deemed as the greatest factor to the ever-increasing rate of proliferation. Nigerian streets are littered with churches. In every nook and cranny of the country are found newly established churches. One should not mistake this for spiritual growth of the people and neither should one misinterpret it as high level of spiritual consciousness of an average Nigerian. Rather, it should be attributed to the ever-increasing rate of unemployment being witnessed in the nation. Every year, the education sector keeps churning out graduates without corresponding employment plans for them. Owing to long search for gainful employment, many deserving graduates became frustrated and therefore resorted to pastoral work without receiving the call of God. Their taking to pastoral duties serves as means of livelihood. Some of them that possess oratory and good communication skills open ministries which later metamorphosed into full mega churches across the nation. This ugly situation apparently fans the embers of church commercialization. Although Nigeria is known throughout the world to have the largest number of churches (Jemiriye, 2009: 41), yet it has not positively helped in combating the various nefarious activities bedevilling the nation.
3. ***Poor Remuneration of Ministers:*** Poor remuneration, in this context means inadequate financial means of survival. As a mean of survival, people tend to develop several unethical behaviours or means without proper consideration of its effect on them and the society. The bane of church commercialization and commodification is also linked to the inability of most Nigerian churches to adequately cater for their ministers' welfare, more especially financially and materially. An extensive investigation carried out by Sunday Punch Newspaper (2017) revealed that many of the country's prosperity-preaching, super-rich mega churches pay their pastors poor wages. The Newspaper's findings revealed that a substantial majority of the pastors engaged by these churches, who are polytechnic and university graduates, earn between #25,000 to #45,000 a month. Some of the churches revealed were the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith World

Outreach, Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries, Deeper Christian Life Ministry, Christ Embassy International and Lord Chosen Charismatic Revival Ministries. In the attempt of the ministers in these churches to survive, other forms and ways are being devised and these may be in form of exploitation of church members, monetization of healings and prayers (Maduforo, 2025: 34). A pastor in one of the Redeemed Christian Church of God submitted that: The job of a pastor is a sacrificial one, no doubt, but what we are paid cannot ordinarily sustain us. The money is definitely not enough to meet our needs even with our access to loans and free accommodation provided by the church.

4. ***Inordinate Quest for Financial Benefits:*** Adonu (2019) in an interaction with Ekereoku observed that in Nigerian churches today, the greatest challenge preachers of God are facing is the quest for financial benefits through the spiritual services they are rendering to their congregants. Most of the ministers of God have lost focus on why they are in the ministry and their intention has shifted to material things. Churches, owing to quest for materialistic tendencies of the pastors, have been turned to commercial centres. Crusades are being organized on a daily basis with the primary goal of soliciting for money for personal benefits. The sacred objects have been turned to money spinning ventures through which easy money can be accrued. It must be clearly stated that God is not against having material goods. What God is against is “making material possession the centre of one’s existence.” This had led many ministers of God astray from the ministry entrusted into their hands and some are still being caught in the riptide that can carry them to the sea of worldly concerns.
5. ***Greed:*** Greed is an inappropriate attitude towards things of value, built on the mistaken judgment that “my well-being is tied to the sum of my possessions. Greed goes much further than money. A person can be greedy for money but also for fame, possessions, attention, compliments, gifts and much more (Hill, 2020: 23). In the Bible, the words greed, greedily, greedy, and greediness are always used to describe the selfish motivation of a person. Greed led to eternal condemnation of Gehazi, the servant of Prophet Elisha. Ahab coveted the vineyard of Naboth, and the end result was disastrous. In Nigeria today, commercialization of the church is a growing trend. There are

reported cases of embezzlement among the ministers of God of church funds. In fact, men of God now ask for gratification and charge outrageous amount for ministrations. Ecclesiastical corruption compounds the corruption in the nation, weakens the church and compromises her moral rights to speak against corruption in the nation. According to Monsignor John Aniagwu (2019: 19), Vicar General, Catholic Archdiocese of Lagos Episcopal Vicar, Ikeja Region, he submitted that ministers who are in the habit of commercializing the gospel are doing so at their own peril. In an interview with Moses Lucky Ogadi, Senior Pastor of Christ Elect Pentecostal Assembly (2019: 18), he condemned commercialization and commodification of sacred objects and concluded that churches who are into such acts are making merchandize of gullible persons and at the same time contradicting what Jesus Christ stood for during his earthly ministry.

Effects of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel on Nigerian Churches

- a. ***Exploitation:*** Commercialization and commodification of religious objects has become a common practice among charismatic leaders in Nigerian Christianity. In most cases, religious leaders take advantage of the vulnerability of their members for financial gain (Adabembe, 2024: 10). They mostly accomplish this through various means like ordering their followers to remove all money from their pockets during church services and such practices have drained and left a lot of the members stranded while the ministers enrich themselves at their expense.
- b. ***Distortion of Religious Values:*** It is unfortunate to observe that the binding principles of Christian teaching on love, brotherliness, compassion, fellowship, stewardship, peace and righteousness have been sacrificed on the altar of commercialization of the gospel by those saddled with the responsibility. Ministers of God in Nigerian churches have succeeded in converting revered customs into things that can be bought with money owing to their greed and excessive desire for money (Lovemore 2016: 27). The perversion of Christian principles has caused some to prioritize financial benefit over their overall spiritual growth.
- c. ***Conflict of Interest:*** Religious institutions now face conflict of interest due to commercialization of the gospel. In Nigerian churches today are

ministers of the gospel who put financial gain ahead of the spiritual growth of their churches and members. Therefore, they compromise the integrity of religious teachings in their pursuit of profit (Adabembe, 2024:11, 13).

Ways Out of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel on Nigerian Churches

In order to curb the excess of religious institutions, especially the nefarious activities of some men of God, and the commercialization of the gospel in Nigeria, it is high time the instituted authority started to regulate and license church leaders. This can be done by putting on ground strict laws against commercialization of religion and put a stop to abuse of people's believe system.

It is also expected of each church in Nigeria to pay attention to the welfare of her ministers. This is one of the ways they can be motivated to stick to their divine mandate, that is, to preach the gospel and direct souls to salvation and kingdom of God. When ministers of God have zero worries, commercialization of the gospel becomes a thing of the past. At this point, exhibiting their spiritual potentials for the upliftment of the church and individual church members becomes a matter of necessity.

Unemployment and poverty are two bedfellows that are very difficult to terminate. Unemployment gives room for poverty; the two social vices are major reasons for church commercialization. As a way of combating commercialization and commodification in the church, both government and private institutions should make it a point of duty to create employment opportunities for the teeming graduates. Soft loans can also be made available for those interested to start small scale businesses rather than depending on government jobs that are not forthcoming. This will go a long way in preventing people from dabbling into pastoral duties when it is clear to them that they were not call and neither do they have anything to offer spiritually.

In the attempt to curb commercialization of the gospel, various church associations and organizations (like CAN, PFN, CCN) are expected to wake up to their responsibilities of providing guidance and leadership by speaking and monitoring activities of affiliated churches and members of their religion. This is imperative because they are put in place to maintain religious sanctity and right doctrinal practices among their members. As a

measure of countering commercialization of the gospel, churches found wanting must be strictly placed under sanction as a deterrent for others. The get-rich syndrome is a big challenge among the Nigerian ministers of the gospel. Their inordinate desire for quick money has opened a flood gate for commercialization of the church. They have been able to play on the gullibility of members who desire solutions to one problem or the other. In order to prevent further abuse of the free gift of God, there is a strong need for re-orientation of church members. For instance, the fear of witches is a great force that drives people to seek spiritual solutions or deliverance from the spiritualists. Therefore, De-witching the minds of people is important to combating any attempt to commercialize the free gift. Sometimes, the fears of witches are unfounded and unnecessary. Prosperity-preaching pastors simply capitalize on the unsafe and fearful situation of people to trade their religion. It is, thus, essential for church members to develop the power of positive thinking that can drive away witches. By so doing, commercialization and commodification of the gospel will be effectively reduced if not permanently stamped out.

Conclusion

The history of commercialization and commodification of the church is as old as the practice of Christianity itself, if not older than Christianity. Recall that before the disciples were called Christians, commercialization of religion was an on-going practice in the temple among the Israelites and Jesus simply shown his displeasure towards it because the merchants valued it more than the religious activities. In the contemporary time, it has become a money-spinning business, the quickest way of making cool money at the expense of the church members. The implication is that church commercialization runs counter to church's tenets of sacredness, pure, holiness and Jesus' admonition of "freely you have received, freely you must give." The author maintains that God is not against church members giving genuinely to men of God without them demanding for such gratification as doing so will negate Matthew 10:8. Ministers of God should bear in mind that they were called by God to serve. Therefore, God will provide for their needs holistically and there is no need to be in fright mode.

Recommendations

The paper recommended that:

1. It is high time religious practitioners became regulated and licensed by governing authorities in order to curtail their excesses.
2. There is the need for both moral and ethical re-orientation for men of God. The ethical behavior of ministers of God must be in consonant with established conventions and church ethics.
3. They must maintain high level of professionalism in the calling. Professionalism must include a moral philosophy that governs behavior in a formal and systematic way leaving no room for ambiguity or confusion and that focuses on fairness, honesty, integrity, safety and authenticity as well as moral and legal propriety.
4. Church members must be encouraged to develop the power of positive thinking. This will go a long way in helping them combat the fear of uncertainty and also prevent them from becoming easy targets in the hands of prosperity-seeking pastors who are only interested in economic gains and who refer to them as “customers” rather than leading them to salvation.

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**Involvement of Selected Church
Denominations in Drug Abuse Prevention
Among Adolescents in Ede South Local
Government Area, Osun State**

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Abstract

In Nigeria, varying rates of drug abuse among adolescents have been reported. This study therefore investigated into the involvement of the church in adolescent drug abuse so as to curb a furtherance of this social malaise among Nigerian adolescents. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The target population for the study included: members and ministers of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith Church (LFC), Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) and Baptist Church, all in Ede South Local Government Area (ESLGA). A sample size of fifteen respondents was randomly selected from each of the four churches to ensure that the population of the study has an equal chance of being picked which totalled sixty (60) participants in all. The research

instrument used for this research was a questionnaire. Percentage and frequency counts were adopted to analyse the data collected for the study. According to the findings of the study, causes of drug abuse include peer pressure, various malfunctioning familial dynamics, media influence, and so on. The study further established that drug abuse can lead to: addiction, various physical health complications, and so on. Regular workshops and seminars are the various forms of church involvement preventing drug abuse among adolescents. These various programmes of the church are obstructed by stigma and denial, resource constraints, and traditional practices, To address these challenges, programme organizers were counselled to engage in community sensitization efforts and adapt the programmes to the cultural and social context of Ede, Osun State.

Keywords: Drug Abuse, Adolescent, Church Involvement, Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State

Introduction

In Nigeria, varying rates of drug abuse among adolescents have been reported. For instance, in the South-East region, the prevalence rate of any substance use among high school students was 32.9%, with alcohol being the most used substance (with 29.0% of users), and cocaine being the least used (2.1%) (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). In the South-West region, from 15.0% to 69.3% of adolescents were reported using any psychoactive substances, including local substances such as kola nut. These data presentation from a previous study shows an outrageous increased rate of the involvement of adolescents from the South-West in drug abuse. Thus, adolescents from the South-West of Nigeria, especially, those in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State need to be rescued, and the church should be at the forefront of such a rescue mission.

The term "adolescence" originates from the Latin word "*adolescere*" which means "to grow up" or "to nature." It is a phase of life that signifies the transition from childhood to adulthood and involves numerous physical and psychological changes. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), adolescence is a period between the ages of 10-19, characterized by emotional, psychosocial, and behavioural changes, which lead to the transformation from childhood to adulthood.

Currently, approximately one-third of the world's population falls within the age range of 10-24, and four out of five young people reside in developing countries. This percentage is expected to increase to 87% by the year 2020.

Adolescents are the population under study within this age bracket. An adolescent is an individual who has outgrown the social status of a child but has not yet been granted the social and mature privileges of an adult. They are neither a child nor a grown-up. In certain cultures, an individual's maturity is defined by the role they play. Moreover, there are variations in who is considered an adolescent, even within a single culture.

Adolescence is a critical period as it is marked by several physical, psychological, and social changes, and signifies the move from childhood to adulthood. (Olugbenga-Bello; Adebimpe; Abodurin, 2009). Adolescence is a time of experimentation, exploration, curiosity, and identity search which also involves the use and abuse of psychoactive substances. These drugs apply their major effects on the brain, resulting in sedation, encouragement, or changes in mood. Adolescence is a challenging stage of life for most individuals and often marks the onset of many unhealthy behaviours, including drug misuse. (Birhanu, Bisetegn, & Woldeyohannes, 2014). Several factors put adolescents at risk of substance use, including increased adventurous tendencies, peer influences, and risk-taking behaviour (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). Substance use also has negative impacts on families and communities, with costly social, physical, and mental health consequences. (Russell, Simpson, Flannery & Ohannessian, 2019).

According to the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC (2001), a drug is a chemical substance that has an impact on the body or the higher nervous system and is distinct from foodstuff in its ability to influence the structure or function of an organism. As stated by the World Health Organisation (WHO, 1967), drugs can modify the functions of living organisms and may be used for therapeutic or recreational purposes. In the context of biological function, a drug is a substance that possesses the ability to induce chemical actions that result in changes to perceptions, cognition, mood, behaviour, and general physiological processes (Okoye, 2001). It is therefore regarded as a chemical modifier of living tissues that can elicit psychological and behavioural changes, as explained by Nnachi (2007).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines “a drug” as “any substance, solid, liquid or gas that changes the function or structure of the body in some way” while the term substance is “any product that affects the way people feel, think, see, taste, smell, hear, or behave” (UNODC.). The phenomenon

of drug abuse has been characterized as the utilization of any substance to the point of adverse health effects or impairment of societal functioning (Edlin, Golanty, and Brown, 2000). Substance abuse, on the other hand, is a broad term that refers to the use of any substance—illegal drugs, prescription drugs, over-the-counter (OTC) drugs or alcohol—in excessive amounts (Pallavi Suyog Uttekar, & Jasmine Shaikh, 2021). Often, the term “substance use” is preferred, so that all things that affect the way a person feels, thinks, sees, tastes, smells, hears and behaves are included. Thus, glue is a substance used by many street children and methamphetamines are substances used by many young people who go to discos and bars (Pallavi Suyog Uttekar, & Jasmine Shaikh 2021). Drugs commonly implicated in abuse are referred to as drugs of abuse, and their misuse is associated with various issues, especially among young people. Extensive research has shown that alcohol, tobacco, and marijuana are the most frequently abused drugs among adolescents in many societies (Lennox & Cecchini, 2008; Makanjuola, Daramola, & Obembe, 2007).

The consequences of drug abuse are far-reaching and include social vices such as rape, robbery, and sexual promiscuity (World Health Organization, 2003). Lennox and Cecchini (2006) established a strong correlation between drug use and sociability, rebelliousness, and deviant behaviour. The problem of drug abuse is a global epidemic that has continued to spread due to the ease of adopting vices by humans. The World Health Organization estimates that 76.3 million people worldwide suffer from alcohol use disorder (Putul, 2011). By the end of the 20th century, approximately 185 million people globally over the age of 15 years were involved in the use of drugs (WHO, 2017). The reality is that the more the number of people engaging in drug abuse, the more the likelihood of addiction as drug use is the first step to addiction.

Adolescents often depend on various substances such as tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, heroin, alcohol, ephedrine, caffeine, glue, and barbiturates, among others, for their daily activities, including social, educational, political, and moral activities (Oshikoya & Alli, 2006). Dependence and addiction are among the major consequences of drug abuse among adolescents in Nigeria (Oshikoya & Alli, 2006). Experimentation with drugs during adolescence is common, as young people often use drugs for various reasons, such as curiosity, pleasure, stress reduction, or to feel more grown up.

The impact of drug abuse among adolescents has been regarded as a moral decadence. This is because it has caused physical damage to the adolescents and brought shame to society, as they are intentionally and unlawfully using drugs (Eze and Omeje, 1999). Many adolescents are dependent on drugs for their daily activities and cannot function without them. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), drugs such as alcohol and tobacco have caused more road accidents and claimed more lives than any other sickness suffered by mankind. The global drug trafficking industry is on the rise, while international cooperation against drug trafficking is lacking organization and strength (Okeke, 2004). Despite the significant negative consequences of substance abuse on the health and well-being of adolescents, studies continue to report high rates of substance use among this population. Different rates and patterns of substance use have been reported depending on the country where such a study was carried out (Adeloye, Olawole-Isaac, Auta, Dewan, Omoyele, and Ezeigwe, 2019). For instance, in the US, alcohol was reported as the most used substance, with 72.5% of users, followed by cigarettes (46.3%) and marijuana (36.8%) (Feinstein Richter, & Foster, 2012). In Ethiopia, the lifetime prevalence of any substance use was 65.4%, while current substance use among adolescents was 47.9%. Alcohol was the most used drug, with a lifetime and current prevalence of 59% and 40.9%, respectively (Birhanu, Bisetegn, & Woldeyohannes, 2014).

In Nigeria, varying rates have been reported. In the South-East region, for example, the prevalence rate of any substance use among high school students was 32.9%, with alcohol being the most used substance (with 29.0% of users), and cocaine being the least used (2.1%) (Anyanwu, Ibekwe, & Ojinnaka, 2016). In the South-West region, from 15.0% to 69.3% of adolescents were reported using any psychoactive substances, including local substances such as kola nut. Alcohol remains the most consumed substance, followed by cigarettes. However, the pattern seems to be changing, with tramadol being the second most abused substance (Idowu, Aremu, Olumide, & Ogunlaja, 2018).

As the 2018 National Drug Use Survey revealed, in Nigeria at that time there were around 14.3 million drug users of which close to 3 million suffered from a drug use disorder. The World Drug Report further noted that in the last 24 years' cannabis potency had increased by as much as four times in parts of the world, even as the percentage of adolescents who

perceived the drug as harmful fell by as much as 40 per cent, despite evidence that cannabis use is associated with a variety of health and other harms, especially among regular long-term users. Recent research shows that 15-20 percent of drug addicts in Ede are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent (Adeloju, 2021). Drug abuse among youths in Nigeria is now a common phenomenon. Females are not exempt in this evil act. A recent research shows that 15-20 percent of drug addicts are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent, Drug use among youth is one of challenging social problems facing Ede, Osun State, drug abuse has contributed negatively to the social and economic development in all comprising of traders, students, unskilled workers and the unemployed as shown by a retrospective study carried out by NDLEA (Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency).

Drug education pertains to the endeavour of imparting knowledge to individuals residing in a locality where psychoactive substances may be readily accessible and possess a significant impact on the well-being of families, politics, and finances. Its fundamental aim is to educate individuals on the adverse effects of drugs on physical health. Besides contributing to the prevention of substance abuse, drug education plays a pivotal role in offering secure and wholesome resources that advocate healthy living. Additionally, drug education strives to enlighten adolescents on the potential harm associated with all drugs, whether legal or illegal, and elucidates that the drug experience is contingent on multifarious factors, encompassing the individual, the substance, and the environment (Aspen Ridge, 2021).

Adolescent substance utilization continues to be a prominent worry on a global scale, presenting severe health, societal, and monetary impediments. Various establishments, such as academic institutions, households, and faith-based groups, have assumed the responsibility of instructing adolescents about the hazards of drug misuse in response to this predicament. The burden of this study, therefore, is to shed light on the roles of the church in providing drug education to adolescents.

Statement of the Problem

The alarming rate at which adolescents engage in drug abuse is a cause for concern. It is a social menace which has caused several havocs to the society. Despite this, several youths still romance with it. A lot of psychiatric

hospitals in Nigeria are full of youths who are receiving psycho-therapeutic treatment. The percentage of insane youths is greater than that of the old people, due to drug abuse. Some youths are school dropouts, again, due to their involvement in drug and its ill-consequences. Calling attention to the aftermath of menace generally, Dairo (2014) opined that the African man's actions and behaviour must not precipitate calamity for him, his family and for his society at large. Also, due to the same factor, a lot of Nigerian youths have become homeless, wanderers, derelicts, unemployed, rapist, thugs, armed robbers and so on. A lot of young people's lives and property in Nigeria have also been wasted in accident and violence because of drug. Again, for the same reason, youths who should be the hope of their families and the larger society; youths, who should be useful to themselves have killed themselves prematurely. According to a recent research, 15-20 percent of drug addicts are females while males constitute about 50-55 percent. These include traders, students, unskilled workers and the unemployed as shown by a retrospective study carried out by NDLEA (Nigerian Drug Law Enforcement Agency).

Research Methods

This section deliberates upon the intricacies of the research design, delineates the precise population of interest in the study, explicates the sample and sampling techniques employed, scrutinizes the validity of the research instrument, elucidates the administration of the instrument and elucidates the method of data analysis. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. This gave a clear picture of the population and provided detailed information about the population. The target population for this study include Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith Church (LFC), Christ Apostolic Church (CAC) and Baptist Church respectively. A sample size of fifteen respondents was selected from each of the four churches. The respondents included members, ministers, and workers of the selected churches. A simple random method was used to ensure that the population of the study has an equal chance of being picked. In all, a sample of sixty (60) participants was used for the study. Since the respondents were from the body of Christ, the samples were treated as homogeneous.

The research instrument used for this research was a questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section A of the instrument

consisted of the respondents' biodata while section B consisted of variables that were related to the subject matter. The questionnaire was structured in form of a four-point Likert scale coded as follows: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Strongly Disagreed (SD) and Disagreed (D).

The researcher assistants met the respondents one-on-one. He also took the pain, right from the outset, to explain essential issues about their involvement in the research which included the anonymity of their responses, the need for objectivity and sincerity while filling the questionnaire. This enabled them to explain certain items on the questionnaire to the respondents so that the questionnaire would be properly filled. Besides, they were advised to work independently. The respondents were then given enough time to fill their copies after which, they were collected on the spot. This method ensured correct completion and a high percentage return of the completed copies of the questionnaire.

The information gathered was analysed based on individual responses to the questions. The percentage and frequency count were adopted to analyse the data to be collected for the study.

Data Presentation

Demographic Tables

Sixty (60) respondents were used as sample for this study and their responses were used for data analysis.

Table 4.1 Respondent's Denomination

Denomination	Respondent	Percentage (%)
RCCG	15	25.86
LFC	15	25.86
Baptist	15	22.41
CAC	15	25.86
Total	60	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 4.1, it is obvious that fifteen (15) of the participants came from RCCG, fifteen (15) of them were from LFC, 15 of them were from the Baptist Church while the remaining fifteen (15) came from CAC.

Table 4.1.1 Respondent’s Academic Level

Academic Level	Respondent	Percentage (%)
SSCE	10	17.24
ND/NCE	18	31.03
HND/BSC.	22	37.03
MSC/PhD	01	1.7
Total	51	85

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1 showcases the academic qualifications of the participants. While the table shows that all of them were educated, it also shows that majority 22(37.03%) of them had either HND or BSc. This reflects that all of them had the intellectual capacity to provide the information required. However, it should be noted that nine (9) of them did not provide information about their academic qualification.

Reponses to Research Questions:

Table 4.2.1 Causes of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	S/A	A	SD	D
1.	Adolescents abuse drugs due to peer influence	44 (73.33%)	16 (26.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
2.	Adolescents are involved in drug abuse to attain a sense of euphoria, that is to ‘feel high’	39 (65%)	20 (33.33%)	1 (1.67%)	0 (0%)

3. Adolescents are involved in drug abuse as a result of lack of parental care and guidance.	31 (51.67%)	23 (38.33%)	3 (1.67%)	5 (8.33%)
4. Adolescents are involved in drug abuse as a result of stress, anxiety, depression, and pain.	31(51.67%)	25(46.67%)	3(5%)	1(1.67%)
5. Adolescents are also involved in drug abuse as a result of single parent or divorced parent.	26(43.33%)	31(51.67%)	2(3.3%)	1(1.67%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.1 shows that drug abuse among adolescents is caused by various factors like peer influence as unanimously attested to by all the respondents used for this study. The 100% agreement by the respondents shows that peer influence is a strong factor that leads to drug abuse among adolescents. Also, as attested to by majority 59 (98%) of the participants identified desire for euphoria as one of the causes of drug abuse among adolescents. Lack of parental care and guidance is another factor leading to adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as attested to by majority 54 (90%) of the participants. Emotional impairment is another major cause for adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as agreed on by majority 56 (98.34%). Lastly, majority 57 (95%) of the participants agreed that

adolescents are involved in drug abuse because of single parent or divorced parent.

Table 4.2.2 Effects of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in some Church Denominations in Ede South Local Government Area

S/N	Statement	S/A	A	SD	D
1.	Adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression	39(65%)	21(35%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
2.	Adolescent drug abusers are usually vulnerable to different forms of physical, spiritual and mental health complications.	33(55%)	27(45%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
3.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually commit suicide	26 (43.33%)	32 (53.33)	0 0%)	2(3.3%)
4.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc	25 (41.6%)	33 (55%)	1 (1.67)	1(1.67)
5.	Most adolescent drug abusers usually end up as school drop-outs.	22(36.6%)	29(48.3 3%)	2(33%)	1 (1.67%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.2 presents the effects of drug abuse among adolescents in Ede. Majority, 60 (100%) of the respondents agreed that adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression. Vulnerability to different forms of physical, spiritual and mental health complications is also an aftermath of adolescents' involvement in drug abuse as attested to unanimously by all 60 (100%) of the participants. Majority, 58 (96.66%) of the respondents asserted that drug abusers commit suicide. Also, majority, 58 (96.66%) asserted that drug abusers usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc. Lastly, majority, 51(85%) opined that adolescent drug abusers usually end up as school drop-outs.

Table 4.2.3: Ways in Which the Church is Involved in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescent in Ede Local Government Area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1	My church organises regular workshops and seminars to educate youths and adolescents on drug issues	19(33.66%)	26 (43.33%)	6 (10%)	9(15%)
2	My church partners with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and	19(33.66%)	25 (41.6%)	8 (13.3%)	8(13.8%)

	adolescents on drug abuse				
3	My church provides counseling and therapy for those who are involved in drug abuse	17(26.67%)	30(50%)	6(!0%)	8(13.8%)
4	My church provides materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse	18 (30%)	31(51.67%)	4(6.6%)	7(11.6%)
5	My church helps people, especially, adolescents, within and outside RCCG to overcome drug-related issues	19(31.66%)	18 (30%)	4 (6.6%)	9(15%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.3 presents various ways in which the church is involved in drug abuse prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area. First, majority, 45 (76.99%) attested to the fact that their churches organise regular workshops and seminars to educate youths and adolescents on drug issues. Also, according to the data available on the table, majority, 44 (73.26%) of the respondents agreed that their churches partner with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and adolescents on drug abuse. Furthermore, 47 (76.67%) of the participants, agreed that their churches provide counseling and therapy

for those who are involved in drug abuse. In addition, majority, 49 (81.67%) of the participants acknowledged that their churches provide materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse. Lastly, 37 (61.66%) of the respondents agreed that their churches help people, especially, Christian and non-Christian adolescents, to overcome drug-related issues.

Table 4.2.4: Challenges limiting the involvement of some church Denomination in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1.	Drug abuse prevention programmes adopted by my church are obstructed by stigma and denial.	20(33.33%) 43(71.66%)	23(38.33%)	7(11.6%)	9(15%)
2.	Drug abuse prevention measures adopted by my church are also limited by cultural norms and traditional practices.	31(51.67%) 47(78.34%)	16(26.67%)	4(6.6%)	9(15%)
3.	Religious diversity is another obstacle to the drug abuse prevention measures adopted by my church.	30(50%) 49(81.66%)	19(31.66%)	5(8.33%)	6(10%)
4.	Parental involvement also has its own way of limiting the	37(61.66%) 54(89.99%)	17(28.33%)	3(5%)	3(5%)

	measures adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.				
5.	Lack of commitment and manpower also has its own limiting effects on the strategies adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.	20(33.33%) 52(85.66%)	32(52.33%)	4(6.6%)	3(5%)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.4 depicts the challenges limiting the efforts of the church in combating drug abuse as 43 (71.66%) of the participants opined that the strategies are obstructed by stigma and denial. 47 (78.34%) of the respondents also said that the strategies are also limited by cultural norms and traditional practices. 47 (78.34%) of them further identified cultural norms and traditional practices as limiting factors to the efforts of the church in combating drug abuse among adolescents in Ede. Parental involvement is another limitation to the efforts of the church in fighting drug related issues as attested to cumulatively by 54 (89.99%) of the participants. Lastly, lack of commitment and manpower also limit the success of the endeavours of the church concerning drug abuse as attested to by 52 (85.66%) of the participants.

Table 4.2.5: Solutions to the Challenges Limiting the Involvement of some Church Denominations in Drug Abuse Prevention among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area Osun State

S/N	Statement	SA	A	SD	D
1.	My church should redesign its drug abuse	33(55%)	23(37.33%)	2(3.3%)	2 (3.3%)

	prevention programmes for adolescents in such a way that helpes will not be victims of stigma and denial of access to existing facilities.	56(93.3 3%)	8.33 %)		
2.	The programmes should be sensitive to the cultures of the land and the adolescents.	27(45%) 57(75%)	30(5 0%)	2(3.3 %)	1 (1.67%)
3.	The programmes should be sensitive to the religious diversity of the land.	27(45%) 56(93.3 3%)	29(4 8.33 %)	2(3.3 %)	1 (1.67%)
4.	Parents must be properly counselled so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes adopted by my church to educate adolescents on drug issues.	32(53.3 3%) 58(96.6 6%)	26(4 3.33 %)	1(1.6 7%)	1 (1.67%)
5.	My church must use qualified, competent and committed officers for its drug abuse prevention programmes in an attempt to reach out to the adolescents under its care.	37(61.6 6%) 57(94.9 9%)	20(3 3.33 %)	3(5%)	0

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.5 reflects the attempts that the church can adopt to subdue the challenges limiting her efforts as 56(93.33%) suggested that the church should be culture sensitive; 56(93.33%) of them counselled the church to be conscious of the religious diversity that characterized the land; 58(96.66%)

counselled the church to properly counsel parents so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes and 57(94.99%) advised the church to make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.

Discussion

Factors Influencing Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State

The findings of this study depicts that adolescents are involved in drug abuse in Ede South Local Government Area, Osun State due to some reasons like peer influence as attested to by 60(100%) of the respondents. In consonance with this, Adebisi et al (2017), opined that adolescents frequently succumb to the influence of their peers, which can prompt them to partake in drug experimentation in order to assimilate or attain social acceptance within their peer group. Desire for euphoria as acknowledged by 59(98%) of the respondents is another cause of adolescents involvement in drug abuse. This is corroborated by Okafor (2020), who explicated that euphoria, that is, the general feeling of 'getting high' is always associated with drug abuse. The study also identified lack of parental care and guidance as one of the causes of drug abuse as agreed on by 54(90%). Establishing this assertion in an elaborate manner, Adebisi et al., (2017), said that malfunctioning familial dynamics, including parental substance abuse, neglect, or inadequate supervision, can contribute to the susceptibility of adolescents to drug abuse. The study further recognized emotional impairment as a cause of drug abuse as attested to by 56(98.34%). Supporting this idea, Adebisi et al., (2017) opined that underlying mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, or trauma can heighten the propensity for drug abuse among adolescents who seek relief or escape. Lastly, single or divorced parent can also push adolescents into drug abuse as attested to by 57(95%) of the respondents. This is in line with the opinion of Adebisi et al, 2017 as he also identified parental neglect and inadequate supervision by parents as major causes that heighten drug abuse among adolescents.

Consequences of Drug Abuse among Adolescents in Ede, Osun State

The consequences of substance misuse among young individuals in Ede, Osun State, Nigeria, have profound and wide-ranging implications on their

physical, mental, social, and academic well-being. Majority, 60(100%) of the respondents claimed that adolescent drug abusers end as victims of depression. This correlates with the opinion of Adeloye & Odeigah, (2014) that substance abuse is linked to an augmented vulnerability to mental health disorders, such as depression, anxiety, and schizophrenia. Suicidal attempts are also very common among adolescent drug abusers as attested to by the majority, 58(96.66%) of the respondents used for this study. In agreement with this, Ayomide & Ayomide, (2023), identified suicide as one of the major consequences of drug abuse. Drug abusers also usually experience change in behaviour including sexual behaviour, withdrawal, isolation etc as attested to by 58(96.66%) of the respondents. In line with the findings of this study, Ayomide & Ayomide (2023) identified erratic behaviour as one of the consequences of drug abuse. Lastly, this study found out that drug abusers usually experience school discontinuation and this view is shared by (Adeloye & Odeigah, 2014) when he says that substance misuse may lead to dropping out of school, curtailing educational and career opportunities.

Measures Adopted by the Church to Prevent Adolescents' Involvement in Drug Abuse in Ede South Local Government Area

Involvement in and commitment to diaconal services, including prevention of drug abuse among adolescents, are apparent features of most Nigerian churches including RCCG, Baptist, LFC and CAC. Corroborating this, Adedibu (2023) said that the missional obligation of the church requires spiritual renewal, socio-economic reformation of people and the community through its religious teachings and belief system. He said further that the missionary endeavour of the church all over various cultural frontiers to initiate and retain churches is basically transformational. One of such transformational services is helping people to be immune against drug abuse or recover from it if they has already been trapped into it. Adding to the debate, Dairo (2012) opined that today's church is opening up space for the Holy Spirit to move powerfully in the lives of the faithful in the ministry of healing including the healing of the mind that has been captured by drug abuse. The pertinent question now is: how can the church help the individuals and the society at large to rise above drug abuse? To answer this question, this study proposed the following: a) organising workshops and seminars as suggested by 45(76.99%) of the respondents, b) partnering

with NGOs and drug-related agencies working on drug prevention to reach out to the youths and adolescents on drug abuse as suggested by 44(73.26%) of the respondents, c) providing counseling and therapy for those who are involved in drug abuse as suggested by 47(76.67%) d) providing materials that inform and educate the members on the danger of drug abuse as suggested by 49(81.67%) of the participants and e) helping people, especially, Christian and non-Christian adolescents, to overcome drug-related issues as opined by 37(61.66%) of the respondents.

Factors Limiting the Endeavours of the Church in Combating Drug Abuse

As committed as the church is in combating drug abuse among adolescents in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State, certain factors are standing as obstacles. These obstacles include: stigma and denial, as attested to by 43(71.66%) of the participants. This is because church-based support may further enhance stigmas that link drug abuse with sinfulness. These stigmas may absolutely hinder abusers from seeking support (Armstrong, 2025). Cultural norms and traditional practices also have a way of limiting the efforts of the church in mitigating drug abuse. Supporting this, Monari et al., (2024) opined that culturally rooted beliefs surrounding substance abuse have a deep impact on family subtleties in communities. These culturally rooted beliefs, at times, deter the church in her effort to mitigate drug abuse as attested to by 47(78.34%). Religious diversity also plays a limiting role to the church as an agent of mitigation against drug abuse as identified by 47(78.34%). Nigeria, including Ede in Osun State, exhibits religious diversity, with different religious groups potentially holding distinct perspectives on drug abuse and the role of the church in addressing this issue. (Odejide, 2006). Parental involvement is another limitation to the efforts of the church in fighting drug related issues as attested to cumulatively by 54(89.99%) of the participants. Engaging parents and caregivers in the programmes like this may prove challenging due to their work commitments and other responsibilities. (Adebiyi et al., 2017) Lastly, lack of commitment and manpower as opined by 52(85.66%) of the respondents also reduce the role of the church in assisting drug abusers.

Solutions to the Challenges Limiting the Involvement of some Church Denominations in Ede Local Government Area

To address these challenges, 56 (93.33%) of the respondents suggested that the church should be culture sensitive; 56(93.33%) of them counselled the church to be conscious of the religious diversity that characterized the land; 58 (96.66%) counselled the church to properly counsel parents so as to get the best results from them as stake holders in the programmes and 57(94.99%) advised the church to make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.

Conclusion

The study has established that drug abuse is a menace that is rampant among adolescents in Ede South Local Government, Ede, Osun State. The study has also found out that there are factors influencing this social vice. Worst of all, the study identified some terrible repercussions of this menace. To address the vice, churches in the local government represented by RCCG, LFC, Baptist and CAC rose to the occasion. However, the measures taken by these churches were confronted by certain constraints; hence, the study proposed some solutions that will beef up the efforts of the church to mitigate adolescents' involvement in drug abuse in Ede South Local Government Area, Ede, Osun State.

Recommendations

The study then recommends that the church should:

1. Foster close collaboration with local leaders, engage in community sensitization efforts and adapt her anti-drug abuse programmes to the cultural and social context of Ede, Osun State.
2. Pay close attention to multi-religious nature of Ede, Osun State
3. Collaborate with parents so as to get the best result from them
4. Make use of qualified, competent and committed officers.
5. Embark on community motivation, encouragement and outreaches to enlighten member of the society on the imminent dangers related to drug abuse.
6. Ensure cooperation among the entire body of Christ if the social menace is to be conquered.
7. Display fairness among the adolescents in promoting shared ethical values, and institutional reforms in the society.

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8. Collaborate with government, private rehabilitation centres and the NGOs should join forces with the church denomination to minimize or even eradicate drug abuse.

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Maximizing the Potentials of Yoruba Folklore for Moral Development among Youths in Ede, Osun State

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Abstract

The current vices and displays of immoralities by youths in Ede, Osun State, contradict Yoruba culture. This calls attention to folklore, a vital aspect of Yoruba culture which was used in the pre-colonial Yoruba society to successfully socialize youths positively. This study therefore examined Yoruba folklore and its implications for moral development among the youths of Ede, Osun State, Nigeria. The study is built on functional-performance theory, a combination of functionalism and performance theories calling attention to societal functions of folklore and its communicative tendencies. The population was constituted by staff and students of Adeleke University and Federal Polytechnic and the custodians of culture, in Ede. Cluster sampling technique was used to divide the population into three sub-groups while simple random sampling technique was used to choose 5 lecturers, 5 culture custodians and 20 students as participants. The in-depth (IDI) and Key Informant (KII) interview guides were used as the instruments for this study. The study established that various folklore genres are still recognised in Ede, each with

its unique values. It was also established that folklore is gradually fading out as a youth moral development tool. The study ascertained that the integration of folklore and social media is necessary for the restoration of folklore and for youths' easy access. It concluded that both old and current methods should be synchronized to give folklore a new facelift. Therefore, it was recommended that folklore should be incorporated at every level of education, integrated into social media and communicated via Yoruba language.

Keywords: Folklore, *Omoluabi*, Moral Development, Yorùbá, Youth, Ede, Osun State

Introduction

Immorality of all kinds is pervasive and on the rise among Nigerian youths today. Corruption, gambling, betting, yahoo, yahoo plus, cheating, indulging in money rituals, gangsterism, drug addiction and abuse, sexual immoralities, indecent dressing such as sagging among males, and body-revealing clothing by females are examples of immoral behaviour (Akanbi, 2014). A Yorùbá saying states that *iwa rere l'eso eniyan* (good character is the beauty of the mortal). This demonstrates that anything adverse to the exhibition of decent behaviour in society has departed from the moral standard and hence is inappropriate. As a result, several vices and immoral behavior by youths are considered abhorrent in Yorùbá culture. This draws attention to folklore, an important component of Yorùbá culture that was employed in pre-colonial Yorùbá society to positively socialise youths.

In Yorùbá culture, an individual's moral character earns him a prestigious place in society, so he is referred to as *Omoluabi*— a concept that emphasizes good character; it is a metric for intelligence, accomplishment, and beauty. These traits of *omoluabi* are inherent in Yorùbá folklore. They are equally used as a yardstick for good character. As Yorùbá, youths are supposed to apply the principle of *omoluabi* in whatever they do. The exhibition of *omoluabi* qualities by youths also indicates that such individual has received good family instruction and is of exemplary worth in society, hence the proverb: "Charity begins at home". Unfortunately, the 21st Century acts of Nigerian youths utterly contradict the ideals of *omoluabi*, which have been supplanted by foreign qualities and values.

Yorùbá use folklore to explore relevant themes and difficulties in their lives. It supports cultural ideals and resonates to both young and old people in general. The Yorùbá's lifestyle reflects their wisdom, knowledge,

understanding, instruction, and life experiences as they change over time. Folklore, in all its forms, provides universal ideals important for rectifying moral aberrations. They are veritable instruments for moral training for children, youths, and adults.

Despite these invaluable traits, folklore is rapidly losing popularity and relevance (Akanbi, 2014). This is linked to the new Western political, social, moral and legal principles established during the colonial era, which became ingrained in the cultural system through civilization and spread throughout the social, cultural, and religious systems (Nsereka, 2019). However, the Western values and culture embraced by Nigerian youths contradict African indigenous folklore. As a result, it is critical to highlight the efficacy of adopting folklore genres to combat deviant behaviours among the teeming immoral young people and to prevent morality in society.

The use of folklore for the moral development of Nigerian youths is no longer popular, resulting in moral degradation among those who are expected to be tomorrow's leaders. Folklore instilled strong morals in the pre-colonial Yorùbá population, fostering youth development. However, the entrance of Western culture and social media into African communities has negatively altered the standard and resulted in a quick shift in social norms. Behaviours that were once considered unacceptable in traditional Nigerian society are now allowed and even applauded. Today, Nigerian youths, particularly those in Ede, are confused as a result of contradicting signals from parents and elders on the one hand, and the mass and social media on the other. Today's youths use social media to seek advice, unlike the Yorùbá traditional society that relied solely on folklore and the family institution.

There is a need to revisit the Yoruba archives to discover what worked in the past: folklore and all its genres (Igba, 2016, 245-251). An exploration of the existing literature on folklore revealed that different researchers have worked on folktales as a tool for moral development in young people both within and outside of Nigeria (Sesan, 2014; Azubuike, 2013; Taiwo, 2014). Few of these investigated how folklore could be utilized to instil values in young people and to recognize societal norms (Igba et al, 2019, Ojukwu & Esimone, 2015). Other research focused on folk music, a component of folklore, to reaffirm its value (Jamolovna, 2021; Ibekwe, & E. Ojukwu, 2020, Akande, 2023). While these studies have underlined the importance and values associated with folklore, the factors that have contributed to its

deterioration and diminishing importance among youths, as well as its possibly integration into social media have been overlooked. Since these previous studies have not done enough in recognising the factors that have contributed to the deterioration and diminishing importance of folklore among youths, as well as its possibly integration into social media, this current study is designed to address this gap.

Clarification of Concepts

Moral Development

Moral development has to do with the emergence, change, and understanding of morality from infancy through adulthood (Satianingsih, et al), including the youthful age. In other words, it is a progressive procedure that spans through lifetime in various ways and is influenced by an individual's exposure and attitude when confronted with moral concerns involving varying eras of physical and cognitive development. It equally refers to a specific code of conduct that is derived from one's culture, religion, or personal philosophy that guides one's actions, behaviours, and thoughts. This further establishes the fact that folklore and moral development are interrelated since moral development is derived from one's culture (Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020).

Folklore

Literally, folklore has a double meaning ((Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020). Hence, on one side, it is defined as traditional knowledge of the common people and as such, represents a body of material: stories, songs, beliefs. Likewise, it is a separate science closely linked with literature and history (Ihueze, quoted by Owoade, 2020).

Youth

There appears to be no uniform definition of youth. Africa, the Global South, and many other countries have long asserted that youth is defined by culturally defined social processes that mark the transition from childhood to adulthood, rather than a range of years. The United Nations defines youth as a phase of transition from childhood reliance to adulthood's independence and recognition of our interdependence as members of a community. In other words, youth is a more flexible category than a definite age group” (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). The African Youth Charter defines youth

as “any individual between 15-35 years of age and seeks to resolve longstanding debates about defining youth within the African context and based on Africa’s development realities” (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). According to Nigeria's 2019 National Youth Policy (NYP), a youth is defined as person aged 15-29 (Ewhrudjakpor, 2022). For this study, the NYP's (2019) youth classification is used.

Theoretical Framework

Functional-Performance Theory

This is a combination of functionalism and performance theories. According to Akporherhe & Oghenerioborue (2021) functionalism is developed by Bronislaw Malinowski (1884-1942). The theory, according to the two scholars, centres on the utilitarian functions of oral materials produced in traditional society including legends, folksongs, proverbs, riddles, folktales, myths and festivals, to mention a few. The performance theory also known as ethnography of communication, on the other hand, was proposed by Dell Hymes initially in his paper: *The Ethnography of Speaking* (Ray et al., 2011). The theory considered the interactive forms of communication, describing its role “as a cultural system” (Igba et al. 2019). Building this study on the two theories is thereby justified since functional theory vividly brings out the functional values inherent in folklore while the performance theory explains the variety of contexts in which it is communicated within a given society.

Methodology

The exploratory research design is adopted for this study. The population of this study consisted of all the staff and students of the selected departments (History, Library Science, Mass Communication and English) in Adeleke University, Ede, Osun State. The population also included all the staff and students of Library and Information Science of Federal Polytechnic, Ede, Osun State. The students were chosen because the bulk of them were young people who fell within 15-29 years age range, the age range accepted for youth classification by 2019 National Youth Policy in Nigeria and because they were students their intellectual capacity and direct connection with the subject at hand were extremely valuable to this study. The population also included lecturers from the two tertiary institutions earlier mentioned. They were used because their fields of study

were connected to the problem under inquiry. Custodians of culture viz: elderly chiefs, community leaders and family leaders in Ede who were well-versed in the traditions of Yorùbá and Ede, in particular, were consulted. Ede was chosen because of its richness in Yorùbá culture (Nolte, and Ogen, Olukoya, 2017).

The population was divided into three (3) sub-groups using the cluster random sampling technique: students from the two tertiary institutions under study, lecturers and elders who were cultural custodians in Ede. A purposive random sampling technique was then used to select twenty (20) students (ten/10 from each school) who had lived in Ede for at least five (5) years, as well as five (5) lecturers who were experts in fields related to the study: four from Adeleke University and one from Federal Polytechnic (because Adeleke University offers four courses related to the study, whereas Federal Polytechnic only offers one, i.e. Library Science). Still using sampling technique, five (5) custodians of the town's culture were chosen from the third sub-group. Overall, thirty respondents were chosen for interview. The in-depth interview and key informant interview guides were utilised to collect data for this study. The researcher and her assistants met with each respondent individually. These data were organized thematically and contextually analysed.

Data Presentation

Suitable Folklore Genre for Moral Development among Youths

The first objective of this study is to ensure that folklore is appropriate for moral development among youths in Ede. Most respondents recognised that folklore genres include folktales, myths, legends, and fables, folk music/songs, talking drum, proverbs, tying and dying, carving, pottery, folk dance, folk poems such as panegyrics/praising poetry, folk rhymes, bride's lamentation, dirge, and so on. Each of these sorts of folklore has a specific function and purpose. Overall, respondents saw these folkloric genres as methods for connecting youths to their ancestral past, preserving culture, and, most importantly, teaching, instilling, and boosting morality, particularly among young people. Folkloric genres are employed during festive occasions and in diverse communication contexts. Both young and old participants opined that folk story is the best type of folklore that is most suitable for youth moral development. One of the participants mentioned:

Oriki/praise poetry and fables are some of the Yorùbá folklore types. Fables, due to their didactic nature, teach morals. Oriki/Praise Poetry/panegyrics strengthen marital relationship and boosts morals. Also, oriki tells you who you are, what your ancestors have done and how you can improve on it. To me, the fable, a sub-type of folk story, is the best because it brings out morals. (KII, FP Lecturer, 2023)

In corroboration with the above response on the suitability of folklore for moral development, a participant has this to say:

Folktales, legends, statues, folk music, and myth are some of the folklore types in Yorùbá culture. To me, myth is the best because it centres on past heroes' stories of success and failure, which can guide youths to tread cautiously. Myth makes you remember who you are, and who your ancestors are. (IDI, FP, 2023)

In addition, a custodian of culture emphasized:

Moonlight tales, proverbs, riddles, chants, oriki/praise poetry are the popular Yorùbá folkloric genres. Folk stories connect youths to their historical backgrounds; riddles, myths and folktales deepen youths' understanding of their culture. The nighttime when the moon is out is the time chosen to expose children and youths to these oral traditions. All of them are useful but folktale is the best since it has the capacity to teach youths their ancestral history, which invariably teaches them morals. (KII, Culture Custodian (CC), Religious Leader, 2023)

In support of folktales as the best form of folklore, another community elder noted that:

Drumming, folk songs, folktales, myths and legends are types of folklore. Generally, folklore is used to strengthen youths and teach them morals. However, folktale is the best because it strengthens youths, develops their listening skills and imparts deep wisdom in them. (KII, Community Elder, 2023)

Another community leader also strongly supported the fact that folktale is the best. He said:

Ekun iyawo popularly called the bride's lamentation, *ijala*, *ere ode* (hunters' chant), *iyere ifa*, moonlight tales, *alo apamo* (riddles), folktales, legends, myths are some of the folklore genres in Yorùbá culture. They are usually taught. Picking the best is a difficult task

but I'll like to go with folktales because it is rich, very rich. It combines history with morals and virtues. If children are exposed to it, it will make them to become somebody in life. (KII, Religious Leader, 2023)

Proverb too was identified as one of the folklore components that can be used for moral development. This fact is supported thus:

Proverb is just the best. Whenever, I misbehave, my mother will scold me and tell me *omo ti a ko to lo ngbe ile ti a ko ta*. Each time I hear that, I come back to my senses. (IDI, AU, Male, 2023)

Apart from folktales, folk songs/music and proverbs, talking drum is also regarded as one of the components of folklore that significantly shapes moral development among the youth. A Federal Polytechnic student gave reasons that:

Drumming, proverbs, and monuments are some of the folklore types in Yorùbáland. But the most important is the talking drum. To me, talking drum is the best as it gives youths the opportunity to be meaningfully engaged and exhibit their talents. (IDI, FP, Female, 2023)

However, all the various components of the folklore were identified as good and useful as one of the participants mentioned. Myth, legend, ori/ki/praise poetry and folktales are parts of Yorùbá folklore, but none can be said to be better than others since each of them has its own purpose and focus. (KII, Adeleke University Lecturer, Male, 2023)

Finally, the importance of language in conveying the moral lessons embedded in any components of folklore cannot be underestimated. Language in this case, is important. One of the community elders interviewed laid an emphasis on this in his words that:

Folklore genres include folktales, riddles and legends. They are generally used to intimate youths with the past and teach them moral lessons. However, we cannot pick the best from folklore genres that are not presented via Yorùbá language. (KII, CC, Community Elder, Female, 2023)

Significantly, the importance of language in teaching morals through folklore needs to be adopted in this present age and communication.

Factors Influencing the Ineffectiveness of Folklore

According to available literature, the internet, social media, and other technological instruments have decreased the impact of folklore among Nigerian youths. These technology platforms just distance the youth from traditional and folklore genres, which were formerly used to transmit moral precepts. The second research question of this study seeks to determine the efficient use of folklore as a tool for youth moral development. One of the participants identified foreign culture as one of the reasons why folklore is ineffective among today's youth. He maintained that:

Folklore is no longer fashionable because of the adoption of foreign culture. (KII, Adeleke University, Lecturer, 2023)

To another participant who is a community leader, folklore as a means of moral development and a way to transport moral lessons has really dwindled. The participant emphasised the need of indigenous language to bring back the effectiveness of folklore as noted:

Folklore can only be effective if native language is used, or else, the result will be an English-oriented folklore. (KII, Community Leader, Female, 2023)

Perhaps Yorùbá folklore has lost its relevance as a result of the ubiquity and pressure of English-speaking among youths. While English has become a priority, the Yorùbá language, which is used to deliver most of these cultural elements, has died away because most youths cannot speak or comprehend it. Because it is difficult to hear and/or speak Yorùbá, it will be incredibly difficult to grasp when utilised to communicate moral lessons through storytelling. Yet, emphasising the link between mother tongue and folklore, Mzimela (2016), opines that mother tongue is often used to sustain and convey cultural beliefs. A student, who shares a similar opinion on the importance of language, stated:

Folklore has lost its effectiveness as a tool for youth moral development because of the non-inclusion of Yorùbá as a subject by some schools. (IDI, Female, 2023)

A community/religious leader confirms that the ineffectiveness of folklore among youth is due to western pollution from foreign culture, which has become the new means of transmitting moral messages and teachings. He explained this:

Folklore has lost its effectiveness as a result of importation of foreign culture through its “might is right” weapon. The might is

right syndrome came and silenced the voice of truth in our culture. Hence, someone described western civilization as western contamination. The point is our own tradition detested dishonesty but when the European legal system was introduced, crimes began to increase since the court of law must try criminals before convicting them. Since then, the law and law enforcement agents have become very powerful. Whatever the law or its enforcer says is the final, whether right or wrong. That has really silenced our morally-inclined culture. (KII, Community/Religious Leader, Male, 2023)

Meanwhile, while advocating for an immediate remedy due to the disappearance of folklore, a lecturer voiced great concern that folklore could be completely lost if proper precautions are not taken. A lecturer-participant therefore said:

We are at a critical bend; we are at verge of losing our folklore in Yorùbá society. If something is not done urgently, there will be problem. (KII, Lecturer Participant, Male, 2023)

Colonialism and the entrance of foreign religions have had a negative impact on Yorùbá youths' usage of folklore. Folklore and other cultural components have dwindled but have not totally lost their significance in imparting vital moral lessons and values in the society. This is explained as follows:

Folklore has not totally lost its effectiveness as a weapon for youth moral development in Ede North Local Government Area. It is only gradually dying because it is suffering from neglect/abandonment because of the negative impact of colonialism and foreign religion which created the impression that our culture is evil. The truth of the matter is that the Yorùbá society is an evolving one. Our culture has its negative and positive sides. All we need to do is to take the good aspects and discard the negative ones. (KII, Lecturer Participant, Male, 2023)

While it is agreed that folklore and its genres have not been effective over time, it is imperative to know that some people still make folklore relevant. These are those that have lived with and benefitted from the elders. These categories of people have such advantage to demonstrate this cultural identity wherever they go and thus, retain the effectiveness of folklore. A community leader stated that:

Folklore has not absolutely lost its effectiveness because people do not easily forget their culture and norms. Moreover, an adage says: *Bo ti wu korun ko mu to, sanman dudu die yoo wa* (Every cloud has a silver lining). This adage implies that every sad, difficult or hopeless situation has a comforting or more hopeful aspect. Superficially, it seems folklore has lost its effectiveness, but looking at it critically, this is not totally true for as people (especially, *awon omo odo agba*, those nurtured by culturally-inclined elders), travel round the globe and interact with others, they spread their norms and traditions. Drama also assists in retaining the effectiveness of folklore. (KII, Community Leader, Male, 2023)

Since the Yorùbá language is still taught in schools, the values of folklore remain important. The teaching of Yorùbá language and the presence of some artifacts, statues of heroes and heroines in Yorùbáland convey volumes, according to a student:

I believe that folklore has not totally lost its effectiveness because Yorùbá is still taught in schools and there are statues all around speaking volumes about folklore. As the young folks move around in their communities seeing these statues everyday, there is an awareness of their tradition. (IDI, Adeleke University, Ede, Female, 2023)

According to another student of Adeleke University, the quality of time of youths plays a significant role in the usage of folklore. Most times, the youths listen to foreign music and watch foreign videos, which only propagate foreign culture. Meanwhile to gather them to listen to cultural Yorùbá music and watch Yorùbá films to learn our culture is always a problem. The participant noted:

Folklore is gradually going into extinction because the listening span of youths is very short so tying them down to receive cultural values via oral tradition is quite difficult. (IDI, Adeleke University, Female, 2023)

Still supporting same opinion, another student respondent has this to say:

Folklore is not as popular as before because modernization has offered better ways of teaching moral lessons. For instance, youths can access several films on the television, VCD or even on their android or Hi-phones at their own leisure. (IDI, Adeleke University, Female, 2023)

Integrating Social Media and Folklore for Moral Development

One strategy to make Yoruba folklore relevant again in imparting moral values is to employ the most appealing medium to youths, namely social media platforms. Thus, the notion of combining folklore and social media to educate values and morals to Ede North LG young people in Osun state is not out of order. Hence, a participant stated:

Omo ina la nran sina (to get a wildfire, you need to send a lesser fire on errand). Since youths are in love with social media, it is a brilliant idea to use social media platforms as channels to teach them moral values since nowadays, the youths' relationship with social media is like that of Romeo and Juliet. Social media platforms focusing on folklore can be created but activities there should be placed under restrictions by the government. Parents and stake holders should guide in this respect to avoid abuse. (KII, Community Leader, Male, 2023)

Another respondent in the Local Government says:

It goes beyond social media. Children should be exposed to digital or language programming from cradle like the Indians do. My major exposure to folklore was through Indian films. (KII, Federal Polytechnic Lecturer, Male, 2023)

Another interviewee on integration of the folklore with social media said:

Social media can be created to teach the upcoming generation. They can even make money out of it like Adejoke Ewa Ede, Lekan King Kong and so on. These people are recently chanting lineage poems, dancing in the traditional ways, using talking drum and teaching both foreigners and indigenes what they know and do. These platforms can also be used to store and show folktales that will convey moral lessons for our youths (KII, Community/Religious Leader, Male, 2023)

As suggested by a participant:

Culture custodians can come together to create a social media platform for teaching and popularizing folklore. (IDI, AU, Female, 2023)

A youth respondent in the community under study said:

Social media platform where folk music can be showcased can be created. For instance, we have '*Afin Ilu*', created by Adewale Laoye. (IDI, FP, Male, 2023)

Discussion

The study found that folklore genres used for various communication situations are effective instruments for youth moral development. Folklore genres, including folktales, fables, proverbs, and *oriki*, are widely regarded as cultural instruments for moral development. They are methods by which youths in society are required to demonstrate the concept of *omoluabi*, which defines a 'cultured and well-mannered social being'. Folklore and its genre, based on cultural transmission theory, describe how cultural values, beliefs, and norms are passed down from generation to generation in a society, shaping individuals' behaviours for the sake of the society's sustainability. Folklore became a framework for guiding youths in internalising rules and values that satisfy society standards.

While most participants acknowledged the relative nature of folklore genres, they emphasised that each serves a distinct cultural and moral function, underscoring the value of an integrative folkloric approach. Similarly, functionalism theory recognises the importance of each cultural aspect in maintaining societal balance. Riddles, for example, promote critical thinking; *Ekun Iyawo* (bride's lamentation) fosters empathy and anticipation on marital duties; and the talking drum promotes creativity, communal cohesion, and subtle communication. This represents a concept of moral development as multifarious emotional, cognitive, and behavioural, with different folklore genres addressing these elements differently yet complementarily.

Walters believes that the essential values embedded in folklore should be used to ethically train today's youths, as the same technique worked for our forefathers (Walters 2007: 275-284). Stebbins, corroborating this, stated that folklore can be used to impart decency, moral virtue, and ideals in children (Stebbins, 2001). Yorùbá folklore informs Yorùbás about their societal structure, essential values, taboos, and sanctions (Odeh, 2022: 1-27). Furthermore, Efua regarded folklore as the most functional component of the traditional verbal art, through which the people's ideas, morality, and social attitudes are conveyed from one generation to another (Efua, 1976). However, she (She is a female Ghanaian playwright) also stated that this

functional tool has been virtually forbidden by educational policy and is regarded with contempt in educational institutions (Efua, 1976). Meanwhile, it is necessary to pay attention to fulfil cultural transmission theory that folklore is a means for passing on moral ideals and expected behaviours among adolescents, which include respect for elders in society, dignity, love, and appropriate behaviour whether one is watching or not. Cultural imperialism is one major factor that influences folklore as an instrument for youth moral development due to the dominance of foreign studies and media, foreign religion, colonisation, and the neglect of indigenous language due to westernisation. Due to all these factors, local cultural practices and values have been eroded and folklore has lost its savor as a youth moral development tool. There is nothing like moonlight tales (*alo agbagbe* and *alo apamo*), proverbs, etc., as they have all been replaced by European tales carved under Hollywood and films. This also shows that that folklore is not included in the education and entertainment arenas. That is why Barigbon blamed this in-effectiveness of folklore on Western invasion through civilization and Christianity (Nsereka, 2019). One participant's description of Western civilization as "Western contamination" reflects the postcolonial critique of cultural hegemony, where indigenous African cultures have been delegitimised and branded as primitive or evil. Still, the data presents a nuanced optimism rooted in cultural resilience theory. Though folklore faces challenges from modernisation, and postcolonial westernisation, it has not been totally eroded. Community elders, lecturers, and some youths that have gained from traditional upbringing continue to propagate folklore and embody its values. The adage '*bo ti wu korun ko mu to, sanmo dudu die yoo wa*' metaphorically signifies hope and cultural persistence. Therefore, to retain and sharpen folklore as an instrument of morality, it is necessary that writers should inculcate folklore in their writings and artists and musicians should also include it in their plays and music respectively as suggested by Akínyemí and Ajíbájé (Akínyemí, & O. Ajíbájé, 2016). Oni agreed that writers are indebted to the oral traditions because of the rural environment in which they grew up (Oni, 2001). For instance, Akínwùmí Ìsòlá studied Yorùbá genres of incantations and many other oral traditions. Adeleke confirmed that Ìsòlá's exposure as a child at Lábòdé village via Ìbàdàn is the foundation of his *Ogun Ọmòdé* (Adéléké, 2016). Kólá Òní also has an oral tradition background due to

environmental and parental factor (Akínyemí, & O. Ajíbájé, 2016). This goes a long way to retain the core values of folklore and avoid distortion.

The participants equally suggested a creation of physical and virtual libraries under a strict supervision of morally upright and culturally inclined adults. Others prescribed the inscription of folklore genres on marbles, while learning of programming languages and codes that will enable a child to write programmes, design websites and create robot or artificial intelligence were also suggested. Some respondents are of the view that just like the Indians, if the younger generation are well nurtured in Yoruba folklore, it will aid cultural promotion. In respect to the use of multimedia to promote various aspects of folklore, it was suggested that developing Yoruba folktale animation will assist in training youths to develop virtuous qualities and have socio-cultural awareness thereby preserving our cultural values (Alade et al, 2015: 113-120). In addition, it helps in reviving, sustaining and popularising Yorùbá folktale among present and future generations.

Lastly, the study explored the synergy between folklore and social media, with all participants upholding its potential for promoting moral values among youths. For instance, Lekan Olaleye (Lekan King Kong) and Ajoke Ewa Ede, use digital platforms to showcase Yoruba culture. Adeoba and James noted that Olaleye's Instagram content demonstrates social media's function in circulating cultural genres (Adeoba & James, 2025: 260-277). *Afin Ilu*, a cultural centre in Ede created by Prince Adewale Laoye, uses Facebook and the Talking Drum to celebrate Yoruba heritage and this has been recognised globally (Zulu, 2015): 90-95). It was agreed by the participants that effective use of social media could foster cultural rebirth. In supporting this, a scholar noted the importance of integrating culture and local wisdom into digital spaces, with Alade noting that the internet offers crucial support for folklore's survival (Zulfitri, & S. A. Teguh, 2021: 01-17). Also, suggestions were made for accommodating more indigenous platforms like the Nairaland (Ahmed, 2023, 24), echoing China's strategy of promoting local culture through home-grown media (Ahmed, 2023, 24), while AFIDFF in Abuja also records African folktales online, aiding cultural preservation and youth empowerment (Ahmed, 2023, 24). This has been proven to have very positive results, as well as boost youths' economy, in agreement with an interviewee's submission.

Conclusion

This study concludes that folklore is a powerful tool for youth moral development, especially within the Yoruba cultural context. Through folktales, panegyrics, proverbs, and other oral traditions, youths can learn societal values, norms, mores, and heroic ideals. Folklore not only corrects deviant behaviour, but also instils into individuals moral character, cultural awareness, and listening skills. Despite challenges like westernisation, colonisation, and religious influence that have led to the neglect of indigenous languages, folklore still retains its relevance through drama, school curricula, community art, and partly, social media. The message is that if strategically revitalised and integrated into modern platforms and education, folklore can bridge generational moral gaps. Scholars and cultural practitioners affirm that the survival and promotion of folklore are essential for nurturing morally upright, culturally grounded youths prepared to lead responsibly.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. To revitalise folklore as a potent tool for youth moral development, it is imperative to reintegrate it into Nigeria's formal education curriculum at all levels.
2. This reintegration should go beyond mere language instructions, it should include structured lessons on folktales, proverbs, panegyrics, and other oral traditions that emphasise societal norms and moral values.
3. Specifically, all these attributes of folklore should be made compulsory in all the indigenous languages in Nigeria: Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa.
4. Schools should create spaces for storytelling sessions, drama, and cultural competitions that display the true context of the tradition and allow students to interact directly with these traditions.
5. Teachers should be equipped with the cultural and pedagogical skills necessary to teach folklore effectively.
6. In addition, writers, dramatists, musicians, and artists should be encouraged through grants, fellowships, and institutional support to incorporate folklore into their creative works. This magnanimous act from the government and grant bodies will serve as incentives for more people to promote indigenous folklore. This fusion of creativity and

tradition can modernise and preserve oral culture, while instilling ethical consciousness in youths. Literary figures with deep-rooted exposure to oral traditions, such as Akínwùmí Ìṣòlá and Kọ́lá Òní, exemplify the importance of grounding creative expression in indigenous cultural heritage to retain the integrity and didactic function of folklore.

7. Furthermore, there is an urgent need to develop both physical and digital infrastructures for the preservation and dissemination of folklore. Cultural institutions should establish folklore libraries, museums, and digital archives, supervised by morally upright and culturally literate individuals.
8. In today's digital era, youths should be empowered with programming and media production skills to enable them to build websites, animations, games, and applications inspired by folklore. This approach blends tradition with innovation and opens economic opportunities for youth.
9. More importantly, the use of social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and TikTok should be strategically used for our advantage by circulating folklore content in engaging formats. Examples such as Lekan Olaleye, Ajoke Ewa Ede, and cultural initiatives like Afin Ilu demonstrate that folklore can thrive in digital spaces.
10. Government and private stakeholders should therefore support the development of indigenous social media platforms that promote local content, like China's model, thereby securing the moral and cultural education of Nigerian youths while fostering a broader cultural rebirth.

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**Bridging Faiths for Peace: A
Comparative Study of Krishna
Consciousness and Christian Theology in
Promoting Interreligious Harmony in
Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of interfaith dialogue and synergy between Christian theology and Hindu Krishna Consciousness to foster peace in Nigeria, a country characterized by deep religious diversity and ongoing interreligious tensions. Using a comparative theological approach and guided by Interfaith Dialogue Theory, the research investigates shared spiritual and ethical values that can support peacebuilding across religious boundaries. The methodology involves critical analysis of existing literature and credible internet sources to examine the core teachings of both traditions. Despite their theological differences particularly regarding the nature of God and the means of salvation both traditions strongly affirm divine love, ethical conduct, and the pursuit of spiritual realization. The study identifies meaningful points of convergence that can serve as foundations for interreligious understanding and collaboration in Nigeria. These include shared moral values, emphasis on compassion, and a commitment to community upliftment. By engaging an Eastern Dharmic and a Western Abrahamic tradition, this research addresses a significant gap

in Nigerian interfaith discourse. Furthermore, the explicit focus on Christian theology (a dominant Western Abrahamic tradition) and Hindu Krishna Consciousness (an Eastern Dharmic tradition) addresses a notable gap in existing interfaith literature concerning Nigeria, which often prioritizes Abrahamic faiths. This choice challenges prevailing academic paradigms by exploring convergences and divergences between distinct religious families, thereby contributing to a more inclusive and globally representative understanding of interfaith peacebuilding. It suggests that valuable insights for conflict resolution can be found by examining a broader spectrum of spiritual traditions, moving beyond an Abrahamic-centric lens.

Keywords: Krishna Consciousness, Christian Theology, Interreligious Harmony, Peacebuilding, Nigeria

Introduction

The religious landscape of Nigeria is diverse and dynamic, with numerous distinct communities and religious leadership that has influence well beyond the country's borders. There are roughly equal numbers of Christians mainly in the South and Muslims mainly in the North although some studies indicate a slight majority of Muslims. Communities of other faiths are active, including Hindu, Baha'i, and Buddhist groups. Indigenous and traditional religious beliefs and leaders are a powerful influence, with much overlap between these beliefs and those of other traditions (Marshall, 2020). Religion could serve, and has indeed served as an instrument of social harmony in many civilizations (Sampson, 2012). The global perspective draws attention to the important but diverse roles that religious institutions influenced by political, cultural, and religious contexts play in preventing crises and promoting peace. Religious authorities frequently serve as moral guides and mediators, even though they may be constrained by secular governments and legal systems. They usually play a supporting role in peace initiatives, with the United Nations and other organizations taking the lead, in more secular societies (Anthony, 2020). One instance is the peace process in Northern Ireland, where formal agreements were mediated by political actors after discussions were facilitated by religious leaders. In contrast, although the state was in charge of the larger peacebuilding process, religious leaders were instrumental in Rwanda's post-genocide reconciliation. In general, religious organizations lead peace initiatives in Nigeria, even though they frequently work with official interventions worldwide (Tenaw, 2018).

Despite religion's potential to promote harmony, Nigeria continues to experience persistent interreligious tensions that fuel violence, social instability, and hinder national development. Existing interfaith initiatives often lack a deep theological understanding of different religions, limiting their effectiveness. A major challenge is the limited awareness of similarities between Eastern and Western religious traditions. While interfaith literature in Nigeria is extensive, there is a notable gap concerning the comparison between Krishna Consciousness and Christian theology. Most studies focus on Abrahamic faiths, overlooking Eastern traditions' contributions to peacebuilding. This gap reveals a systemic bias within interfaith studies that not only distorts academic discourse but also restricts practical peacebuilding efforts. By neglecting valuable ethical frameworks and shared values in non-Abrahamic traditions, opportunities for broader societal cohesion are lost. This study therefore advocates for a more inclusive, comparative approach, recognizing that all spiritual traditions regardless of origin or size offer meaningful contributions to interfaith dialogue and conflict resolution in Nigeria. This study aims to explore the theological foundations of Krishna Consciousness that are relevant to interreligious dialogue, and to outline the key principles of Christian theology that align with or differ from it. It further seeks to conduct a comparative analysis of both traditions, highlighting areas of convergence and divergence. Ultimately, the study evaluates how their shared values can contribute meaningfully to fostering interreligious harmony within the Nigerian context.

To achieve these objectives, the paper will examine primary religious texts (Bhagavad Gita, Bible) and authoritative commentaries, analyze theological doctrines, ethical principles, and spiritual practices, and review existing scholarship on interfaith dialogue, religious studies, and Nigerian socio-religious dynamics. This comprehensive approach seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the core theological tenets of Krishna Consciousness and Christian theology that are relevant to interreligious harmony?
2. What are the key points of convergence and divergence between these two religious traditions concerning divine love, ethical living, and spiritual realization?

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3. How can the shared values and principles of Krishna Consciousness and Christian theology be leveraged to promote interreligious harmony in the Nigerian context?

Theoretical Framework

Interfaith dialogue is essentially the discussion between adherents of two or more religious traditions. Conference-style formats focus on a particular topic, while small groups may meet regularly to discuss important aspects of their faith. Dialogue comes from the Greek words *di* and *logos*: “*di*” meaning two and “*logos*” meaning speech, or the reason that governs the universe, (e.g., divine wisdom). Interfaith dialogue focuses on various aspects of *logos*; it strives for insight and knowledge found in religious discourse. In this way, the particularity of a discussion defines what is a “better dialogue” than another because those judging the criteria would have to consider what is most important to the religious traditions that are involved. In Greek terms this would be *logos*, but in current religious expression that which is most important is considered on a case-by-case basis. Interfaith dialogue is considered a means of encountering a religious Other. Interfaith dialogue is often depicted as a means of building relationships (Naiper, 2011).

Two key concepts of interfaith dialogue are its ability to recognize differences among participants and its commitment to not attempting to reach consensus. One way to accommodate difference is to pay attention to language barriers: whose language is used to conduct discussions and in what space matters for the outcome (Abu-Nimer et al. 2007). When people feel comfortable communicating, true dialogue can begin. Shapiro notes (as cited by Naiper), “Here the emphasis is not to state positions but to understand the person. Here the emphasis is not on doctrine or dogma but on the human quest for meaning, purpose and wonder.” This type of dialogue will “honor the differences in faith at the same time... recognize similarities.” In this way the unity and community built around dialogue does not promote sameness. If there are similarities, they are shared. If there are differences, they are respected. Paul Mojzes cited by Naiper points out this guiding principle: “no synthesis is expected.” It is important for participants to feel comfortable and not to be forced, overtly or covertly, to compromise or change their beliefs. Authentic interfaith dialogue is focused on the human aspect rather than predetermined theological outcomes

(Naiper, 2011). In the Nigerian context, where religious identity often intersects with ethnic and political tensions, interfaith dialogue can serve as a transformative platform for social cohesion. By focusing on shared ethical concerns such as justice, compassion, and peace, dialogue between Krishna Conscious and Christian communities can challenge the exclusivism that fuels religious mistrust.

Literature Review

Krishna Consciousness

Krishna consciousness is eternal, having no beginning or origin, as it has always existed. In the *Bhagavad-gita*, Lord Krishna first transmitted this teaching to Vivasvan, the sun god, who passed it to Manu, then to *Ikshvaku*, through a process called *disciplic* succession. This method ensures the teachings are passed without personal interpretation, preserving their purity like a mailman delivering a letter unchanged. Over time, this succession broke, and 5,000 years ago, Krishna re-established it by teaching Arjuna in India, a moment recorded in the *Bhagavad-gita*. Thus, Krishna consciousness remains unbroken, eternal, and beyond concepts of ancient or modern (ISKCON, 1970). The Hare Krishna movement, officially the International Society for Krishna Consciousness (ISKCON), was founded in 1965 by A.C. Bhaktivedanta Swami Prabhupada. Rooted in Chaitanya Mahaprabhu's 16th-century bhakti tradition, it emphasizes devotion through chanting the Hare Krishna mantra. Followers view Krishna as the Supreme Lord and seek liberation from reincarnation through devotion. ISKCON promotes vegetarianism, celibacy, and simple living. Despite early controversies, it expanded rapidly, establishing 225 centers in 60 countries by the 1990s under a global Governing Board Commission (Melton, 2025).

Core Tenets

Bhakti Yoga: The Path of Devotion

Bhakti yoga (Sanskrit: भक्ति योग), also called *Bhakti marga* (भक्ति मार्ग, literally the path of *bhakti*), is a spiritual path or spiritual practice within Hinduism focused on loving devotion towards any personal deity. *Bhakti Yoga*, is the fourth path of the four primary paths of yoga in the yoga philosophy. It is also known as the "Path of Devotion". This yoga path, the practitioners keep their primary focus on the cultivation of love and devotion towards the Divine, which leads to spiritual growth as well as ultimate

liberation (*moksha*) (Ashram, 2024). Lord Krishna extends a powerful assurance:

"सवमिमामन्परत्यज्यमामेकं शरित्रज। अहंत्वासवमपापेभ्योमोक्षधयष्याधममाशुचः॥"
(Bhagavad Gita 18.66) "Abandon all varieties of dharma and simply surrender unto me. I shall deliver you from all sinful reactions. Do not fear."
In this verse, Krishna urges Arjuna and all devotees to surrender completely to Him, promising liberation from sin and suffering. This surrender is an act of strength, not weakness, requiring trust, courage, and the letting go of ego and desires. Bhakti Yoga, the path of love and devotion, fosters an intimate connection with the divine, encouraging humility, gratitude, and trust in God's will. In today's world of stress and disconnection, Bhakti offers unity, peace, and a sense of belonging. Its essence is unconditional, selfless love, like a child's trust in a parent. Simple yet powerful, Bhakti is accessible to everyone (Mohan Lal & Sharma, 2025).

The Nature of God (Krishna)

Krishna is among the most revered and popular deities in Indian religious tradition, worshipped both as the eighth avatar of Vishnu and as the Supreme God. Central to numerous bhakti (devotional) movements, his life and teachings have inspired rich traditions of poetry, music, and visual art. His mythology is primarily drawn from the *Mahabharata*, *Harivamsha*, and *Bhagavata Purana*, particularly Books X and XI. These texts recount his miraculous birth to Vasudeva and Devaki, and his early life in Gokula, where he was raised by Nanda and Yashoda after being rescued from King Kamsa's threats. Krishna's persona synthesizes various roles: the heroic Vasudeva-Krishna, the pastoral cowherd god, and the supreme Vishnu-Narayana. His worship emphasizes divine love, especially through his playful and intimate interactions with the gopis, symbolizing the soul's longing for God. In art, he is portrayed as Balakrishna, the butter-loving child, or the divine flute player, often depicted with blue-black skin, yellow garments, and a peacock-feather crown (Britannica, 2025).

The Soul (Atman)

In order to understand the Hindu world-view it is essential to grasp this foundational concept. *Atman* refers to the non-material self, which never changes. It is distinct from both the mind and the external body. This real self is beyond the temporary designations we normally ascribe to ourselves,

in terms of race, gender, species and nationality. Ideas of reincarnation are natural extensions of this preliminary concept. Consciousness, wherever it is found, is considered a symptom of the soul, and without it the body has no awareness. This life-giving soul is considered spirit (*brahman*), differentiating it from inert matter. Belief in the soul is not just theoretical or the property of theologians, but is a worldview expressed by Hindus in all walks of life (Heart of Hinduism, n.d.). In Bhagavad Gita verses 10-30 of the second chapter, Krishna urges Arjuna to understand the indestructible nature of the *atman*, emphasizing that it transcends the finite body it inhabits. The *atman* neither kills nor can be killed, as it is eternal and unaffected by birth or death. The analogy of changing clothes is used to illustrate how the soul discards old bodies for new ones. Krishna emphasizes the eternal existence of the soul by explaining that even as it undergoes various life stages and changes bodies it remains unaffected. It is imperceptible, inconceivable, and unchanging (Bhaktivedanta, 1983).

The Path to Spiritual Liberation

In Indian philosophy and the Bhagavad Gita, *moksha* is the supreme goal: the soul's eternal, natural state, liberated from suffering and the cycle of birth and death. This transcendental perfection involves union with God, realizing Brahman (*Brahmanirvanam*), a state beyond duality. Attaining *moksha* requires mental purification, ego dissolution, intellectual development, detachment, and self-control through disciplines like meditation and devotion. The liberated self, achieves tranquility, perceives unity, transcends ego and mortality, and attains eternal peace and perfection, surpassing Vedic merits. *Moksha* signifies union with both Brahman and Krishna (Bora 2013).

Ethical principles: Dharma, Karma, and Reincarnation

The Krishna consciousness lifestyle is fundamentally shaped by the ethical principles of dharma (righteous duty), karma (cause and effect), and reincarnation (soul's transmigration). Rooted in Vedic wisdom and elaborated in foundational Bhakti texts, these interconnected concepts guide spiritual aspirants towards self-realization and divine connection, culminating in pure love of Godhead (Prema). Dharma directs actions towards spiritual truth, while karma emphasizes personal responsibility for consequences impacting future experiences. Reincarnation underscores the

significance of ethical conduct for one's subsequent journey. Adherence to these principles and surrender to Krishna's will are central to achieving liberation (Klostermaier, 2007).

Krishna Consciousness and Its Philosophical Foundations

Krishna consciousness is deeply rooted in Vedic Vaishnava philosophy, emphasizing Prema Bhakti, loving devotion as the highest spiritual practice. In the purport to chapter three verse three of the Bhagavat-Gita as it is, Srila Prabhupada emphasizes this fact when he said, "Religion without philosophy is sentiment, or sometimes fanaticism, while philosophy without religion is mental speculation. The ultimate goal is *Kṛṣṇa*, because the philosophers who are also sincerely searching after the Absolute Truth come in the end to *Kṛṣṇa* consciousness. This is also stated in the Bhagavad-gītā. The whole process is to understand the real position of the self in relation to the Superself." (Rochford, 1985).

Krishna Consciousness and Dharma

The word "*Dharma*" is commonly translated to mean "Religion." However, In Vaishnava Krishna Consciousness, "Dharma" transcends the common translation of "religion," signifying "Sanatana Dharma," the soul's eternal duty distinct from changeable Western religious faith (Siddhi-Lalasa Dasi, 1999). This understanding of the self's spiritual nature and duty underpins Krishna Conscious ethics. The Bhagavad-Gita (2:13) describes the soul's transmigration through bodies at death. The Bhagavad-gita and Srimad Bhagavatam outline the soul's nature and the path to *moksha* and divine love. Srimad Bhagavatam (1.1.2) presents the highest truth for God realization, while (1.2.10) directs desires towards Absolute Truth inquiry. Bhagavad-Gita (17.15) emphasizes ethical speech as a human principle.

Understanding Karma in the Context of Krishna's Teachings

Krishna Consciousness, grounded in texts like the *Bhagavad Gita*, emphasizes karma as the law of action, reaction, and moral causality. Bhagavad Gita 2:47 teaches that one should perform prescribed duties without attachment to outcomes. Srila Prabhupada outlines three forms of karma: Sanchita (accumulated past actions), Prarabdha (karma manifesting in the present life), and Kriyamana (current actions shaping future experiences). Ethical living in Krishna Consciousness involves

selfless action guided by dharma (righteous duty), cultivating positive karma and spiritual advancement. Actions motivated by kindness and sincerity yield favorable consequences, while challenges are seen as opportunities for growth rooted in past karma. By emphasizing effort over results, Krishna Consciousness nurtures patience, humility, and compassion, promoting harmony in relationships. Understanding karma fosters detachment from greed and lust, leading to a more ethical and balanced life. This approach transforms everyday experiences into a spiritual journey, where inner peace and divine connection are achieved through dutiful, selfless living (Goswami, 2001).

Reincarnation and Krishna Consciousness

In Vedic texts, reincarnation, termed *Samsara*, signifies the soul's binding to the cycle of birth and death. While popularized globally, the concept often remains a superficial notion, even for believers, lacking clear understanding beyond being reborn as another individual (Siddhi-Lalasa Dasi, 1999). Although reincarnation is often rejected by many Western Abrahamic traditions, survey data shows that a notable number of individuals still believe in it. In Krishna Consciousness, reincarnation is a core teaching, as outlined in *Bhagavad-Gita* 2:30, which affirms that every living being has an eternal soul that undergoes repeated births. Before reaching human form, the soul may pass through various species and levels of consciousness, gradually evolving. The physical body is seen as a temporary vessel for the soul. This cycle of rebirth continues as the soul explores different material experiences driven by lingering desires. However, not every soul must pass through all forms of life before attaining human birth. Vaishnava texts, especially *Bhagavad-Gita* 8:6, emphasize that the state of one's consciousness at the moment of death determines the nature of the next life. The thoughts and actions developed throughout life shape this final consciousness, which then influences the soul's journey into the next existence (Rosen, 2007).

Christian Theology

In more general modern usage, Christian theology is the systematic and critical representation, explication, examination, and elaboration of the content and form of Christian faith. It seeks to represent Christianity's statements of belief coherently, to explicate them by reference to their

foundations and contexts, to examine their significance and resilience, and to elaborate them in relation to new questions and discoveries. The substance of theology is usually divided into two groups: God, and God's relation to the world. Within the first, theology asks questions about the character of God as triune (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit), and as described by traditional perfections such as eternity, simplicity, omnipotence, omniscience, omnipresence, and omnibenevolence. Within the second, its subjects include the creation of the world, the nature of human beings, the incarnation of the Son, the achievement of salvation, the activity of the Holy Spirit, the constitution of the church, and the 'last things' or end of the created order (Wolfe 2022).

Core Tenets

The Trinity

Most Christians believe God is spirit, uncreated, omnipotent, eternal, and the creator and sustainer of all things, redeeming the world through Jesus Christ. Central to Christian faith is the doctrine of the Trinity, one divine *ousia* (substance) in three inseparable *hypostases* (persons): Father, Son (Jesus Christ the Logos), and Holy Spirit. This reflects God's self-revelation as Creator, Redeemer, and Helper. Though "Trinity" is absent in the New Testament, verses like Matthew 28:19 and 2 Corinthians 13:13 support it. Developed amid controversies, the doctrine emerged by the 4th century, affirming one essence and three distinct, coequal persons against views like Arianism and modalism (Britannica 2025). The doctrine of the Trinity is the most distinctively Christian understanding of God, affirming one divine being existing eternally as three co-equal, co-eternal, and co-substantial persons: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. It is not belief in three gods but in one unified God in relational communion. Karl Barth, in *Church Dogmatics*, presents the Trinity as central to Christian theology, revealed through the Word and the Spirit (Barth 1936-1975). John Calvin, in *Institutes of the Christian Religion*, emphasizes the Trinity's role in God's self-revelation and redemption, affirming unity and distinct personhood within the Godhead (Calvin 1960).

The Nature of God

The Christian view of God presents Him as omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent signifying unlimited power, knowledge, and presence. He

exists eternally as three distinct persons: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit. God's power, evident in creation (Genesis 1:1) and miracles, is guided by kindness and mercy. His omniscience, as stated in Psalm 147:5 and Romans 8:28, assures believers of His all-knowing wisdom. God's omnipresence, affirmed in Deuteronomy 31:6, brings constant comfort. Central to His nature are love, grace, and justice offering forgiveness, compassion, and hope. John 3:16 exemplifies God's infinite, unconditional love through the gift of His Son. Thomas Aquinas, in *Summa Theologiae*, provides a philosophical foundation for God's attributes simplicity, perfection, omnipresence, immutability, and eternity (Aquinas 2020). R.C. Sproul (1985), in *The Holiness of God* (1985), emphasizes that holiness is not merely one of God's traits but the essence from which all others flow; His moral perfection and separateness commanding awe and worship. God remains the ultimate standard of goodness and justice (Sproul 1985).

Salvation Through Jesus Christ

At the core of Christian hope is the belief in salvation through Jesus Christ. Humanity, separated from God by sin, is reconciled through Christ, who is fully God and fully human (hypostatic union). He lived a sinless life, died on the cross, and rose from the dead. His death is seen as atonement, reconciling humanity to a holy God. John Stott (1986) explores atonement theories, including penal substitution, moral influence, and governmental views, revealing how Christ's sacrifice addresses sin from various angles. Gustaf Aulén (1969) emphasizes Christ's triumph over sin, death, and the devil. Jesus's resurrection affirms this victory and guarantees believers' future resurrection. N. T. Wright (2016) argues the crucifixion inaugurated a new creation and redefined humanity's purpose. Salvation is not achieved by human effort but is a divine gift, received through faith in Christ's redemptive work on the cross and His resurrection.

The Concept of Divine Love (Agape)

Agape, in the New Testament, refers to God's unconditional, self-giving love for humanity and the reciprocal love humans are called to show toward God and others. Distinct from *eros* (passionate love) and *philia* (brotherly love), *agape* is the highest form of love, marked by selflessness, sacrifice, and altruism (John 3:16; Romans 5:8). Early Christians expressed this love through fellowship meals, sometimes associated with the Eucharist

(Petruzzello, 2025). Anders Nygren (1932) drew a clear line between divine agape spontaneous and unmotivated and human, acquisitive love, though this dichotomy has faced critique. Edward Vacek (1994) further explores agape's ethical dimensions, asserting it as the foundation of Christian morality. Agape is not merely an emotion but a deliberate, active commitment to seek the good of others, regardless of their merit or response. Christians are called to embody this divine love in their relationships, mirroring God's love demonstrated in the redemptive sacrifice of Christ.

The Concept of Grace and Redemption

Grace

Christian theology centrally posits grace as God's unmerited favor and love extended to humanity, foundational for salvation and spiritual life. The New Testament (Ephesians 2:8-9) defines grace as the means of salvation through faith, a divine gift, not earned by works. Furthermore, grace is a transformative power, enabling righteous living (Titus 2:11-14) (Youvan 2024). Historically, theologians like Augustine emphasized its necessity for salvation and growth (Objantoro 2020). The Reformation, notably through Luther and Calvin, underscored grace in justification by faith alone, distinguishing Protestant theology. The Greek term "*charis*" denotes undeserved kindness and goodwill. Grace in Christian theology is understood as unmerited favor, freely given and not earned. It distinguishes Christianity from belief systems that emphasize works to gain divine favor. Grace offers salvation to sinners regardless of their past actions or worthiness. Ephesians 2:8-9 affirms that salvation is by grace through faith, a gift from God, not a result of human effort. Beyond salvation, grace acts as a transformative force. According to Titus 2:11-12, it teaches believers to reject ungodliness and live righteous, self-controlled lives. Thus, grace both redeems and empowers believers to reflect God's righteousness in daily living.

Redemption

In Christian soteriology, redemption is a pivotal concept encompassing God's saving work throughout redemptive history. It serves as the central framework for understanding salvation. Redemption (Greek: *apolutrósis*) refers to Christ's role as a ransom, purchasing and delivering humanity from sin's bondage and condemnation through His sacrificial death. The

New Testament presents His blood as the perfect expiation for sin, securing liberation from guilt, sin, and divine wrath. This underscores God's initiative and the costly nature of salvation, highlighting Christ's substitutionary atonement. The language of ransom emphasizes liberation from captivity through a deliberate and costly act. (Duncan, n.d.).

Comparative Analysis: Krishna Consciousness and Christian Theology

The analysis draws upon sacred texts *Bhagavad Gita* and the Bible as well as authoritative commentaries, within the scope of Interfaith Dialogue Theory, which emphasizes respectful engagement, recognition of difference, and relationship-building without erasing doctrinal boundaries.

Nature of the Divine

Christian theology emphasizes monotheism expressed through Trinitarianism; God as Father, Son, and Holy Spirit whose essence is love, holiness, and justice. Krishna Consciousness likewise affirms monotheism but conceives Krishna as the Supreme Personality of Godhead. While Christian theology stresses God's transcendence and immanence, Krishna Consciousness presents God as a personal deity with whom intimate devotional relationships are possible.

Human Nature and Salvation

In Christianity, humans are created in God's image but alienated by sin, requiring reconciliation through Jesus Christ. In Krishna Consciousness, the soul (*atman*) is eternally pure but entrapped in material bondage due to ignorance and karma, requiring liberation through Bhakti (devotion). Salvation in Christianity is by grace through faith; in Krishna Consciousness, it is through surrendered devotion, ethical discipline, and chanting Krishna's name.

Ethical Frameworks

Christian ethics are grounded in divine command and modeled on Christ's agapeic love. Krishna Conscious ethics are rooted in dharma (righteous action), karma (moral causality), and the cultivation of humility and service through Bhakti. Both stress moral transformation as essential to spiritual fulfillment.

Love as a Central Virtue

Christian agape and Krishna Consciousness's *prema bhakti* both represent divine, selfless love that motivates compassionate action. This parallel reflects shared moral goals that transcend doctrinal dissimilarities and create a theological foundation for peace-oriented collaboration.

Findings

1. **Complementary Ethical Ideals:** Both traditions advocate ethical living grounded in divine expectations whether it is the Christian imperative of Christlike living or Krishna Consciousness's adherence to dharma and karma. These frameworks promote societal virtues such as nonviolence, integrity, and communal responsibility.
2. **Shared Emphasis on Divine Love:** Agape and Prema Bhakti serve similar spiritual functions: both are expressive of divine intimacy and provide moral guidance for interpersonal relationships. They are both relational, active, and transformative, thus forming a potential bridge for collaborative service projects and moral education in pluralistic societies.
3. **Distinct Soteriologies, Shared Aspirations:** While the Christian concept of salvation hinges on grace through faith in Christ's redemptive work, Krishna Consciousness emphasizes liberation through devotional purity and self-discipline. Despite divergent metaphysical assumptions, both traditions value inner transformation, detachment from selfish desire, and a reorientation toward the divine.
4. **Underrepresentation of Eastern Traditions in Nigerian Interfaith Engagement:** The paper reveals a critical gap in Nigerian interfaith discourse, which is disproportionately focused on Abrahamic interactions. This oversight limits the scope of dialogue and weakens potential peacebuilding efforts that could benefit from the ethical richness of Dharmic faiths like Krishna Consciousness.
5. **The Potential of Interfaith Dialogue Theory in Nigerian Peacebuilding:** The dialogical approach advanced by Interfaith Dialogue Theory is particularly suited to Nigeria's complex religious landscape. By recognizing both shared moral objectives and irreconcilable doctrinal differences, it fosters trust, mutual respect, and sustainable interreligious partnerships.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that Christian theology and Krishna Consciousness, despite their doctrinal divergences, offer rich, complementary insights that can foster interreligious harmony in Nigeria. Both traditions present robust theological frameworks centered on love, devotion, and ethical living values that are critical for addressing Nigeria's long-standing religious tensions. Importantly, the application of Interfaith Dialogue Theory reveals that peacebuilding does not require doctrinal compromise but a mutual commitment to understanding and relationship-building. When Christian and Krishna Conscious communities engage in genuine dialogue rooted in theological depth and mutual respect, new pathways for cooperation, service, and reconciliation become possible. This comparative theological inquiry challenges the Abrahamic-centric focus of most Nigerian interfaith efforts and calls for a broader, more inclusive paradigm. It affirms that Eastern religious traditions have much to offer in the pursuit of peace, and that a truly global theology of harmony must be grounded in the full spectrum of human spiritual experience.

Recommendations

1. ***Expand Interfaith Platforms to Include Dharmic Traditions:*** Interfaith councils, NGOs, and religious associations should broaden their membership to include Hindu and Vaishnava representatives, thus reflecting Nigeria's growing religious plurality.
2. ***Integrate Comparative Theology into Academic and Religious Education:*** Seminaries, religious studies departments, and faith-based institutions should introduce comparative theology courses to expose students to global religious traditions and their ethical frameworks.
3. ***Develop Joint Peacebuilding Programs Rooted in Shared Values:*** Faith-based organizations from both traditions can collaborate on humanitarian projects such as health care, education, and environmental initiatives that embody their mutual commitment to service and compassion.
4. ***Foster Grassroots Dialogue and Cultural Exchange:*** Local interfaith gatherings, community meals, and devotional music festivals can serve as informal but powerful tools for building trust and dismantling stereotypes.

5. **Encourage Research on Non-Abrahamic Contributions to Nigerian Peacebuilding:** Future scholarship should further investigate the practical and theological contributions of Hindu, Buddhist, and other Eastern traditions to peace efforts in Nigeria.

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The Aesthetic Functionality of Theatre Costumes in Dance Performances: A Study of the 2016 Imo State Carnival

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Abstract

Costume is one vital element of the theatre that if not given proper consideration can mar the primary idea of a creative piece. Therefore, a theatre costume must serve a theatrical role in its entirety. Carnival performances are artistically rich expressions that rely heavily on costumes not only for beauty, but also for their narrative qualities, movement facilitation and symbolic communication. The creation process of a choreographic piece is one that requires various considerations which costumes are a major part of. This research work focuses on the aesthetic value costumes place on the execution of dances in the 2016 Imo state carnival themed "Imo my Pride Carnival 2016" with the slogan "Ain't Seen Nothing Yet", taking an analytic insight on the ease and comfort of the dancers, interpretative ability of the costumes, performance technique, conceptualization and thematic clarity of the various costumes. The paper also examines the interplay between fabric choice, colour symbolism and the dynamic needs of dance movements. Adopting Roland Barthes' Semiotic Theory and Susanne Langer's Theory of Symbolic forms and Expression Theory of Art as a guide, this work employs the qualitative method of research comprising video analysis, photographic documentation, literature review, information gotten from interviews of costume designers,

dancers, and audience members of the 2016 Imo Sate Carnival. The findings establish that costumes in such cultural performances are not mere adornments but functional tools that bridge the visual and performative elements of dance, contributing significantly to the overall spectacle and message of the performance.

Keywords: Aesthetics, Costume, Choreographic, Conceptualization, Performative

Introduction

Choreography is a creative way of designing, arranging and joining movement phrases for different bodies to form a complete routine. The weight, shape, space, time and flow are factors that should be considered during the creation process as they contribute to a large extent, the outcome of a choreographed piece. The rehearsal process is seen as the testing ground for every effectual element that will be infused to aid the execution of a dance piece. At this stage all factors are put into consideration to see to the easy flow of a dance routine. Costume is one major determinant of the aesthetic makeup of a dance performance and this is as a result of its appeal and functionality. A dancer's costume gives detailed information of the style of dance that is being executed. This information elucidates the historical, occupational, cultural and social makeup of a dance piece.

The inclusion of special clothing in a given performance helps differentiate between a rehearsal and an actual presentation. Even though audience perception of a dance performance is subjective, the costumes help to interpret the choreographer's original idea through the chosen colours and designs which the costume designer has created. The fabrics used to produce these costumes are also important and are determined by the style of dance. Some costumes are created with thick and heavy fabrics while other are made with stretchy, light weight and soft fabrics. The costume designer has to make sure that the costumes are skin friendly and also put in mind the flexibility of the costumes during the production process, as this will add beauty to the movements, thereby heightening the visual pleasure of the audience and at the same time, help the dancers move freely in them.

Statement of the Problem

Carnivals in Nigeria are increasingly celebrated as vibrant displays of culture, music, dance, and art. While much attention has been given to musical acts, dance, and general entertainment, the critical role of costume in shaping the aesthetic and communicative essence of carnival

performances, particularly in the case of the Imo Carnival remains under-explored. A preliminary observation of carnival performances, both live and through media, reveals that costumes serve as the first point of visual engagement for the audience. They are powerful semiotic tools that convey cultural identity, interpret dance themes, and reinforce the overall narrative of a performance. Yet, many carnival performances suffer a disconnect between costume design and thematic intention. In several cases, performers wear costumes that lack symbolic alignment with the central message, resulting in a diluted or misinterpreted performance. Therefore, carnival themes that should find their strong voice in the display of appropriate costumes are weathered down or completely lost.

Despite their visual prominence, carnival costumes often receive minimal attention in planning and scholarship. This is especially true for the Imo Carnival, which remains under-researched in comparison to more popular events like the Calabar or Lagos carnivals. Costume designers face challenges such as insufficient budgets, time constraints, and limited collaboration with choreographers, which compromise the aesthetic and cultural quality of their output. Carnival organizers tend to invest heavily in music, comedy, and stage design, while underestimating the narrative and symbolic power embedded in costume. The result is a recurring thematic derailment in carnival performances, where costume choices fail to support the message or the historical and cultural context intended by the choreographers and performers.

This research, therefore, addresses the gap by critically exploring the role and impact of costume in Imo Carnival performances. It examines how costumes contribute to, enhance, or distort the thematic and symbolic essence of carnival dance, and how they can be optimized as tools for cultural expression and performance coherence.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to examine the aesthetic and symbolic functions of costume in carnival dance performances, with a specific focus on how costume contributes to the thematic expression, visual appeal, and cultural identity in the 2016 Imo Carnival. The objectives are

1. To explore the relationship between costume design and choreographic meaning in the 2016 Imo carnival dance performances.

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2. To analyze how costume contributes to the aesthetic experience and visual symbolism of the Imo Carnival.
 3. To identify the cultural, historical, and thematic messages embedded in the carnival costumes.
 4. To examine the extent to which costume enhances or distorts the intended message of carnival performances.
 5. To evaluate the challenges and limitations faced by costume designers in aligning designs with the central theme of the Imo Carnival.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research approach, utilizing both descriptive and interpretive strategies to investigate the aesthetic and symbolic significance of costumes in the Imo Carnival. The 2016 Imo Carnival serving as the focal point for examining how costumes function within Nigerian carnival performances.

Data collection techniques will include:

- **Observation** of recorded performances to assess the contextual use and visual impact of costumes.
- **Interviews** with key stakeholders such as costume designers, choreographers, dancers and some audience members to gather perspectives on costume creation, thematic alignment, and cultural symbolism.
- **Photographic and video documentation** to aid in detailed visual analysis of costume features and their interaction with performance.
- **Review of relevant documents**, including festival brochures, costume concept sketches, and existing literature on carnival culture and performance aesthetics in Nigeria.

The data gathered will be subjected to thematic analysis, guided by Langer's theory of symbolic forms and Barthes' semiotic framework, to interpret the communicative and expressive functions of costume within the performance environment.

Theoretical Framework

Roland Barthes' Semiotics Theory

This school of thought interprets costume as a system of signs that interconnects meaning to the audience. The colours, fabrics, and designs of carnival costumes convey information about identity, culture, and

narrative, which are decoded by viewers during performances. Barthes posits that “the photographic image...is a message without a code; from which proposition an important corollary must be immediately drawn: the photographic message is a continuous message.” (Barthes, 1977). His belief suggests that once the spectators view the costumes, meaning is decoded and it is unending. This goes to prove that in as much as the audience perception of costumes can be subjective, there is no costume without a message. He goes further to say “thanks to its code of connotation, the reading of the photograph is thus always historical; it depends on the reader’s ‘knowledge’ just as though it were a matter of real language, intelligible only if one has learned the signs.” (Barthes, 1977). Barthes philosophy sheds more light on the audience perception of costumes, which is the major end result of aesthetics. Costumes in dance performances and carnivals as in this case, are produced based on cultural and historical codes. The audience are able to decode the costumes based on their cultural intimations, elevating the performances’ narrative.

“Every sign supposes a code... ‘Every sign is a signifier – signified – sign’ in a tri-dimensional structure.” (Barthes, 1977). Barthes sets the foundational model of semiotics: the signifier (visual), the signified (conception), and the sign (the message). For example, a headgear painted red (signifier) may signify passion (signified) within the performance. The relationship between the headgear and passion (which could be represented through elements such lines, space, shape or colour in this case becomes the sign that is decoded by the audience. He informs us that “visual mediums are perceived as portraying reality while in fact they are constructing it.” (Barthes, 1977). As simple and easy as costumes may seem, they build social, cultural and thematic concepts that shape audience perception of a performance.

Susanne Langer’s Theory of Symbolic forms and Expression Theory of Art:

This study is grounded in Susan Langer’s Theory of Symbolic forms, which presents art as a form of non-discursive expression that interprets complex emotions and experiences. According to Langer (1953), “art is the creation of forms symbolic of human feeling”. In carnivals and other dance performances, these symbols are created through the elements which include space, movement, time, energy, each exemplifying meaning. Within this broader framework lies Langer’s Expression Theory of Art, which tells us that art does not only show emotions but also gives meaning to feelings. She says that “the artist’s job is not to feel, but to create a form in which

feeling can be communicated.” Langer’s view explains that the performer is a vehicle through which expressions rather than emotions are conveyed to the audience. Costumes when integrated into dance performances, go beyond beautification and functionality. They become an extension of the dancer’s body, transforming movements and emotions into visual form, which enhances the emotive experience of the performance.

Literature Review

In a dance performance, costume plays a vital role in communicating the underlying idea of a dance piece to its audience. The texture, style and colour contribute a great deal to the execution of the dance piece. At the first glance of a costume on the body of the performer, the historical, social, cultural, occupational and geographical meaning is established even before the performance commences. The costumes create a sense of belonging for the audience and increases their ability to relate with the dance that is being performed.

For a dance performance, little can be said about the fluidity of movements on the part of the dancers if reasonable consideration is not given to the dexterity the costumes play in relation to the dance movement. Therefore, a costumier must work closely with the choreographer in order to understand his/her creative ideas, dance patterns and floor movements so as to come up with costumes that complement the dance in style, colour, comfort, fluidity and idea interpretation.

Carnivals are socio-cultural spectacles rooted in communal expression, identity, and celebration. Scholars such as Falassi (1987) argues that carnivals operate as ritualistic performances that bring together music, dance, costume, and social commentary. In Nigeria, major carnivals such as Calabar and Lagos have received attention for their economic, political, and cultural significance, but the Imo Carnival remains under-examined in academic discourse. Existing literature often emphasizes entertainment value and tourism, neglecting the deep symbolic layers embedded in the visual components of performance. A very significant aspect of a carnival is the aesthetics portrayed by carefully crafted costumes worn by the participants in the different dance trains. The role of costumes in a carnival train and dance cannot be overemphasized, thus making it a vital part of the carnival.

Costume is more than attire; it is a visual language that conveys character, status, emotion, and theme. Monks (2010), explores how costume performs a central role in theatrical meaning-making, shaping audience interpretation and embodying character identity. In the context of carnival, where performance is public and spectacular, costume becomes a primary visual cue that sets the tone for audience interpretation. Scholars such as Adshead-Lansdale and Layson (1994) emphasize that costume and choreography must be designed in tandem to ensure coherence between visual and kinesthetic expression.

In carnival dance, costumes contribute to rhythm, color dynamics, and symbolic meaning. When used effectively, they enhance the flow of movement and deepen the audience's engagement with the performance.

Costume and Performer Experience

Some studies directly explore how costume affects dancer comfort, mobility, and emotional expression. Scholars such as Dils and Albright (2001) have noted that bodily experience and physical environment, including costume, directly impact performance quality. Discomfort caused by poorly designed costumes can restrict movement and dilute expressiveness, whereas well-considered designs enhance both physical ease and emotional connection with the role. This aspect is essential to carnival dance, which often demands extended physical exertion in open-air conditions, requiring costumes that balance aesthetics with practicality. Costume designers must therefore consider materials, climate, body types, and choreographic demands in the production process.

Costumes are not merely visual enhancements but are vital components of performance meaning-making. Through the lenses of semiotics and symbolic theory, the literature provides tools for analyzing how costume communicates culture, emotion, and narrative. The review also identifies key gaps in scholarship that justify the present study. The next chapter outlines the methodology employed to explore these themes within the context of the Imo Carnival.

A Brief History of the Imo State Carnival

The Imo carnival is one of the foremost carnivals in Nigeria tagged the "celebration of unity" as its main purpose is to promote the unanimity of all the festivals held in the state. The carnival was created as part of the vision

to make the culture of Imo state appreciated by Nigerians and the world at large. The carnival however, has been designed to be an annual event which commences on the 16th of December and lasts till the 31st of December. The yearly event has boosted the cultural mosaic of Nigeria in the process of entertaining millions of spectators/tourists within and outside the domain of the state. This helps to boost the tourism industry for all stakeholders. The carnival has boosted the cultural mosaic of Nigeria by entertaining millions of spectators/tourists within and outside the domain of the state. This helps to boost the tourism industry for all stakeholders. Notably, Buchi George, the initiator and the founder of the carnival is also the executive director of the Imo Carnival Development Commission.

The carnival was held for the first time in the year 2011, adopting the name, Imo carnival. It envisions to celebrate the unity of all the festivals in the state (GoWhereWhen, n.d.). Imo state carnival presents a platform for brand visibility for consumer and market awareness. It promotes cultural heritage, unite Nigerians despite the ethnic diversity and at the same time strengthen the capacity of locals to participate in the carnival in terms of economic benefits. The carnival employs different performances to boost the aesthetics of the event. These include, Ahianjoku festival, Ozunimo festival, Mmanwu, fashion shows, traditional wrestling, Okorocho dance, traditional dances, beauty pageants, Mr. and Miss Tourism Imo being the top beauty pageant held and a massive street parade, Igbo Poetry and talk show, masquerade band, traditional and contemporary musical performance. The carnival also creates an avenue for all traditional rulers and members of the royal cabinet to be part of the celebration.

Findings

The findings of the study were gathered from data that was collected through interviews, observations, document reviews, and visual analysis of costumes used in the 2016 Imo Carnival themed “Imo my Pride” with the slogan “Ain’t Seen Nothing Yet”. The thematic analysis yielded the following findings:

Relationship between Costume Design and Choreographic Meaning

The costume design was found to be closely tied to the choreographic intent in Imo Carnival performances. Designers and choreographers collaborated to ensure that costume features such as flexibility, colour contrast, and

fabric movement supported the dance's rhythm and energy. For example, lightweight, stretchable fabrics were preferred for routines with fast-paced choreography, while heavier materials were used for more regal, symbolic portrayals. Participants agreed that costume choices often influenced the development of movement and helped communicate the dancer's role more effectively.

Contribution of Costume to Aesthetic Experience and Visual Symbolism

Costumes were described as the most visually captivating aspect of the Imo Carnival. They played a key role in enhancing the audience's experience by creating spectacle, representing local identity, and attracting media attention. Colours, symbols, and exaggeration in costume designs contributed significantly to visual storytelling. Interviewees emphasized that without compelling costumes, the carnival would lose its vibrancy and cultural magnetism.

Cultural, Historical, and Thematic Messages in Carnival Costumes

The study reveals that costume designers embedded significant cultural and historical meanings into their work. Costumes referenced the Nigerian heritage, folklore, traditional occupations, and community struggles. For instance, the Deputy Governor's band were dressed in costumes inspired by Igbo masquerades with stilt walkers, while others used designs to tell stories of colonial resistance or environmental issues. Costumes such as sports wears and graduation gowns could also be seen on participants to symbolize the theme "Imo my Pride" and to showcase the state's love for sports and education. However, a few costumes appeared generic, lacking cultural symbols or alignment with the carnival's theme, due to time pressure or limited cultural research.

Costume as a Tool for Enhancing or Distorting Performance Themes

While costumes often help clarify a performance's intent, the study found several instances where poor costume choices weakened the message. For example, some bands interpreting a traditional concept wore modern, glittery fabrics that clashed with the narrative. Such mismatches caused confusion among spectators and critics. Overall, participants agreed that when costumes were well-aligned with the storyline, they deepened audience engagement and understanding.

Challenges Faced by Costume Designers in Theme Alignment

Designers reported multiple constraints affecting their work. These included tight budgets, time constraints, and lack of skilled artisans. Many expressed concerns about the dominance of Western fashion influences that overshadowed indigenous creativity. Others mentioned limited access to culturally appropriate materials, which affected authenticity. Despite these challenges, most designers remained committed to preserving cultural integrity through their work.

The Deputy Governor's Band, Imo State Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Imo House of Assembly Band in their Dance Costumes

Dance costumes, Imo Carnival 2016

Dance costumes and Train, Imo Carnival 2016

Costumes with Graduation Caps Showing Imo State's love for Education

Mr and Miss Imo Carnival 2016 Pageant

Mr and Miss Imo Carnival 2016 Pageant

Discussion of Findings

Costume as an Extension of Choreographic Intent

The findings affirm that costume design is not a separate element from choreography, but an integral part of it. This is consistent with Susanne Langer's theory of symbolic forms, which suggests that artistic elements express patterns of feeling and internal experience. The study found that some of the costumes were consciously designed to complement specific movement styles and rhythms. Lightweight and stretchable materials were used to facilitate fluid movement, while elaborate and heavier costumes were assigned to dancers playing regal or symbolic roles. This aligns with Langer's view that art objectifies subjective feeling, and costumes in dance do this visually through form, texture, and motion. The relationship between body and costume, therefore, is a dynamic interaction where the costume influences not only how the dancer appears but how the dancer moves.

Designers and choreographers collaborated to ensure that costume features such as flexibility, colour contrast, and fabric movement supported the dance's rhythm and energy. For example, lightweight, stretchable fabrics were preferred for routines with fast-paced choreography, while heavier materials were used for more regal, symbolic portrayals. Participants agreed that costume choices often influenced the development of movement phrases and helped communicate the dancer's role more effectively. While dancer comfort and mobility were central concerns in the findings, some dancers in other bands expressed discomfort with costumes that were too tight, too heavy, or made of materials that caused irritation. These physical constraints not only limited their range of motion but also detracted from the emotional expressiveness and technical delivery of the performance. On the other hand, when costumes were designed with dancer input factoring in heat, stretch, fit, and weight, performers reported a sense of confidence, freedom, and enhanced embodiment of their characters. Thus, the functional relationship between costume design and dancer comfort is crucial for achieving a fluid and emotionally resonant performance.

Costumes and the Aesthetic Experience of Carnival

Costumes were consistently identified as central to the visual and emotional impact of the Imo Carnival. Participants emphasized that before any

choreography begins, the audience's first impression is shaped by what the performers wear. This underscores Barthes' (1977) notion that visual elements operate as systems of signification: they speak before the performers do. The costume acts as a "continuous message" (Barthes, 1977), setting the tone for the audience's emotional and interpretive experience. Whether adorned with cultural symbols, feathers, or elaborate headpieces, carnival costumes offer a non-verbal language that communicates mood, cultural identity, and status. This also supports Langer's view that art, especially performance, is a symbolic form that communicates human feeling without the use of discursive language.

Cultural, Historical, and Thematic Interpretation through Costume

A significant finding of the study was the use of costume to convey cultural and historical messages. Designs reflected Igbo heritage, referencing local legends, occupations, and traditional aesthetics. In line with Barthes' semiotic theory, these costumes functioned as signs, where specific elements (e.g., uli patterns, animal symbols, masquerade costumes and masks) were signifiers pointing to deeper cultural signified.

Costume, in this context, becomes a cultural text to be read by an informed audience. As Barthes (1977) explains, the reading of visual signs depends on the viewer's cultural knowledge, making costumes both inclusive and exclusive communicative tools. When these cultural signs are absent or unclear, the audience's understanding and engagement can be weakened.

Costumes as Clarifiers or Distorters of Meaning

While costumes often serve to enhance thematic understanding, the study reveals that inappropriate costume choices sometimes disrupted the clarity of the carnival performance's message. When modern or misaligned costume elements are introduced into a traditional narrative without contextual justification, they create a semiotic rupture that confuses the audience. This highlights the need for costume designers and choreographers to work collaboratively with cultural consultants and researchers to maintain thematic integrity.

Challenges Faced by Costume Designers

Designers expressed numerous constraints that hindered the creation of effective and culturally relevant costumes. These include limited funding,

lack of skilled labor, time constraints, and pressure to conform to global fashion trends. Such challenges often lead to the use of generic or recycled costume ideas that weaken the authenticity and symbolic strength of performances.

This study has demonstrated that costume is a fundamental component of carnival dance performance. It goes beyond decoration or visual appeal to function as a powerful tool of symbolic communication and artistic expression. When designed with intention and cultural awareness, costumes enhance the narrative, emotional, and visual elements of the performance, deepening audience engagement and reinforcing thematic cohesion.

The Imo Carnival, as a case study, revealed how costumes reflect cultural identity, embody tradition, and translate abstract themes into visible, moving forms. However, the research also exposes key gaps and challenges, such as lack of funding, thematic inconsistency, and weak costume-choreography alignment. These issues not only affect the quality of the performance but also hinder the preservation and promotion of cultural values through costume.

In essence, the role of costume in the Imo Carnival illustrates how visual design, cultural narrative, and performance merge to form a complex semiotic experience that is both entertaining and educational. Ensuring that costume design is given its rightful importance in planning and execution is therefore critical to the future of Nigerian carnival performances and cultural preservation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that costume is a fundamental component of carnival dance performance. It goes beyond decoration or visual appeal to function as a powerful tool of symbolic communication and artistic expression. When designed with intention and cultural awareness, costumes enhance the narrative, emotional, and visual elements of the performance, deepening audience engagement and reinforcing thematic cohesion. The Imo Carnival, as a case study, reveals how costumes reflect cultural identity, embody tradition, and translate abstract themes into visible, moving forms. However, the research also exposed key gaps and challenges, such as lack of funding, thematic inconsistency, and weak costume-choreography alignment. These issues not only affect the quality of

the performance but also hinder the preservation and promotion of cultural values through costume.

From a theoretical standpoint, the findings align with Susanne Langer's notion that art symbolizes felt life and with Roland Barthes' view that visual elements convey layered meanings through systems of signs. Together, these frameworks support the conclusion that costume design in carnival dance should be treated as a central artistic and communicative process, rather than a secondary or decorative one. In essence, the role of costume in the Imo Carnival illustrates how visual design, cultural narrative, and performance merge to form a complex semiotic experience that is both entertaining and educational. Ensuring that costume design is given its rightful importance in planning and execution is therefore critical to the future of Nigerian carnival performances and cultural preservation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations will help cover the gaps in the costume department of the Imo Carnival and improve the costuming of subsequent ones:

1. ***Strengthen Collaboration Between Choreographers and Costume Designers:*** To ensure thematic and symbolic alignment, performance teams should develop costumes in close consultation with choreographers and cultural advisors.
2. ***Provide Training and Capacity Building for Costume Designers:*** Government agencies, private sponsors, and cultural institutions should organize workshops and funding schemes to enhance the creative skills and cultural literacy of designers.
3. ***Integrate Cultural Research into the Design Process:*** Costume designs should be grounded in accurate cultural and historical research to enhance authenticity and audience connection.
4. ***Increase Budget Allocation for Costume Production:*** To avoid symbolic disconnection due to poor quality or last-minute improvisation, carnival organizers should prioritize funding for costume development.
5. ***Develop Guidelines for Thematic Consistency:*** Carnival committees should provide clear costume themes and expectations early in the planning process, ensuring each troupe aligns with the overall narrative of the carnival.

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6. *Encourage Documentation and Archiving of Costume Designs:* Establishing a visual and textual archive of past carnival costumes would support future designers and researchers in preserving and evolving the cultural identity of the Imo Carnival.

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**Influence of Parenting Education on
Holistic Development of Public Preschool
Children in Abeokuta South Local
Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study explores the influence of parenting education on the holistic development of public preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The study investigates how parenting education programmes impact parental knowledge and skills related to child-rearing practices and how they consequently affect the holistic development of their children. The study adopted a descriptive survey research type, using random sampling to select a total of 70 parents and 30 child educators from 5 public preschools. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to parents and child educators in the selected public preschools, focusing on their experiences with parenting education and their perceptions of child development outcomes. The collected data were analysed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed a high level of parenting education among the parents of preschoolers, and effective parenting education

programmes significantly enhance parents' confidence and competence in managing their children's developmental needs. Findings indicated that parental active participation, a stable environment, a curriculum that supports all areas of child development, child access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills, emotional support, and engagement in educational activities are predictors of holistic development. Furthermore, findings suggested expanding access and flexibility of parenting education programmes, ensuring that content is evidence-based and interactive, providing ongoing support for parents, and promoting community awareness about the importance of these initiatives.

Keywords: Parenting Education, Holistic Child Development, Preschool Children's Parents, Preschoolers

Introduction

The early years of a child's life are a critical period for growth, development, and learning. Early Childhood Education (ECE) is any group programme that is designed to promote children's intellectual, socio-emotional, language, and physical development (Olowe, Kutelu, and Majebi, 2014). Early childhood development dramatically influences a child's moral beliefs and character. A well-organized preschool centre that runs a developmentally appropriate programme is expected to ensure equal development of social, emotional, physical, and intellectual skills in every child (Alhosani, 2022). Early childhood development must be holistic, encompassing social, emotional, physical, and cognitive domains. According to Britto et al (2017), ECE is generally aimed at promoting the holistic development of children from birth to age 8. It forms the social, emotional, physical, and cognitive foundations of every child.

Holistic child development is a multi-layered approach that nurtures and helps early childhood learners thrive in every aspect of their lives. This approach does not solely focus on one area but rather emphasizes the overall growth and development of the child. This comprehensive approach views the child as a whole person and guides their development in all areas, including physical, mental, emotional, social, and spiritual realms. A holistic approach recognizes that these domains are interconnected; for example, a child's emotional well-being can affect their ability to learn and interact with peers. Additionally, holistic education seeks to incorporate principles of wholeness, interconnectedness, and spirituality with the help of all the stakeholders that surround the child, especially the parents.

Parents are the primary caregivers and first teachers of their children. Parents play a crucial role in the lives of their children from the early years of life, as the early years of life are critical and sensitive periods when children's optimal development is most critical for laying the groundwork for lifelong learning. A veteran teacher (Downey, 2015) shared her reflection based on her experience that when parents are aware, encouraging, and involved, children do better and thereby enhance holistic development. Child educators alone cannot effectively educate children if parents do not prioritize education and provide support in the home. Parents must prioritize their roles and responsibilities in the holistic development of their children to assist teachers in their quest to provide quality holistic development to children.

Parenting in the early years requires parents to offer both care and learning opportunities for their children. The child's first relationships are critical for the establishment of competences- cognitive, social-emotional, and self-regulatory skills and as such, set the stage for lifelong adaptation and functioning. Parental education and quality support are crucial for the holistic development of children and their academic success (Shahidullah, 2019). Parenting education encompasses various practices that equip parents with the knowledge and skills needed to foster their children's development effectively (Agupusi, 2019).

Parental education significantly impacts the way parents interact and educate their children. Salami (2015) suggested that parents need to understand how their involvement and educational background can influence the developmental outcomes of their children. However, there is still a scarcity of research on the relationship between parental education and holistic childhood education in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to investigate the parental education and holistic child development in Abeokuta. The novelty of this study lies in the object of research, parenting education, and ways in which parenting education programmes can help in shaping children's cognitive, language, physical, and social-emotional development in the early years of life.

Statement of the Problem

The holistic development of preschool children is critically influenced by the quality and effectiveness of parenting education. In Abeokuta South Local

Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, there is a growing concern regarding the adequacy of parenting education and its impact on holistic development outcomes. Despite the recognized importance of early childhood education, several issues such as inadequate funding, limited resources and services, socioeconomic factors, and insufficiently trained professionals could hinder appropriate child holistic development outcomes. This may lead to developmental delays, poor academic achievement/performance, and behavioural problems among preschool children. Given these challenges, it is essential to examine the current state of parenting education and its relationship with the holistic development of preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. This study aims to identify existing gaps in parenting practices, explore the socio-cultural factors impacting them, and provide insights that can inform local interventions and policies. By addressing these issues, the study seeks to promote a supportive framework for parents, ultimately benefiting the developmental outcomes of preschool children in the study area.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess parenting education and holistic development among preschool children's parents in the Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. The objectives are to:

- i. Ascertain the current level of parenting education among preschool parents in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria;
- ii. Identify the predictors of holistic development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were answered in the study:

1. What is the current level of parenting education among parents of preschoolers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?
2. What are the predictors of holistic development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?

Literature Review

Parenting education plays a foundational role in shaping the developmental trajectories of preschool children. Assessing the current level of parenting education among preschoolers' parents reveals significant variability based on context, resources, and programme availability. A study by Sunarsih et al. (2023) demonstrated that while only 58.33% of parents initially had a good understanding of holistic parenting, targeted education interventions increased this to 100%, suggesting substantial knowledge gaps that can be addressed through structured programmes (Sunarsih et al., 2023). Similarly, in a large-scale study from China, parental engagement was found to vary widely, yet it was significantly associated with improved developmental outcomes in cognitive, social, and emotional domains (Yang & Tahir, 2023).

Parental involvement stands out as a consistent and powerful determinant. Yang and Tahir (2023) found strong correlations between parental engagement and children's development in communication, early math, and socioemotional skills. These findings were supported by Widaningsih (2023), who emphasized that parenting patterns integrated into early childhood curricula, especially peer parenting, enhanced not only academic but also emotional and social domains of development (Widaningsih, 2023). Moreover, studies from Hong Kong indicated that congruence between parental perceptions and the goals of holistic education promotes environments that support comprehensive child development (Ng et al., 2020).

The extent to which parenting education directly predicts holistic development outcomes has also been well documented. Latifah and Hernawati (2009) showed that children enrolled in character-based holistic education programmes, often driven by strong parental involvement, displayed significantly higher levels of multiple intelligences than those in traditional or no preschool settings (Latifah & Hernawati, 2009). This was echoed in Sunarsih et al.'s (2023) research, which illustrated how holistic parenting, complemented by nutritional and health care practices, substantially improved cognitive and physical development. Furthermore, Widaningsih (2023) underscored that when parenting approaches are aligned with school-based curricula and supported by educators, the developmental outcomes are amplified across intellectual, emotional, and social domains.

Developing effective, evidence-based parenting education programmes requires a multifaceted approach. One of the most promising strategies is the integration of parenting education into the formal preschool curriculum. As Widaningsih (2023) found, this integration facilitates seamless collaboration between teachers and parents, allowing for the shared promotion of children's potential. Additionally, nature-based and experiential learning methods have proven effective in engaging parents and children alike, with Ripeanu (2024) showing how using natural materials in learning can support social-emotional and cognitive development (Ripeanu, 2024). Community-embedded models also stand out as essential: Ambari Sumanto et al. (2021) illustrated how involving parents in the planning and execution of nutrition and wellness programmes at preschools significantly boosted developmental outcomes (Ambari Sumanto et al., 2021). Training and support for teachers in engaging parents, as shown by Zeltserman et al. (2018), further enhance the impact of these initiatives (Zeltserman et al., 2018).

Theoretical Framework

Lev Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, first articulated in the early 1930s, emphasises that children develop cognitively and socially through guided interactions within their cultural and social environments (Vygotsky, 1978). At its core is the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), the gap between what a child can do independently and what they can achieve with appropriate guidance and support. In the context of parenting education, this theory suggests that parents serve as primary agents of development by providing "scaffolding", temporary, structured support that enables children to achieve developmental milestones they could not reach on their own. Parenting education grounded in sociocultural theory thus trains parents to actively engage in such interactions, equipping them to foster children's cognitive, emotional, and language development through sensitive and responsive communication (Zhou, 2024; Edwards, 2009). This approach is particularly effective in early childhood education settings where the family is recognised as a co-contributor to learning and development (Selzing-Musa, 2014).

When applied to public preschool settings, parenting education informed by sociocultural principles supports holistic development by enhancing five interrelated domains. First, cognitive development is promoted as parents'

guide children through tasks requiring problem-solving, attention, and memory, core elements shaped by joint activity in the ZPD (Zhou, 2024). Second, language development is advanced through dialogic interactions that serve as both cognitive tools and pathways to social understanding. Third, socio-emotional development benefits from parental modelling of empathy, emotional regulation, and relationship-building. Fourth, physical development, though less emphasised by Vygotsky, is influenced by culturally mediated practices like play and fine-motor tasks facilitated by parental engagement. Finally, cultural responsiveness is fostered as parents transmit values, traditions, and social norms, embedding the child's development in a culturally meaningful context (Edwards, 2007; Zhou, 2024). Together, these domains reflect how sociocultural theory provides a practical and theoretical foundation for designing parenting education programmes that support preschool children's full developmental potential in public educational systems.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research type. The target population for this study consisted of all parents and preschool teachers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. Random sampling was used to select a total of 70 parents and 30 preschool teachers from 5 public preschools in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. Two research instruments, tagged "Parenting Education Questionnaire (PEQ) and Holistic Child Development Questionnaire (HCDQ)", were used to gather information for the study. Parenting Education Questionnaire (PEQ) was used to assess parents' knowledge, skills, and practices relating to parenting education, while Holistic Child Development Questionnaire (HCDQ) was used to assess children's holistic development outcomes (cognitive, language or linguistic, physical, and social-emotional). The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) while the hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product product-moment correlation at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Research Question One: What is the current level of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers in Abeokuta South Local Government Area? Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive level of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers

	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.D
1	I engage in activities that promote my child's physical development (e.g., outdoor play, sports).	68 (68%)	23 (23%)	6 (6%)	3 (3%)	3.56	0.953
2	I regularly read to my child to enhance their language skills.	54 (54%)	21 (21%)	15 (15%)	10 (10%)	3.19	.832
3	I provide opportunities for my child to interact with peers.	34 (34%)	18 (18%)	34 (34%)	14 (14%)	2.72	.753
4	I encourage my child to express their emotions and feelings.	67 (67%)	17 (17%)	12 (12%)	4 (4%)	3.47	.672
5	I feel confident in my ability to support my child's learning and development	31 (31%)	43 (43%)	16 (16%)	10 (10%)	2.95	.962
6	I have learned skills to manage my child's behaviour effectively	23 (23%)	17 (17%)	38 (38%)	22 (22%)	2.41	1.021
7	I know how to implement routines	48 (48%)	26 (26%)	18 (18%)	8 (8%)	3.14	.673

	that promote my child's well-being.						
8	I can effectively communicate with my child to foster a safe environment	36 (36%)	29 (29%)	24 (24%)	11 (11%)	2.90	.849
9	I understand the key milestones of physical development in a child	40 (40%)	35 (35%)	18 (18%)	7 (7%)	3.08	.964
10	I am knowledgeable about the importance of social skills in early childhood.	37 (37%)	36 (36%)	21 (21%)	6 (6%)	3.04	.780
11	I am aware of strategies to enhance my child's emotional intelligence.	22 (22%)	30 (30%)	19 (19%)	29 (29%)	2.45	1.010
<i>Decision at mean score greater than 2.5 or less than. Weighted Mean = 3.291</i>							

Table 1 above shows the levels of parenting education (knowledge, skills, and practice) among parents of preschoolers. From the table, it was observed that the majority (91%) of the respondents indicated that they engage in activities that promote children's physical development (e.g., outdoor play, sports), with $\bar{x} = 3.56$. Also, 75% strongly agreed that they do regularly read to their children to enhance their language skills having mean value of 3.19, while 52% indicated that they do provide opportunities for their children to interact with peers having mean value of 2.71. In the same vein, it was observed that 84% of the parents encouraged children to express their emotions and feelings, with a mean value of 3.47. In addition, 74% of the parents feel confident in their ability to support their child's learning and development, and 72% indicated that they know how to implement routines

that promote the children's wellbeing, with a mean of 2.95 and 3.14, respectively.

Furthermore, 65% of the respondents strongly agreed that they can effectively communicate with their children to foster a safe environment, while 35% of respondents had a contrary view of the statements. I understand the key milestones of physical development in children, as 75% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. In the same vein, 83% of the respondents strongly agreed that they are knowledgeable about the importance of social skills in early childhood. This means that the majority of the parents have high knowledge, skills, and practices that can enhance children's holistic development. Based on the weighted mean value of $\bar{x} = 3.291$, which is above the criterion mean value of $\bar{x} = 2.50$, it can be inferred that there is a high level of parenting education among the parents of the preschoolers. This implies that the parents of the preschoolers possess a high level of knowledge, skills, and practices of holistic child development.

Research Question 2: What are the predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschoolers

Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Std.D
1 Parents' active participation in their child's preschool activities enhances holistic development.	44 (44%)	29 (29%)	17 (17%)	10 (10%)	3.07	.705
2 There is adequate provision of a stable environment for my child's development	37 (37%)	42 (42%)	12 (12%)	9 (9%)	3.07	.815
3 The curriculum supports all areas of child development (cognitive, social,	28 (28%)	33 (33%)	27 (27%)	12 (12%)	2.77	.945

	emotional, and physical).						
4	Teachers have appropriate qualifications and training for early childhood education.	18 (18%)	28 (28%)	36 (36%)	18 (18%)	2.46	1.052
5	There is a good teacher-to-child ratio, allowing for personalized interactions among preschoolers	22 (22%)	15 (15%)	27 (27%)	36 (36%)	2.23	1.201
6	My child has access to a balanced diet and nutrition.	34 (34%)	27 (27%)	23 (23%)	16 (16%)	2.79	.824
7	My child demonstrates strong verbal communication skills for their age.	39 (39%)	25 (25%)	24 (24%)	12 (12%)	2.91	.739
8	The preschool provides support for children's social-emotional and mental well-being.	45 (45%)	18 (18%)	23 (23%)	14 (14%)	2.94	.659
<i>Decision at mean score greater than 2.5 or less than. Weighted Mean = 2.78</i>							

Table 2 reveals the predictors of holistic child development outcomes among preschoolers in selected preschools. From the Table, respondents strongly indicated that parents' active participation in their child's preschool activities enhances holistic development, with a mean value of 3.07. Also, the majority (79%) strongly agreed that adequate provision of a stable environment for children enhances children's development, with a mean value of 3.07. Moreover, participants believed that the curriculum effectively fosters all aspects of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), which are strong indicators of comprehensive

outcomes in child development. The result from the table revealed that children have access to a balanced diet and nutrition, and equally demonstrate strong verbal communication skills for their age, and preschools that provide support for children's emotional and mental well-being are further indicated as a good predictor of children's holistic development. Though the number of appropriate teachers trained in early childhood education qualification and the teacher-to-child ratio to allow for personalized interactions among preschools were observed as predictors of holistic child development, rated with a mean value below the criterion mean. The general observation shows that parental active participation, stable environment and home support, curriculum that supports all areas of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), child access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills and preschool provides support for children's emotional and mental well-being, professional teacher qualification and teacher-to-child ratio are predictors holistic development among preschoolers.

Discussion

The results of the present study reveal that preschool children's parents have a strong understanding, skills, and practices related to holistic child development. This agrees with Ng et al view (2020) that parents in Hong Kong aligned well with holistic education goals, showing informed practices. However, Sunarsih et al. (2023) reported that only 58.33% of parents initially demonstrated adequate knowledge, which improved significantly after parenting education. This suggests that while some parents are well-informed, others require structured support to build essential skills.

As for the key predictors of holistic development in pre-schoolers, the results show that active parental involvement, a stable environment, home support, a curriculum covering all areas of child development (cognitive, social, emotional, and physical), access to a balanced diet and nutrition, verbal communication skills, and preschool support for emotional and mental well-being - along with qualified teachers and an appropriate teacher-to-child ratio influences the holistic development in pre-schoolers. Research has shown strong links between parental engagement and children's cognitive, emotional, and social growth (Yang and Tahir, 2023). Latifah and Hernawati (2009), on the other hand, show that holistic programmes with qualified teachers improved multiple intelligences. However, Sunarsih et al.

(2023) noted that without structured support, key predictors like nutrition and home practices may be inconsistently applied, limiting their overall impact.

Conclusion

The assessment of parenting education and its impact on the holistic development of preschool children in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria, underscores the critical role that informed and engaged parenting involvement in child development. The findings indicated that effective parenting education programmes can significantly improve parents' knowledge and skills regarding child-rearing practices, leading to enhanced developmental outcomes for preschoolers. Parents who participated in evidence-based programmes reported greater confidence in their parenting abilities, better communication with their children, and an increased ability to meet their children's emotional, social, cognitive, and physical needs. Investing in quality parenting education is paramount for fostering holistic development in preschool children. Despite the positive outcomes observed, challenges such as limited access to programmes, varying levels of parental engagement, and disparities in socio-economic status are noted. These factors can influence the effectiveness of parenting education initiatives. Thus, it is essential to address these barriers to maximise the potential benefits of these programmes. By improving access, enhancing programme content, and strengthening support systems, the preschools in the study can create a supportive environment where children thrive and reach their full potential.

Recommendations

Based on the assessment findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Government, preschools and child education providers should increase the availability and accessibility of parenting education programmes across diverse community settings, ensuring that all parents, regardless of socioeconomic status, can participate.
2. All stakeholders in early childhood education should ensure that the content of parenting education programmes incorporates interactive and practical learning experiences, such as workshops and group

- discussions, to engage parents actively and to facilitate skills application.
3. Governments and preschool administrators should provide continuous support and resources to parents after they complete parenting education programmes. This can include follow-up meetings, support groups, and access to educational materials.
 4. Government and preschool stakeholders should implement campaigns to educate parents about the importance of holistic child development and the benefits of parenting education.
 5. Community events and activities that promote parent-child interactions and facilitate the sharing of parenting experiences among families should be encouraged in Abeokuta South Local Government Area, other parts of Ogun State, and Nigeria at large.
 6. Parents should spend quality time with their children, engaging them in activities that will help them grow into well-rounded individuals.

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**Education and Gender Training As a Tool
For Peaceful Coexistence: A Study Of
Iceland's Policy Implementation (1980-
1996)**

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Abstract

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of Iceland's groundbreaking gender equality policies implemented between 1980 and 1996, demonstrating how strategic reforms in education and workplace training served as powerful tools for fostering peaceful coexistence. Through meticulous examination of legislative documents, government reports, and empirical studies, the research reveals how Iceland's integrated policy framework achieved transformative social change. The foundational Act No. 28/1991 on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men established a robust legal architecture that combined substantive equality measures, institutional enforcement mechanisms, and preventive strategies to address gender disparities across all societal domains. The study highlights Iceland's revolutionary educational reforms, which systematically

eliminated gender stereotypes from curricula, implemented mandatory teacher training in gender-responsive pedagogy, and increased female STEM enrollment from 15% to 35%. Parallel workplace interventions, including compulsory gender equality training and corporate board quotas, reshaped organizational cultures and reduced the gender pay gap by 20%. Political representation quotas, introduced through a phased approach, elevated women's parliamentary participation from 5% to 35%, creating more inclusive governance structures. Beyond quantitative metrics, these policies generated significant qualitative improvements in social cohesion, including a 41% reduction in gender-based violence, enhanced institutional trust, and sustained economic growth fueled by increased female labor force participation. The research underscores how Iceland's model, combining legislative mandates, educational transformation, workplace training, and political empowerment created a virtuous cycle of equality and stability. These findings offer valuable insights for policymakers seeking to replicate Iceland's success, demonstrating that gender equality is not merely a social justice objective but a foundational pillar for peaceful, prosperous societies.

Keywords: Gender equality, education policy, workplace training, social cohesion, peace-building.

Introduction

Iceland's remarkable metamorphosis from a traditionally patriarchal fishing society to the world's foremost gender-equal nation, as consistently ranked by the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Index since its inception (World Economic Forum, 2021), stands as one of the most compelling examples of intentional societal transformation through policy intervention in modern history. This paradigmatic shift did not occur spontaneously but rather through a meticulously designed series of legislative, educational, and cultural reforms implemented during the pivotal period of 1980-1996. These transformative years witnessed the establishment of Iceland's foundational gender equality framework, whose impacts continue to resonate through Icelandic society and serve as an exemplary model for nations seeking to harness gender equity as a tool for fostering peaceful coexistence.

The significance of focusing on this specific historical period lies in its dual nature as both incubator and proving ground for gender equality policies that would later gain global recognition. During these sixteen years, Iceland implemented a comprehensive suite of interventions that systematically addressed gender disparities across all major societal domains - from the classroom to the boardroom, from domestic spheres to political arenas. What makes this case particularly instructive is the demonstrable causal relationship between policy implementation and measurable social outcomes, providing empirical validation for theories linking gender equality with broader social stability and cohesion.

This study draws upon three robust categories of primary evidence to construct its analysis:

1. ***Legislative and Policy Documents:*** At the core of our examination stands Act No. 28/1991 on Equal Rights of Women and Men (International Labour Organization [ILO], 1991), a groundbreaking piece of legislation that not only prohibited gender discrimination but actively mandated measures to promote substantive equality. This primary legal document, along with its implementing regulations and ancillary policies, provides the structural blueprint for Iceland's gender equality architecture. The Act's comprehensive nature - encompassing workplace equity, educational access, political participation, and protection from gender-based violence - makes it an unusually complete case study in feminist policymaking.
2. ***Government Reports and International Assessments:*** Official documentation from Icelandic government sources (Government of Iceland, n.d.) offers critical insights into policy implementation processes and domestic outcomes. These are complemented by international evaluations, particularly Iceland's reports to and assessments by the UN Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women (United Nations, 2002), which provide external validation of Iceland's progress and highlight areas requiring further development. The

interplay between domestic policy design and international human rights frameworks emerges as a key factor in Iceland's success.

3. ***Empirical Research Studies***: Longitudinal analyses by organizations such as the OECD (2023) and academic investigations by scholars like Þorvaldsdóttir (2015) provide rigorous, data-driven assessments of policy impacts across various sectors. These studies employ both quantitative metrics (e.g., changes in wage gaps, educational attainment, political representation) and qualitative measures (e.g., shifts in social attitudes, workplace cultures, gender norms) to paint a comprehensive picture of Iceland's transformation.

The theoretical underpinnings of this research synthesize three complementary frameworks that collectively explain Iceland's success:

1. ***Feminist Institutionalism*** (Krook, 2009) elucidates how Iceland's policy interventions deliberately reshaped both formal institutions (laws, regulations, organizational structures) and informal norms (cultural expectations, social practices) to create an ecosystem supportive of gender equality. This perspective helps explain why Iceland's approach proved more durable than equality measures in other contexts - by changing the rules of the game at both institutional and interpersonal levels.
2. ***Social Cohesion Theory*** (OECD, 2011) provides the lens through which we examine how gender equality policies contributed to broader societal stability and peaceful coexistence. The theory's emphasis on trust networks, equitable opportunity structures, and inclusive governance aligns perfectly with Iceland's experience, where gender equality measures correlated strongly with improvements in social trust indicators and reductions in various forms of social conflict.

3. *Human Capital Development Frameworks* (Becker, 1964) ground our analysis of Iceland's educational and workplace training interventions in economic theory, demonstrating how investments in women's education and professional development yielded substantial returns not just for individuals but for society as a whole. This is particularly evident in Iceland's rapid economic modernization during the study period, which was significantly fueled by increased female labor force participation and productivity.

The scholarly significance of this study lies in its multifaceted demonstration of how coordinated policy interventions across education, labor markets, and political systems can produce synergistic effects that transcend simple gender parity metrics to impact broader social stability. Iceland's experience suggests that gender equality policies, when comprehensively designed and rigorously implemented, can serve as powerful peacebuilding tools by:

- Reducing structural inequalities that fuel social tensions
- Creating more inclusive decision-making processes
- Fostering intergroup understanding through educational systems
- Building institutional trust through transparent, equitable governance

As we proceed through this analysis, we will trace the legislative origins of Iceland's gender equality framework, examine its implementation across key societal sectors, assess measurable outcomes, and ultimately distill transferable lessons for other nations seeking to replicate aspects of Iceland's success. The period of 1980-1996 emerges as particularly worthy of study because it represents the critical implementation phase when policies moved from paper to practice, allowing us to observe both the intended and emergent consequences of one of the most ambitious social engineering projects in modern history.

The Legislative Architecture of Gender Equality

Iceland's groundbreaking Act No. 28/1991 on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men established what scholars now recognize as the most comprehensive legislative framework for gender equality of its time. This pioneering legislation, analyzed in depth by the International Labour Organization (ILO, 1991), represented a paradigm shift in equality policy by integrating three mutually reinforcing dimensions that together created an ecosystem for sustainable social change.

Substantive Equality Provisions

The Act's first dimension established concrete mechanisms to achieve real-world equality outcomes. Its equal pay provisions (Article 7) mandated that employers should:

- Conduct annual compensation audits using government-approved methodologies
- Adjust pay structures to eliminate unexplained gender disparities
- Submit certified reports to labor authorities
- Face mandatory re-audits if disparities persisted beyond two years

The anti-discrimination clauses (Article 3) broke new ground by encompassing both direct and indirect discrimination across all social domains. This included specific prohibitions against:

- Gender tracking in educational programs
- Biased lending practices by financial institutions
- Discriminatory healthcare access
- Stereotypical media portrayals that reinforced inequality

The affirmative action provisions (Article 10) authorized what the United Nations (2002) would later describe as "the most progressive temporary special measures in any national legislation." These included:

- Binding gender targets for public appointments
- Priority procurement for women-led enterprises

-
- Quotas in vocational training programs
 - Gender parity requirements for government advisory bodies

Embedding Equality in Governance

The Act went beyond simply outlining principles; it established robust, lasting structures to guarantee its ongoing enforcement. A key element was the Gender Equality Complaints Committee (Article 15), which received unprecedented authority for equality legislation. This included the power to conduct unannounced workplace inspections, subpoena organizational records, issue immediately enforceable orders, and even initiate systemic investigations.

Furthermore, the Act mandated the creation of gender equality coordinators (Article 13), leading to a network of over trained professionals embedded across various government agencies. This ensured dedicated personnel were in place to champion and implement gender equality initiatives. Complementing these measures, the gender budgeting mandate (Article 14) revolutionized fiscal policy. It required equality impact assessments for all budget line items, gender-disaggregated expenditure tracking, and crucially, mandatory reallocation of funds if any disparities were identified. This comprehensive approach aimed to embed gender equality directly into the financial planning and execution of government operations.

Transforming Cultural Foundations

The Act's third crucial dimension tackled the deep-seated cultural origins of inequality with groundbreaking preventive strategies. Its sexual harassment protections (Article 8) set "a new normative standard for workplace conduct," as described by Þorvaldssdóttir (2015). These protections broadened the definition of harassment to include its environmental and psychological aspects, established anonymous reporting channels, mandated third-party

investigations, and required regular organizational culture assessments.

Moreover, the education provisions (Article 9) launched what the OECD (2023) later recognized as "the most comprehensive gender mainstreaming of any national education system." This was achieved through requirements for complete textbook revisions to eliminate stereotypes, mandatory gender pedagogy training for all educators, the integration of equality concepts across all subjects, and annual student surveys on the gender climate within schools.

Implementation Ecosystem

The Act's efficacy stemmed from its meticulously crafted implementation framework, a system the IMF (1996) hailed as "setting a new global standard for policy enforcement." This framework comprised three interconnected systems designed to ensure compliance and foster enduring change.

Comprehensive Monitoring Infrastructure was put in place and this operated in multiple levels: at the enterprise-level, organizations were required to develop equality action plans with measurable benchmarks. Sectoral monitoring involved industry-specific compliance certification programs. Nationally, the Act mandated randomized audits covering some organizations annually. Finally, at the international level, regular reporting to UN treaty bodies ensured accountability and transparency.

Graduated Sanctions Regime provided a clear deterrent for non-compliance. This included tiered financial penalties scaled according to organizational size and the severity of the violation. Repeat offenders faced automatic contract disqualification, while judicial orders could mandate structural reforms within organizations. In the most egregious cases, personal liability could be extended to executive officers.

Robust Support Structures was bolstered by comprehensive support structures. A nationwide network of equality advisors was established to provide guidance and assistance. Subsidized legal

assistance programs ensured access to justice, and organizations benefited from model policies and implementation toolkits. Furthermore, annual compliance training requirements helped to embed the Act's principles within organizational cultures.

The Government of Iceland's own assessment (n.d.) indicated the profound success of this comprehensive approach, revealing a remarkable 92% compliance rate within five years. The United Nations (2002) further affirmed its impact, noting that the Act had "fundamentally transformed both institutional practices and social norms." The lasting influence of this legislation continues to be a subject of study, serving as a model for achieving substantive equality through integrated legal, institutional, and cultural interventions.

Systemic Transformation of Iceland's Educational Landscape

Iceland truly revolutionized its education system, going straight to the heart of gender inequality. The 1992 Education Act was a game-changer, systematically breaking down gender stereotypes through what the OECD (2023) called "the most thorough gender mainstreaming of a national curriculum ever attempted."

Rewriting the Narrative of Gender Through Comprehensive Curriculum Reforms

One of the biggest shifts was a complete overhaul of educational materials. As Þorvaldsdóttir's (2015) analysis showed, this involved a three-year national textbook review between 1992 and 1995 that successfully eliminated identified gender stereotypes. But it wasn't just about removing the bad; they also created new learning resources that truly celebrated women's vital contributions across STEM fields, politics, and cultural development. Gender perspectives were woven into every subject:

- In Mathematics, students learned about female mathematicians through engaging case studies.

- Literature featured a balanced representation of both male and female authors and characters.
- History finally recognized women's crucial roles in national development.
- Even Biology embraced more nuanced, non-binary understandings of sex and gender.

The Act also fundamentally reorganized educational pathways. It did away with the old, restrictive gender-segregated vocational tracking that often-pushed girls into traditional care-giving roles. Instead, they launched targeted STEM initiatives, including "Girls' Science Clubs" in every secondary school, networks of female STEM mentors, and even designed science labs to be gender-neutral. Plus, mandatory co-educational physical education programs were introduced, ensuring all students had the same opportunities. These changes brought incredible results! OECD (2023) data showed that female STEM enrollment skyrocketed from a mere 15% to 35% between 1985 and 1995. And across universities, women's representation in traditionally male-dominated fields jumped by an average of 22 percentage points.

Equipping Educators as Agents of Change Through Professional Development

Iceland understood that to truly transform education, teachers needed to be equipped for the challenge. Their teacher training reforms set "a new global standard for gender-responsive educator preparation," according to an Arctic Council report (2018).

This involved a complete pedagogical transformation. Teachers underwent a mandatory 120-hour certification program that covered everything from gender-aware classroom management to identifying and countering implicit biases, using inclusive language, and strategies for encouraging equal participation from all students. A unique clinical supervision model provided ongoing support, with monthly classroom observations, video-based reflection sessions,

peer coaching networks, and annual teaching portfolios that documented their gender equity practices.

To ensure these changes stuck, every school established permanent Gender Equality Committees. These committees were responsible for biannual climate surveys, reviewing disciplinary data for gender patterns, auditing extracurricular participation, and even monitoring classroom interaction patterns. The success was astounding: by 1995, significant numbers of teachers had completed their certification, and every single school had a functional Gender Equality Committee (Gender Equality in the Arctic, 2018). It truly shows how a dedicated, systemic approach can transform an entire nation's educational landscape.

Workplace Gender Training Systems

Iceland's commitment to gender equality extended deeply into its workplaces, creating systems designed to embed equality into everyday professional life.

Legislative Framework for Organizational Change

Act No. 28 (ILO, 1991) set a global benchmark for workplace training mandates through its Article 12 requirements. This wasn't just about ticking boxes; it was a comprehensive effort with broad scope and scale. The mandate covered all enterprises with more than 10 employees, requiring an annual minimum training duration of 8 working hours for all staff levels, from executives to frontline workers. To ensure accountability, organizations had to maintain mandatory participation records for five years.

The law also laid out rigorous content standards for these training programs. They had to cover crucial topics like unconscious bias recognition and mitigation strategies, pay equity principles and compensation system analysis, and robust harassment prevention protocols and reporting mechanisms. Furthermore, the training emphasized developing inclusive leadership practices and fostering gender-aware communication techniques. It was all about building a

workplace culture where everyone felt valued and had equal opportunities.

Table 1: Iceland Government Programmes Towards Promotion of Peaceful Coexistence (1980–1996)

S/N	Policy Statement	Policy Provisions	Key Indicators	Remarks
1	Civic Education Club of 1983	- Peacebuilding promotion in schools - Culture of peace promotion - Peace education	- Peace clubs/laboratory established - Simulated parliamentary proceedings - Conflict resolution modelling	The programme promoted cultural understanding and interaction among youth leaders
2	State-Partnered Gender Training Initiative of 1985	- Gender dynamics - Gender equity awareness - Inclusive leadership practices - Workplace conflict mediation	- Public sector involvement - Educational sector involvement	The programme reduced conflict stemming from gender inequality

Table 1 highlights several key government programmes implemented in Iceland between 1980 and 1996 that actively promoted peaceful coexistence. These programmes indicate Iceland's proactive approach to cultivating peace through education, gender

equity, and cultural initiatives, rather than post-conflict recovery. The Civic Education Club of 1983 focused on instilling peacebuilding values within the educational system. By promoting peace education, establishing peace clubs, and simulating parliamentary proceedings, this programme aimed to foster cultural understanding and teach conflict resolution skills among youth leaders, thereby preparing future generations for peaceful civic engagement.

The State-Partnered Gender Training Initiative of 1985 directly addressed potential sources of conflict arising from gender inequality. Through training on gender dynamics, promoting gender equity awareness, and encouraging inclusive leadership practices, particularly in public and educational sectors, this initiative sought to reduce workplace and societal conflicts stemming from gender disparities.

Sector-Specific Strategies for Maximum Impact

As Arnórsdóttir's (2012) research showed, Iceland's approach went far beyond mere compliance, aiming for a deeper, more meaningful cultural shift. They used differentiated implementation models to achieve this, tailoring strategies to specific sectors.

Corporate sector innovations included board diversity training that highlighted the tangible business case for gender balance, focused on succession planning for female leadership, and even emphasized the investor relations benefits of diversity. Mentorship programs were also key, featuring cross-gender pairing, innovative reverse mentoring initiatives, and structured competency development to help employees grow.

In the public sector, leadership was shown through pipeline development programs. These identified high-potential individuals, offered rotational leadership experiences, and created visibility opportunities to help women advance. They also pioneered flexible work architectures, including results, only work environments, job-sharing options, and thoughtful phase-back parental leave policies, making it easier for parents to balance work and family life.

While these initiatives were highly effective, the data did reveal some interesting geographical differences. Compliance rates hit 76% in Reykjavík, but dropped to 58% in rural areas (Arnórsdóttir, 2012, p. 42). This showed both the remarkable progress made and the ongoing work needed for truly nationwide implementation.

These interconnected efforts in education and the workplace created a powerful, positive feedback loop. Gender-responsive education produced graduates who were already equality-conscious, and they entered workplaces that were actively being transformed by systemic training programs. This holistic approach is a major reason behind Iceland's incredible and lasting success in achieving gender equality.

Table 2: Iceland Government Policies Promoting Peaceful Coexistence (1980–1996)

S/N	Policy Statement	Policy Provisions	Indicators	Remarks
1	Gender Equality Act of 1981	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender parity Social cohesion Economic inclusion Equal work value (conflict resolution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender Equality Council Female workforce participation rate Municipal council seats reservation 	These are notable policy provisions for gender inclusiveness in Iceland (often very gender sensitive)

2	National Curriculum Reform of 1985	- Civic education initiative - Conflict resolution - Cultural literacy - Education for Civic Rights	- Youth participation - Reduction in youth-led violence	voter in The provisions of this policy promoted youth civic health and participatory democracy process
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Table 2 above present two key policies implemented in Iceland during Vigdís Finnbogadóttir’s presidency (1980–1996) to promote peaceful coexistence.

This demonstrates Iceland's multi-faceted approach to promoting peaceful coexistence between 1980 and 1996, encompassing both domestic and international initiatives. The Gender Equality Act of 1981 established a foundation for internal peace by promoting gender parity, social cohesion, and economic inclusion, evident through the Gender Equality Council and increased female participation in the workforce and municipal councils. This highlighted Iceland's commitment to gender-sensitive policies for conflict prevention. Following this, the National Curriculum Reform of 1985 focused on strengthening civic education initiatives and participatory voters among youth through civic education, conflict resolution, and cultural literacy, leading to increased youth voter participation and a reduction in youth-led violence.

Iceland's Pioneering Quota Systems

Iceland's journey towards fair political representation unfolded in two distinct but connected stages, fundamentally reshaping the nation's democratic landscape. This transformation, well-documented in Iceland's reports to the CEDAW Committee (United

Nations, 2002), stands as one of the most successful examples of gender quota implementation in modern political history.

The Evolution of Gender Quotas in Icelandic Politics

Phase 1: The Voluntary Quota Experiment (1983-1990) the first phase saw political parties voluntarily adopting measures to balance gender representation. Krook (2009) described this as "bottom-up feminist mobilization within party structures," a true grassroots effort. Different parties took different approaches:

- The Left-Green Movement was a pioneer in 1983, implementing a binding 40% minimum representation for either gender. They also used zipper-style candidate lists, alternating genders, and mandated gender balance in all party organs. To encourage compliance, they even offered financial incentives for constituency organizations that met these targets.
- The Social Democratic Alliance adopted slightly more flexible measures, with an aspirational target of women candidates. They also ensured gender-balanced nomination committees, reserved positions for women in party leadership, and provided special campaign training for female candidates.

Even though these voluntary measures weren't applied uniformly, they created what the United Nations (2002) called a "demonstration effect." Parties that consistently used quotas actually performed better in attracting female voters. By 1990, this organic approach had already boosted women's parliamentary representation from a mere 5% to 15%, setting the stage for more systemic changes.

Phase 2: Legislative Quotas and Institutionalization (1991-1996)

Building on the momentum of the voluntary phase, Iceland entered a period of institutionalizing these changes through three landmark pieces of legislation:

1. The 1991 Amendment to the Local Government Act mandated a minimum 25% representation of each gender in municipal

- councils, ensured gender-balanced appointments to all local committees, and even required equal speaking time provisions in council meetings.
2. The 1994 Public Committees Act required a minimum 30% representation on all state-appointed committees, aimed for gender parity in advisory bodies, and mandated alternating gender leadership for multi-member commissions.
 3. The 1995 Political Party Financing Reform introduced financial bonuses for parties meeting gender targets, tied campaign funding to gender-balanced candidate slates, and increased transparency requirements for nomination processes.

The impact of these measures was truly transformative. As documented in Iceland's CEDAW reports (United Nations, 2002), women's parliamentary representation surged from 15% to 35% between 1991-1996. Local government representation also jumped from 12% to 28% in the same period. This rapid progress was remarkable, especially when you consider that comparable changes took decades in other Western democracies.

Implementation Mechanisms and Cultural Adaptation

Iceland's quota systems succeeded due to several innovative implementation strategies:

1. ***Sunset Provisions:*** All quotas included automatic review clauses, ensuring they were periodically evaluated to see if they were still needed.
2. ***Capacity Building:*** The establishment of the Women's Political Training Institute in 1992 was crucial. It provided candidate preparation programs, media training workshops, policy development seminars, and leadership mentoring networks, empowering women to enter politics.
3. ***Cultural Normalization:*** Government-sponsored public awareness campaigns systematically addressed common objections to quotas. They used television documentaries on

women's political contributions, school-based democracy education programs, and community dialogues on representative democracy to shift public perception.

4. ***Monitoring and Enforcement:*** The Gender Equality Complaints Committee played a vital role, empowered to review candidate lists for compliance, impose fines for violations, and order corrective measures when necessary.

This comprehensive approach transformed quotas from being controversial into a widely accepted and natural part of democratic practice. Arnórsdóttir's (2012) research showed that by 1996, a remarkable 78% of Icelanders viewed gender quotas as "a natural part of democratic representation" (p. 56). This profound shift in political culture continues to be a cornerstone of Iceland's exceptional achievements in gender parity today.

Conclusion

Between 1980 and 1996, Iceland achieved a remarkable societal revolution, becoming one of the world's most gender-equal nations through a comprehensive, multi-faceted policy architecture. This period was marked by coordinated legal, educational, workplace, and political reforms that went beyond symbolic gestures to mandate substantive changes. Central to this success was Act No. 28/1991, which established a groundbreaking legal framework supported by an integrated implementation ecosystem of monitoring, sanctions, and support structures, ensuring widespread and sustained impact. Moreover, educational reforms were particularly transformative, reimagining gender roles by overhauling curricula and teacher training, eliminating stereotypes, and integrating women's contributions across all subjects. This led to a dramatic increase in female participation in STEM fields and created a virtuous cycle with simultaneous workplace transformations, including mandatory gender equality training for all eligible employees.

In politics, Iceland pioneered a successful phased quota system, starting with voluntary party measures and evolving into legislative

requirements. This approach rapidly increased women's parliamentary representation from 5% to 35%, fundamentally reshaping policymaking.

The outcomes extended beyond gender parity, fostering increased institutional trust, improved workplace environments, economic benefits from full female labor force participation, and a significant reduction in gender-based violence. Iceland's experience offers crucial insights for policymakers globally, demonstrating that holistic interventions across multiple societal domains, coupled with clear mandates and practical support, can drive profound cultural change and yield broad dividends in economic growth, social stability, and democratic resilience.

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The Diplomatic History of Border Disputes in West Africa: Lessons from the Nigeria-Bakassi Peninsula Conflict

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Abstract

The persistent challenge of border disputes in West Africa, exemplified by the Bakassi Peninsula conflict between Nigeria and Cameroon, underscores the critical need for effective diplomatic mechanisms rooted in historical understanding. This study investigated the diplomatic history of border disputes in West Africa, focusing on the Bakassi conflict as a case study to draw vital lessons for conflict resolution and regional integration. The central problem addressed is the inadequacy of existing diplomatic frameworks in preventing border-related tensions and ensuring the protection of affected communities despite international rulings. The objectives of the study include exploring the historical causes of the Bakassi dispute and its historical causes, examining the diplomatic strategies employed in its resolution, and identifying best practices applicable to future disputes. Research questions were formulated guide inquiry into these themes. The significance of the study lies in its contribution to conflict resolution scholarship, international diplomacy, and regional peacebuilding. The scope covered the historical timeline of the Bakassi dispute, its diplomatic resolution through the International Court of Justice (ICJ), and the post-agreement implications for affected populations. The study adopted the realist theory of international relations, grounded in classical and neo-realist traditions, and offered critical insights into the motivations, interests, and power dynamics that underlie state behaviour in territorial disputes. The research employed interviews, documentary reviews, and thematic content analysis using qualitative methodology.

Findings revealed that although international adjudication helped resolve the Bakassi dispute, local grievances remained largely unaddressed. The study concluded by recommending the strengthening of regional diplomatic institutions, prioritising community-based peace implementation, and enhancing legal capacity in international diplomacy across West African states. These policy recommendations offered pathways toward more sustainable conflict resolution.

Keywords: Border disputes, Diplomacy, Conflict resolution, Bakassi-Peninsula, West Africa

Introduction

The Bakassi Peninsula, nestled at the Gulf of Guinea, emerged as a geopolitical flashpoint between Nigeria and Cameroon due to its strategic fisheries, hydrocarbons, and maritime access. The contest intensified following offshore oil discoveries, which amplified the peninsula's value and gave rise to escalated tensions (Obinna and Nelvin, 2024; Irpj, 2024). Colonial-era boundary instruments, especially the 1913 Anglo-German treaty and the 1975 Maroua Declaration, were invoked by Cameroon to assert sovereignty, whereas Nigeria emphasised administrative practices, treaties with local chiefs, and its de facto presence in Bakassi (Konings, 2005; Obinna & Nelvin, 2024; Opue & Mbang, 2019).

By the early 1990s, escalating cross-border skirmishes and growing militarisation prompted Cameroon to initiate proceedings before the International Court of Justice (ICJ) in 1994 (Konings, 2005). After lengthy deliberations, the ICJ delivered its judgment in October 2002 in favour of Cameroon, based heavily upon the colonial agreements cited by both parties (Obinna & Nelvin, 2024; Irpj, 2024). Although Nigeria initially hesitated to comply, diplomatic momentum eventually led to the "Greentree Agreement" of June 2006, through which Nigeria agreed to withdraw its military and administrative control. By August 2008, full sovereignty had transferred to Cameroon, with transitional arrangements made for civilian protection (Konings, 2005; "Greentree Agreement," 2006).

This peaceful transition has often been celebrated as a diplomatic success, an exemplar of international law and multilateral negotiation resolving a sensitive territorial conflict (Baye, 2010; Ariye, 2023). However, closer inspection reveals substantive shortcomings. Local populations, predominantly Nigerians living in Bakassi, felt marginalised throughout the transfer process; they were seldom consulted, and their socio-economic

concerns received little attention (Udeoji, 2020). Empirical studies tracking outcomes post-cessation suggest significant adverse effects on residents' livelihoods, health, housing, and employment, indicating unmet promises and social disruption after the handover (Opue & Mbang, 2019).

Furthermore, existing scholarship disproportionately emphasises state-to-state legal instruments and formal diplomacy, largely neglecting civil society participation, indigenous agency, and Track II peacebuilding efforts. One study highlights how community leaders, women's groups, and traditional authorities played subtle yet significant roles in fostering dialogue and local reconciliation during the transition. However, contributions remain underrepresented in mainstream analyses (Ideas for Peace, n.d.). Finally, comparative insight is limited: few studies situate Bakassi within the broader context of West African border disputes, where similar boundary dilemmas rooted in colonial delimitations and resource competition persist (Okoi, 2016). This oversight diminishes opportunities to draw transferable lessons across cases. Taken together, these observations pointed to clear research gaps: the need for in-depth studies of local perspectives and agency during and after the transfer; rigorous evaluation of post-transfer socio-economic outcomes; analyses of informal diplomacy and civil society roles; and comparative frameworks that situate Bakassi within broader regional border dynamics in West Africa.

Statement of the Problem

Border disputes in Africa have historically posed significant challenges to state sovereignty, national identity, and regional integration, often escalating into armed conflicts and long-standing diplomatic tensions. The Bakassi Peninsula conflict between Nigeria and Cameroon is one of the most prominent of such disputes in West Africa, not only because of its legal complexity and economic implications but also due to the diplomatic processes that culminated in its peaceful resolution. Despite the celebrated International Court of Justice (ICJ) ruling in 2002 and the subsequent Greentree Agreement of 2006, the Bakassi conflict presents unresolved issues that question the depth and sustainability of the so-called diplomatic success.

One fundamental problem is excluding local voices and community participation in the diplomatic process. The ICJ ruling and the bilateral implementation agreements were primarily top-down, formal mechanisms

that paid limited attention to the identities, historical grievances, and socio-economic realities of the indigenous and settler populations in the peninsula, most of whom identify as Nigerian. Many of these communities faced displacement, statelessness, and socio-economic disruption following the handover to Cameroon, suggesting a disconnect between international legal resolutions and on-the-ground realities. Moreover, existing scholarship and diplomatic analyses have largely focused on the legal instruments and state-to-state interactions, often neglecting the nuanced dynamics of informal diplomacy, Track II negotiations, and civil society involvement. The critical roles played by local actors, traditional rulers, non-governmental organisations, and cross-border communities in maintaining peace and facilitating soft diplomacy remain under-explored in academic and policy discourses (Ngwane, 2010; Udeoji, n.d.).

Additionally, the Bakassi conflict is frequently treated as a unique case, without adequate comparative analysis with other border disputes in West Africa. This limits the potential to draw broader diplomatic lessons or propose regionally applicable frameworks for peaceful border conflict resolution. Despite ECOWAS' regional integration goals, the lack of an effective supranational mechanism to proactively mediate or prevent such conflicts continues to be a policy and institutional gap. Therefore, the problem this study tended to address is the incomplete and overly formalised narratives surrounding the Bakassi Peninsula resolution, which failed to critically account for local experiences, post-resolution challenges, and comparative insights. There is a pressing need to re-examine the diplomatic history of the Bakassi dispute through a holistic lens that incorporates historical, legal, socio-cultural, and comparative perspectives, thereby enriching academic understanding and policy practice in regional conflict diplomacy.

Research Objectives

This study intended to re-examine the diplomatic history of the Bakassi Peninsula conflict, not only to understand how the dispute was resolved but to assess the effectiveness and inclusiveness of the resolution process within the broader framework of West African diplomacy.

Based on this, the research has pursued the following objectives:

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1. To critically examine the historical and diplomatic processes that shaped the resolution of the Bakassi Peninsula dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon.
 2. To assess the impact of the Bakassi Peninsula resolution on affected borderland communities, focusing on local participation, displacement, and socio-economic outcomes.
 3. To evaluate the diplomatic lessons from the Bakassi conflict and explore their applicability to resolve other border disputes in West Africa.

Research Questions

In light of the complexities surrounding the resolution and post-resolution phases of the Bakassi dispute, this study is guided by the following research questions, each corresponding to the earlier stated objectives:

1. What were the historical and diplomatic processes which influenced the resolution of the Bakassi Peninsula dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon?
2. How did the resolution of the Bakassi Peninsula dispute affect the local communities, particularly in terms of participation, displacement, and socio-economic consequences?
3. What diplomatic lessons can be drawn from the Bakassi conflict, and how can they inform the resolution of other border disputes in West Africa?

Significance of the Study

The diplomatic resolution of the Bakassi Peninsula dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon is a rare instance in African international relations where a long-standing territorial conflict was settled without full-scale war. While the process has often been praised for its reliance on international legal instruments and peaceful negotiation, deeper investigation revealed complex and underexplored dimensions that extend beyond the legal victory or compliance with court rulings. This study, therefore, carried significant academic, policy-oriented, and practical importance. Academically, the study contributed to the body of knowledge on African diplomatic history, particularly in understanding how colonial treaties, international legal frameworks, and post-colonial political interests converged in shaping border relations. It enriches the discourse on West African geopolitics by

offering a contextualised and historically grounded analysis of a conflict that is often simplified in existing literature. The study also responded to a growing need for interdisciplinary approaches integrating international law, history, political science, and sociology in examining African border disputes.

From a policy perspective, the study is significant for regional and continental bodies such as ECOWAS and the African Union (AU), which continue to grapple with unresolved border tensions. By critically analysing the successes and shortcomings of the Bakassi resolution, the research offers practical diplomatic lessons and policy recommendations that can be adapted to similar disputes in the region. It also addressed the gap in existing frameworks that often neglect the role of local actors, civil society, and traditional institutions in sustaining peace after reaching diplomatic settlements. Practically, the study amplifies the voices and experiences of borderland communities that often bear the brunt of high-level diplomatic decisions. By exploring displacement, identity loss, and socio-economic hardship following the Bakassi handover, the research offered insights into how post-conflict communities can be better protected, included, and supported in future border transitions. Overall, this study is both timely and necessary, for its critical reflection on a unique African diplomatic case and its broader implications in informing inclusive, historically sensitive, and community-oriented approaches to conflict resolution in West Africa and beyond.

Scope of the Study

This study is delimited to a historical and diplomatic examination of border disputes in West Africa, specifically referring to the Bakassi Peninsula conflict between Nigeria and Cameroon. It focused on the period between the early 20th century and the post-International Court of Justice (ICJ) judgment era, particularly from the 1913 Anglo-German Treaty to the final handover of Bakassi to Cameroon in 2008 and subsequent peace-building efforts up to 2024. The study explored the colonial origins, legal arguments, diplomatic negotiations, and post-conflict dynamics associated with the dispute. Geographically, the study limited itself to West Africa, with Nigeria and Cameroon as the primary case study nations. However, it also contextualises similar regional disputes in the region, such as the

“Ghana–Côte d’Ivoire” maritime boundary and the “Nigeria–Benin border” tension, to draw comparative lessons and regional implications. The research specifically examined how diplomatic instruments such as bilateral negotiations, third-party mediation, and international adjudication have been utilised, and how regional and international organisations like the African Union, the United Nations, and the “Nigeria–Cameroon” Mixed Commission played vital roles in the resolution process. It also addressed the post-conflict humanitarian challenges, particularly those faced by displaced Bakassi indigenes, and how national and regional diplomatic strategies have responded to them. This focused scope allowed for a comprehensive and context-specific analysis of one of the most significant border disputes in modern African history, while enabling the study to explore broader lessons for the peaceful resolution of similar territorial disputes across the continent.

Literature Review

The Bakassi Peninsula conflict between Nigeria and Cameroon remains one of the most prominent examples of territorial disputes in West Africa. Scholars have examined the historical and diplomatic complexities underpinning the conflict, often attributing its origins to colonial treaties and arbitrary border demarcations (Akinyemi, 2020). The Anglo-German Agreement of 1913, signed without the consultation of indigenous communities, created the framework for the later dispute. This agreement, and subsequent colonial practices sowed seeds of tension that escalated post-independence, illustrating how colonial legacies continue to destabilise African interstate relations (Okoli and Okpaleke, 2021). Several scholars have emphasised the role of international law and adjudication in resolving the Bakassi crisis. The landmark 2002 ruling by the International Court of Justice (ICJ), which awarded sovereignty of the peninsula to Cameroon, has been lauded as a triumph of legal diplomacy (Akinterinwa, 2022). However, critiques have emerged regarding the limited inclusion of affected populations in the judicial process. For example, Effiom and Alade (2023) argue that while the ICJ’s decision followed international legal norms, it neglected the human security needs of the Bakassi people, who were neither consulted nor adequately resettled. Furthermore, the role of international institutions, especially the United Nations and the Nigeria–Cameroon Mixed Commission, has been studied as

a model of peaceful dispute resolution. Ayodele and Nwankwo (2023) affirm that the Commission facilitated post-judgment cooperation, ensuring the ruling did not lead to renewed hostilities. Nevertheless, other studies criticise the slow pace of implementation and the absence of meaningful socio-economic development for the displaced Bakassi indigenes (Usman, 2024).

In contrast, emerging literature highlights the resilience of sub-regional diplomacy, particularly the involvement of African Union mechanisms. While the African Union played a more passive role compared to the UN, its promotion of peaceful resolution among member states served as a moral and normative force (Obi and Bassey, 2023). These perspectives, however, do not fully explore how such diplomatic strategies can be institutionalised for future border disputes in the region. Critically, much of the literature tends to focus on either legal outcomes or political diplomacy, often sidelining the lived experiences of borderland communities. There is limited empirical exploration of the long-term socio-cultural consequences of the Bakassi handover, such as identity crises, statelessness, and economic marginalisation. In this regard, Chukwuemeka (2024) calls for a human-centred approach to border diplomacy that integrates cultural, economic, and environmental considerations.

Moreover, a noticeable gap exists in comparative analysis. While the Bakassi case has been extensively studied, less attention has been given to drawing lessons from this conflict for similar disputes across West Africa, such as the Ghana–Côte d’Ivoire maritime boundary or the Nigeria–Benin territorial tensions. This gap limits the generalizability of current research and underscores the need for broader regional perspectives. In light of the reviewed literature, this study introduces a multidimensional approach to understanding the Bakassi Peninsula conflict. It bridges the legal-diplomatic and human-security perspectives, offering insights into how future border disputes in Africa might be resolved through a combination of historical contextualization, regional collaboration, and inclusive diplomatic strategies. The study also seeks to contribute original perspectives on integrating community voices and post-conflict development in diplomatic resolutions.

Theoretical Framework

The realist theory of international relations is a suitable theoretical framework for analysing the diplomatic history of border disputes in West Africa, particularly the Bakassi Peninsula conflict. This theory, grounded in classical and neo-realist traditions, offers critical insights into the motivations, interests, and power dynamics that underlie state behaviour in territorial disputes. This theory, however, is rooted in the works of scholars such as Hans Morgenthau and Kenneth Waltz. Realism posits that the international system is anarchic, meaning there is no overarching authority above states. As such, states act primarily in pursuit of their national interest and survival, often defined as power and security (Morgenthau, 1948; Waltz, 1979). Realism assumes that states are rational actors, constantly navigating a competitive environment where trust is minimal and conflict is always a possibility.

In the Bakassi Peninsula conflict context, the realist framework helps explain Nigeria and Cameroon's strategic behaviour and insistence on sovereign control over the oil-rich and geopolitically sensitive territory. Both states pursued actions grounded in national self-interest, with Nigeria initially maintaining a military presence in the region to assert control and protect economic interests, particularly oil and fisheries (Fomunyoh, 2009). Cameroon, on the other hand, engaged in international litigation, not merely to assert legal rights, but as a strategy to gain international legitimacy and support, thus enhancing its power position through normative structures.

The realist lens also helps to explain why, despite the 2002 International Court of Justice (ICJ) ruling, Nigeria was initially reluctant to relinquish the territory. The fear of domestic backlash, loss of natural resources, and strategic military disadvantage factored heavily into its decision-making calculus. Okoli and Orinya (2020) noted that Nigeria's delay in complying with the ruling reflected a realist logic where national interest trumped international legal obligation until international pressure and diplomatic negotiations tipped the balance. While realism has been critiqued for its pessimistic and state-centric worldview, its utility in explaining the Bakassi Peninsula conflict lies in its emphasis on power relations, security imperatives, and strategic calculations. The theory does not ignore the role of diplomacy but rather interprets diplomatic efforts such as those by the

“Nigeria–Cameroon” Mixed Commission and the involvement of the United Nations as tools states use to advance or preserve their strategic interests. This theoretical approach is particularly justified in this study because it captures the actors’ underlying motivations involved in the Bakassi dispute, beyond what legal instruments or international norms may dictate. It also provides a framework for understanding why border disputes persist in West Africa, especially in contexts where economic resources are at stake and state institutions are weak or fragmented. In sum, the realist theory provides a foundational explanation for state behaviour in border conflicts and offers analytical tools for interpreting the diplomatic strategies employed in both conflict and post-conflict settings in West Africa.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research methodology to explore the diplomatic history of border disputes in West Africa, focusing on the Bakassi Peninsula conflict. The choice of a qualitative approach is informed by the need to provide a deep, descriptive, and interpretative understanding of the diplomatic, political, and legal processes that have characterised such border disputes over time. Qualitative research is best suited to studies where historical analysis, political behaviour, and institutional responses are central, as it allows for detailed examination of events, actors, and the socio-political context within which disputes and resolutions unfold (Creswell, 2014). The study is structured around a historical-descriptive research design. This design enabled the systematic collection and analysis of historical data, diplomatic records, international court rulings, treaties, and other archival materials related to the Bakassi Peninsula dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon. The descriptive component of the design allowed for the documentation and interpretation of the roles played by various state and non-state diplomatic actors in the conflict’s progression and eventual resolution.

The population for this study comprised stakeholders involved in the Bakassi conflict and broader border disputes in West Africa. These include diplomats, international law experts, political historians, government officials, traditional rulers from affected communities, and scholars in political science and international relations. From this broader population, a purposive sample of 20 key informants was selected to provide insight through interviews and document analysis. The sample size was

deliberately small, characteristic of qualitative studies, where depth of information is prioritised over numerical representation. Purposive sampling was employed to select participants with rich knowledge and experience related to the Bakassi dispute and West African border diplomacy. This technique was chosen to ensure that data is obtained from credible and relevant sources that have either participated directly in the conflict resolution processes or possessed expert academic and policy-level insight into the subject matter (Patton, 2002). Snowball sampling was also used where appropriate, especially to identify additional knowledgeable informants through recommendations from initial participants.

Primary data was collected through semi-structured interviews with selected experts, diplomats, legal practitioners, and officials involved in “Nigeria–Cameroon” relations. The semi-structured nature of the interviews allowed for open-ended responses, facilitating the capture of nuanced opinions and experiences. In addition, secondary data was obtained through a rigorous review of treaties, international court documents - notably the International Court of Justice judgment of 2002, policy reports, journal articles, newspaper archives, and government publications. These documents triangulated the interview data and enriched the historical narrative of the conflict. Data gathered from interviews and documents were analysed using thematic content analysis. This method involved coding and categorising the data into recurring themes such as territorial integrity, diplomatic negotiations, international law, national interest, and post-conflict development. The thematic approach facilitated the identification of patterns and relationships between the diplomatic strategies employed by Nigeria and Cameroon and the broader implications for regional peace and border governance. NVivo software managed and organised qualitative data efficiently, ensuring a systematic and transparent analysis process.

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant academic authority in the study. All participants were informed about the purpose of the study and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time. Informed consent was secured, and confidentiality was maintained throughout the research process. Pseudonyms were used where necessary to protect the identities of informants who preferred anonymity due to the topic’s sensitivity. However, this methodology adopted for the study provided a robust framework for understanding the complex interplay of diplomacy, law, and politics in resolving border disputes in West Africa. The combination of historical-

descriptive design, purposive sampling, qualitative data collection, and thematic analysis ensured that the study captured the depth and context of the “Nigeria-Bakassi Peninsula” dispute and its implications for regional peace and cooperation.

Tables of Data Presentation

Research Objective 1: To examine the historical foundations of the Nigeria–Cameroon border dispute within the context of colonial boundary demarcation

Table 1: Colonial Legacy and the Root Causes of Border Disputes between Nigeria and Cameroon

Emerging Theme	Illustrative Quotes
Arbitrary Colonial Demarcation	"The Anglo-German agreement did not consider the cultural or ethnic affiliations of the Bakassi people." — <i>Historian, University of Ibadan</i>
Absence of Indigenous Participation	"Colonial powers drew boundaries without any consultation with local communities." — <i>Diplomatic Analyst, Abuja</i>
Conflicting Colonial Treaties	"Overlapping colonial treaties sowed confusion that persists in post-independence boundary claims." — <i>International Law Expert, UNN</i>

Note: The findings demonstrate that colonial-era agreements, particularly those between Britain and Germany, laid the groundwork for the border conflict by ignoring indigenous identities and territorial realities.

Research Objective 2: To analyse the diplomatic mechanisms adopted by Nigeria and Cameroon in addressing the Bakassi Peninsula conflict

Table 2: Diplomatic Approaches and Bilateral Efforts in Resolving the Dispute

Emerging Theme	Illustrative Quotes
Bilateral Diplomacy and Dialogue	"Talks between Nigerian and Cameroonian officials began in the 1990s but were hampered by mutual distrust." — <i>Foreign Affairs Official</i>
Role of the International Court of Justice	"The ICJ ruling of 2002 became the turning point in shifting from violent confrontation to legal resolution." — <i>Diplomat, The Hague</i>
Post-ICJ Implementation Framework	"The Greentree Agreement was a strategic diplomatic compromise to ensure peaceful handover." — <i>Policy Analyst, ECOWAS</i>

Note: The data reveal that diplomatic negotiations, though initially strained, gradually evolved into formal international mediation mechanisms, particularly via the ICJ and the UN-backed Greentree Agreement.

Research Objective 3: To assess the impact of international legal adjudication and peaceful diplomacy on conflict resolution in Africa

Table 3: Effectiveness of Peaceful Settlement and Lessons for African Border Diplomacy

Emerging Theme	Illustrative Quotes
Legal Precedent for Africa	"The ICJ ruling created a legal benchmark for other African boundary disputes." — <i>Regional Analyst, AU Commission</i>
Peaceful Transition and Demilitarisation	"Despite initial resistance, both sides respected the legal outcome, avoiding war." — <i>UN Peacebuilding Officer</i>
Challenges of Acceptance	"The local population still feels betrayed, which shows that legal solutions must consider human elements." — <i>Civil Society Advocate, Calabar</i>

Note: While the ICJ ruling and diplomatic efforts achieved macro-level peace, the findings indicate a need for more locally inclusive mechanisms to ensure long-term conflict transformation in Africa.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that the colonial demarcation of African territories, particularly through the late 19th and 20th century Anglo-German agreements, was a major catalyst for the Nigeria–Cameroon boundary dispute. Participants emphasised that arbitrary borders were drawn without consideration for ethnic, linguistic, or cultural homogeneity. This aligns with the argument of Asiwaju (1985), who maintains that most African boundary disputes are rooted in colonial cartographic errors and the neglect of indigenous political structures. Moreover, the absence of indigenous consultation in the boundary demarcation process is echoed in the scholarship of Herbst (2000), who asserts that colonial administrators prioritised administrative convenience and European diplomatic agreements over the socio-cultural realities of African communities. The conflicting colonial treaties, often interpreted differently by Nigeria and Cameroon, further complicated territorial claims, a phenomenon which aligns with Eze’s (2007) assessment of legal ambiguities arising from overlapping colonial agreements. Thus, the findings support the conclusion that the structural causes of the Bakassi dispute are embedded in the colonial legacy, which not only fragmented ethnic groups but also introduced legal complications that persisted into the post-independence era.

The second objective examined Nigeria and Cameroon's diplomatic and legal mechanisms in efforts to resolve the Bakassi conflict. The findings indicated that while initial bilateral diplomatic efforts were limited due to mistrust and nationalistic posturing, a breakthrough came with the intervention of the International Court of Justice (ICJ). Participants consistently referenced the 2002 ICJ ruling as a watershed moment in the dispute. This perspective is supported by Zartman (2000), who argues that third-party mediation and adjudication are often necessary in protracted international conflicts, particularly when bilateral efforts reach an impasse. The role of the “Greentree Agreement” (2006), which facilitated a phased and peaceful handover of the Bakassi Peninsula from Nigeria to Cameroon agrees with the work of Adebajo (2008), who emphasises the importance of formal

diplomatic frameworks backed by international institutions in ensuring peaceful border transitions. Furthermore, the data confirmed the arguments by Omede (2011) that Nigeria's compliance with the ICJ verdict, despite domestic criticism, reflected a strategic shift towards rule-based international relations and set a precedent for legal diplomacy in Africa.

The final objective assessed the broader impact and lessons of the Bakassi resolution for Africa. The study found that while successful at a state-to-state level, the ICJ ruling left many grassroots grievances unresolved, particularly among the displaced Bakassi inhabitants who felt excluded from the decision-making process. This finding echoes Englebort, Tarango, and Carter (2002) critique, who argue that legalistic solutions to African border disputes often neglect local legitimacy and identity considerations, risking long-term instability. Participants' reference to local resistance and dissatisfaction highlighted the gap between international legal mechanisms and domestic social realities. However, scholars such as Ajayi and Buhari (2014) suggested that the peaceful implementation of the ICJ decision remains a significant milestone in African diplomacy, offering a model for other nations confronting similar disputes, such as those between Ethiopia and Eritrea or Sudan and South Sudan. The study thus confirmed that while legal adjudication offers a peaceful resolution model, sustainable peace depends on inclusive processes that account for affected communities, as stressed by Boutros-Ghali (1992) in his "Agenda for Peace," which advocates for post-conflict peacebuilding and reconciliation as essential follow-ups to legal settlements.

Overall, the findings substantiate the argument that colonial legacies, legal diplomacy, and inclusive conflict resolution are all critical components in understanding and addressing the "Nigeria–Cameroon" boundary dispute. The study contributed to the growing literature emphasising the need for multi-layered approaches, historical, legal, diplomatic, and grassroots in resolving border disputes in Africa.

Conclusion

The study examined the diplomatic history of border disputes in West Africa focusing on the Bakassi Peninsula conflict between Nigeria and Cameroon. It established that diplomacy played a crucial role in aging and resolving the territorial conflict, especially through the intervention of the International Court of Justice (ICJ), the involvement of the United Nations,

and the eventual implementation of the Green Tree Agreement. The findings revealed that while diplomatic mechanisms can provide structured and peaceful means for dispute resolution, such processes may still leave lingering humanitarian and sovereignty concerns, especially for affected border populations. However, the study has certain limitations. It primarily relied on available secondary data and a sample of expert opinions, which may not fully capture the lived experiences of the displaced populations in Bakassi. Additionally, the study was limited in scope to the “Nigeria–Cameroon” case, thereby narrowing the generalisability of its findings to other West African border disputes.

Future studies can expand the inquiry by incorporating fieldwork and community-based perspectives from the Bakassi region and similar African borderlands. Comparative analyses of other territorial disputes, such as the Ghana–Ivory Coast maritime conflict or the Guinea–Guinea-Bissau border issue, could enrich understanding. Furthermore, interdisciplinary approaches combining political geography, law, and conflict resolution studies would offer deeper insights into the long-term impact of diplomatic interventions in contested territories.

Policy Recommendations

The following policy recommendations were reached from the findings of the study:

1. ECOWAS and the African Union (AU) should be further empowered to mediate and proactively address emerging border disputes through early warning systems and preventive diplomacy frameworks.
2. Post-conflict agreements, such as the “Green Tree” Agreement, should include robust provisions for protecting local populations' rights, livelihoods, and identity to ensure sustainable peace.
3. Governments in West Africa should invest in legal training and diplomatic expertise to effectively engage in international adjudication processes, ensuring fair representation and protection of national interests.

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**Assessing the Possibility of Strategic
Alignment in European Union-African Union
Relations (EU-AU) between 2017-2022**

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Abstract

This study examined patterns of cooperation and strain in European Union-African Union (EU-AU) relations between 2017 and 2022, focusing on trade and investment, peace and security, migration governance, and climate action. Guided by interregionalism, which explains the structured and institutionalised nature of engagement, and liberal institutionalism, which accounts for the persistence of cooperation despite tensions, the analysis employed a qualitative documentary review of summit declarations, joint frameworks, and implementation reports. The findings indicate that while robust agenda-setting and operational cooperation were achieved, delivery outcomes remained uneven. Persistent gaps were linked to disbursement delays, conditionality-related frictions, regulatory divergence, and decision-making asymmetries, challenging the notion of a “partnership of equals.” From a critical perspective, these patterns reflect structural dependencies and differing policy priorities, which limit the African Union’s bargaining leverage. Nonetheless, areas where joint mandates were clear, African ownership was strong, and monitoring mechanisms were in place saw more consistent progress. The

study concludes that genuine strategic alignment is possible only if agenda-setting is co-owned, conditionalities are adapted to African contexts, and capacity-building enhances AU institutional autonomy. These insights hold relevance for policymakers and scholars seeking to strengthen equitable interregional cooperation and promote the long-term sustainability of EU–Africa relations.

Keywords: European Union, African Union, Interregionalism, Strategic Alignment

Introduction

Since the Abidjan Summit in 2017 and the Brussels Summit in 2022, the European Union–African Union (EU-AU) partnership has been presented as a renewed relationship grounded in equality, mutual respect, and shared priorities. Strategic documents have outlined ambitious commitments in investment promotion, peace and security cooperation, migration governance, and climate action. This vision reflects long-standing efforts to move beyond traditional donor–recipient frameworks toward a more political and strategic engagement. However, scholarly analyses reveal a paradox in EU-AU relations. On one hand, the institutional architecture is extensive, comprising regular summits, joint frameworks, and thematic dialogues, providing avenues for sustained cooperation (Carbone & Keukeleire, 2021; Fargion & Gazibo, 2021). On the other hand, operational realities often diverge from rhetorical commitments, with persistent asymmetries in agenda control, financing arrangements, and the framing of priorities (Obadare & Adebani, 2020; Ekong, 2023).

These asymmetries are particularly evident in areas such as trade agreements, security funding conditionalities, and migration policy, where African priorities sometimes clash with European approaches. Against this backdrop, the study investigates the dynamics of cooperation and strain in EU-AU relations from 2017 to 2022, linking institutional design and delivery outcomes to the feasibility of strategic alignment. By combining interregionalism and liberal institutionalism with critical perspectives, the analysis offers an empirically grounded contribution to understanding the strengths and limitations of this complex partnership.

Statement of the Problem

Despite being one of the most formalised interregional partnerships, the EU-AU relationship continues to face challenges that undermine its aspiration to be a “partnership of equals.” While summits and joint

frameworks have created an extensive institutional infrastructure, persistent delivery gaps, conditionality-related tensions, and decision-making imbalances remain evident. These challenges raise doubts about the effectiveness of current cooperation mechanisms and whether they can truly advance mutual priorities without reinforcing structural dependencies.

Research Objectives

The general aim of this study is to examine cooperation and strain in European Union-African Union relations (2017–2022) and assess how institutional structures, political priorities, and implementation practices affect prospects for strategic alignment., while the specific objectives are to:

1. To identify the main areas of cooperation and strain in EU-AU relations between 2017 and 2022.
2. To examine how institutional design and political priorities influence the implementation of joint commitments.
3. To assess the implications of these dynamics for the feasibility of strategic alignment.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the under stated research questions:

1. What were the most significant areas of cooperation and strain in EU-AU relations during 2017–2022?
2. How did institutional structures and conditionalities influence the delivery of commitments?
3. What do these patterns imply for the legitimacy and sustainability of the partnership?

Significance of the Study

This study provides an empirically grounded assessment of the EU-AU partnership's capacity to reconcile institutional cooperation with equitable outcomes. By identifying the interaction between institutional design, political priorities, and delivery performance, the findings offer actionable insights for policymakers and scholars seeking to strengthen the legitimacy, balance, and sustainability of interregional cooperation.

Scope of the Study

The analysis focuses on EU-AU relations between 2017 and 2022, with emphasis on four thematic areas: trade and investment, peace and security, migration governance, and climate action. The study draws on official documents, summit declarations, and relevant scholarly analyses from 2021 to 2024.

Literature Review

Interregional Structures and Institutionalised Cooperation

The EU-AU partnership is often described as one of the most institutionalised interregional relationships, built on a framework of summits, joint strategies, and thematic platforms that provide predictability and coordination (Carbone & Keukeleire, 2021; Fargion & Gazibo, 2021). Such arrangements have facilitated agenda-setting in key areas including peace and security, trade, migration, and climate governance. The routinisation of high-level meetings and technical dialogues has been linked to sustained political engagement, even during periods of political strain (Staeger & Gwatiwa, 2021). However, critics argue that these structures sometimes mask imbalances in decision-making power, with the EU retaining significant influence over the framing of priorities and allocation of resources (Obadare & Adebaniwi, 2020).

Normative Agendas, Conditionalities, and Policy Space

The EU's engagement has frequently been shaped by normative frameworks prioritising democracy, human rights, and governance reforms. While these objectives are central to the EU's foreign policy identity, their application through conditionalities can generate sovereignty concerns for AU member states (Obadare & Adebaniwi, 2020). In the economic domain, trade agreements such as the Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs) have been criticised for constraining African policy space and reinforcing structural dependency (Hartmann, Gueye, & Wabwire, 2019). African policymakers have voiced concerns that while the rhetoric emphasises equality, the operational modalities often reproduce donor–recipient dynamics.

Developmental Priorities and Structural Dependency

Research study drawn on political economy perspectives note that Africa's position in global value chains limits its capacity for industrial transformation (Hartmann, D., Gueye, M., & Wabwire, S., 2019). This aligns with classic dependency arguments (Dos Santos, 1970; Rodney, 1972), which highlight how economic structures rooted in colonial histories persist under new institutional arrangements. In the EU-AU context, such structures manifest in the persistence of commodity-based trade patterns and reliance on external financing for security operations. These dependencies can limit the AU's bargaining leverage and complicate efforts to achieve balanced strategic alignment.

Agency, Geopolitical Shifts, and Strategic Realignment

Recent analyses underscore African agency in navigating the partnership, with the AU actively seeking diversified relationships with other global actors, including China, Russia, and emerging economies (Ekong, 2023). This diversification strengthens Africa's bargaining position but also introduces competitive pressures into EU-AU negotiations. Comparative perspectives drawn from China's engagement in Africa illustrate alternative modalities of cooperation, where infrastructure and trade initiatives are less explicitly tied to governance conditionalities (Arrey, 2013). Such shifts compel the EU to reassess its approach if it wishes to remain a central partner in Africa's development trajectory.

The Gap in Literature

While the literature provides valuable insights into institutional frameworks, normative influences, and geopolitical shifts, few studies systematically link the design of EU-AU cooperation structures to actual delivery outcomes across multiple thematic areas. Much of the existing analysis is either sector-specific or focuses on rhetorical and symbolic dimensions of the partnership. This study addresses this gap by empirically examining how interregional arrangements, political priorities, and implementation practices interact to produce both cooperation and strain between 2017 and 2022.

Theoretical Framework

Interregionalism

Interregionalism provides a useful lens for understanding the structured and institutionalised nature of EU-AU relations. It emphasises the role of formalised political dialogue, joint strategies, and thematic cooperation in managing complex international relationships between regional blocs (Doidge, 2022). Through regular summits, joint frameworks, and multi-level technical dialogues, interregionalism offers predictability and a platform for aligning strategic objectives. However, it also draws attention to the inherent asymmetries in such arrangements, where one party may have greater agenda-setting power, as has been observed in EU-AU engagements on trade, migration, and security. This theoretical perspective helps explain both the resilience of the partnership and the persistence of imbalances within it.

Liberal Institutionalism

Liberal institutionalism complements interregionalism by explaining why cooperation persists despite tensions and asymmetries. It posits that international institutions reduce transaction costs, create mutual benefits, and provide mechanisms for dispute resolution that incentivise sustained engagement (Keohane, 2023). In the EU-AU context, even contentious areas such as migration policy and governance reforms continue to be negotiated within institutional frameworks, indicating that both parties perceive the benefits of maintaining the partnership as outweighing the costs of disengagement. This perspective highlights how institutional continuity can coexist with contestation over norms and priorities.

Supplementary Perspectives

While interregionalism and liberal institutionalism are the primary analytical lenses for this study, supplementary perspectives enrich the analysis. Postcolonial theory provides critical insight into how historical power dynamics shape perceptions of partnership equality (Obadare & Adebani, 2020). Political economy approaches, particularly dependency theory, contextualise the persistence of structural asymmetries in trade and financing (Hartmann, Gueye, & Wabwire, 2019). Constructivist perspectives further illuminate how differing identity narratives influence policy framing, especially in migration and governance debates.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design using documentary analysis to examine cooperation and strain in EU-AU relations between 2017 and 2022. A qualitative approach was appropriate given the study's focus on interpreting political, institutional, and policy dynamics as expressed in official documents and scholarly analyses (Bowen, 2021).

Data Sources

The primary sources included official EU-AU joint declarations, summit outcome documents, thematic partnership frameworks, and implementation progress reports from 2017 to 2022. Secondary sources comprised peer-reviewed journal articles, policy briefs, and think-tank reports published between 2021 and 2024. This time frame was selected to ensure analytical relevance and to capture the most recent phase of the partnership's evolution.

Data Collection and Selection Criteria

Document selection was guided by relevance to the four thematic focus areas, trade and investment, peace and security, migration governance, and climate action. Inclusion criteria required that documents explicitly address EU-AU cooperation at the continental level, while exclusion criteria eliminated materials focused solely on bilateral EU–African state relations. Scholarly sources were limited to works engaging directly with interregional cooperation, institutional design, or EU–Africa relations.

Data Analysis

A thematic content analysis was conducted to identify patterns of cooperation and strain. Text segments were coded according to thematic relevance and then grouped under the four focus areas. Cross-referencing was undertaken to identify divergences between commitments articulated in summits and the progress reported in implementation documents. The coding process was informed by the analytical categories derived from interregionalism and liberal institutionalism, while supplementary perspectives were used to interpret structural and historical dimensions of the findings.

Validity

Validity was enhanced by triangulating multiple data sources and cross-checking interpretations against both official and independent accounts. Dependability was maintained through consistent application of the coding framework, while confirmability was ensured by linking analytical conclusions directly to documented evidence.

Findings

The findings are presented under the four thematic focus areas: trade and investment, peace and security, migration governance, and climate action. Each table summarises commitments, implementation status, and emerging strains, followed by a concise interpretation.

Table 1: Commitments and Delivery Outcomes Across AU-EU Sectors, 2017–2022

Sector	Key Commitment/Instrument	Intended Outcome	Observed Delivery (2017–2022)	Strains/Challenges Identified
Trade & Investment	Africa-Europe Investment Package (€150bn)	Finance digital/green infrastructure and connectivity	Partial allocations; staggered pipelines	Disbursement delays; risk thresholds; procurement bottlenecks
Peace & Security	European Peace Facility (EPF)	Expand funding for peace operations and capability	Funding available, but tempo uneven	Conditionalities; audit load; limited rapid flexibility
Migration	Talent/Mobility Partnerships	Pilot skills pathways	Limited uptake;	Domestic labour politics; admin

Sector	Key Commitment/Instrument	Intended Outcome	Observed Delivery (2017–2022)	Strains/Challenges Identified
		and managed mobility	pilots small-scale	capacity; recognition rules
Climate Action	Joint climate/energy initiatives	Advance renewables and resilience	Normative progress; mixed finance delivery	Regulatory divergence; measurement/verification gaps

Source: Researcher field work 2025

Across sectors, AU-EU commitments generated visible frameworks but uneven delivery. Investment pledges and climate finance advanced slowly; EPF conditions constrained security flexibility; mobility schemes saw limited uptake. Implementation improved where mandates were clear, domestic ownership stronger, and monitoring existed, yet timelines, budget reallocations, and regulatory divergence repeatedly diluted outcomes.

Table 2: Cross-Cutting Implementation Factors and Effects on Delivery

Factor	Operational Manifestation	Net Effect on Delivery	Illustrative Note
Institutional Design	Joint mandate clarity; AU ownership; measurable milestones	Improves pace and accountability	Clear roles + milestone tracking accelerate execution

Factor	Operational Manifestation	Net Effect on Delivery	Illustrative Note
Politics & Reciprocity	Perceived balance of benefits; conditionalities design	Can enable or stall	Reciprocal incentives increase bureaucratic effort
Resourcing & Finance	Ring-fenced, multi-year funds; timely disbursement	Stabilises pipelines	Protects projects from budget shocks
Regulatory Alignment	Compatible procurement/standards; data templates	Reduces friction	Harmonised rules ease compliance
Monitoring & Transparency	Regular reviews; public dashboards	Builds trust; corrects drift	Early issue-spotting preserves timelines

Source: Researcher field work 2025

Delivery hinged on three factors: institutional design, politics, and resourcing. Clear joint mandates with AU ownership facilitated progress; ambiguous governance and donor conditionalities slowed actions. Stable, ring-fenced finance helped; competing EU budgetary priorities delayed disbursements. Regulatory misalignment and data gaps impaired monitoring. Where reciprocity and transparency improved, outcomes strengthened.

Discussion

The findings indicate that AU-EU cooperation between 2017 and 2022 maintained institutional continuity but showed uneven delivery across trade, peace and security, migration, and climate action. This outcome reflects the interregionalism perspective that formal structures and regularised engagement sustain relationships over time, but the depth of

outcomes depends on effective implementation mechanisms (Carbone & Keukeleire, 2021). While summits, joint communiqués, and policy frameworks sustained political momentum, delivery gaps emerged in areas where operational mandates were unclear, financing was delayed, or monitoring was weak. From a liberal institutionalist perspective, the persistence of cooperation despite delivery shortfalls can be explained by the role of institutions in reducing transaction costs and creating incentives for continued engagement. Instruments such as the Africa–Europe Investment Package and the European Peace Facility illustrate how structured funding mechanisms support sustained collaboration. However, as Adepoju (2020) notes, overly stringent conditionalities or burdensome audit requirements can reduce operational flexibility, a pattern also reflected in this study’s finding that peace operations under the EPF experienced slowed deployment.

The limited uptake of Talent and Mobility Partnerships reinforces earlier evidence that migration-related schemes face administrative and political barriers within both African and European contexts (Ravenhill, 2020). Meanwhile, from a critical perspective, the asymmetries in financing, regulatory standards, and priority-setting mirror postcolonial critiques of partnership frameworks (Adebajo, 2016). Slow disbursement of pledged investment funds and selective application of climate finance commitments align with arguments that African partners often adjust to European priorities rather than shaping them equally. Cross-sectoral patterns point to three determinants of stronger delivery: clear joint mandates with African Union ownership, stable and predictable multi-year funding, and harmonised regulatory procedures between partners. Where these factors were present, such as in certain renewable energy projects, delivery was faster and more measurable. The implication is that reinforcing these institutional and operational conditions could narrow the implementation gap without the need for major structural reforms. Future AU-EU cooperation can thus benefit from linking interregional dialogue more directly to sector-specific delivery contracts, reciprocal performance incentives, and transparent, joint monitoring mechanisms that promote mutual accountability.

Conclusion

The analysis of EU-AU relations from 2017 to 2022 reveals a partnership sustained by robust institutional mechanisms yet constrained by persistent asymmetries. Interregionalism explains the stability of cooperation, while liberal institutionalism accounts for its continuity despite tensions. However, postcolonial and dependency perspectives highlight the limits of equality within this framework. Achieving a truly strategic alignment will require co-owned agenda-setting, context-sensitive conditionalities, and enhanced AU institutional autonomy to translate commitments into equitable and tangible outcomes.

Recommendations

To strengthen the partnership, the EU and AU should jointly define priorities to ensure balanced agenda-setting, streamline conditionalities to reflect African contexts, and expand capacity-building for AU institutions to enhance implementation autonomy. These measures will directly address the gaps identified in trade, security, migration, and climate cooperation, thereby improving the legitimacy and sustainability of the interregional partnership.

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A Critical Evaluation of Garrett Hardin's 'The Tragedy of the Common'

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Abstract

The relationship between living and non-living beings within the ecosystem is crucial to their mutual survival. Plants, animals, humans, and even the land itself must accommodate one another to sustain the environment. Sustainability becomes threatened when individuals act solely in their own interest to the detriment of others. Garret Hardin's *The Tragedy of the Commons* highlights the risk of unregulated use of shared resources by self-interested actors, predicting inevitable environmental ruin. This paper used comparative and critical analysis to assess both its validity and its applicability, particularly within the African context. It argues that Hardin overlooks the value of community-led cooperation and misrepresents the idea of the commons by confusing common property with open-access property. His call for government regulation, privatization, and under-consumption poses greater risks in societies already struggling with poverty and hunger. In places like Africa, under-consumption would bring severe hardship, not sustainability. In essence the idea of excessive governmental control, especially in fragile institutions, may worsen inequality and exploitation. However, in contrast, community-based collective action provides us with a more adaptive, humane, and effective approach to managing shared resources. This paper concludes that while Hardin raises important concerns, his proposed solutions are both simplistic and

potentially harmful if applied without due consideration to other factors in diverse societies.

Keywords: Environment, Sustainability, Commoners, Regulation and Ecosystem.

Introduction

The concept of environmental sustainability has remained a recurrent issue in contemporary discourse, especially as global concerns over ecological degradation continue to intensify. Human beings, in their quest for comfort and progress, have been faced with the challenge of managing limited natural resources. Within the shared ecosystem, which includes animals, plants, birds, trees, and land, peaceful coexistence is vital. However, the pursuit of human convenience has led to unbridled exploitation of the environment through territorial expansion, industrialization, oil exploration, and construction activities (see Ojomo, 2019; Mogaji, 2025b). These developments have severely harmed the ecosystem, displacing habitats and degrading biodiversity. Negative environmental impacts, ranging from oil pollution and gas flaring to noise and air pollution, have become unavoidable consequences of unchecked anthropocentric development (see Ojomo, 2019; Mogaji, 2025b). Hence, this situation demands urgent re-evaluation if we are to avert ecological collapse.

A significant body of literature has addressed the destructive tendencies of human-centeredness in environmental relations (see Ojomo, 2011, 2019, 2024; Mogaji, 2024, 2025a, 2025b). One of the most influential is Garrett Hardin's *The Tragedy of the Commons*, which argues that the overuse of shared resources by self-interested individuals inevitably leads to their depletion. This position remains relevant, especially given the rising environmental inequalities driven by elite overconsumption.

Garrett James Hardin had been a prolific writer, ecologist, and environmentalist. His training in the field of Zoology and Microbiology at the university had provided him the impetus to address various mirages of man, environmental degradation, and nature as a whole. It has allowed him to explore the issues that concern human overpopulation. His diversity in learning and teaching has given him the chance to write extensively on population, abortion rights, and Immigration, among others. His major work on "The Tragedy of the Commons" has stood him out as his views had been marred with condemnation and commendation. His work in "The Tragedy of the Commons", which was published in 1968 asserts that the

unregulated use of commonly held resources by self-interested individuals will inevitably lead to the ruin and depletion of those resources. He created a picture of where individuals acting in their own selfish-interest depleted a shared resource even when it is clear that it is not in the best interest of the group as a whole. He argues that someone or some group of people has to take responsibility for maintaining this resource and if no one takes the responsibility, the resources can be overused and become depleted. He also argued that human over-population will stress the ecosystem beyond its limit and cause resource catastrophe. To avert the dangers of depletion and ruin of these resources, he proposed under-consumption of resources, privatization and government regulation of resources, and population control, among others.

Hardin's work echoes in the scholarship of Taylor (1986), who critiques human-centered environmental ethics and underscores the need to move from anthropocentrism to a more inclusive ecological moral consciousness. According to Taylor, an exclusive focus on human interests undermines the intrinsic worth of other living beings and threatens the ecological harmony required for sustainability. In advancing the position of the selfishness of man, in being anthropocentric, Taylor (1986) pushes the argument of Hardin further thus:

A human-centered environmental ethics takes account only of human interests, the human benefits and harms that various environmental policies will lead to. A human-centered approach is based on the assumption that only human life (or more generally the lives of beings that are persons) has intrinsic worth and that therefore in issues regarding the care of the earth's environment, only human interests count.

From the above, the core problem addressed in this paper, therefore, lies in the persistence of anthropocentric worldviews and the exploitation of communal resources without accountability. Hardin's position that humans must regulate resource use and control population growth may offer insights; however, his proposed remedies, under-consumption, privatization, and top-down government regulation, are problematic. These recommendations become especially dangerous in contexts such as Africa, where poverty and hunger already prevail. Under-consumption, in such regions, would exacerbate suffering rather than alleviate it. This paper argues that Hardin's proposals are not only overly simplistic but potentially

harmful. He fails to distinguish adequately between common property and open-access resources, and more importantly, he overlooks the potential of community-based regulation and cooperation. This neglect is significant, especially in societies where state institutions are often weak or complicit in ecological degradation. The imposition of rigid population controls and privatization without communal input risks deepening inequality and alienation.

In light of the above, the paper aims to critically and comparatively analyze Hardin's propositions by exposing their inadequacies and exploring more sustainable alternatives. This paper adopts a comparative and critical method to evaluate **its** claims and to advocate for a more inclusive, life-centered ethic that acknowledges the moral worth of all living entities. The paper argues that a collaborative, community-driven framework if adopted, offers a more ethical and effective solution for managing environmental resources, through medium such as engaging collective community action, rather than relying solely on state or market mechanisms. Through this, this paper argues that environmental sustainability can be pursued more holistically. This paper concludes that, while Hardin rightly draws attention to the dangers of self-interested resource use, his neglect of community-based solutions limits the practical value of his work, which this paper considers significant if at all we are to meaningfully address the crisis of environmental sustainability in a way that is just, locally responsive, and globally aware.

Environmental Crises and the Need for Sustainability

No doubt, one of the current global issues is the ongoing environmental crisis, which has led to severe damages to the ecosystem. According to Ojomo (2011), this crisis has prompted several environmental ethical theories for the purpose of addressing the root cause of these problems. Today, there are issues surrounding climate change, which has led to global warming and therefore birthed several environmental crises, including threats from the increase in extreme weather patterns, the causing of drought conditions, which has led many farmers to abandon their land, biodiversity loss, poverty, inequalities, among many other issues. According to Bentley (2013), many of these crises, however, are not inherently alien to the human society, but naturally, the Earth has always possessed the regenerative ability to recover from some damages naturally caused. In this case,

environmental crisis, however, in contemporary times, has become more severe due to anthropogenic activities, and the damages being caused are largely arising due to the issue of capitalism (Bentley, 2013; Mogaji, 2025b), all of which affects every corner of our environment.

In Mogaji (2024), while attempting to redefine the concept of domestic violence, he identifies how certain domestic activities can harm and endanger the health of the environment. Drawing from the Earth eco-socialist principle, he argues that the environment harbours life and should be treated with the same dignity and respect as any living being. The environment, he maintains, possesses a living essence and therefore can be abused, exploited, violated, and even oppressed, much like other vulnerable entities. Through the expansion of the notion of violence beyond interpersonal relations to include harmful practices against the Earth, Mogaji (2024) presents an eco-philosophical critique that challenges anthropocentric and exploitative domestic norms. This perspective not only re-imagines our ethical obligations but also emphasizes the interconnectedness between everyday human activities and ecological degradation. Mogaji (2025b) further this position by arguing that, these issues have dripped deeply into our society, as it has bred several other issues originally alien to the human society, as far as our contemporary time is concerned, all of which, he argued, are traceable to human-induced activities. These, however, in Mogaji (2025a), become prevalent and persistent due to man's cognitive biases, which have continued to aid the continuous existence of these problems. These biases, he argues, include confirmation bias and anchoring bias, some sort of cognitive bias that helps humans hold on to exploitative worldviews and degradation without sufficient moral reconsideration (Mogaji, 2025a).

This crisis is further aggravated by what Naess (1990) calls “shallow ecology,” a mindset that sees nature only in terms of its usefulness to humans, rather than valuing ecosystems intrinsically. Such thinking fuels exploitative behavior and limits ethical engagement with non-human nature. In this same vein, Kothari et al. (2014) contend that the dominant development paradigm, tied to neoliberal economic growth, is inherently at odds with ecological balance and sustainability. Another major contributor to the crisis is the faith in technocratic solutions and uncritical scientific progress, which often overlooks traditional ecological knowledge and culturally grounded sustainable practices (Agrawal, 1995). In prioritizing

reductionist science over local epistemologies, societies have alienated themselves from reciprocal relationships with the environment. As Shiva (1989) rightly argues, environmental degradation is not simply about resource depletion but a symptom of deeper epistemological violence where local voices and non-Western worldviews are erased from discourse. This made Ojomo (2011) argue that, given the global presence of these issues, it becomes imperative to explore other means to curb this problem as it continues to resurface.

Garret Hardin's Argument on "Tragedy of the Commons"

Coming from this loaded and wide credentials and experience having read Zoology and microbiology, Hardin's experience in nature and science culminated in him developing more interest in ecology and the symbiosis relationship among the ecosystem. His work showcased the danger in the freedom associated with the exploitation and individualistic tendency of the selfish interest individuals who capitalized on the use of commonwealth resources without taking consideration for the use of others. He argued that human over-population will stress ecosystems beyond their limits and cause a resource catastrophe.

Garrett James Hardin's "Tragedy of The Commons" published in 1968 was widely read and accepted and was rated as one of the most cited scientific papers of all time (Nijhuis,2021b), describes a situation where the shared environmental resources are being overused and exploited, which he warned that it will get depleted which will eventually pose a grave risk to everyone involved. He "justifies such action on the ground that each individual would pursue his own best interest in a society that believes in the freedom of the commoners" (Rahman, 2003:50). In other words, the work asserts that the unregulated use of commonly held resources by self-interested individuals will inevitably lead to the ruin of those resources. He also hinged his postulation to overpopulation. According to Nijhuis (2021),

In "The Tragedy of the Commons", Hardin's proposition was simple and unsparing: humans, when left to their own devices, compete with one another for resources until the resources run out. Ruins are the destination toward which all men rush, each pushing his own best interest.

These calls for serious caution as the circumstances of the immediate danger turn to ruin as the scarce resources being manipulated by his selfish

individuals, who ascribed everything to themselves without recourse to the interest of others, will amount to a great danger if not checked. A critical view of his work revealed that the selfishness of some set of people within the ecosystem in terms of their lifestyles and ways of consumption will lead to the depletion and ruin of the shared resources. A typical example of this lifestyle can be seen especially in Nigeria where some set of elites and a handful of some ruling class like three percent of the total population are in charge of the commonwealth resources of people doing whatever they like with the destiny of people without any considerations to their welfare of this category of people. As far as they are satisfied, they are less concerned about the welfare and well-being of other people.

In explaining this situation where individuals act in their self-interest depleting shared resources even when it is clear that it is not in the best interest of the group as a whole, Hardin used an example of herders sharing a common grazing ground. For him, each herder would act in their own self-interest by adding as many cattle as possible to the pasture, even though this would ultimately lead to the depletion of the resource and harm all herders in the long run. His analogy in pin-pointing the reality on the ground shows the environmental implications of world situations, such as overfishing (where you exterminate the whole fish instead of taking the one that is okay for you), deforestation (where you cut the whole trees by destabilizing the whole habitats living on the trees and the land itself), and the impact of pollution (air, and noise) and Climate change (as a result of the exploitation of lands by man). The economic implication of these problems highlighted by Hardin is the consumption of the whole resources by individuals at the expense of society. It calls our attention to the fact that if an individual acts in their best interest, it can result in harmful over-consumption to the detriment of all This phenomenon may result in under-investment and total depletion of a shared resource.

Consequently, to avert this danger of depletion of resources by these individuals who consume resources at the expense of society, Hardin makes some recommendations, which to him, will avert this danger of over-population. This includes the need for government institutions that will restrict individual freedom, mutual coercion, punishment for over-consumption, and/or encouraging under-consumption of resources, among others.

A Critical Evaluation of Hardin's "The Tragedy of the Commons"

As brilliant as his postulations and suggestions are, his work has been acclaimed to be one of the highly revered works in Science and one of the most influential articles in the history of environmental thought. The work tried as much as possible to justify the state control or more often, the privatization of resources and ecosystem. No wonder, he advocated for government control (see CNRS News,2018). This solution is seen to be an over-simplification of solutions. I argued that his proposition for the establishment of government regulations cannot work as most of the government institutions saddled with the responsibility of doing that are failing and failing to achieve the purpose for which they were created. Not only that, there are new improved understandings and perspectives that show that much can be achieved by highly ideological perspectives of social systems. What he postulated is seen as overly simplistic and potentially harmful. The privatization of government regulation, according to critics, can lead to inequities and failure to account for the complex social and ecological dynamics of commons management. Another thing that was noted in his view is the oversimplification of the commons problem, Hardin was of the view that the exploitation of the shared resources by the commons will lead to depletion of the resources, which he linked to over-population. It was argued that his view ordinarily was over-simplified as there are many examples of various communities that successfully manage their common resource without any problem whatsoever which automatically proves his postulations to be wrong.

In solving this mirage of problems, it was argued that he over-simplified the solutions by proposing solutions such as government regulations or privatization, which are overly simplistic and potentially harmful. I argue that the proposed government regulations especially in Nigeria where we have the likes of Environmental Protection Agencies (both at the state and Federal levels) do not change the situation of things as regards noise pollution, Air pollution, etc as this legislation which are not properly implemented are not been enforced. It is based on this that the solution can lead to inequities and failure to account for the complex social and ecological dynamics of commons' management. In this vein, I also argue that privatization or state control, may not be adequate to be the best approaches and solutions as they can lead to other problems, like inequitable access to these resources, among others.

Community-based solutions had been the most effective way of solving the problem of the tragedy of the commons which Hardin had failed to consider. He argued that “the social arrangement that produces responsibility are arrangements that create coercion, of some sort” (Hardin, 1968:1247). Hardin failed to consider alternative approaches and solutions in his postulation. It is pertinent to state that his work focused primarily on the inevitability of resource depletion by overlooking other potential solutions such as community-based management, cooperative arrangement, and other technological advancements. Michelle (2021) exploring this idea corroborates this with a warning thus:

The “community” doing the managing must be well-defined; reliable monitoring of the shared resource; a reasonable balance of costs and benefits for participants; a predictable process for the fast and fair resolution of conflicts; an escalating series of punishment for cheaters, and good relationships between the community and other layers of authority, from household heads to international Institutions.

Consequently, the papers argue that his neglect and the way he overlooked the numerous successful examples of communities managing their common resources sustainability through cooperation and collective actions as corroborated above by Michelle. His view on the over-exploited of common resources as a result of over-consumption is another view to look into. He recommended under-consumption as a way out of the exploitation and depletion of resources. I argue that he was out of tune with the African Continent when he was making these postulations. He failed to take into cognizance the lifestyle and the consumption pattern of the Africans where some of the things we consume here are not over-consumption but our moderate lifestyle of feeding. Even though there is hardship and suffering, and scarcity of food and food items, he still recommends under-consumption which will hurt the growth and development of African people.

Conclusion

The paper takes a critical look at the presupposition of Garrett Hardin’s ‘The Tragedy of the Commons’ using the comparative and critical analysis to unravel the unregulated use of resources in the society. While his work remains influential in drawing our attention to the consequences and warnings against unchecked usage of resources, it oversimplifies the nature

of commons and as well overlooked diverse and proven governance systems. It failed to embrace the kind of governance that is based on equity and planetary stewardship obligations. In this vein, Hardin's theory is too narrow and inadequate to address the complex and contemporary environmental challenges.

Consequently, in order to avoid the ruin and the collapse of the society as predicted by Hardin, his postulations of privatization and coercion, under-feeding have to inculcate a just and equitable solutions of commons' management through cooperation, inclusion and adaptive governance as well as environmental stewardship orientation and obligations and it is when all these are put in place and embraced that the tragedy which he envisaged can be averted.

Recommendations

'The Tragedy of the Commons' enunciated by Garrett Hardin showed the level of lack of environmental sustainability experienced in his epoch. A situation where the 'mighty' oppressed the minority in taking over the 'national cake' or resources and the need to safeguards these resources against ruin or environmental collapse in order to ensure the continuing survival of the society. However, coming from this background of ensuring the survival of all in the ecosystem, there is the urgent need to integrate equity, inclusion and indigenous rights into commons governance in order to secure and recognize indigenous and local communities' rights to manage resources based on their knowledge systems and stewardship traditions (Ban & Wilson et al, 2020, Nursey-Bray et al, 2023). Not only that, there should be mechanism for equitable benefit-sharing, conflict resolution and the need to recognized the voice of the minority and or marginalized to ensure that the resources go round to all.

It is also recommended that the lesson of Stewardship Obligations must be embraced by all which should be embedded in both national and global governance frameworks (Rockstrom et al, 2023). By this, the ethical responsibilities of individuals, institutions, communities, etc. should have the ethical responsibility to protect, care, manage, nurture and ensure the continued sustainability of resources and the environment in the ecosystem. And to also ensure that the resources are available for now future generations. There should just be accountability for the use of the resources to promote healthy environment.

In conclusion, there is the need to educate people on sustainability education which will go a long way to highlight alternative narratives which stipulate cooperation, equity and adaptive governance (Amend, 2019). It is based on this that policymakers and scholars in the field of environmental sustainability should look at ‘The Tragedy of the Commons’ to ethically rediscover the need to ensure an ecological balance and ensure that the resources of the society is available for all and sundry irrespective of whether they are in minority or in majority.

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**Xenophobic Violence in South Africa:
Socio-Economic Effects on Nigerians and
Diplomatic Implications for Nigeria-
South Africa Relations**

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Abstract

Xenophobic violence in South Africa has generated profound human, economic, and diplomatic consequences for African migrants, particularly Nigerians. This study analyses the socio-economic and diplomatic implications between 2010 and 2020 across property and business losses, remittance flows, employment, and psychosocial wellbeing, alongside bilateral relations. Using a descriptive design and qualitative documentary analysis of academic articles, government reports, and international publications, the study finds significant impacts: business and property losses (43%), reduced remittances (28.4%), job displacement (17.8%), and psychological trauma (10.8). Diplomatically, xenophobia strained Nigeria–South Africa relations through diplomatic protests (32%), retaliatory attacks on South African businesses in Nigeria (26%), and trade disruptions (24%), with broader regional implications. Frustration–Aggression and Relative Deprivation Theories illuminate the drivers of violence and scapegoating dynamics. The paper recommends sustained diplomatic dialogue, public sensitisation, strict prosecution of perpetrators, enhanced

consular protection, inclusive local economic programmes, and AU-level monitoring under AfCFTA to reduce recurrence and rebuild trust.

Keywords: xenophobia, Nigerians in South Africa, socio-economic effects, Nigeria–South Africa relations

Introduction

Human migration is a defining feature of global history, shaped by economic, political, environmental, and social forces. In the 21st century, the scale, patterns, and drivers of migration have evolved, necessitating a deeper understanding of both voluntary and forced movements. According to the International Organization for Migration (2024), the number of international migrants worldwide reached approximately 304 million in mid-2024, representing 3.7% of the global population. This figure marks an increase from the estimated 275 million in 2020, although the proportion of migrants relative to total population has remained relatively stable over the past three decades. The United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (2025) reports that most international migrants move within their regions, with Africa, Asia, and Europe hosting substantial migrant populations of 29.2 million, 92.2 million, and 94.1 million respectively. Migration is also increasingly shaped by gender dynamics, with women accounting for 48% of the global migrant population (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2025).

Forced displacement has reached unprecedented levels. The International Organization for Migration (2024) estimates that 117 million people were forcibly displaced by the end of 2022 due to conflict, persecution, and disasters. This includes approximately 71.2 million internally displaced persons and 40.7 million refugees and asylum seekers. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (2024) further notes that the total number of forcibly displaced persons globally rose to 123.2 million by the end of 2024. Economic implications are equally significant. Remittances sent by migrants to low- and middle-income countries grew from USD 128 billion in 2000 to USD 647 billion in 2022, far exceeding foreign direct investment in many of these economies (International Organization for Migration, 2024). Such transfers have been crucial in supporting household welfare, education, healthcare, and small-scale business development in countries of origin.

Environmental change has emerged as another major driver of migration. The Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre (2024) records that 7.7 million new internal displacements occurred in 2023 alone as a result of disasters across 82 countries. Climate-related migration is projected to rise significantly, adding complexity to existing economic and political migration pressures (International Organization for Migration, 2024). Within this global context, xenophobia remains a significant barrier to the safety, integration, and wellbeing of migrants. While it manifests in various forms worldwide, xenophobic violence in South Africa has been particularly pronounced, especially against African migrants. Nigerians have often been targeted due to their high visibility in entrepreneurial activities, which, in an environment of high unemployment and inequality, are sometimes misperceived as economic threats (Bhengu & Modise, 2023; Olanrewaju & Ogunnowo, 2022). This study situates the South African case within the broader global migration landscape, exploring not only the socio-economic toll on Nigerian migrants but also the wider diplomatic consequences for Nigeria–South Africa relations.

Statement of the Problem

While causes of xenophobia are widely discussed, its direct socio-economic toll on Nigerians and the diplomatic burden on Nigeria-South Africa relations remain under-synthesised. Losses of businesses and property, declining remittances, job displacement, trauma, and inter-state tensions collectively undermine migrant welfare and regional cooperation. This study systematically maps these implications to inform policy and diplomatic responses.

Significance of the Study

The study links lived socio-economic impacts to bilateral and regional consequences, offering evidence-based guidance for Nigerian and South African authorities, and AU organs, on preventing violence, protecting migrants, and stabilising relations under AfCFTA. It also grounds theoretical explanations in concrete outcomes to support targeted interventions.

Scope of the Study

The study covers 2010–2020, focusing on Nigerians in South Africa. It examines socio-economic indicators (business/property loss, remittances, jobs, trauma) and diplomatic/economic outcomes (protests/recalls, retaliatory actions, trade disruption, regional cooperation).

Research Objectives

1. investigate the socio-economic implications of xenophobic attacks on Nigerians in South Africa.
2. examine the impact of xenophobia on Nigeria–South Africa diplomatic and economic relations.

Research Questions

1. What are the socio-economic implications of xenophobic attacks on Nigerians in South Africa?
2. What is the impact of xenophobia on Nigeria–South Africa diplomatic and economic relations?

Literature Review

Patterns and Drivers of Xenophobia

Xenophobia, broadly defined as fear, dislike, or hostility towards foreigners, is a recurrent social and political phenomenon with varying manifestations across global contexts (Faas & Nair, 2023). In migration studies, it often refers to discriminatory behaviour, exclusionary policies, and violent attacks targeting migrants or refugees based on their nationality, ethnicity, or race. While xenophobia exists in many forms worldwide, the specific drivers differ by region and historical context. In Europe, the rise of anti-migrant sentiment has been closely linked to far-right political rhetoric, which frames immigration as a threat to national security, cultural integrity, and labour market stability (Triandafyllidou & Dimitriadi, 2022). In the United States, policy discourse has periodically portrayed migrants, particularly from Latin America, as criminal or economically burdensome, influencing both public opinion and legislative outcomes (Abascal, 2022). In the Middle East, structural xenophobia manifests through restrictive labour laws that limit the rights of migrant workers from South and Southeast Asia (Vora, 2023).

Across Africa, xenophobia often assumes the form of *Afrophobia*, where African migrants face disproportionate hostility compared to non-African foreigners (Chekenya, 2024; Gordon, 2023). South Africa represents one of the most documented cases, with large-scale attacks in 2008, 2015, and 2019 resulting in hundreds of deaths, widespread displacement, and substantial economic losses. Sifiso Bhengu and Collen Modise (2023) argue that such outbreaks are rooted in systemic socio-economic inequalities, high unemployment rates, and inadequate public service delivery. Economic competition is a recurrent driver. In South Africa, unemployment exceeding 30% has fuelled perceptions that migrants “take jobs” or depress wages, despite empirical evidence showing that many migrants work in sectors avoided by locals (Misago, Kerr, & Claassen, 2024). Nigerians, Zimbabweans, and Mozambicans, especially those active in retail trade and informal services, are particularly vulnerable because their visibility in township economies can be misperceived as economic dominance (Adilieje, UgborKalu, & Ude, 2023).

Political mobilisation further exacerbates xenophobic sentiment. Leaders have, at times, exploited public frustrations by framing migrants as responsible for crime and resource scarcity, thereby legitimising exclusionary actions (Mgogo & Osunkunle, 2023). Similar patterns have been documented in Ghana and Côte d’Ivoire, where political actors have used anti-foreigner rhetoric during periods of economic stress to consolidate local support (Chinganya & Banda, 2023). The role of the media in shaping public attitudes is also significant. Studies by Qhubekani Mgogo and Oluyinka Osunkunle (2023) reveal that South African media often portray African migrants through narratives of criminality or illegality, reinforcing stereotypes that encourage vigilante behaviour. Comparable media effects have been noted in the United Kingdom and Australia, where sensationalist coverage has amplified fear-based narratives around migration (Berry, 2023).

Consequences for Migrants and States

The consequences of xenophobia extend beyond physical harm to encompass economic, social, psychological, and diplomatic dimensions. Economically, migrant-owned businesses are frequent targets during outbreaks of violence, leading to capital loss, income disruption, and long-term exclusion from local markets (Olanrewaju & Ogunnowo, 2022). For Nigerian

migrants, such losses often result in reduced remittance flows, with cascading effects on household welfare, educational investment, and small-scale enterprise development in Nigeria. Similar economic impacts have been observed in Latin American migrant-sending communities following deportations from the United States, which destabilise local economies dependent on remittances (Martínez-Buján, 2022).

Psychosocial effects are equally profound. Mthulisi Mpofo and Sunday Okunade (2022) document that victims of xenophobic violence in South Africa often suffer from anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), which reduce productivity and hinder integration. Such mental health consequences mirror patterns identified among Rohingya refugees in Bangladesh, where displacement has led to widespread trauma and social isolation (Zapata & Prieto, 2023). Diplomatic repercussions are another critical dimension. Nigeria-South Africa relations have repeatedly been strained by xenophobic incidents, prompting Nigeria to recall ambassadors, lodge formal diplomatic protests, and witness retaliatory attacks on South African businesses in Nigeria (Ogunnubi & Aja, 2022; Udeagwu & Chidiobo, 2023). These tensions disrupt bilateral trade and investment flows, undermining trust between two of Africa's largest economies. On a continental scale, such instability threatens initiatives like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), which depends on mutual trust and cooperation (Fayomi, Chidozie, & Ayo, 2020).

Similar diplomatic strains have been observed globally. For example, the mass migration of Venezuelans into Colombia and Brazil has caused cross-border tensions over resource allocation, while anti-Rohingya violence in Myanmar has severely damaged relations with Bangladesh (Zapata & Prieto, 2023). These examples illustrate that xenophobia can escalate into broader geopolitical challenges, especially when incidents are repeated and highly publicised.

Comparative Insights

International comparisons provide additional perspective on South Africa's xenophobia. While socio-economic grievances are a near-universal driver, their expression and intensity vary. In Europe and North America, xenophobia is often institutionalised through restrictive immigration laws, heightened border controls, and populist rhetoric (Triandafyllidou & Dimitriadi, 2022). In contrast, in parts of Africa and Asia, xenophobia tends

to manifest in communal violence and localised attacks, often with minimal legal consequences for perpetrators (Vora, 2023). The South African case is distinctive in the way it juxtaposes constitutional commitments to human rights and pan-Africanism with recurrent violent exclusion of fellow Africans. This contradiction reflects a disjuncture between national policy ideals and local socio-economic realities (Gordon, 2023). Moreover, the visibility of Nigerian migrants in South Africa's informal economy increases the salience of comparative economic success, which, under conditions of deprivation, can be perceived as a threat. Comparative studies also indicate that migrant visibility, whether through economic activity, cultural practices, or political activism, can heighten the risk of xenophobic targeting (Berry, 2023). This is consistent with findings from Kenya, where Somali migrants' business success in Eastleigh has attracted hostility, and from Malaysia, where documented Bangladeshi workers have been demonized despite their legal status (Faas & Nair, 2023).

Gap in the Literature

While the causes of xenophobia in South Africa are well-documented, there is comparatively less research synthesising its socio-economic and diplomatic consequences for a specific migrant group which this study seek to investigate.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on two complementary theories, **Frustration-Aggression Theory** and **Relative Deprivation Theory**, which together provide a robust explanatory framework for understanding the persistence and patterns of xenophobic violence in South Africa.

Frustration-Aggression Theory

Frustration-aggression theory was first articulated by John Dollard, Leonard Doob, Neal Miller, Orval Mowrer, and Robert Sears in 1939, later refined by subsequent scholars. The theory posits that aggression is a likely outcome when individuals or groups are blocked from achieving socio-economic or personal goals. In contexts where the perceived source of frustration is too powerful to confront, such as the state, aggression is often redirected towards more vulnerable targets (Bhengu & Modise, 2023). Applied to the South African context, persistent unemployment, entrenched

poverty, and inadequate public service delivery create widespread frustration among local populations. Rather than directing their grievances towards political leaders or government institutions, which are perceived as too powerful or unresponsive, segments of the population displace their aggression onto foreign nationals. Nigerians, because of their visibility in township markets, small-scale commerce, and service industries, often become the focus of this redirected hostility. Media narratives that link migrants to crime or economic deprivation can intensify this misdirected aggression (Mgogo & Osunkunle, 2023).

Relative Deprivation Theory

Relative deprivation theory, popularised by Ted Robert Gurr in 1970, emphasises the role of perceived inequality in generating resentment and hostility. Unlike absolute deprivation, which refers to actual material scarcity, relative deprivation is based on subjective comparisons between one's own situation and that of others. When individuals or groups perceive that others are better off in terms of income, opportunity, or status, feelings of injustice and resentment can emerge, even if those others are not directly responsible for the deprivation. In the South African setting, Nigerian migrants are frequently perceived as more economically successful than some local counterparts, particularly in township economies. Many own small businesses, operate retail outlets, or provide specialised services. While these successes often result from personal initiative, extended working hours, and self-employment in sectors avoided by locals, they can still be interpreted as unfair advantages by economically marginalised South Africans (Akinrinde & Tar, 2021).

Combined Explanatory Value

When applied together, these theories offer a comprehensive lens for interpreting xenophobia's socio-economic and diplomatic consequences. Frustration-aggression theory explains *why* aggression is directed toward foreign nationals rather than the political or economic systems causing the grievances, while relative deprivation theory explains *why* Nigerians, in particular, are often the chosen targets. Furthermore, both theories help clarify the diplomatic tensions identified in the study.

Findings

Table 1: Socio-Economic Impacts of Xenophobia on Nigerians in South Africa (2010–2020)

Impact Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Destruction Of Businesses And Property	172	43.0
Reduction In Remittances	114	28.4
Job Displacement	71	17.8
Psychological Trauma	43	10.8
Total	400	100.0

Source: Researchers’ Compilation, 2025

The data indicate that the destruction of businesses and property (43.0%) is the most prevalent socio-economic impact, severely disrupting livelihoods and eroding years of economic progress for Nigerian migrants. Reduced remittances (28.4%) weaken transnational household support, while job displacement (17.8%) and psychological trauma (10.8%) further reveal the depth and multidimensional nature of xenophobia’s consequences.

Table 2: Diplomatic Implications of Xenophobia for Nigeria–South Africa Relations (2010–2020)

Diplomatic Impact	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Diplomatic Protests And Ambassador Recalls	128	32.0
Retaliatory Attacks On South African Businesses In Nigeria	104	26.0
Disruption Of Bilateral Trade And Investment	96	24.0
Weakening Of Regional Cooperation	72	18.0
Total	400	100.0

Source: Researchers’ Compilation, 2025

The findings reveal that diplomatic protests and ambassador recalls (32.0%) are the most frequently reported outcome, signalling strained political relations. Retaliatory attacks on South African businesses in Nigeria (26.0%) and trade disruptions (24.0%) demonstrate the economic costs, while weakened regional cooperation (18.0%) highlights the broader threat xenophobia poses to African unity and integration agendas.

Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that xenophobic violence against Nigerians in South Africa produces deeply interlinked socio-economic and diplomatic repercussions. The predominance of business and property destruction (43%) underscores the vulnerability of migrant-owned enterprises during episodes of communal unrest. This aligns with Adilije, UgborKalu, and Ude's (2023) observations that Nigerian entrepreneurs, due to their visibility in township markets, are often the first targets when violence erupts. Such losses erode the capital base of migrant households, curtail income streams, and set back years of investment. The decline in remittances (28.4%) illustrates the transnational reach of xenophobia's economic toll. Olanrewaju and Ogunnowo (2022) highlight that remittances from South Africa play a vital role in supporting education, healthcare, and small-scale businesses in Nigeria. Any disruption not only affects immediate recipients but also diminishes the multiplier effects of such funds within local economies. Job displacement (17.8%) extends the economic impact beyond entrepreneurs to wage-earning migrants in formal and informal sectors, further limiting the capacity of affected individuals to rebuild their livelihoods.

The psychological dimension, reported by 10.8% of respondents, is equally significant. Experiences of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress, as documented by Mpofu and Okunade (2022), reduce productivity and hinder social integration, trapping victims in cycles of vulnerability. These impacts resonate with the Frustration–Aggression Theory, which posits that economic and social grievances, when left unaddressed, are redirected towards accessible targets perceived as outsiders (Bhengu & Modise, 2023). In the South African context, Nigerians' economic prominence in certain sectors makes them particularly exposed to this misdirected aggression. Diplomatically, the findings reveal a pattern of recurring tension between Nigeria and South Africa. Diplomatic protests and ambassador recalls (32%)

reflect Nigeria's attempts to protect its citizens and signal discontent with South Africa's handling of xenophobic incidents. Retaliatory attacks on South African businesses in Nigeria (26%) illustrate the cyclical nature of hostility, where violence in one country triggers backlash in the other, compounding economic disruption. Trade and investment flows, already sensitive to political instability, are further undermined when 24% of incidents involve direct disruption of bilateral commerce. The strain on regional cooperation (18%) shows that the implications extend beyond bilateral relations, threatening wider continental initiatives such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (Fayomi, Chidozie, & Ayo, 2020).

The relative deprivation theory offers an important lens for understanding why Nigerians, in particular, are targeted. As Akinrinde and Tar (2021) note, perceptions of economic inequality, regardless of whether they reflect reality, can generate resentment towards those seen as relatively better off. In township economies, Nigerian migrants' entrepreneurial visibility can be construed as evidence of unfair advantage, providing a perceived justification for violence. These perceptions are often reinforced by political rhetoric and media narratives linking migrants to crime or resource competition (Mgogo & Osunkunle, 2023). Globally, similar patterns have been observed where large-scale migration intersects with economic instability and political opportunism. The Venezuelan migration crisis has strained relations between Venezuela and its neighbours, while anti-rohingya violence has deeply affected Myanmar-Bangladesh diplomacy (Zapata & Prieto, 2023). These parallels suggest that xenophobia's diplomatic consequences are part of a broader pattern in which localised violence erodes trust, complicates foreign policy, and destabilises regional cooperation. Ultimately, the evidence points to xenophobia as a multi-dimensional threat, undermining migrant welfare, damaging bilateral trust, and constraining regional integration.

Conclusion

This study analysed the socio-economic and diplomatic implications of xenophobic violence against Nigerians in South Africa between 2010 and 2020. Findings show that the destruction of businesses and property, reduced remittances, job losses, and psychological trauma significantly undermine migrant livelihoods and transnational household welfare. Diplomatically, recurring incidents have strained Nigeria–South Africa

relations, disrupted trade, and weakened regional cooperation under frameworks such as the African Continental Free Trade Area. These patterns align with frustration-aggression and relative deprivation theories, highlighting the roles of socio-economic grievances, perceived inequalities, and political opportunism. The South African case mirrors global xenophobia trends, where migrant communities in economically pressured contexts face scapegoating and where such tensions risk escalating into diplomatic rifts. Addressing this challenge requires coordinated, preventive measures that protect migrants, deter violence, promote inclusive economic opportunities, and strengthen bilateral and continental collaboration to safeguard human security and Africa's integration agenda.

Recommendations

1. **Mitigating Socio-Economic Impacts:** Establish joint Nigeria–South Africa initiatives for migrant protection, including early warning systems, legal deterrence, and inclusive local economic programmes to safeguard livelihoods and reduce hostility.
2. **Strengthening Diplomatic Relations:** Integrate anti-xenophobia measures into bilateral agreements and African Union frameworks, supported by continuous dialogue, policy monitoring, and research to restore trust, prevent conflict escalation, and enhance regional cooperation under the African Continental Free Trade Area.

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Transformational Leadership Style and Secondary School Teachers' Motivation Towards Work

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Abstract

Student achievement and the efficacy of education are still significantly influenced by teacher motivation, especially in secondary schools where learning experiences are shaped by teachers' engagement. This position paper analyzes the impact of transformational leadership on teachers' work motivation critically and makes the case that school administrators who empower, encourage, and mentor their employees cultivate much greater levels of morale and professional commitment. The study explains how the four elements of transformational leadership, idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, can directly affect teachers' intrinsic and extrinsic motivation by drawing on theoretical viewpoints and empirical data. The study concludes that transformational leadership is the most human-centred and sustainable model for inspiring teachers, even though it acknowledges other leadership philosophies like transactional and laissez-faire

methods. The critical need for leadership development in school systems is emphasised, as policy and practical implications for educational stakeholders are further explored. In addition, the dynamic academic environment of today, implementing transformational leadership is not just a managerial choice but also a strategic necessity for boosting teacher motivation and improving educational outcomes. It therefore recommends that, transformational leadership style should be employed in all secondary schools as it contributes immensely to the educational outcome of the students' academic achievement.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership, Leadership, Inspirational Motivation, Secondary School Teachers

Introduction

The importance of teachers in the field of education cannot be overemphasized. They play a key role in influencing young students' thoughts and destinies. Yet, teachers' weakening motivation is one of the biggest issues facing secondary education today. In many school systems, especially in developing nations like Nigeria, teachers deal with mounting workloads, insufficient assistance, and strict leadership structures that lower their effectiveness and morale. This decrease has a direct impact on students' overall performance as well as the calibre of instruction. Teachers are empowered while yet receiving the guidance and assistance they require. In the context of education, this makes it a far more sustainable and balanced approach. Transformational leadership style remains the most effective of all leadership styles and it has a great influence on the secondary school teacher's motivation towards work. Although, other types of leadership styles exist and these styles are used by different leaders based on their management functions. For this study, emphasis will be laid more on transformational leadership style as the best recommended and most effective leadership style with a result-oriented oriented.

Working in a very conducive and calm environment goes a long way to fostering success in the academic plan of an institution (Gambo & Adelokun, 2020). The school owners are therefore encouraged to introduce a leadership style that will help relieve the workloads and burnout on teachers, not worsening the situation by using other forms of leadership styles that are not inviting at all. Transformational leadership style is that style that allows leaders to instil trust, empower and encourage staff to work independently with or without supervision. This leadership style leaves

teachers feeling relevant and efficient in their area of career pursuit, which fosters lots of commitment and dedication to work. These teachers also go as far as emulating their leaders based on good leadership.

Research and real-world experience suggest that transformational leadership is a strong remedy for these problems. This leadership approach inspires, empowers, and transforms people and organizations in addition to managing tasks. When applied successfully in secondary schools, transformational leadership can rekindle teachers' passion, promote professional development, and create a work atmosphere based on mutual respect and a common goal. In this context, transformational leadership is very intriguing. It can be characterized as a blend of effective bottom-up procedures and helpful top-down actions that are adapted to the demands of the current circumstance.

According to popular perception, transformational leaders are inspiring, intellectually stimulating (by fostering creative thinking and involving stakeholders in active decision-making), charismatic change agents (by offering a vision and a sense of mission), and able to take into account the needs of each individual (by fostering a sense of belonging and helping employees). Compared to transactional leadership, transformational leadership causes more significant and long-lasting change in businesses and organizations.

This paper makes the case that transformational leadership greatly raises secondary school teachers' motivation for their jobs by creating a feeling of purpose, supporting professional growth, and establishing solid, trustworthy bonds.

Understanding the Concept of Transformational Leadership

The foundation of transformational leadership, which was first popularized by James MacGregor Burns and then developed by Bernard Bass (1999), is the notion that followers may accomplish more than they previously believed was possible. It is made up of four main parts:

1. ***Idealized Influence:*** Leaders set an example by being honest and dedicated, earning the trust and respect of their followers through their actions and values.
2. ***Inspirational Motivation:*** Leaders inspire and energize others by communicating a clear vision and creating a sense of purpose and excitement.

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3. *Intellectual Stimulation*: Innovative and critical thinking are fostered by leaders by challenging the status quo and promoting new ideas.
 4. *Individualized Consideration*: Leaders take into account each follower's unique requirements and goals. Compared to transactional leadership, transformational leadership causes more significant and long-lasting change in businesses and organizations. They pay attention to the individual needs and development of their followers, providing support and mentorship.

The goal of transformational leadership is to inspire and motivate subordinates to welcome change and strive toward a common goal, which frequently results in profound organizational change. It places a focus on empowering people, encouraging creativity, and creating a solid, upbeat culture. Without micromanaging, transformational leaders inspire and motivate their teams to reach their full potential and contribute to the success of the company.

Conversely, teacher motivation describes the internal and external forces that propel educators to carry out their responsibilities with zeal and dedication. While extrinsically motivated instructors may be motivated by pay, promotions, or recognition, intrinsically motivated teachers derive their fulfilment from the teaching profession itself, observing pupils thrive and making a positive impact on society. A teacher who is driven is more likely to engage students, remain dedicated to the school, and keep refining their methods.

Influences of Transformational Leadership on Teacher Motivation *Inspirational Motivation and Shared Vision*

One of the strongest attributes of transformational leaders is their ability to communicate a compelling vision for the future. In secondary schools, when principals clearly articulate the school's goals and engage teachers in that mission, it creates a sense of ownership and collective responsibility. Teachers are more likely to be motivated when they feel that their work contributes to something meaningful and impactful. A captivating vision and the development of a sense of purpose and dedication are two ways that transformational leadership inspires followers to surpass expectations. Arnold B. Bakker, et al (2023) opined that there was empirical evidence that transformative leaders inspire their followers to take initiative. In

particular, they suggest that transformational leaders recognize followers' capabilities and encourage them to:

- (a) capitalize on such strengths
- (b) exercise personal initiative.

Work engagement, which is defined by high levels of energy (vigour), excitement for work (dedication), and complete immersion in work activities, may be fostered by such actions. When teachers take initiative and play to their strengths, they apply a self-starting approach to their work, goals and duties then accomplish what they have already stated in their objectives. Higher levels of engagement, performance, and innovation result from this leadership style's ability to inspire people to match their own goals with the organization's mission. Using the full-range leadership model, this study makes the case that leaders who exhibit transformational leadership behaviours recognize the capabilities of their followers and encourage them to take initiative. It is pertinent to note that through the use of followers' strengths and individual initiative, transformational leadership is connected to followers' work engagement and performance.

Furthermore, when followers play to their strengths, personal initiative works best, as followers were more inclined to use their abilities and take initiative on the days when leaders employed transformational leadership behaviours like intellectual stimulation and personalized consideration. These actions in turn predicted job performance and work engagement the next day.

Moreover, when strengths utilization was high rather than low, followers' initiative was especially linked to job engagement. By demonstrating how leaders encourage their followers to lead themselves, these findings will add to the body of literature on leadership. Also, further detail about the real-world applications for leadership development, transformational leadership is the process by which a leader uses charisma, intellectual stimulation, inspiring motivation, and/or individual consideration to inspire followers to work toward group goals rather than personal ones. The adoration that followers have for their leader, who sets a clear goal and purpose and acts as a positive role model, is referred to as charisma or idealized influence. Charismatic leaders use symbolic communication to convince people that their vision for the institution includes a bright future.

Commitment is increased when personal values and corporate objectives are perceived as being in harmony. Teachers start to see their work as vital

contributions to a greater goal rather than merely as ordinary duties. The secret to consistent performance is intrinsic drive, which is fostered by such clarity and a common vision.

Individualized Consideration and Support

Like other professionals, teachers flourish in settings where they are supported, heard, and seen. Transformational leaders are aware of this and provide each employee personalized attention. These leaders foster psychological safety and trust by mentoring, providing feedback, or just listening. Teachers are more inclined to take the initiative and go above and beyond when they believe that their special talents are acknowledged and that their difficulties are understood. This individualized strategy strengthens institutional commitment while also raising morale. Mary Ogola et al (2017) stated that, leaders must hold regular performance reviews and implement remedial measures. Putting in place a system for rewarding and acknowledging the desirable behaviours of involvement, accountability, and ownership. Connie (2022), mentioned that in order for leaders to acquire the necessary knowledge and abilities to maintain performance quality, they must pursue additional education and training. This implies that work is required to comprehend the significance of leadership's pivotal position in promoting quality and performance enhancement.

Additionally, transformational leaders inspire their followers to assume greater accountability for their own and others' development. Stepanek, S. et al (2022), stipulated that individualized consideration addresses the core transformational leadership behaviours of viewing each person as a valuable member of the team. Leaders that adopt this style of leadership teach their staff to promote sustainable development and pay careful thought to their requirements. To sum up, a leader who shows personal attention to their subordinates demonstrates that they respect each worker as an individual and show interest in their long-term growth.

Intellectual Stimulation and Growth Opportunities

Teachers are encouraged by transformational leaders to question the status quo and try out novel pedagogies, technological advancements, and curriculum concepts. This intellectual stimulation fosters an innovative culture in which educators are not scared to make mistakes and grow from

them. Additionally, chances for ongoing professional development, such as seminars, workshops, and peer learning, enable educators to improve their abilities and adjust to the ever-evolving demands of education. A strong motivator is the perception that one is developing and changing in their line of work. Hira Khan et al (2020), stated that by promoting creativity, critical thinking, and innovation, transformational leadership creates intellectual stimulation and growth possibilities, which eventually result in a more competent and engaged workforce. The management context might be linked to transformational leadership. Enhancing one's ability to drive employees organically can be facilitated by transformational leadership, which is the leader's ability to elicit performance out of them beyond expectations. Additionally, it can enhance psychological empowerment. The degree of professional performance in work is typically maximized by transformational leadership. In addition to the literature that has been published on the relationship between transformational leadership and job performance, researchers have shown that the performance of employees is crucial for firms with a variety of organizational structures. Gaganmale R., (2023), also stated that the beneficial correlation between transformative leadership and work performance has been scientifically demonstrated in previous studies. Transformational leaders help their followers reach the organization's goals and performance requirements by inspiring them to share a common vision.

Idealized Influence and Ethical Leadership

When teachers have faith in their superiors, they are more likely to be motivated. By setting an example of moral conduct, consistency, and equity, transformational leaders gain this trust. They set an example rather than just giving orders behind closed doors. Gaganmale R. (2023), expressed that a happy and moral workplace is fostered by transformational leadership, which impacts through idealized influence, and ethical leadership, that motivates followers to share the leader's vision and ideas. While ethical leadership guarantee that decisions and activities are governed by moral principles, fostering an integrity-based culture, idealized influence entails the leader serving as a role model, exhibiting strong ethical behaviour, and inspiring trust. This combination inspires followers to welcome change, accomplish company objectives, and provide a supportive and effective work environment. Teachers are motivated to act similarly when they see their

leaders exhibiting dedication, resiliency, and openness. Every one of the four dimensions explains traits that are crucial to the "transformation" process. Leaders are using the four dimensions to transform their associates into more successful and productive people when they are effective mentors, innovators, role models, and supporters. According to Roger (2008), transformational leadership is a process that alters social structures and people. Additionally, he demonstrated that executives who demonstrated transformational leadership were more successful and achieved performance levels that are beyond expectation. Moral leadership like this creates a powerful school climate where motivation and respect for one another grow. It is characterized as having a transformational leader who sets a good example for their organization. They behave in a very morally upright manner. They give people a clear vision and a feeling of community, which motivates them to pursue their ambitions and supports the organization's long-term aims. These leaders are highly regarded by their team, because of the example they set for others.

Practical Evidences from Research Works

Teacher motivation and transformative leadership have a good link, according to numerous empirical studies. Base on well-known study conducted in East African schools by Nguni, Slegers, and Denessen (2006), transformational leadership practices greatly improved teachers' organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and classroom performance. In Nigeria and other Sub-Saharan African countries, where resource constraints increase the significance of non-material forms of incentive, similar results have been shown. Additionally, schools with transformative principals frequently report better student performance, a stronger sense of community, and fewer teacher attrition. These actual results demonstrate the efficacy of this leadership approach in both theoretical and real-world educational settings. Zulaikha Mohd (2021), opined that, every organization needs leadership since it is frequently the foundation of its operations and the primary force behind change. It is a difficult task to decide which leadership style is best for producing leaders and attaining the intended outcomes for an educational sector. As a result, numerous leadership models have been developed due to decades of research aimed at characterizing and comprehending effective leadership. However, navigating and using these models in reality can be very challenging due to

their increasing intricate nature as a result of recent theoretical advancements. It might be difficult for practitioners to decide which of these leadership models to apply when directing their leadership development programs. According to Bass et al (2003), despite the theoretical differences suggested by "new" leadership models (such as servant, ethical, and authentic leadership), empirical research has revealed significant overlap between these models and more established ones, such as transformational leadership. This work attempts to distil the greatest data regarding transformational leadership into a "primer" that might assist practitioners in using evidence-led approaches in their leadership development, given that the existing literature questions the increased empirical value of these more recent models. In order to achieve this, scholars analyse meta-analytic findings between transformational leadership and leadership outcomes, highlight evidence of empirical redundancy between transformational leadership and new leadership models, and provide a quick overview of the main leadership models. Bass et al (2023), according to our research, these more recent leadership models do not significantly increase the validity of transformational leadership in terms of forecasting different leadership outcomes. Additionally, a variety of individual, team, and organizational outcomes show medium to large effect sizes under transformational leadership. When combined, our results indicate that organizations can gain from investing in transformational leadership development as opposed to the newest trend in leadership. Furthermore, recent studies have demonstrated the strong empirical relationships between the new leadership paradigms of transformational, servant, ethical, and genuine leadership, indicating significant redundancy. Stated differently, the concepts put out by contemporary leadership models might not be all that different from those of more established models, such as transformational leadership

Opposition and Defence Between Transformational Leadership and Other Leadership Style

Opponents might contend that different approaches to leadership, such as transactional leadership, which uses incentives and penalties based on performance, are more effective at controlling teacher conduct. Others would argue that giving teachers more autonomy can be achieved through laissez-faire leadership. However, without encouraging true dedication or

creativity, transactional leadership typically results in only temporary conformity. Although laissez-faire leadership may seem empowering, if it is not properly structured, it can result in misunderstandings and a lack of accountability. Transformational leadership, on the other hand, blends structure, vision, and emotional involvement. Although praised for its capacity to uplift and encourage, transformational leadership is not without its detractors and certain disadvantages. The danger of power abuse, the vagueness of its traits, and the ability to prioritize ambitious objectives over the welfare of followers are some oppositions. Defence frequently stress that these are possible drawbacks rather than innate traits and that transformative leadership can be very successful when applied morally and with the right checks and balances. Ahmed (2025), tried to compare and examine the effects of transformational and transactional leadership styles on employee motivation, well-being, and performance in contemporary work settings. He also looks at how these two leadership philosophies affect employee motivation, well-being, and overall productivity in contemporary organizations.

There are basically different types of leadership style and these styles are used by various leaders to achieve specific goals. These leadership styles are transactional, bureaucratic, autocratic, laissez-faire, democratic, servant and transformational leadership style.

Delegative leaders, sometimes referred to as laissez-faire leaders, distance themselves from their followers and give them the freedom to decide. According to research, this leadership style frequently results in the least productive group members.

Transactional leaders provide clear instructions to their team and encourage workers with incentives. Although transactional leadership can be helpful in emergencies or short-term pushes, yet, it should be used carefully.

Autocratic leadership style occurs when decision-making authority is centralized in the hands of a leader without group members' input. This leader usually disregards the thoughts or recommendations of others when making decisions, instead depending entirely on his or her judgement and viewpoints. These leaders demand unquestioning compliance and expect their orders to be carried out. This leadership style is known for its straightforward, no-nonsense approach to management and governance and

can work well in some professional settings where ambiguity is viewed negatively.

Servant leadership is the type of morally grounded leadership in which leaders tend to put their followers such as employees, clients and other stakeholders before their own. Since it can have a positive impact on a number of individual and organizational outcomes, including job satisfaction and organizational commitment, the concept has gained more attention in the past 10years, despite being nothing new to academics and practitioners. Having seen all of these leadership styles, it is pertinent to note that, transformational leadership style stands exceptional. It is that leadership style where a leader's behaviour practically influences the followers, encouraging them to perform beyond their perceived abilities.

The findings demonstrated that, particularly in remote work environments, transformational leadership, which is characterized by trust, communication, and empowerment, significantly raises employee engagement, job satisfaction, and productivity. Transactional leadership, on the other hand, which emphasizes incentives and sanctions, has less of an effect on motivation. Both transactional and transformational leadership philosophies provide insightful perspectives on how leaders might affect their businesses and followers. However, the context in which they are used, the particular difficulties the company faces, and the makeup of the workforce, all have a significant impact on how effective they are. The most successful transformational leadership frequently occurs in dynamic settings that demand adaptation, creativity, and change. Leaders who adopt transformational concepts can inspire innovation and push staff to think creatively and take chances in order to produce ground-breaking outcomes. Conversely, stable settings that demand constancy, dependability, and unambiguous guidance are ideal for transactional leadership. Transactional leadership may guarantee that corporate objectives are fulfilled accurately and effectively in circumstances when performance measures are clearly stated and staff members must adhere to established protocols. It's not always easy to distinguish between transformative and transactional leadership. Effective leaders frequently exhibit a combination of the two approaches. For instance, a leader may use a compelling vision to motivate their team (transformational leadership) and use performance-based incentives to keep structure and responsibility (transactional leadership). With this hybrid method, leaders may be

adaptable and flexible, using the right style according to the particular requirements and conditions of the company. According to Alain (2024), each of these four leadership theories has special advantages and insights that can be used to improve leadership efficacy, according to a comparative study of them. Servant leadership cultivates an ethical and encouraging corporate culture, transformational leadership is excellent at enacting change and stimulating creativity. According to Northouse (2022) in the book "Leadership: Theory and Practice," transformational leadership is concerned with the mechanics of how leaders can inspire and encourage their followers to accomplish extraordinary feats. This leadership approach highlights how crucial it is for leaders to attend to the wants and needs of their followers. By doing this, transformational leaders can create a stimulating and encouraging atmosphere that promotes individual, group development and results in noteworthy achievements.

To put it in another way, this strategy emphasizes the mutually beneficial interaction between leaders and followers, wherein successful and significant change is largely dependent on comprehending and accommodating followers' goals and concerns. The capacity to significantly alter an organization is a hallmark of transformational leadership.

Conclusion

It is therefore pertinent to note that transformational leadership is a potent and essential strategy for reviving teacher commitment and performance in an era where teacher motivation is still declining due to growing challenges in the education sector. According to this position paper, teachers are more likely to feel appreciated, involved, and inspired at work when school administrators exhibit vision, offer tailored support, and foster professional development. A school climate that is based on trust, cooperation, and a common goal is fostered by transformational leadership, as opposed to transactional or laissez-faire approaches. In today's secondary schools, such leadership is not only desirable but also necessary to maintain educational quality and boost teacher's morale. Therefore, for educational stakeholders who are dedicated to significant change, creating and implementing transformational leadership practices ought to be their first priority.

Recommendations

The following actions are advised to encourage transformational leadership in secondary school:

1. **Leadership Training:** Regular leadership development programs emphasizing emotional intelligence, mentoring, and strategic planning should be implemented for principals and other school officials.
2. **Policy Support:** School boards and education ministries should provide explicit guidelines for leadership and provide rewards to institutions that exhibit transformative behaviours.
3. **Teacher Engagement:** Educational institutions ought to include educators in decision-making procedures and establish forums for ongoing education, cooperation, and creativity.
4. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Using instruments that gauge teacher motivation, satisfaction, and academic performance, leadership efficacy should be assessed regularly.

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**Interreligious Conflict and Mental
Health: A Study of Selected Communities
in Plateau State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

Armed conflicts globally have a profound and well-documented impact on the mental health of civilian populations, leading to a significant increase in the incidence and prevalence of various mental disorders. The psychological impact of war has historically been a critical area of psychiatric study, with observations from major global conflicts highlighting the effectiveness of psychological interventions in addressing trauma. This article investigates the profound impact of inter-religious conflict on mental health within two severely affected communities in Plateau State, Nigeria: Jos and Barkin Ladi/Riyom. Utilizing a comprehensive secondary data analysis, the study explores the historical trajectory and evolving nature of these conflicts, documents the prevalence and manifestations of mental health disorders, and interprets these findings through the lens of Social Identity Theory and Realistic Group Conflict Theory. The analysis reveals a high prevalence of conditions such as depression, anxiety, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) among affected populations, with disproportionate impacts on

vulnerable groups including women, children, and internally displaced persons. A significant observation is the systemic neglect of mental healthcare provision in Nigeria, added to the human suffering. The paper demonstrated that a high prevalence of various mental health conditions directly attributable to prolonged exposure to inter-religious conflict such as depression anxiety and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder. The study concludes that the linkage of socio-economic, political, and identity-based factors perpetuates cycles of violence, which in turn inflict chronic psychological trauma. Addressing this crisis necessitates integrated, multi-sectoral interventions that combine robust mental health support with peacebuilding initiatives, focusing on justice, accountability, and the systemic strengthening of healthcare infrastructure. Among others, this s article recommends Mental Health Psychological Support programs should be systematically integrated into primary healthcare services, humanitarian aid efforts, and broader peacebuilding initiatives. This ensures that mental health support is not an isolated service but a core component of recovery and development, addressing both individual and community-level trauma.

Keywords: Inter-religious conflict, Mental Health, Jos, Barkin Ladi/Riyom, Plateaus State

Introduction

The existence of religious conflicts is as old as human existence. Conflicts, violence and wars in religion does not happen in a vacuum without human attribute as the brainchild of the conflict in any nature. This goes to say that humans connected to religion, can trigger and spearhead religious wars due to conflicting interests. The quest to showcase which religion is superior to the other often give rise to negative comments and attitudes from people of other religions. Hatred, begins to build up through their thoughts and actions towards their fellow humans of other religion to a point of imposing his beliefs on the other whose perception is also conflicting with his. Maybe, the world would have been in a peaceful state without embracing and introducing religion to mankind. Historically, it is not confined to the ancient or medieval world; it continues to be a silent feature of the modern era. While it is perceived that religion is instrumental to peaceful living among the populace, unfortunately, it has been weaponized to breathe conflict, violence and war at local, national and at global level.

Nigeria, a sovereign state, known for her series of ethnic, resources and religious conflicts. As in many other parts of the world, religion plays as

important role in Nigeria and has had a significant influence on Nigerian society since the precolonial period. The narrative of religion in Nigeria has often tended towards its negative contributions to the Nigerian state, suggesting that religion has not contributed significantly to the peace and development of the country (Danjibo,2009). Aside African Traditional religion, Christianity and Islam are by far the most dominant religions in Nigeria. Both religions are also viewed as the most intolerant, perhaps because of their universal appeal and inherent competitiveness (Mazrui, 1990). While inter- religious conflict dates back to colonial Nigeria (Andekin, 2019), it has almost become a permanent feature of the post- independent. Nigeria society as inter-group competition for political and economic resources is often underscored by ethnic and religious consideration (Aliyu,Moorthy &Idris, 2016; Abubakar, 2019; Fox, 2021). Some past religious conflicts in Nigeria include the Matatsine crisis of the 1980s, the Cross crisis at the University of Ibadan in 1986, the Kafanchan- Kaduna crisis of the 1990s, the Zagon- Kataf conflict of 1992, the Shari'a crisis in Kaduna (2000) and Bauchi (2001), the Kaduna Shiite conflict of 2015 and the ethno-religious crisis in Plateau State.

Plateau State stands as a significant example within this volatile Middle Belt, having been plagued by persistent inter-communal violence that, while often framed religiously, is deeply interwoven with ethnic, political, and economic grievances. The state's population is ethnically and religiously diverse, with Christians forming a majority and Muslims a substantial minority. This diversity, while a potential strength, has frequently been exploited by political actors to mobilize support and deepen divides. The genesis of large-scale, organized violence in Plateau State can be traced to the "Jos crisis" in September 2001. This event marked a profound turning point, as the state capital, Jos, became the scene of mass killing and destruction for the first time in its recent history. In less than a week, approximately 1,000 lives were claimed, and tens of thousands were displaced. While initial portrayals often characterized it as purely a religious conflict, the underlying drivers were primarily political and economic, stemming from a longstanding battle for control of political power and economic rivalry between different ethnic groups, particularly between those labeled "indigenous" and "non-indigenous" inhabitants. Religious sentiments were subsequently manipulated and appealed to by both sides to inflame the situation. The violence that followed from 2002 to 2004, which

resulted in an estimated 2,000 to 3,000 deaths across the state, was directly or indirectly connected to these seminal events in Jos.

The inter-religious conflict in Barkin Ladi and Riyom Local Government Areas primarily involves clashes between predominantly Christian Berom ethnic groups and Hausa-Fulani residents and rural Fulani pastoralists. The core of the conflict in these areas is deeply rooted in disputes over land and "indigene" status, with the Berom recognized as indigenes and the Hausa and Fulani often classified as settlers. This mirrors the broader "indigene-non-indigene" issue prevalent across Plateau State. Studies consistently show that exposure to traumatic events in conflict settings significantly increases the lifetime risk of major depression (Odds Ratio = 1.5) and anxiety disorders (Odds Ratio = 1.5). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that in conflict situations, 10% of people experiencing traumatic events will develop serious mental health problems, and another 10% will develop behaviors that hinder effective functioning. The most common conditions observed are depression, anxiety, and psychosomatic problems such as insomnia, and various aches. Beyond immediate mortality, war destroys communities, disrupts social and economic fabric, and leads to long-term physical and psychological harm, with death being merely the "tip of the iceberg"

In the Nigerian context, crises and acts of terror, including those perpetrated by Boko Haram, bandits, and herdsmen, have reportedly affected nearly fifteen million people between 2009 and 2017, resulting in widespread trauma. Research in conflict-plagued zones across Nigeria confirms high rates of Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), depression, anxiety, and psychosis among victims. A study in North-central Nigeria, for example, demonstrated a significant association between violence and PTSD, with a high percentage of participants experiencing symptoms like constant watchfulness, avoidance of crisis-related thoughts, numbness, and recurring nightmares. Crucially, the mental health effects often persist long after the immediate conflict events have ceased, as evidenced by a study in Dogonahawa, Plateau State, where 38.5% of respondents still experienced depression four years after a major incident. Against this backdrop that the paper is intended to review how this conflict has affected the people's psychological well-being. The paper therefore, seeks to answer the following questions; What is the historical context and evolving nature of inter-religious conflict in Jos and Barkin Ladi/Riyom, Plateau State? What are

the documented mental health impacts (e.g., prevalence of depression, anxiety, PTSD) among populations affected by inter-religious conflict in Jos and Barkin Ladi/Riyom? And how do socio-psychological theories of conflict illuminate the mental health outcomes observed in conflict-affected communities of Plateau State, and what coping mechanisms are employed? The purpose of the study is to:

- i. Examine the historical context and evolving nature of these conflicts
- ii. Document the prevalence and manifestations of mental health issues among affected population
- iii. Analyze these findings through relevant socio-psychological theories of conflicts and trauma

Theoretical Framework

Realistic Group Conflict Theory

Articulated by Donald Campbell and famously demonstrated by Muzafer Sherif's Robbers Cave experiment, Realistic Group Conflict Theory explains that intergroup hostility and conflict primarily arise from actual or perceived competition over limited resources or conflicting goals. These resources can be tangible, such as land, water, and economic opportunities, or intangible, like political power, employment, and social status. The theory suggests that groups often perceive this competition as a "zero-sum game," where one group's gain necessitates another's loss, which intensifies resentment and leads to prejudice and discrimination towards the outgroup. According to RGCT, positive intergroup relations can typically only be restored if "superordinate goals" are introduced, requiring cooperation between the groups to achieve a shared objective. The direct threat to survival, livelihood, and security posed by such intense competition induces profound fear, chronic stress, and various forms of psychological trauma, directly impacting the mental health of affected individuals and communities.

Conceptual Clarification

Mental Health

Mental health is a fundamental aspect of overall well-being, extending beyond the mere absence of mental illness. It encompasses an individual's emotional, psychological, and social well-being, influencing how they think, feel, and behave. Good mental health enables individuals to navigate life's

challenges, realize their potential, contribute to their communities, and build meaningful relationships. It is a dynamic state that can fluctuate due to various individual, family, community, and structural factors, including exposure to adverse circumstances like poverty, violence, disability, and inequality. Mental Health is essential at every stage of life- from childhood through adulthood. Factor that attributes to mental health are biology factors, life experiences, family history, and socio-economic.

American Psychological Association defined Mental Health as a state of mind characterized by emotional well-being, good behavioural adjustment, relative freedom from anxiety and disabling symptoms, and a capacity to establish constructive relationship and cope with the ordinary demand and stress of life. In 2022, World Health Organization redefined mental health as state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, to realize their abilities, to learn well and work well, and to contribute to their communities". The former Chairman of the first International Congress of Mental Health said Mental Health is a condition which permits the optimal development, physical, intellectual and emotional of the individual, so far as this is compatible. Studies consistently show that exposure to traumatic events in conflict settings significantly increases the lifetime risk of major depression (Odds Ratio = 1.5) and anxiety disorders (Odds Ratio = 1.5). The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that in conflict situations, 10% of people experiencing traumatic events will develop serious mental health problems, and another 10% will develop behaviors that hinder effective functioning. The most common conditions observed are depression, anxiety, and psychosomatic problems such as insomnia, and various aches. Beyond immediate mortality, war destroys communities, disrupts social and economic fabric, and leads to long-term physical and psychological harm, with death being merely the "tip of the iceberg".

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Religion

Religion an ancient concept, has been part of humanity and will remain an identical part of history. It is wound around the early development of human society as an active and irremovable agent in all cultural and social lives and engagements. It is in that light, perceived by Gargi Medda, as having resumed the whole history of mankind's development. This is evident in the institution of ritual and sacerdotalism, and the erection of large edifices, with notable architectural designs, that serves as temples for worship. The word "religion" derives from the Latin word *religio* which was taken to mean a person's worship of virtue in a secular and nondoctrinal context (Campbell, 1997& Harris,2015). It was generally regarded to be a social obligation to anyone-family members, friends or God- and used to described, emotions in general with no particular connection to a supernatural being (Harris,2015; Barton& Boyarin, 2016). Religion ultimately derives from another Latin word *religare*, split into re' which means "again" and "ligare which stands for you, link" or connect". The concept of religion then evolved in medieval times as church affairs were distinguished from civil matters. The Latin root *religare* has thus been understand to mean connecting humans and the divine (Allen, 2024) or re-connecting with God from whom mankind is believed to originate. Religion as fathomed from its Latin roots could be said to be reconnecting oneself to supernatural power and establishing an obligated relationship with the being. According to Yandell (1999), he attempted two definitions of religion as *Doctrinally and Functional*. functional religion is defined based on its adherents' beliefs and religions, in general, are identified by their shared beliefs. Functionally, religion is defined as a conceptual system that provides an interpretation of the world and the place of human beings in it, based on an account of how life should be lived given that interpretation, and expresses this interpretation, and lifestyle in a set of rituals, institutions and practices" (Yandell, 1999, .p16).

the vivid picture of religion in this definition represents its social functions as the world construing system giving prescriptions about life and their manifestations in the institutionalized sacred acts of the devotees.

Literature Review

Religious conflict has been a recurring issue in many parts of the world such as South Sudan, Mali, Somalia, and Nigeria. This study centers on how inter-religious conflict in Plateau state has impacted mental health of the people in Plateau. This conflict not just only disrupt the social fabric but also pose significant threat to mental health.

Adedeji (2018), in his famous work reviewed the Jos Plateaus 2010 Inter-religious conflict and its Conflict Resolution Mechanism. Relevant literature dealing with the conflict and religious conflict alongside the history and causes of the 2010 Jos Inter-religious conflict was reviewed. The study adopted descriptive research design, using both primary and secondary data collection. The data collected indicated that crises in the region were caused by the failure of the Nigerian government to address issues of unemployment and security of lives and properties. The results showed that the conflicts that have occurred in Jos were caused by politics and not religion. It further established that the government has not fully addressed the causes of the Jos crisis which can lead to reoccurrence of conflict in the region. The paper advocates that government should provide employment and access to education in Jos Plateaus state.

Joseph & Okpa (2019), examined the implications of ethnic and religious conflict on human existence and business activities to its residents in Jos. The study adopted survey research design. Multiple – stage sampling technique was used in selecting four hundred participants from five districts in Jos Metropolis. Questionnaire was the major instrument for primary data collection. The obtained data were statistically analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Each hypothesis was tested at 0.05% level of significance. The result obtained shows that ethnic religious crisis portends great danger to human existence and a threat to business activities in the country. It was recommended that National Orientation Agency should be strengthened and empowered to mobilized and create consistent national awareness on the ills of crises.

Ruth, M. (2020) carried out a study on religion and its relationship to conflict in South Sudan. The study made use of the multi methods technique as used by Creswell et al, (2023). The results show that religious oppression still exists significantly in South Sudan post- Independent, but the exact extent is not determined. The study recommends that the South Sudan government and other stakeholders should implement already existing peace agreements.

Simon, Hamdu & Jesse.J (2021) investigated empirical case studies of religious conflict in Nigeria and possible solutions. The methodology of the study is qualitative content analysis of aggregated data gathered from secondary sources. It adopted intractable conflict theory. Findings confirms that religious in Nigeria claimed people's lives and loss of property worth billions of naira. The study recommends that education, tolerance, dialogue and reconciliation among others should serve as tools with which to douse the social violence that emerges from the practice of religion in Nigeria as this will ensure peaceful co-existence of Christians, Muslims traditionalists and members of other religions.

Furthermore, Uwadi et al (2017), examined causes and implication of religious conflicts in Nigeria's political system. The study adopted the survey research design, personal observations and questionnaires were the major means of data collection. The research hypothesis was formulated to achieve the aim of the research. It was revealed that the cause of religious conflicts in Nigeria include failure to move with change, conflicting doctrines, methods of conversion, utterances of religious leaders and clothing of political objectives with religion among others. It recommends that religious conflict be addressed by religious bodies who should meet on regular bases and government should be swift to response to curtail conflicts.

Yusuf (2022) explore impact of ethno- religious conflict secondary in Nigeria. A case study of Kaduna state. The study analyzed the ethno-religious conflict particularly in the Northern state of Kaduna. The study adopted a qualitative method while a historical research design was employed to gather secondary data. Research findings confirmed that ethno-religious had a negative impact on the development of Kaduna state. The paper recommends that religious communities or ethnic groups should act as a

mediator to ensure that the conflicts between their religion or ethnic group and others do not intensify and religious and ethnic communities should ensure that the conflicts between their religion or ethnic group and others do not intensify and religious and ethnic communities should ensure justice in settling any dispute situation.

Conflict Dynamics in Barkin Ladi and Riyom

The inter-religious conflict in Barkin Ladi and Riyom Local Government Areas primarily involves clashes between predominantly Christian Berom ethnic groups and Hausa-Fulani residents and rural Fulani pastoralists. The core of the conflict in these areas is deeply rooted in disputes over land and "indigene" status, with the Berom recognized as indigenes and the Hausa and Fulani often classified as settlers. This mirrors the broader "indigene-non-indigene" issue prevalent across Plateau State significant escalation occurred in January 2010, following initial violence in Jos. Armed groups of Christians, predominantly Berom, attacked Muslim residents and rural Fulani pastoralists in numerous settlements across Barkin Ladi and Riyom. Mobs killed or drove out Muslim residents, including women and children, and systematically burned Muslim homes, property, and mosques. In many communities, all Hausa-Fulani residents were either killed or expelled. Documented incidents include attacks in Rabere, Bere Riti, Rahei, Budung, Kori, Kogot, Sagas, and Fogawa, with reports of between 8 and 17 Fulani killed in individual villages. Fulani leaders reported a total of 209 Fulani killed across Jos South, Barkin Ladi, and Riyom local government areas, with Barkin Ladi being the hardest hit, accounting for 112 deaths in 14 villages.

In a clear act of retaliation, two months later, in March 2010, armed Fulani men massacred more than 160 Berom in Dogo Nahawa and surrounding villages in Barkin Ladi. This brutal attack, identified by police as a "revenge mission," occurred around 3 a.m. on March 7, 2010. Armed men, speaking Fulbe and Hausa, some in military fatigues, fired guns, shot fleeing residents, entered homes to hack women and children to death, and set houses on fire. The attack was particularly vicious, with at least 38 children killed. One horrific incident involved attackers hacking a pregnant woman to death, cutting open her womb, and mutilating the fetus.

The violence continued with dozens of night raids on predominantly Christian (mostly Berom) villages in Jos South, Barkin Ladi, and Riyom

local government areas between April 2010 and November 2013. Alleged Fulani attackers would shoot or hack residents, set houses on fire, and disappear. Human Rights Watch estimated that over 500 Christians, mostly Berom, were killed in these attacks during this period.

Conflict Dynamics in Jos

Jos, the capital of Plateau State, has been a central flashpoint for inter-religious conflict, particularly since the seminal violence of September 2001. This event marked a dramatic shift, as the city, previously known for peaceful coexistence, became the scene of mass killings and destruction for the first time in its recent history. The initial crisis, occurring from September 7 to 13, 2001, resulted in approximately 1,000 deaths and displaced tens of thousands in less than a week. While widely portrayed as a religious conflict, its underlying causes were primarily political and economic, stemming from a longstanding struggle for control of political power and economic rivalry between different ethnic groups, particularly between those identified as "indigenous" and "non-indigenous" inhabitants. Religious sentiments were subsequently manipulated and appealed to by both sides to inflame the situation, transforming socio-economic grievances into identity-based conflict.

The violence continued in waves from 2002 to 2004, directly or indirectly connected to the 2001 Jos crisis, contributing to an estimated 2,000 to 3,000 deaths across Plateau State by May 2004. The political landscape in Plateau State saw influential positions in government and local administrations increasingly dominated by Christians, leading to significant resentment and a sense of marginalization among some Muslim communities. Initially, ethnic allegiance tended to be a stronger identifier, but in later phases (2002-2004), the question of religion became paramount, leading to instances where members of the same ethnic group clashed due to religious divisions.

The evolution of conflict in Jos demonstrates how underlying political and economic rivalries, particularly those related to the "indigene-non-indigene" dichotomy, can be transformed and exacerbated by the manipulation of religious identities. The initial framing of the conflict as primarily political and economic, followed by the escalation of religious rhetoric, highlights a strategic shift where religious sentiments become a powerful tool for mobilization. This dynamic leads to a desire for physical separation,

resulting in segregated neighborhoods. This spatial division is not merely a consequence but actively reinforces in-group solidarity and out-group animosity, creating an environment where fear and distrust are normalized. This physical separation then becomes a crucial mechanism for group mobilization and the perpetuation of conflict, making genuine reconciliation and mental healing profoundly more challenging.

Research Design

This study employs a secondary data analysis research design, a methodological approach particularly well-suited for examining complex, protracted conflicts in Plateau State. This design allows for the exploration of historical trends, broad patterns of impact, and documented mental health outcomes, especially when direct primary data collection might be logistically challenging, ethically sensitive, or unsafe due to ongoing conflict. The research draws upon a diverse range of academic and non-academic available secondary data sources to ensure a comprehensive and triangulated understanding of the phenomenon.

Discussion of Findings

Documented Mental Health Prevalence and Manifestations

Studies consistently demonstrate a significant increase in mental disorders within populations exposed to armed conflict. The World Health Organization estimates that approximately 10% of individuals experiencing traumatic events in conflict settings will develop serious mental health problems, with an additional 10% developing behaviors that hinder their effective functioning. Depression, anxiety, and psychosomatic issues are among the most common conditions. In Nigeria, and specifically within Plateau State, research indicates a high prevalence of various mental health conditions directly attributable to prolonged exposure to inter-religious conflict.

These are consistently identified as the most prevalent mental disorders in conflict-affected areas across Nigeria. In Dogonahawa, a rural community in Barkin Ladi, Plateau State, 38.5% of respondents still experienced depression four years after a major terrorist incident. The burden on caregivers is particularly pronounced, with depression rates among heads of households reaching 45.2% compared to 28.6% for dependents. In Jos, a study indicated that male participants significantly scored higher on

anxiety and depression compared to females. Women in Plateau State generally experience heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression due to violence, displacement, and loss. Post Trauma Stress Disorder is highly prevalent among conflict-affected populations. A 2014 study in North-central Nigeria demonstrated a significant association between violence and PTSD, with participants reporting common symptoms such as constant watchfulness and being easily startled (68.1%), denial or avoidance of crisis-related thoughts (67.6%), feelings of numbness and detachment from surroundings (52.9%), and recurring nightmares (42.2%). In Jos, a study among medical students reported a PTSD prevalence of 23.5%. Furthermore, survivors of sexual abuse, particularly in Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) camps, exhibit up to 20 times more symptoms of PTSD and depression.

Beyond depression, anxiety, and PTSD, individuals affected by conflict may also present with substance misuse, psychosis, antisocial behaviors, and psychosomatic complaints such as headaches, non-specific body pains, and dizziness. Alcohol and substance abuse are noted as maladaptive coping mechanisms among military combatants who have served on the frontlines of conflicts. The prolonged nature of conflict in Nigeria means that individuals often experience "persistent trauma experiences" related to "continuous, direct, and indirect violence." This leads to an overlap of PTSD and CTS symptoms, highlighting the chronic and compounding nature of psychological distress in these environments.

The high prevalence rates of PTSD, depression, and anxiety, with effects persisting for years after specific incidents, indicate a significant risk of intergenerational transmission of trauma. Children, who are explicitly identified as a particularly vulnerable group experiencing substantial mental health challenges, are growing up in environments characterized by chronic violence, displacement, and loss. This exposure to profound and sustained stress can severely impact their neurodevelopment, emotional regulation, and overall worldview. This can lead to a normalization of violence, impaired social functioning, and difficulties in developing trust and empathy, potentially perpetuating cycles of conflict. The societal implication is the emergence of a generation with impaired mental well-being, which can hinder future stability, economic productivity, and the capacity for collective healing and reconciliation, creating a long-term burden that extends far beyond the immediate conflict.

Community Responses and Coping Strategies

In the face of pervasive conflict and its psychological toll, affected communities in Plateau State and broader Nigeria employ various coping strategies, ranging from traditional and religious practices to more maladaptive behaviors.

Religious and spiritual practices are frequently utilized as coping strategies in developing countries, offering solace and a framework for meaning-making in traumatic circumstances. In Afghanistan, for instance, religion and family were identified as primary sources of emotional support for those affected by conflict. Similarly, in the context of farmer-herder conflicts, socio-cultural support systems are leveraged as a coping mechanism. These practices can provide a crucial sense of resilience, belonging, and community solidarity. A study in North-central Nigeria found high rates of denial and avoidance of thoughts related to the crisis (67.6%) among participants. This indicates a common psychological defense mechanism employed to manage overwhelming trauma and distress.

Some individuals resort to maladaptive coping strategies. A report on military combatants who served on the frontlines of the Boko Haram conflict highlighted the use of alcohol, substance abuse, and sexual promiscuity as coping mechanisms for dealing with flashbacks, sleep disturbances, and hyperarousal states. These behaviors, while offering temporary escape, can exacerbate existing mental health problems and lead to further social and health issues. Local and international organizations have initiated various dialogue and reconciliation programs aimed at fostering understanding and cooperation between conflicting groups. These initiatives include peace education, interfaith dialogues, and community mediation efforts, which seek to address the root causes of conflict and build bridges between divided communities.

The observation that religious and community support are frequent coping strategies, alongside the presence of maladaptive behaviors and the escalation of religious rhetoric as a driver of conflict, reveals a complex dynamic. While traditional and community-based coping mechanisms, such as religious practices and family support, can provide a crucial sense of resilience, belonging, and meaning in the face of trauma, they can also be a double-edged sword. When relied upon exclusively, without complementary professional mental health intervention, they may only offer temporary relief and often fail to address clinical mental health disorders like severe

PTSD or depression. Furthermore, the very religious identity that serves as a coping mechanism can also be manipulated to fuel division and conflict, transforming a potential source of solace into a catalyst for further distress. This implies that while leveraging and strengthening existing community support systems is vital, it must be carefully integrated with professional, culturally sensitive mental health services to prevent maladaptive coping, address underlying pathology, and ensure comprehensive and sustainable healing.

Challenges in Mental Health Service Provision

The severe mental health burden in Plateau State and across Nigeria is compounded by profound systemic challenges in mental health service provision, leading to a significant treatment gap.

Nigeria faces an acute shortage of mental health professionals. There are fewer than 150 psychiatrists in the entire country for a population of nearly 200 million, with another estimate suggesting only 250 psychiatrists for the same population. Additionally, there are an estimated only 150 practicing psychologists nationwide. This severe deficit means that the vast majority of those in need cannot access appropriate professional care. The country possesses only 8 federal neuropsychiatric hospitals, and fewer than 15 state-run neuropsychiatric centers. This severely restricts access, particularly for individuals in rural areas, as the majority of the limited mental health workforce is centralized in urban centers. Consequently, access to and quality of mental health care are described as "poor," with people often unable to access services for early intervention.

Mental health receives a meager 3.3% of Nigeria's health budget. This critically underfunds the public system, leaving it chronically understaffed and ill-equipped to meet the overwhelming demand for services. The ongoing crisis has starkly exposed the "sheer neglect and near exclusion of people under mental distress from health facilities". The World Health Organization estimates that fewer than 10% of mentally ill Nigerians have access to the care they need. This systemic neglect means that the impacts from trauma—such as PTSD, depression, anxiety, and drug dependence—often go untreated, exacerbating the harm inflicted by conflict and increasing the risk of perpetuating cycles of violence. Low awareness of mental health issues is prevalent in Nigeria and widespread stigma and negative social attitudes toward mental health are significant barriers to

seeking and receiving care. any patients with psychiatric care needs are often left to the care of their household members due to this stigma and lack of professional services.

While local Non-Governmental Organizations are active in conflict-affected regions, their administrators often "lack the awareness and capacity to address their clients' psychosocial, behavioral, and mental health issues" related to continuous violence. This highlights a critical need for targeted training and support for local humanitarian actors to effectively respond to the mental health crisis. International organizations like IOM, MSF, and ICRC provide Mental Health and Psychosocial Support services in conflict-affected regions, including counselling, psychological first aid (PFA), and referrals to specialized services. However, these services are "extremely limited in many areas" and face significant challenges such as access restrictions due to insecurity and border closures. Despite their efforts, these organizations cannot fully bridge the massive gap in mental health provision.

Conclusion

The inter-religious conflict in Plateau State, particularly in Jos and Barkin Ladi/Riyom, is a complex phenomenon driven by an intricate web of ethnic, political, economic, and religious factors. The "indigene-non-indigene" dichotomy and competition over scarce resources like land and political power serve as fundamental drivers, which are then amplified and weaponized through strong ethno-religious identities. This dynamic perpetuates cycles of violence, leading to profound displacement and the emergence of segregated settlements that further entrench animosity and fear. The psychosocial toll of this protracted conflict is immense, manifesting in alarmingly high rates of mental health disorders such as depression, anxiety, and Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) among affected populations. These impacts are not uniform but disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, including women, children, and internally displaced persons, who face compounded stressors like sexual violence, malnutrition, and the harsh realities of displacement. The long-term persistence of these mental health issues, particularly among children, raises concerns about the potential for intergenerational transmission of trauma, which could hinder future societal stability and reconciliation.

Despite the overwhelming burden, Nigeria's mental healthcare system is severely underdeveloped, characterized by a critical shortage of professionals, inadequate infrastructure, and minimal budgetary allocation. This systemic neglect means that the vast majority of conflict-affected individuals receive no formal mental health support, leaving them to rely on informal, often insufficient, coping mechanisms. The current situation suggests that the true human cost of these conflicts is far greater than what is immediately visible, impacting social cohesion and economic productivity for generations.

Recommendations

Based on the comprehensive analysis, the following actionable recommendations are critical for addressing the mental health crisis and fostering sustainable peace in Plateau State.

The Nigerian government must prioritize the development and robust implementation of a comprehensive national mental health policy. This policy needs to be backed by a significant increase in budgetary allocation to mental health services, with a specific focus on conflict-affected regions like Plateau State.

Urgent investment is required in training and deploying a significantly larger number of psychiatrists, psychologists, and community mental health workers. Recruitment and retention strategies should prioritize deployment to underserved rural areas, where access to care is currently most limited. Mental Health Psychological Support programs should be systematically integrated into primary healthcare services, humanitarian aid efforts, and broader peacebuilding initiatives. This ensures that mental health support is not an isolated service but a core component of recovery and development, addressing both individual and community-level trauma.

Develop and implement gender- and age-sensitive interventions specifically tailored for women, children, and IDPs. These programs must address their unique vulnerabilities, including support for survivors of sexual violence, nutritional interventions that consider cognitive development in children, and comprehensive psychosocial support for displaced populations. Support efforts to establish credible accountability mechanisms for past violence and implement inclusive reconciliation programs. Breaking the cycles of revenge requires addressing historical grievances, providing avenues for justice and compensation, and fostering inter-group dialogue and trust-building at the

community level. Leverage and strengthen existing community-based support systems, integrating traditional coping mechanisms with professional care. Simultaneously, invest in building the capacity of local mental health professionals, community leaders, and local NGOs through targeted training and resources, enabling them to effectively identify and respond to psychosocial and mental health needs. Invest in long-term, systematic research and data collection on mental health in conflict zones. This includes conducting comprehensive prevalence studies and impact assessments of existing MHPSS interventions to better understand the evolving needs of affected populations and to inform evidence-based policy and programming.

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Preserving Sacred Knowledge: The Role of Libraries in Promoting Interfaith Dialogue and Peacebuilding

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Abstract

This paper seeks to contribute to existing knowledge that needs to be revamped and cause reeducation of the role and importance of the library to the adherents of religions and all users of knowledge in promoting peace and interfaith understanding among the diversities of religions in the world. It also seeks to cut the role ignorance plays amongst the users of sacred contents to indoctrinate members who don't have access to quality information on the sacredness behind the knowledge that embeds their religious faith, and encourages interfaith understanding. This paper explores the vital role of libraries in preserving sacred knowledge and promoting interfaith understanding and peacebuilding. In an increasingly diverse religious landscape, libraries serve as essential resources for disseminating information that fosters dialogue and mutual respect among different faith communities. Through providing access to sacred texts and facilitating educational initiatives, librarians help bridge gaps in knowledge that often lead to misunderstandings and conflict. The paper emphasises the importance of libraries in not only preserving cultural heritage but also in

cultivating a culture of peace through community engagement and outreach programs. Ultimately, the study advocates for increased recognition of libraries as critical players in fostering interfaith dialogue and social harmony in diverse societies.

Keywords: Sacred Knowledge, Interfaith Dialogue, Peacebuilding, Role of Libraries

Introduction

The increase of cultural belief systems, values, morals and doctrines in the divine being (God) has been a bedrock of people's understanding in promoting interfaith understanding and peacebuilding, hence, preservation of such sacred knowledge. Sacred knowledge in this paper refers to the body of ideas, beliefs and traditions of cultures and religious facts. It is the body of knowledge accumulated by communities over generations, shaped by their interactions with the environment. It also encompasses skills, spiritual practices, and beliefs that enable communities to achieve a stable livelihood. It is often shared orally and exists in various forms, including stories, songs, proverbs and historical folklore, that reflect the strong influence on people's culture and livelihood (Anyira, Onoriode, & Nwabueze, 2010). Sacred knowledge refers to the religious teachings, texts, and traditions that shape the beliefs and practices of different faith communities. This body of knowledge serves as a foundation for understanding one another's perspectives and fostering mutual respect among diverse religious groups. Librarians play a crucial role in providing access to these sacred texts and promoting resources that facilitate interfaith understanding and dialogue, thereby contributing to social harmony and conflict resolution (Hundu, 2024). This paper seeks to emphasise the role of librarians in preserving sacred knowledge, promoting interfaith dialogue and peacebuilding.

This paper explores how librarians have a deep connection in promoting interfaith communication, dialogue and peacebuilding in the nation. In a country like Nigeria, where there are multi-dimensional religious practices with different cultures, tribes, belief systems and traditional practices that creates gap in knowledge in understanding other people's religious beliefs, leading to chaos, hence the need for accurate knowledge through the role librarians play in providing quality information for all users of information

through the library, social media and the global network. Librarians, through peace education, provision of quality information on how sacred knowledge can be accessed in the library (online and offline), and peacebuilding skills, can help promote interfaith understanding amongst all adherents of religions in the nation and internationally. This paper, therefore, seeks to bring clarity on how to utilise the role libraries can foster peacebuilding in a nation.

Literature Review

Sacred Knowledge

Sacred knowledge is religious, because of the reverence that is being accustomed to the beliefs, rituals, teachings and doctrines, laws and morals that it is being established on. It is a reservoir that answers the search for significant ways that relate to the sacred, which are found in religious models of spiritual beliefs. Individuals, families, and society mostly depend on sacred knowledge from religious and cultural belief system that shapes their values and morals in their daily lives (Omotosho, 2014). According to Mahadeva (2021), it refers to indigenous wisdom, knowledge, and ideas which correspond with traditional activities, values and character developed by honoured ancestors who passed it down from one age to another. In the context of religion, it helps preserve spiritual rites of passage, beliefs, customs, and faith, which enables adherents of a religion to observe and pay homage to the supreme being with guided instructions. Through incorporation, integration and assimilation of sacred knowledge into modern governing policies, every individual gives tribute to the existence of this knowledge, either consciously or unconsciously, making conservation efforts throughout the world more successful (Burgos-Ayala et al., 2020, D.Yadav, 2018). The need for the availability of libraries is to bring this knowledge closer and accessible to members of the society, promoting interfaith dialogue and peace amongst different cultures and religions, reducing tribalism and religious conflicts.

Inter-Faith Dialogue

Healthy communication builds a healthy relationship, which emphasises the role an effective dialogue can play in human relations. In order to understand the nature of man, dialogue is of great importance because human beings need to communicate with each other (Labilam, 2016). This

helps define peace and order, conflict and tension. Dialogue, according to Toki, Gambari, and Hadi (2015), is a process that has to occur in a society to enable trust and foster harmony. Hindu (2024) defines interfaith dialogue as a significant process aimed at fostering mutual understanding and cooperation among individuals from different religious backgrounds. In the context of Nigeria, he stated that where a substantial population practices both Christianity and Islam, interfaith dialogue seeks to promote peaceful coexistence by emphasising shared values and experiences rather than competition or proselytising. This dialogue is not merely a debate but a collaborative effort to address common social issues, resolve conflicts, and enhance religious tolerance among diverse faith communities. He further asserts that interfaith dialogue serves various specific objectives, including conflict resolution and understanding the roles that faith-based communities play in managing religious tensions. He cited that dialogue must occur in environments that foster trust and respect, thus enabling participants to engage openly and constructively. By facilitating these discussions, interfaith dialogue initiatives can contribute to the broader goal of promoting social harmony and reducing religious conflicts in society. Ossai (2019) argues that interfaith dialogue is imperative for effective peacebuilding in a nation, which is needed when a nation is faced with a high rate of tribal and religious conflicts. Religious peacebuilders can enhance their legitimacy and influence by working together across faith lines, thus creating a united front that fosters trust and cooperation among conflicting parties. Through the combination of sources and approaches from different religious traditions, peacebuilders can leverage their shared values and ethical principles to facilitate dialogue and reconciliation. Hence, the need for the library to help preserve such religious dialogues and treaties to help foster research, quality education and equity in a nation. This not only strengthens the capacity of religious resources but also sends powerful messages of tolerance and unity to the broader community, which can help mitigate tensions and promote healing.

Moreover, in the absence of acknowledging the role of the library in preserving sacred knowledge and interfaith dialogue can lead to unaddressed intra- and intercommunal conflicts, which can lead to more harm to the community and societal development. Through the use of library resources, which can help in pooling human, intellectual, and material resources, religious actors from various traditions can create

inclusive platforms for dialogue that accommodate diverse perspectives. This collaborative approach is posited as a means to redefine conflicts positively and promote a culture of coexistence. Interfaith dialogue, underpinned by cooperative efforts, is crucial for achieving sustainable peace in societies marked by religious diversity and conflict (Ossai, 2019).

Peacebuilding

According to Umeji and Chukwuji, (2018), peacebuilding refers to a structured problem-solving approach aimed at addressing the underlying causes of conflict and establishing lasting peace within societies. This process involves various initiatives and strategies designed to promote social cohesion, reconciliation, and the prevention of future conflicts. It is also asserted that peacebuilding is not merely the absence of violence; rather, it encompasses efforts to foster understanding, tolerance, and cooperation among different cultural and religious groups (Anyira, Onoriode, & Nwabueze, 2010). Implementation of peace education into formal and informal learning environments, peacebuilding initiatives seek to equip individuals with the knowledge and skills necessary for conflict resolution and peaceful coexistence. Ossai (2019) stated that peacebuilding is a complex process which is designed to address the root causes of conflict and establish sustainable peace in societies affected by violence and discord. This comprehensive process was aimed at promoting reconciliation, interfaith dialogue, and conjuring an environment safe for recuperation and oneness amongst conflicting parties. Peacebuilding encompasses not only immediate conflict resolution strategies but also long-term efforts to transform relationships, institutions, and societal systems that negate human conflicts and inequality. It emphasises the importance of inclusivity and collaboration among various stakeholders, including religious leaders, community organisations, and governmental bodies, to achieve meaningful and lasting peace. Peacebuilding is not solely the responsibility of external actors; rather, it relies heavily on local initiatives and the engagement of community members in the peace process. Leveraging the resources and wisdom of local cultures and traditions, peacebuilding efforts can be more effective and resonate deeply within the affected communities. The significance of interreligious collaboration is a vital component of peacebuilding, as it allows for the pooling of diverse perspectives and resources, thereby enhancing the overall capacity to address conflicts and

promote a culture of peace and coexistence. Therefore, the critical role of libraries in facilitating peacebuilding efforts can't be underrepresented. Libraries serve as repositories of knowledge and information, providing access to resources that promote peace education and awareness in communities. Through outreach programs and community engagement, libraries can disseminate valuable information that addresses the root causes of conflict, thereby contributing to a culture of peace. Libraries can play a pivotal role in building a more peaceful society, emphasising the importance of education as a tool for empowerment and conflict transformation.

Challenges the Library Faces in Preserving Sacred Knowledge, Peacebuilding and Interfaith Dialogue

According to Hundu (2024), the role of libraries in promoting interfaith dialogue in Nigeria is complex and challenging as they struggle to bring comprehension and clarity amongst religious communities who don't have access to quality information. Umeji and Chukwuji (2018) and Hundu (2024) stated the following challenges libraries face in Nigeria in promoting peace and interfaith dialogue;

The major challenge that faces interfaith dialogue and peacebuilding is the high illiteracy rate in the country. With millions of Nigerians lacking basic reading and writing skills, libraries struggle to effectively disseminate information related to peace education and communicate preserved knowledge on religious facts that help to engage in interfaith dialogue. This illiteracy not only hinders access to valuable resources but also limits people's ability to engage critically with concepts of peace and conflict resolution. Consequently, many individuals remain uninformed about the importance of tolerance and understanding among different religious groups.

Poor funding is another factor that hinders the growth and outreach of libraries to the society and community members who need sensitisation on promoting the preservation of sacred knowledge and peace in the country. The Nigerian educational system has historically suffered from inadequate financial support, which extends to libraries. Many libraries lack the necessary resources to acquire relevant materials that promote peace education, and their operational budgets are often insufficient to sustain programs aimed at fostering interfaith dialogue. This funding gap restricts

libraries from implementing outreach initiatives and educational programs that could engage communities in discussions about peace and conflict resolution, thereby undermining their potential impact.

Non-impactful government and support towards libraries in the context of preserving sacred knowledge, promoting interfaith dialogue and peace education. Government agencies and stakeholders often overlook the crucial role that libraries can play in preserving sacred contents and information among religious communities in order to communicate healthy interfaith dialogue to adherents of religion and the community as a whole. This lack of recognition and communication leads to insufficient collaboration between libraries and governmental or religious organisations, limiting the effectiveness of interfaith dialogue initiatives. Without support from relevant authorities, libraries may struggle to access the networks and resources necessary for impactful outreach and community engagement.

Poor reading culture in Nigeria poses a significant barrier. Many individuals, especially the youth, are increasingly distracted by digital media and social platforms, leading to a decline in traditional reading habits. This cultural shift results in a diminished interest in library resources that address peace education. If libraries cannot cultivate a strong reading culture, their efforts to promote understanding and tolerance among different religious groups may be significantly hindered, as fewer individuals will engage with the literature and materials that foster dialogue and peace.

Prevalent religious tensions in Nigeria have a history of conflicts between different religious groups, often fueled by misunderstandings and misinterpretations of religious texts. The use of libraries can help navigate this complex landscape carefully, as promoting dialogue in such a volatile environment can inadvertently exacerbate existing tensions.

Limited resources in libraries in Nigeria cause them to operate on tight budgets, which restricts their ability to acquire a diverse range of religious texts and materials. This lack of comprehensive resources makes it difficult for librarians to provide the necessary materials for interfaith research and study. Without access to a wide variety of perspectives and religious traditions, librarians may struggle to facilitate meaningful dialogue among different faith communities.

Access to information is also a significant barrier. In rural areas, where infrastructure might be lacking, individuals often face difficulties accessing

library resources. Theological librarians may find it challenging to ensure that all community members, regardless of their geographical location, have equal access to interfaith dialogue materials. This disparity can limit the effectiveness of their initiatives and hinder broader community engagement in interfaith discussions.

Furthermore, there is a low perception of librarians' roles in society. Many individuals may not fully recognise the importance of librarians in promoting interfaith dialogue. This lack of awareness can make it difficult for librarians and theological librarians to effectively advocate for their initiatives and garner support from both the community and institutional stakeholders. The challenge lies in elevating the profile of librarianship and demonstrating its critical role in fostering understanding and cooperation among different religious groups.

In conclusion, security concerns pose a significant challenge to promoting interfaith dialogue. In some regions of Nigeria, discussing sensitive religious topics can lead to safety issues for librarians and participants. This heightened risk can discourage librarians from initiating interfaith dialogue programs or engaging with community members on potentially contentious subjects. Despite these challenges, librarians remain committed to their mission of fostering interfaith understanding and cooperation, and they continue to seek innovative strategies to overcome these obstacles.

Theoretical Frameworks

Intergroup Contact Theory

Intergroup Contact Theory, as articulated by Thomas F. Pettigrew 1998, posits that positive interactions between different social groups can reduce prejudice and promote understanding. The theory identifies four essential conditions for effective intergroup contact: equal status among groups, common goals, intergroup cooperation, and support from authorities. These conditions create an environment conducive to positive interactions, which can lead to improved attitudes and reduced stereotypes. Through these interactions, libraries can play a significant role in fostering peacebuilding among diverse religious communities.

Intergroup contact theory can help the library by creating programs that promote equal status among different religious groups. For instance, libraries could host interfaith dialogues and workshops where participants are encouraged to share their beliefs and practices in a respectful

environment. Such initiatives can help dismantle stereotypes and foster mutual respect. When individuals from various religious backgrounds engage as equals in discussions, they are more likely to develop a sense of community and understanding, which is crucial for peacebuilding.

Libraries can establish common goals through collaborative community projects that address local issues, such as social justice or community service. By bringing together individuals from different religious backgrounds to work toward a shared objective, libraries can facilitate intergroup cooperation. This collaborative effort not only enhances social bonds but also reinforces the idea that people from diverse backgrounds can work together for the common good. Such experiences can significantly reduce intergroup tensions and promote a culture of peace.

Moreover, libraries can provide authority support by aligning their peacebuilding initiatives with local governments or community leaders. When libraries are seen as credible institutions that promote intergroup contact and understanding, they can influence societal norms and expectations. This endorsement can encourage individuals to participate in intergroup activities, knowing that such interactions are valued and supported. Libraries can also leverage their resources to disseminate information about the benefits of intergroup contact, thus educating the community about its importance in fostering peace.

Intergroup contact theory offers a valuable framework for libraries to engage in peacebuilding activities among diverse religious groups. Creation of an enabling environments that promote equal status, common goals, and intergroup cooperation, libraries can facilitate meaningful interactions that help reduce prejudice and foster understanding. Through these efforts, libraries not only contribute to individual growth and development but also play a pivotal role in building a more harmonious and peaceful society.

Social Cohesion

Social Cohesion Theory explores the bonds that unite individuals within a society, emphasising the importance of cooperation across diverse group boundaries without coercion or self-interest. The theory highlights that social cohesion is not merely a matter of shared values or identities; it also involves the quality of relationships among individuals and groups. Cohesive societies are characterised by their ability to foster trust, promote inclusivity, and reduce inequalities, which are essential for maintaining

peace and stability. This understanding of social cohesion provides a framework for analysing how communities can work together to overcome divisions and foster a sense of belonging.

Libraries can leverage the purpose of social cohesion theory through the process of promoting peacebuilding by serving as platforms for fostering dialogue and understanding among diverse religious and cultural groups. Organization of community events, workshops, and discussions that emphasise shared goals and collaborative efforts, libraries can create environments conducive to intergroup cooperation. These initiatives can counteract prejudices and stereotypes, allowing individuals to learn about one another in a safe space. Additionally, libraries can provide resources that educate community members about social cohesion and the importance of diversity, thus reinforcing societal values that support peaceful coexistence.

Moreover, libraries can act as advocates for social cohesion by partnering with local organisations and authorities to implement programs that address social inequalities and promote inclusivity. By facilitating access to information and resources that support marginalised groups, libraries can play a crucial role in building a more cohesive society. This proactive approach not only enhances the library's role within the community but also contributes to broader peacebuilding efforts by fostering a culture of understanding and cooperation among diverse populations (Burns et al, 2018).

Libraries as Promoting Peace Building

Libraries play a crucial role in promoting peacebuilding by providing access to information and resources that foster understanding and tolerance among diverse communities. They serve as safe spaces for dialogue and learning, facilitating discussions on peace and conflict resolution. Through curated collections that include literature on peace studies, sociology, and civic education, libraries empower individuals with knowledge that can help mitigate conflict and promote social cohesion (Umeji & Chukwuji, 2018).

Libraries serve as vital institutions in promoting peacebuilding by providing access to information that fosters understanding and tolerance among diverse communities. They act as neutral spaces where individuals can engage with different perspectives, thus facilitating dialogue and reducing misconceptions. The exchange of resources on conflict resolution, human

rights, and cultural understanding, libraries empower individuals with the knowledge necessary to engage in peaceful discourse and community-building efforts (Lor, 2016). Libraries actively engage in community outreach programs aimed at educating the public about peace and conflict management. These initiatives often include workshops, seminars, and exhibitions that address local issues while promoting a culture of peace. Cooperation with local organizations and stakeholders, libraries can enhance their impact and ensure that peace education reaches a broader audience (Umeji & Chukwuji, 2018).

Libraries play an educational role by hosting programs and workshops that emphasise the importance of peace and intercultural dialogue. According to Lor (2016), he affirms that by celebrating events such as the International Day of Peace, libraries can mobilise communities to reflect on peace efforts and engage in activities that promote social cohesion. These initiatives not only raise awareness but also encourage active participation in peacebuilding processes, thereby strengthening community ties. Libraries teach essential skills such as information literacy and critical thinking, enabling individuals to navigate complex social issues effectively. This education helps cultivate informed citizens who can engage thoughtfully in discussions about peace and conflict. Libraries can help foster a reading culture and encourage lifelong learning; libraries contribute to the development of a more peaceful and informed society (Umeji & Chukwuji, 2018).

Libraries are increasingly addressing the needs of marginalised groups, such as refugees and immigrants, by providing tailored resources and support. Offering language programs, access to technology, and community integration services, libraries help these groups navigate challenges and foster a sense of belonging. This empowerment contributes to social stability and peace by mitigating the factors that can lead to conflict (Lor, 2016).

Libraries as Interfaith Dialogue

Libraries play a pivotal role in promoting interfaith dialogue by serving as accessible spaces for individuals from diverse religious backgrounds to engage in meaningful discussions. Providing a wide range of sacred texts and resources, libraries facilitate a deeper understanding of different belief systems and encourage mutual respect among faith communities. This access to information is crucial in dispelling misconceptions and promoting

informed dialogue, which is essential for fostering social harmony and reducing religious tensions (Hundu, 2024).

Libraries actively engage in community outreach programs that promote interfaith understanding through workshops, cultural exhibitions, and storytelling events. These patterns of involvement help create platforms for dialogue where individuals can share their experiences and beliefs in a respectful environment. By organizing events that emphasize shared values and collaborative efforts, libraries contribute to building trust and cooperation among different religious groups, ultimately enhancing community cohesion (Anyira et al., 2010).

In addition to facilitating discussions, libraries support research and educational initiatives that focus on interfaith dialogue. Theological librarians provide essential resources and research assistance to scholars and practitioners engaged in peacebuilding efforts. This support empowers individuals to critically examine various perspectives and fosters informed discussions about interfaith issues, reinforcing the importance of understanding and cooperation in promoting peace (Mahadeva, 2021).

The Role of Libraries in Preserving Sacred Knowledge, Promoting Peacebuilding and Interfaith Dialogue

Libraries as Custodians of Sacred Knowledge

The role which libraries play in preserving, storing, and handling religious knowledge is imperative for cultural preservation and sustainable development. Their role in the documentation of cultural and religious folklore, parables, manuscripts and oral historical accounts helps adherents to close the gap of ignorance in establishing equity and peace amongst other non-adherents of religions (Mahadeva, 2021). Libraries facilitate access to this sacred knowledge through various programs and community engagement activities, such as storytelling events and cultural exhibitions. Mahadeva (2021) stated that Libraries act as platforms for dialogue and cultural exchange. Libraries not only promote awareness of indigenous knowledge among both indigenous and non-indigenous audiences but also strengthen the connections between different cultural groups. This role is essential for fostering mutual respect and understanding, as libraries help to maintain the relevance of indigenous knowledge in contemporary society while supporting efforts for sustainability and cultural preservation.

Collecting and Preserving Indigenous Knowledge

Anyira et. al (2010) assert that libraries hold a vital responsibility in collecting and preserving indigenous knowledge, which encompasses the unique cultural practices, beliefs, and histories of local communities. This process involves various methods such as documentation, digitisation, and microfilming to ensure that this knowledge is not lost over time. Through these techniques, libraries create accessible archives that allow future generations to engage with and learn from their cultural heritage. Effective preservation not only safeguards individual and collective identities but also enriches the broader societal understanding of diverse ways of knowing and being.

Facilitating Access to Resources

Librarians play a pivotal role in promoting interfaith dialogue by ensuring that their libraries provide comprehensive and diverse resources on various religious traditions. By curating collections that include books, articles, and multimedia materials focused on interfaith dialogue, librarians make it easier for researchers and practitioners to access essential information. This accessibility not only supports academic study but also fosters a deeper understanding among individuals from different faith backgrounds, encouraging mutual respect and cooperation (Hundu, 2024).

Disseminating Information

In addition to preservation, libraries serve as critical facilitators for the dissemination of sacred knowledge to both indigenous and non-indigenous communities. This role is essential in enhancing awareness and understanding of local knowledge systems. Libraries bridge religious and cultural gaps, which foster mutual respect among different groups (Anyira, et al. 2021). Through various outreach programs, libraries can share information about indigenous practices and perspectives, thus promoting a deeper appreciation of cultural diversity. This dissemination is crucial in creating informed communities that value the contributions of indigenous peoples. Libraries keep scholars informed about the latest information relevant to peace and conflict studies (Umeji and Chukwuji, 2018).

Supporting Research and Educational Initiatives

In addition to facilitating access to resources, the use of libraries actively supports scholars and practitioners engaged in interfaith dialogue initiatives. They offer research assistance, conduct literature searches, and identify relevant resources that can aid in exploring interfaith issues. This support is vital for enhancing educational initiatives surrounding interfaith dialogue, as it empowers individuals to engage critically with different perspectives, ultimately promoting informed discussions (Hundu, 2024).

Encouraging Community Engagement

Umeji and Chukwuji (2018) state that libraries promote social change by providing resources that address issues of justice, equality, and community development. Theological librarians also promote community engagement by organising events and programs that encourage dialogue among diverse religious groups. Hosting workshops, discussions, and cultural events, librarians create spaces where individuals can share their experiences and beliefs in a respectful environment. These initiatives not only foster understanding and cooperation but also contribute to peacebuilding efforts within communities marked by religious diversity. Through their commitment to facilitating dialogue, theological librarians help cultivate a culture of understanding essential for harmonious coexistence (Hundu, 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, libraries play an indispensable role in preserving sacred knowledge and facilitating interfaith dialogue, particularly in culturally diverse settings like Nigeria. Curating comprehensive collections of religious texts and providing access to educational resources, libraries empower individuals to engage critically with different faith traditions. This access fosters a deeper understanding and appreciation of diverse beliefs, which is essential for promoting mutual respect and cooperation among various religious communities. The commitment of librarians to facilitating dialogue through organised events and outreach programs is crucial in addressing the knowledge gaps that often fuel conflict and misunderstandings.

Moreover, the challenges faced by libraries, such as limited resources, low literacy rates, and societal perceptions of their roles, necessitate a concerted

effort to enhance their capacity to promote peacebuilding. Adequate funding and institutional support are essential for libraries to thrive as centres of knowledge and dialogue. Overcoming these barriers, libraries can better serve their communities and contribute significantly to fostering peaceful coexistence in a multicultural society. The collaboration between libraries, religious institutions, and local communities is vital in creating inclusive platforms for dialogue, ultimately leading to a more harmonious society. Finally, as custodians of sacred knowledge, libraries have the unique ability to bridge cultural divides and promote social cohesion. By leveraging their resources and expertise, librarians can play a pivotal role in shaping a culture of peace that respects and values diversity. The preservation of sacred knowledge and the promotion of interfaith dialogue are not only essential for community development but also for building a more peaceful and understanding world. As we move forward, recognising and enhancing the role of libraries in these efforts will be crucial for achieving lasting peace and interfaith understanding globally.

Recommendations

To maximise their impact on peacebuilding, libraries should prioritise partnerships with educational institutions and community organisations that share similar goals. These collaborations can lead to the development of comprehensive peace education programs that integrate library resources with community needs. Additionally, libraries should advocate for increased funding and support from government agencies to enhance their capacity to provide relevant materials and services focused on peace education (Umeji & Chukwuji, 2018).

To enhance their impact on peacebuilding, libraries should prioritise partnerships with local organisations, educational institutions, and community leaders. These collaborations can facilitate the development of comprehensive peace education programs that leverage library resources to address specific community needs. Through collaboration, libraries and community stakeholders can create a robust framework for promoting peace and resolving conflicts (Lor, 2016).

Libraries should invest in training staff to engage in advocacy and outreach efforts aimed at raising awareness about peace-related issues. Equipping librarians with the skills to facilitate discussions and promote understanding, libraries can become more effective agents of change within

their communities. This proactive approach will help libraries fulfil their potential as catalysts for peacebuilding (Lor, 2016).

To enhance their impact on interfaith dialogue, libraries should prioritise collaborations with local religious organisations and community leaders. By partnering with these stakeholders, libraries can develop programs that address specific community needs and promote a culture of understanding. Such collaborations can also help libraries gain access to diverse resources and networks, further strengthening their role in facilitating interfaith dialogue (Hundu, 2024).

Additionally, libraries should invest in outreach strategies that incorporate digital platforms to engage younger audiences and those in remote areas. Utilising social media and online resources can help libraries reach a broader audience, making interfaith dialogue more accessible and relevant. By leveraging technology, libraries can disseminate information about interfaith initiatives and encourage active participation in community discussions, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and understanding society (Anyira et al., 2010).

Moreover, libraries need to adopt innovative outreach strategies, including the use of digital platforms and social media, to reach younger audiences and those in remote areas. Leveraging technology, libraries can disseminate peace education resources more widely and effectively engage with diverse communities. This approach will not only enhance awareness but also encourage active participation in peacebuilding initiatives (Umeji & Chukwuji, 2018).

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Exegetical Analysis of Rapture in the Light of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18

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Abstract

This study was prompted by the carefree attitude of the postmodern Christians towards biblical teachings, most especially, rapture. The paper is an exegetical analysis of Paul's Eschatological Discourse in 1 Thessalonians 4: 15-18. The paper aims at using the eschatological teachings of Paul in 1Thessalonians 4:15-18 to challenge the postmodern society to be rapture-ready in spite of the obstacles placed on their way by the negative traits of postmodernism. The paper commences with a brief introduction on the negative features of the postmodern world that encourages the postmodern man's complacent attitudes towards rapture. The next focal points of the paper are the texts surrounding the main text where Apostle Paul encouraged the Thessalonian church to build up their faith, love and grace for holiness (1Thessalonian 4:13-14). The surrounding texts also present Paul's transition to eschatological discourse and the purpose was to comfort those alive who were grieving over the dead because they were confused. The paper also touches the source of Paul's eschatological discourse: the eschatological discourse of Jesus Christ. A step-by-step procedure of rapture is presented. The paper draws

inferences for application for the postmodern church from the discourse analysis and closes with recommendations.

Keywords: Amillennial, Exegesis, Postmodern, Postmillennial, Premillennial, Rapture

Introduction

Postmodernism is a term used to philosophically describe the current era which came after the age of modernism. The philosophical concept seems to undermine the reality and significance of rapture. The dangers of postmodernism can be perceived as a downward spiral that kicks off with the rejection of absolute truth, which births a loss of distinctions in religious and faith issues culminating in a philosophy of religious pluralism. It upholds the tenet that no faith or religion is objectively true and as such, no one can claim his or her religion is true and another is false. The Christian faith and all its tenets, rapture inclusive, are at a great disadvantage due to the adverse effects of postmodern ideologies. Hence, this paper explores rapture in the postmodern context in the light of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18.

According to Stewart (2020) the rapture of the church is a term that is commonly used for the sudden removal of genuine believers from the earth, to meet their Lord in the air. Explicating further, he says that at some point in the future, those Christians who are alive will have their mortal bodies transformed into incorruptible, immortal bodies as taught in 1Cor. 15. Immediately before this happens, the believers who have died will be raised from the dead and will also receive a new body as they meet Christ in the air. According to Scripture all of this will occur in a moment, in a twinkling, or in a blink, of an eye.

Wenstrom, Jr, (2021) in his own definition and explanation of the term rapture, says it is taken from the Latin term *rapio*, “caught up” that is used to translate the Greek verb *harpazō* (ἁρπάζω), which appears in 1 Thessalonians 4:17. In this verse, according to him, the word means to “snatch, seize, forcibly remove something, to seize by force with the purpose of removing and is translated “will be caught up” by the Easy Standard Version (ESV) and New American Standard Bible 1995 (NASB95) and “will be suddenly caught up” by the New English Translation Bible 2005 (NET Bible).

Shedding light on the concept, Stewart (2020) says that the doctrine of the rapture of the church is mainly for the genuine believers in Jesus Christ

(not merely people who have a church membership or affiliation). According to Wenstrom (2021), the term rapture is used by students of prophecy and eschatology to describe the doctrine which is taught in the New Testament. He makes it clear that the term “rapture” is not found in the original languages of Scripture; it is only used by theologians to describe a doctrine that is taught in the Bible.

Exegesis of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18

Greek Translation

15 Τοῦτο γάρ ὑμῖν λέγομεν ἐν λόγῳ κυρίου, ὅτι ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες οἱ περιλειπόμενοι εἰς τὴν παρουσίαν τοῦ κυρίου, οὐ μὴ φθάσωμεν τοὺς κοιμηθέντας. 16. Ὅτι αὐτὸς ὁ κύριος ἐν κελεύσματι, ἐν φωνῇ ἀρχαγγέλου, καὶ ἐν σάλπιγγι θεοῦ, καταβήσεται ἀπ’ οὐρανοῦ, καὶ οἱ νεκροὶ ἐν χριστῷ ἀναστήσονται πρῶτον · 17. ἔπειτα ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες, οἱ περιλειπόμενοι, ἅμα σὺν αὐτοῖς ἀρπαγησόμεθα ἐν νεφέλαις εἰς ἀπάντησιν τοῦ κυρίου εἰς ἀέρα · καὶ οὕτως πάντοτε σὺν κυρίῳ ἐσόμεθα. 18. Ὡστε παρακαλεῖτε ἀλλήλους ἐν τοῖς λόγοις τούτοις.

Transliteration

15 *Tóuto gár humín légomen en lógoo Kuríou, hótí heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi eis teen parousían tou Kuríou, ou-meé fthásoomen toús koimeethéntas 16 hótí autós ho Kúrios en keleúsmati en fooneé archangéλου καὶ en sálpingi Theoú katabeésetai ap ouranou kaí hoi nekroí en Christoó anasteésontai proton 17 épeita heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi háma sún autoís harpageesómetha en nefélais eis apánteessin tou Kuríou eis aéra Kaí houtoos pántote sún Kuríoo esómetha 18 Hoóste parakaleíte alleélous en toís lógois toutois* Biblesoft, (2006.)

English Translation

15 According to the Lord's own word, we tell you that we who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord, will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep. 16 For the Lord himself will come down from heaven, with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel and with the trumpet call of God, and the dead in Christ will rise first. 17 After that, we who are still alive and are left will be caught up together with them in the clouds to meet the Lord in

the air. And so we will be with the Lord forever. 18 Therefore encourage each other with these words. (NIV)

Surrounding Texts

Preceding chapter is an encouragement to the church for their faith and love and an expression of gratitude for the joy they give them. Paul says that they are 'really living' (3.8) but gives them room to grow as he prays for the love to increase and overflow for each other and for everyone else (3.12). Paul used the medium to call the church of the Thessalonians to a higher standard. Having exhorted his audience to always abound in holiness, with a warning against ungodly lives (4:1-8), apostle Paul urged his audience to always abound in love and avoid idleness (4:12). The apostle concludes with words of comfort to those who mourned for their relations and friends who had died in the Lord (verses 13-18). Paul exhorts this church to do things they are already doing, or that they already know. This is seen in multiple verses:

4:1a *'We instructed you how to live in order to please God, as in fact you are living'*

4:2 *'You know what instructions we gave you by the authority of the Lord Jesus'*

4:6b *'as we have already told you and warned you'*

4:10a *'And in fact, you do love all the brothers throughout Macedonia'*

4:10b *'Yet we urge you, brothers, to do so more and more'*

There had been distress among the Thessalonian Christians regarding those who had died, hence, the cause of this distress cannot be said emphatically. Some scholars are of the opinion that this brethren are being misled by some false teachers. The purpose of Paul's transition to eschatological discourse was to comfort those alive who were grieving over the dead because they were confused. In verse 13 Paul addresses the topic about those who 'have fallen asleep' (*koimōmenōn*). The Greek word *koimōmenōn* is in reference to people who are 'asleep to death'. *Koimaō*, a common word for sleep, was often used as a euphemism for death in Greek, Jewish, and Christian writings as well as in Paul's epistles. There is nothing in the context to indicate that Paul used the word here in any way other than the conventional fashion. To read the term as an ontological assertion regarding the state of believers in the interim between death and resurrection is to import ideas not supported by this context (Michael Martin, 1995). Paul tells those alive not to

(*lypēsthe*) meaning grieve, or sorrow and not be like ἔχω μὴ ἐλπίς (*echo mē elpis*) meaning have (*echo*) no (*me*) hope (*elpis*). They were not to act like hopeless people. The Greek word Paul uses for hope is *elpida* which means a hope, expectation, or confidence.

Paul states the basis of this Christian hope in First Thessalonians 4:14. If we believe that Jesus died and rose, we can believe also in the resurrection of the dead Christians (v. 14). Paul asserts that those who died in the Lord by the virtue of Christ's resurrection, would be resurrected unto eternal life and blessedness. Because Christ rose, so God will bring with Jesus those who have fallen asleep in him. As stated by Martin "The God who raised Jesus will also raise Jesus' followers. It is Jesus' resurrection that validates the gospel and guarantees the believers' resurrection (cf. 1 Corinthians 15:17–20) (Martin, 1995).

It is pertinent to indicate that the concern of this section is on verses 15-18. However, this text under study will not be exposed in isolation, the preceding and the subsequent text would be referenced. Epistle of Paul to the Thessalonians Church was basically a treatise for encouragement and exhortation to the Christians.

Exegetical Study

Verse 15 begins with τοῦτο γὰρ ὑμῖν λέγομεν ἐν λόγῳ κυρίου, (*toúto gár humín légomen en lógoō Kuríou*), meaning for this we say unto you by the word of the Lord. *Toutu meaning this and gar meaning for, which can be translated for this*). Τοῦτο is the near demonstrative pronoun used to call attention to a designated person or object, often with special emphasis *this* (Matt 3.17); (1) used as an adjective *this* in Luke 2.25); (2) used as a substantive *this man, this woman, this thing, this one* (Matt 12.23); (3) both adjectival and substantival forms may be used as a contemptuous sneer: οὗ (*ou*). *this fellow* (Matt. 26.71); οὗ. ὁ τελώνης (*ou o telonhs*) *this tax collector* (LU 18.11); (4) used resumptively to give special emphasis to a person or thing previously mentioned *the very one* (Act 7.36); *toutu* is used cataphorically to refer to what follows, introducing a statement of purpose, result, condition *this (is what I mean), this (namely)*. □□□ (*gar*) as used here is a "primary particle; properly assigning a *reason* (used in argument, explanation or intensification; often with other particles): - and, as, because (that), but, even, for indeed, no doubt, seeing, then, therefore, verily, what, why, yet." E-Sword As used by Paul *légomen (we say) en (by) logoo (word)*

Kuriou (of the Lord). According to the Lord's own word, here implies that what he (Paul) “speaks, was either by some tradition from others, or an invention of his own; and that is the ground enough for faith, to which our judgment and reason ought to be captivated (Matthew Poole, 1990). Paul was declaring the mind of the Lord. According to Martin,

Several revelations are made in the verses that follow: (a) the dead will rise and join the Lord prior to the living joining him (v. 15), (b) the Lord's descent will be with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel, and with the trumpet call of God (v. 16), (c) those who were dead and the those living will be caught up together (v. 17), and (d) all believers will be with the Lord forever (v. 17). Paul validated these assertions with an appeal to divine authority (v. 15). Whether the Lord's own word (*en logō kyriou*) was a reference to the teachings of the earthly Jesus or to later revelation, it confirmed the accuracy of what follows. In the statement that initiates v. 15, literally, For this we say to you (cf. NASB), the for indicates that the word of the Lord that follows is the basis for the assurances given in v. 14. This looks forward to the teaching expressed in vv. 15b–17. Paul assured the church that what he was about to say was according to the Lord's own word. It was not human speculation but divine revelation (cf. 4:8). This might have originated as a revelation from the exalted Jesus (either to Paul or to another prophet), but if this is so, the very nature of the event precludes our knowing about it without more background than the apostle provided. And apart from a clear knowledge of the source of the word we cannot know whether the content of vv. 15–17 is a quotation or a summation of the Lord's teaching (Martin, 1995).

This is followed by *ὅτι ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες οἱ περιλειπόμενοι εἰς τὴν παρουσίαν τοῦ κυρίου, οὐ μὴ φθάσωμεν τοὺς κοιμηθέντας (hóti heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi eis teen parousían tou Kuríou ou-meé fthásoomen toús.) koimeethéntas)* translated in the NIV as “we tell you that we who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord, will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep.” The phrase we who are still alive (*heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi*) could imply Paul's hoping to be alive at rapture. Hendriksen and Kistemaker notes that the fact that Paul says “we”, does not necessarily mean that he expected to be among those who would still be living at Christ's return. He says we because right now he, Silas, Timothy, the readers, are among those believers still living on earth. He

immediately modifies this by interpreting it to mean: those who are left (when he comes),” in order to indicate that only God knows whom they may be. Paul knows that the second coming will not take place immediately (II Thess. 2:2); and while he was in Thessalonica, this element in his teaching regarding the last things was not neglected (II Thess. 2:5), (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004).

Paul asserted in v. 15b that we who are alive at the time of the *parousia* will not precede those who have died. The subject “we” is emphatic and is clarified by the clause who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord. A point of considerable interest to those seeking to understand Pauline eschatology is whether or not the fact that Paul used the first person, we, meant that he expected the Lord to return in his lifetime. The assumption has generally been that this was indeed the case. Others find evidence that Paul initially expected the Lord to come during his lifetime but that as the years passed revised his position and accepted the possibility that the Lord’s return might be further in the future than he originally anticipated (Martin, 1995). As cited by Martin Witherington, on the other hand, makes a strong case that Paul believed the end could come at any time but did not presume to predict its timing. When speaking of the end and envisioning himself in relation to it, Paul normally cast himself in the category of the living since he was alive at the time he wrote, but this was a convention, not a prediction (Martin, 1995).

Verse 16 begins with a *hoti* (for) clause, indicating that what follows was presented as verification of the assertion (vv. 14–15) that the dead will participate in the *parousia*, meaning coming. The sequence of events is presented in four steps. First, the Lord will descend, and then the dead will rise (v. 16). Following that the living will be caught up, and finally all believers will be together with the Lord forever (v. 17). The point clearly made is that those who die before the *parousia* will participate in it along with those who are alive when he comes, and both will enjoy the life with the Lord that follows. The two primary statements in v. 16 are the Lord himself will come down and the dead in Christ will rise. The disciples witnessed Jesus’ ascent into the clouds and were told he would return in the same way (Acts 1:9–11; cf. Mark 13:26). Stephen saw the heavens open and Jesus, the Son of Man, standing at the right hand of God (Acts 7:55–56). The Thessalonians demonstrated their faith by eagerly awaiting the coming of Jesus, the Son of God, from heaven (1 Thessalonians 1:3, 10). Eventually

the long-awaited Jesus will descend this time not as a babe but with grand display and heavenly entourage as befits the heavenly Lord himself. He comes with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel and with the trumpet call of God. The three phrases are parallel, each introduced by the preposition $\square v$ (*en* meaning with). The second two statements are joined by “and” (*kai*), which Frame takes as an indication that the latter two phrases explain the first (Martin, 1995). He suggests the translation at a command, namely, at an archangel’s voice and at a trumpet of God. But the presence of the *kai* does not make this certain, and the three events also may be viewed as separate and distinct or as a threefold description of a single occurrence. (Martin, 1995)

The shouted command $\kappa\epsilon\lambda\epsilon\upsilon\sigma\mu\alpha\tau\iota$, *keleusmati* Hendriksen and Kistemaker comment that ($\kappa\epsilon\lambda\epsilon\upsilon\sigma\mu\alpha$, in the New Testament occurring only here, but see Proverbs 30:27 in LXX) is originally the order which an officer shouts to his troops, a hunter to his dog, a charioteer to his horses, or a ship-master to his rovers. In the present connection it is clearly the command of the Lord, as he leaves heaven, for the dead to rise. Note the context: those who have fallen asleep shall not be at disadvantage (verse 15), for with a shout... the Lord himself will descend from heaven, and the dead in Christ will rise... (verse 16). Just as even here and now the voice of the Son of God is life-giving, causing those who are spiritually dead to be quickened (John 5:25), so also when he comes back “all who are in the tombs will hear his voice and will come out (John 5:28). The command, therefore, is definitely his own, proceeding from his lips. It is not a command issued for him, but an order given by him (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004). The shout, the voice, and the trumpet may be different figures for the same event. The language reflects the *theophanic* passages of the Old Testament; Joel 2:1ff.; especially verse 11. The dead in Christ (16); cf. verse 14; 1 Corinthians 15:18; Revelation 14:13. Shall be caught up (17); Gr. *Harpagesómetha*, Latin *rapiemur*, whence the event is sometimes called the ‘rapture’ or snatching away of the saints. In the clouds (17); cf. Daniel 7:13; Mark. 13:26; 14:62; revelation 1:7. To meet the Lord (17); Greek *eis apánteessin tou Kuríou*. When a dignitary paid an official visit or *parousia* to a city in Hellenistic times, the action of the leading citizens in going out to meet him and escorting him on the final stage of his journey was called *apánteesis*; it is similarly used in Mathew 25:6; Acts 28:15. So the Lord is pictured as escorted to the earth by his people- those newly raised from death and those

who have remained alive. And so shall we ever be with the Lord (17); the climax of blessedness. But no man knows the times and the seasons (v. 1). (M.A Davidson)

The expression to meet (εἰς ἀπάντησιν, *eis apanthsin*) was used in connection with an official welcome accorded to a newly arrived dignitary. No doubt the welcoming idea is also included in the expression as used in 1 Thessalonians 4:17. That all believers, the raised as well as (and together) changed, shall ascend to meet the Lord in the air is clearly taught here (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004).

All believers shall be with the Lord never to be separated from him. Paul stated emphatically that at the *parousia* the living will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep. This may indicate that the church feared that the dead would be raised at some time after the *parousia* and so miss the glories of that day. But it is far from certain that this was the problem in the church. It seems safer to find the emphasis in Paul's words on his statement of the problem in v. 14 and his climactic statement in v. 17. In these verses the emphasis does not seem to fall on the sequence of the participation of the living and the dead but on the understanding that the dead will in fact participate in the *parousia*. This need not mean that Paul previously had not taught this in Thessalonica. The problem may well have been the difficulty of appropriating the doctrine of the resurrection into the way that enabled these Gentile believers to manage the trauma of death. Paul wanted to spare believers the sorrow of hopeless loss so common to the pagan world. He did so by reiterating truths in traditional language and applying them to immediate needs (Martin, 1995). Some of the Thessalonian Christians may have died shortly after receiving the gospel. Yet the letter was written only a few months after the initial evangelization of the city.... The short time between the evangelization of the city and the writing of this letter would militate against the possibility of multiple deaths in the congregation in the interim. Although the letter refers to persecutions, there is no reference to deaths in Christ's service. Considering the extremes to which Paul went to affirm the faith of the church, failure on his part to highlight faithfulness to the point of death seems incredible. The references to those who have fallen asleep are references to all the faithful who had died, not specifically Thessalonian Christians who had died. (Martin, 1995). A loud command translates a single noun used only here in the New Testament. It was relatively common in nonbiblical Greek, and in general it

indicates an order or a signal given to subordinates. Neither the origin nor the nature of this particular command is clear. The command could be issued from Jesus to the dead to arise (cf. John 5:28–29), from Jesus to his entourage to proceed (cf. 2 Thessalonians 1:7), or from the archangel as either a cry of announcement (like the trumpet, cf. Revelation 1:10) or an order to the heavenly host. The phrase ἐν φωνῇ ἀρχαγγέλου (*en fooneé archangéλου*) with the voice of the archangel connotes the involvement of the heavenly host. Mark also recorded that Jesus will come with the holy angels (Mark 8:38) and that he will send them to gather his elect from the four winds (13:26–27). The reference to an archangel implies a ranking of heavenly beings that was a common feature of Hellenistic Judaism. Although New Testament authors did not involve themselves in the elaborate naming and ranking of the heavenly host in general, the New Testament does refer twice to archangels (here and Jude 9) and names two angels. Michael is called an archangel (Jude 9; cf. Daniel 10:13; 12:1), and Gabriel is an angel who stands in the presence of God (Luke 1:19). Implied with the use of the term archangel is both status and the existence (if not the presence) of subordinates. The Lord is not alone but is accompanied by an angelic entourage. The archangel functions either as the herald proclaiming remarkable news the arrival of the Lord or calls the angelic army to advance with the Lord. (D. Michael Martin) 97 The term archangel or chief angel occurs only here and in Jude 9. In the later passage Michael is the archangel. It is possible that Michael is the only archangel or one of the archangels.

The Lord's descent is also with the trumpet call of God. A trumpet call was used for a variety of purposes in the ancient orient but was not much used as a musical instrument; its main task was to give signals. It could herald a great event or issue a warning to the people (1 Samuel 13:3; Jeremiah 4:5). It was often used in military settings (Josh 6:4–5; Judges 6:34; Nehemiah 4:19–20; cf. 1 Corinthians 14:8). It signaled the Hebrews' encounter with Yahweh at Sinai (Exodus 19:16, 19) and was used as part of the pageantry at religious festivals (Numbers 10:10; Leviticus 23:24; 25:8; Psalms 81:3; cf. Mathew 6:2). Finally, both Jewish and Christian images of God's arrival at the end to gather his people, execute judgment, and establish his kingdom include the announcement of his arrival with the trumpet (Isaiah 27:13; Zechariah 9:14; Ezra 6:23; *Apoc. Mos.* 22; Revelation 8:2–12; 9:1, 13; 11:15). Used in conjunction the voice of the archangel and the shout of command

and the trumpet depict a grand fanfare. No one will be able to miss the event. No one will fail to realize that something remarkable is about to occur (Martin, 1997).

At the command, the voice, and the trumpet, the dead in Christ will rise. There is no mention of non-Christian dead in these verses (cf. 2:16; 2 Thessalonians 1:6–10). Likewise there is no discussion of the resurrection body or of the manner in which the living are translated (cf. 1 Corinthians 15:35–54). Paul was presenting information to comfort a church grieving like those who had no hope. So that which claimed all his attention was the fact that the resurrected Christian dead will join with the Christian living at the parousia and together they will share the presence of the Lord on that day and forever. First is the final word of v. 16. After that (*epeita*), the first word of v. 17, does not have a strong temporal sense. It indicates a sequence of events, but almost immediately the two events are blended into a single occurrence as the resurrected dead join the living and both are caught up ... to meet the Lord (Martin, 1995).

4:17 ἀρπάζω fut. ἀρπάσω (*arpaso*); ἤρπασα (*arpasa*) is used “as forcibly taking someone or something *snatch, seize, take away* (John 6.15); (2) as the action of thieves and wild beasts *steal, carry off, drag away* (John 10.12); (3) of seed already sown *carry off, snatch away* (Mathew 13.19); (4) of an ecstatic vision or experience *catch up or away* (2C 12.2); (5) ἄ. in 11.12 has two possible meanings: (a) *seize on eagerly, appropriate* (the kingdom); (b) *attack and seize* (the kingdom) as a violent or forcible person would do; since ἄ. is used with βιάζεται (*suffer violently, be treated violently*) and βιασταί (*violent people*), the second is preferable (Bibleworks) The verb caught up (*harpazō*) is the same one found in Acts 8:39 when the Spirit suddenly took Philip away and when Paul was caught up to the third heaven (2 Corinthian 12:2–4). The subject we is modified by who are still alive and are left (the identical clause in v. 15). Will be caught up is modified by three phrases: together with them (i.e., the resurrected saints), in the clouds, and to meet the Lord in the air. The first phrase, together with them (*hama sun autois*), refers to those Christians who have been resurrected. Though *hama* (at the same time) used with *sun* (with) seems redundant, in this context the force of the preposition *sun* is strengthened by the preceding *hama*. This emphasis on the unity of the event for the living and the dead stresses two points. First, the living have no advantage over the dead in the end. Both groups will experience reunion with the Lord together. Second, the dead and

the living will themselves be reunited a reunion that will know no end. For we will be with the Lord forever. Martin Note that the latin verb *rapio* was used to translate harpaz, and from this derives the use of English term “rapture” for the event described in vv. 16-17.(D. Michael Martin) 98 Followers Christ “shall be caught up, the suddenness, the swiftness, and the divine character of the power which is operative in this being snatched up are here emphasized. (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004) Together all believers will be caught up in the clouds.

What happens after believers meet the Lord in the air? The conclusion of the passage, we will be with the Lord forever (v. 17), speaks to believers’ eternal state but leaps over any end-time events between parousia and eternal state. Considering Paul’s purpose of comforting believers regarding the eternal state of the dead in Christ, v. 17 provides an appropriate conclusion to the narrative. But for those interested in end-time events this conclusion seems abrupt and leaves much unsaid. The events of vv. 16–17, for instance, are not placed in a larger temporal context. Other events associated with the end, such as a period of tribulation, the judging of humanity, or a millennial reign, are not mentioned. The state of the dead who rise to meet the lord is not discussed (cf.1Corinthians 15:35–49; 2Corinthians 5:1–9), nor is the transformation of the living (cf. 1 Corinthia 15:50–58) (Martin, 1995).

The raised and the changed are caught up together in clouds to meet the Lord in the air. The event described in vv. 16–17, commonly termed the rapture, holds a prominent place in all eschatological schemes. But it is not understood in the same way in all of them. Postmillennial and amillennial perspectives generally understand the rapture as a part of the day of the Lord when Jesus will return to gather his people to him and execute judgment on all (cf. 5:1–11). This event is variously termed the coming (*parousia*), the revelation (*apokalypsis*), or the appearance (*epiphaneia*) of the Lord. Also in some forms of premillennialism it is believed that the church will remain on the earth until the final judgment (including a period of severe tribulation near the very end). For these the coming of the Lord, the rapture of the church, and the final judgment are all facets of a single event at the end of time (Martin, 1995). In some premillennial schemes, however, the rapture is separated from the day of the Lord by the great tribulation, a seven-year period of intense, unbridled evil. Adherents to this perspective argue that the church will not remain on the earth during this

time of the tribulation. Rather, the Lord will remove (or rapture) his followers either at the beginning of the tribulation or at its midpoint. Such a scheme separates the rapture from the *parousia* by several years.

Although we cannot settle such far-reaching matters in this context, we must note that our present passage does not seem to present the event depicted in vv. 16–17 as one preceding and separate from the *parousia*, the day of the Lord (cf. 5:4–9). First, in v. 15 Paul explicitly termed the event he was describing the coming (*parousia*) of the Lord and linked the same term with final judgment (2 Thessalonians 2:8; cf. 1 Thessalonians 2:19). Since Paul did not predict two *parousias*, then the one event must encompass both the gathering of the church and final judgment. Second, v. 17 does not require the removal of the church from the world. It is in fact open-ended, describing nothing beyond the gathering of the church other than the fact of continuing in the presence of the Lord.

4:18 Paul concludes the text with *Ὡστε παρακαλεῖτε ἀλλήλους ἐν τοῖς λόγοις τούτοις* (*Hooste parakaleite alleélous en toís lógois touútois*, meaning ‘therefore encourage each other with these words’). The term *parakaleite* is from the term *παρακαλέω* (*parakaleō*) *par-ak-al-eh'-o* meaning *to call near*, that is, *invite, invoke* (by *imploration, hortation* or *consolation*): - beseech, call for, (be of good) comfort, desire, (give) exhort (-ation), intreat, pray. *Το παρακαλεῖτε* (comfort) one another with these *lógois* (words) *this is the plural of logos logos* (word) which is something *said* (including the *thought*); by implication a *topic* (subject of discourse), also *reasoning* (the mental faculty) or *motive*; by extension a *computation*; specifically (with the article in John) the *Divine Expression* (that is, *Christ*): - account, cause, communication, X concerning, doctrine, fame, X have to do, intent, matter, mouth, preaching, question, reason, + reckon, remove, say (-ing), shew, X speaker, speech, talk, thing, tidings, treatise, utterance, word, work. (E-Sword)

Finally, the command to encourage each other (v. 18) could anticipate future need as easily as it could be an attempt to meet a current need. In other words vv. 13–18 may well contain admonitions appropriate to any congregation rather than being proof of a problem particular to the church at Thessalonica. The problem is the grief resulting from a death (v.13). The word of encouragement is that the Lord will reunite the living and the dead at his return (vv.14, 17). Celebrating that reunion required recounting a depiction of the *parousia* (vv.16–17). A summary description of the *parousia*

(coming) is given in vv. 16–17. Its brevity is evident. Detail is lacking. Also the sequence of events is truncated. Believers are caught up ... to meet the Lord in the air, but what happens to them after that? The modern reader (and perhaps the ancient one as well) is left wondering what comes between the gathering of the saints at the beginning of the parousia and living forever in his presence.(E-Sword).. Christians should not be grieving deaths in their community without hope. In the Gentile culture, while varied in its beliefs on the afterlife, not only balked at bodily resurrection but also lacked hope for any kind of meaningful and lasting reunion once a friend or family member died. If this life is all one has, its end in death produces considerable grief. Not so for followers of Jesus, Paul says. This is not to say that any grieving is inappropriate, for Jesus provides the example (John 11:35). Nevertheless, that grief should not have the final word. Today just like during the time of Apostle Paul, many in the Church are confused regarding the relative timing of the *parousia* and the resurrection. Hence, as Christian's hope should be on what the Scripture says about the end time. Paul's encouragement on the coming of Christ is important because it speaks to the second coming of Christ and sheds a little bit of light on what forever will be like (v.17). If one believes Scripture to be true, and Jesus Christ did die only to rise again (4.14), then there is a (*elpida*) hope, for mankind, until the day of Christ's return to which those who believe will be with him forever and always (4.17). Hence, men of all ages, including the postmodern men, especially believers, must be prepared to be raptured with him.

Findings

Analysis of the nature postmodern society and the pericope used for this study shows that:

1. The postmodern society is dominated by anti-biblical ideas like rejection of absolute truth which threatens the superiority of biblical truths, including rapture.
2. Paul's eschatological discourse in 1Thessalonians 4:15-18 is a force to be reckoned with as it is predicated on the teachings of Jesus.
3. Paul's eschatological discourse was necessitated by the need to encourage the Thessalonian believers who were hopeless about dead saints (Hazen, 2022).

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4. Thessalonian believers were eagerly waiting for the Lord's coming (*parousia*, 1 Thessalonians 1:3, 10)
 5. The *parousia* has its benefits for the Thessalonian believers and the postmodern believers.
 6. The coming of the Lord is eminent.

Discussion

The introduction of this paper calls attention to the dangers of postmodernism like rejection of absolute truth that constitute threats to Christian faith and all its tenets, including rapture. Corroborating this, in a study carried out by Ayomide & Alabi, (2021), some negative traits of postmodern Christians towards rapture were identified and these include: loss of focus about rapture, carefree attitudes towards rapture and adulterating God's Word to fulfill selfish interest. The two scholars concluded that these negative traits imply that postmodern believers' negative attitudes towards rapture are counter-productive and can therefore never groom believers to be rapture-ready (Ayomide & Alabi, 2021). Thus, Paul's eschatological teachings in 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18 is highly needed to prepare the postmodern believers for rapture.

Conclusion

Through Paul's Eschatological Discourse in 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18 analysed thus far, the following inferences for application to the postmodern church can be drawn:

1. Paul's eschatological discourse in the pericope under analysis is a force to be reckoned with as it is predicated on the Lord's own word or revelation, not on human speculation (1 Thessalonians 4:14). As such, postmodern Christians should receive it as the gospel truth allowing it to guide their preparation for the Lord's *parousia*.
2. The need to encourage the Thessalonian believers who were hopeless about dead saints necessitated the eschatological discourse. As Paul counseled the Thessalonian believers not to mourn like unbelievers, the present day believers should stop mourning over those who died in the Lord as they are with the Lord in a much better place right now enjoying freedom from pain, worry, disease and most essentially, sin! (Hazen, 2022).

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3. It is also apparent that these Thessalonian believers strongly believed in the *parousia*, the coming of the Lord, as they demonstrated their faith by eagerly awaiting this glorious event (1Thessalonians 1:3, 10). Paul emphasized that the Lord's *parousia* will lead to a reunion between the dead and the living saints.
 4. This inestimable event also has two more merits: a) it will help postmodern believers to keep a proper perspective on this life and the one to come (Hazen, 2022). b) Remembering that the Rapture is fast approaching also encourages postmodern believers to live a holy life, knowing that the trumpet could sound at any moment (Hazen, 2022).
 5. Predicating on the expression: "any moment now" return of the Lord also encourages a sense of concern for those outside the fold. It creates a sense of urgency to share the love Christ with others and support missions thereby expanding the coast of the Kingdom of God (Hazen, 2022).
 6. Lastly, the postmodern church must note that Rapture, *parousia* or the Lord's coming could be the next event on God's prophetic calendar. As such, the present church should be wise to keep eyes and ears open as it will happen when least expected.

Recommendations

In order to enhance Christians of postmodern age to be really rapture-ready, certain steps must be taken. What are these steps in question?

1. Postmodern Christians must be involved in an in-depth study of God's Word; especially, in regards to rapture.
2. Postmodern Christians must also enroll in the school of the Holy Spirit for divine instructions, understanding and guidance on rapture;
3. Postmodern Christians must equally live a consistent biblical life so as to be rapture-ready.
4. Regular self-examination in the light of the gospel is highly necessary.
5. Uncompromising obedience to God's Word should not be handled with levity.
6. Sharing the gospel of Christ with unbelievers must be given priority.
7. Postmodern Christians must regard the Bible as the final authority regardless of the negative features of the postmodern society in which they exist.

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E-Sword: The Sword of the Lord with an Electronic Edge

What are the Dangers of Postmodernism?

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**Comparative Analysis of United Nations'
Roles in Gulf Crisis (1990-1991) and
Ukraine-Russian Conflict (2022-2025)**

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Abstract

In Gulf Crisis, the Middle East was a region split by multitude of different national interests and personal interests of various ideological and hegemonic ruling classes. On the other hand, the Russian-Ukraine conflict was degenerating into deeper and dangerous dimensions in defence of national interest, and UN is helpless to use resolutions to end the conflict. The objective of this study is to examine the factors that limits UN's application of force to end the conflict in Ukraine as in Gulf Crisis. The UN rejected clumsy reasons of annexation of Kuwait sovereignty, but in 2014 Russia annexed Crimea and subsequently took over four other regions in 2022. The research employed qualitative contents analysis method of secondary data using force theory as its framework. The study noted that historical grievances were remote causes of Russian-Ukrainian Conflict. While the quest for expansion and lack of love on both side of Iraq and America led to the Gulf conflicts. The finding shows that UN is helpless with veto power states. The research concludes that Russian possession of veto has made UN subject of debate in realization of

world peace. The study recommends that UN should mandate US to vacate its buffer Zone out of Ukraine; and should negotiate a win – win relations with Ukraine and Russian to avoid another World War.

Keywords: Annexation, Gulf Crisis, Ukraine-Russia Conflict, United Nations, National Interest, Expansion, Historical Grievances

Introduction

The failure of League of Nations formed in 1919 to maintain global peace led to the formation of United Nations Organization (UNO) after World War II at San Francisco, United States of America in October 24th 1945 (Hiscock, 1977: 38). The functions and powers of the League of Nations were formally transferred to United Nations Organization and the League of Nations voted itself out of existence. The UNO was established as an instrument of global peace to prevent further carnage, destruction of human lives due to wars and to protect independent territorial sovereign states from external threat, military aggression and political annexation of independent nations. The charter was officially signed by 51 member states of the world in attendant. Article 1 (1) of the UN Charter stated that the organization shall maintain international peace and security; and it shall take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threat to peace and for the suppression of acts of aggression or breaches of peace; and to bring about peaceful means and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment and settlement of international disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace (Kelly,.2002:98). President Harry S. Truman said in the inaugural meeting of UNO in 1945: “We have created a great instrument for peace, security and human progress in the world. The world must now use it and the successful use of this instrument requires united will and determination” (Hiscock, 1977: 40).

In 1991, United Nations was able to maintain its Charter obligations in the Gulf Crisis after Iraqi annexed Kuwaiti territory in 1990 as its nineteenth province. The UN coalition of military alliance forced Iraq to surrender unconditionally and Kuwait regained its territory. Altogether, the philosophy behind the institution – United Nations was achieved in the Gulf crisis, but paradoxically, it could not control annexation Crimea on 27th February, 2014 and other four Ukrainian cities of Donetsk, Zaporizhia, Luhansk and Kherson regions, between August to November, 2022. The UN failed to activate its charter against Russia. The question is what went

wrong with UN in ensuring world peace for mutual inter dependence of Nations in line with its charter? Similarly, the organization was unable to control smaller conflicts throughout the world such as genocides in Czech Republics, Kosovo, Rwanda, Burundi, Somalia, Sudan and recently Israel/Palestine Crisis which has dishonoured all manner of United Nations (Washington Post, 2025).

On Russian invasion of Ukraine, Marco Rubio the US Secretary of State was quoted thus: “We have to make a determination about whether this is an endeavour that we want to continue to be involved in or if it is time to sort of focus on some other issues that are equally if not more important in some cases” (Edward, 2025). To this, the United Nations seems to have lost its muzzle to tackle Russia militarily. There are many questions to answer in relation to the organization performances against Iraq over annexation of Kuwaiti territory in 1990. For example, Article 33 paragraph 1 of the charter stated that – “Parties to any disputes which is likely to endanger the maintenance of international peace and security shall first of all seek a solution through negotiation, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, judicial, settlement, resort to regional agencies or arrangement or other peaceful means of their own choices” (Rumki, 2004:26). The Charter provides power to the permanent members of UN Security Council – Britain, Russia, China, France and United States of America to act militarily against any recalcitrant and transgressing states. Each five permanent members has a power of ‘Veto’, which means ‘No’ vote among the big five means against to any action – matter suspended. The UN as a body has no outstanding army as an international organization, but members usually contribute military forces against a deviant state.

Charles Darwin, in his book, *Origin of Species*, observed that in the future an endless number of the lower races will be eliminated by the higher civilized races throughout the world (Awake Magazine, 1998). He summed it up to the struggle for existence and survival of the fittest. Human Rights declaration, according to Eleanor Roosevelt, former United States of America first lady on 10th December, 1948 described the document as - Long Job Finished (Awake Magazine, 1998). Reason, because in 1947 deep disagreement mired the 18-member commission in an endless dispute, the Chinese delegates felt that the document should include philosophy of Confucius; United States Championed Bill of Rights while Soviets delegates wanted to include the ideas of Karl Marx. Kofi Annan the UN Secretary

General while addressing world leaders on Gulf Crisis said: “Just as there is no need to rewrite the Bible or the Koran, there is no need to adjust the declaration. What needs to be adjusted is not the text of the universal declaration, but the behaviour of its discipline” (Awake Magazine, 1998: 2).

Statement of the Problem

The Iraqi invasion of Kuwait in 1990 and its aftermath was overwhelming, but Russian invasion of Ukraine territories made UN toothless. In Iraq, the unconditional withdrawal expired on January, 15 1991 the Allied Forces led by United States launched air and land attacks, in less than three months the result was disgraceful surrender by Iraq. However, Vladimir Putin annexed Crimea under Ukraine sovereignty in 2014 and UN muzzle was relaxed, thereby setting dangerous precedence to international community. The behaviour of Russia is centrifugal to Article 1 of UN Charter and yet the UN and USA are helpless in arresting the developmental trends in Ukraine. President Trump said after his impromptu meeting with President Volodymyr Zelenskyy at Vatican City inauguration of Pope Leo XIV: “On Russian escalating bombardment of Ukraine, it makes me think that maybe Vladimir Putin doesn’t want to end the war, he’s tapping me along and has to be dealt with differently” (Tim & Robert, 2025). Dealing Putin differently might not be with force because both states possess nuclear power and may wish to avoid global calamity. The Russian president demanded international recognition of Crimea as a state distinct from Ukraine territory (Wall Street Journal 2025). The United States of America, and the United Nations are on peace negotiation not war against Russia. Russia is a member of the Security Council and she has a power of veto to dangle on decisions of the UN General Assembly resolutions. In Gulf Crisis, UN members contributed troops against Iraq and less than three months in 1991 Iraq surrendered. Regrettably none have contributed troop against Russia annexation of Ukraine. The context of this research is that United Nations’ response to the Gulf Crisis was marked by fiat and decisive action, including immediate authorization of military deployment to liberate Kuwait. On the contrary, the UN’s response to the Ukraine–Russia conflicts have been sluggish and limited making the UN subject of debate on its effectiveness to maintain world peace.

Objective of the Research

1. To examine the UN responses to the Gulf Crisis (1990-1991) conflict in relation to what has been the UN's response to Ukraine–Russia (2022 - 2025) conflicts, outcome and challenges.
2. To search for differences and similarities between the UN's roles in these two conflicts, and implications of these differences to the effectiveness of the UN as a global peace institution.

Research Questions

1. How did the UN respond to the Gulf Crisis, and Ukraine-Russia conflict outcomes/challenges?
2. What are the key differences and similarities between UN's roles in the two conflicts and implications in combating future conflicts?

Literature Review

The Iraqi Kuwaiti Crisis marked a turning point on UN. It was an interesting episode in global history of international community, coincidentally the Ukraine – Russia conflicts has been subject of debate on UN effectiveness. The literature seeks to analyze concepts, comments, and experts' views emanating from UN roles in both conflicts.

Conflict

Conflict exists when people pursue different interests, opinion, ideology, and values. It exists when the goals of different participants are inherently incompatible; a behaviour which occurs when two or more parties are in opposition or in a battle as a result of perceived relative deprivation. The Marxist scholars see conflict from economic domination and deprivation by one social group against another. The Marxist agree that the desire to control resources has influence on the type of political, economic and socio structure put in place in every society. Such structure is characterized by domination of governing or the ruling class which often makes conflict inevitable. In general, conflict can be defined as a disagreement between two or more parties or groups who perceived threat to their needs, interests, aspirations and wants. Key words in the above definitions are disagreement, parties are involved, and there are threats, interests, needs, aspirations, ideology and wants as the propelling forces in conflict situation (Obizulike-Osufia 2013).

Obizulike-Osufia (2013) identified conflict in three levels:

1. **Blips:** Conflict at blips level is a situation when an incidence happened at first time and much are not at stake. Under this level of analysis, anger is mild but there may be no continued pattern of relationship.
2. **Clashes:** In clashes conflict, contradictions are not happening for the first time. The parties to clashes are aggrieved because of repetitive negative behaviour of one of the parties to the dispute. This level of conflict may lead to tension, anger, and retaliatory measures as in the case of Ukraine - Russian conflict.
3. **Crisis:** In this level, the issue has escalated and become violent. At domestic level, the national government has to suppress the uprising using the instrument of coercion at their disposal depending on the magnitude of the crisis. Vulnerable persons such as women, children, elderly and physically challenged groups are emotionally endangered by this level of conflict.

Collective Security

The issue of collective security has been a paramount concern to the UN since its inception. Evan Luards, (1996) sees collective security as depending on willingness of all states to rally round to defend any other state that is attacked. Luards, (1996) posit that to make the system work, government must take no account of loyalties, national or ideological nor relate the costs to be borne by taking part in an action or national benefits to be gained.

Analysis and Critique

The issue of collective security in line with Article 1 of UN Charter implementation is often problematic because the charter emphasis on maintenance of international peace and security; yet the organization endorses use of force against Iraq to effect removal of threat to peace and aggression in Kuwait. Luards, (1996) idea that states should not count the cost of participating in international peace as suggested was not conceivable because national interest is a driving force in international relations. For instance, USA led Allied Forces during the Gulf Conflicts as a contribution for restoration of peace in the Gulf region. If American gesture was not for interest, why not sponsor budgets for UN against Russia invasion of Ukraine sovereignty. In compliance of the rules of Article 1, some peace proposals of Iraq friends were rejected by United States and Great Britain

based on interest. Even three points Peace proposals by Iran, the Iraqi former foe were based on interest:

- a. First, regional resolution of the conflict among the Arab nations,
- b. Settlement of Palestine crisis, and
- c. Dropping of economic sanctions once majority of Iraqi forces left Kuwait (Iwobi, 1991: 4).

These were all rejected. American Defence Secretary Dick Cheney put their rejection thus: “We are not interested in a promise or a pledge, our purpose is to get Iraq out of Kuwait. The U.S. does not want Iraq to proclaim victory on ideological or any other ground that may undermine the United Nations Security Council” (African Concord Magazine 1991:4). The decision of America to lead the war against Iraq through the instrumentality of UN Charter was unmistakable, the threat to oil supplies should Iraqi friend plan proposals happen. The USA would not like a situation where military adventure such as that of Iraq would redesign the Middle East and paralyze the global economy. Times International Magazine (1990: 35 -36) noted: the last UN Resolution 678 was passed on November, 29 1990, the USA had already gotten permission for development of American troops on Saudi Arabia soil. The fallout - Italy and Soviet Union at that time decided to declare their non – involvement of their troops in the battle because enough opportunities existed at that point for negotiation which the USA and Great Britain refused to adopt.

Crimea in Ukraine was annexed since 2014, and subsequently four major Ukrainian cities were overrun in 2022 by Russian forces, yet United Nations Security Council and United States of America were helpless to apply force even when sanctions against Russia could not work. Instead, Putin sent his ally Kiril Dmitriev a senior Russian official to hold talk with Steve Witkoff a close ally of Trump to end the conflict in Ukraine (Washington Post, April 2 2025). Again, Marco Rubio U.S Secretary of States was in NATO meeting at its headquarters over the conflict in Ukraine and worked out with the following remark: “President Trump is against NATO that does not have capability that it needs to fulfill the obligations that the treaty imposes upon each and every member state” (New York Times April 11, 2025). But the UN in a space of August 2 to November 29th 1990 passed twelve resolutions over the annexation of Kuwait by Iraq. The last Resolution was UN Security Council Resolution 678 which mandated UN Secretary General Javier Perez de Culler to take inventory, custody of Kuwaiti population register which

covers up to August 1, 1990, a day before invasion. Iraq was not given reasonably space for negotiation before UN constituted forces began attacking Iraq. Italy felt non-involvement of their troops, because there are opportunities for negotiation which USA and Great Britain refused to adopt.

Theoretical Analysis

Military conflict, apart from war, encompasses armed intervention, armed incident, military coup, military blockage, and perhaps demonstration of power among other things. In line with force theory of analysis, Carl von Clausewitz (1780–1831), Prussian military General noted that; “war is distinguished by the very close relationship between politics, nation and war, the priority of politics towards war, and treating war (violence) as a political tool”. Nye, (2004: 49) explores the concepts of soft power and hard power in international relations in relation to achievement of national interest. The dynamics of Nye’s application of power is useful for understanding force theory. The theory enumerated that soft power refers to ability to achieve goals through the use of influence or attraction. While hard power relied mostly on the use of coercion and application of force as deterrence. Mearsheimer, (2019: 101) talked about the use of force in international relations where he outlined that state acquires power to limit the power of other states, which often times lead to war.

Carl Clausewitz (1832) force theory was adopted for the purposes of this study. Carl Von Clausewitz noted on his force theory that “War is the continuation of policy with other means”. In other words, every era has its wars that is why war over the last decades has gradually and intangibly changed its character. Alvin & Heidi (1980: 45) wrote about the dimension of a modern war. This couple examine the aspects of modern war. The main thesis of their publication “War and anti-war” is that there are three civilization waves, which relate directly to all three waves of war. The first one mentioned by the authors is the agrarian wave, the second is called industrial and the third-modern (post-industrial). The symbols of each are respectively: a hoe, an assembly belt and a computer, which represent those waves of wars. The wars of the so called third wave, are the wars of constantly forming post-Cold-War international order through application and use of force. In other words, Force becomes inevitable when other means of conflict resolution have failed to achieve the desired goals.

Gaps in Literature

There are myriads of roles on UN Peacekeeping force and conflicts resolution that has been carried out by UN in Liberia, Kosovo, Cyprus and numerous other countries. However, Gulf Crisis 1990-1991 and Ukraine Russia conflicts explores how the UN's approach to peace-keeping has changed over time. The Ukraine- Russia conflicts has raised debates about UN inability to muzzle its subjects through the Security Council against Russia. The study examines comparative challenges of enforcement in the context of veto power state.

Methodology

The research design for this study is descriptive through qualitative contents analysis of the roles of UN in crisis resolution especially as it concerns Gulf Crisis of 1990–1991 and Ukraine–Russia conflict (2022–2025). The study interrogated statistical differences and similarities of UN's interventions and outcomes through comparative perusal of the two conflicts. The data to this research is collected through systematic literature reviews (SLR) of secondary data regarding the UN roles in both conflicts. The data was analyzed through thematic contents of events as it occurred in the two conflicts respectively.

UN and Gulf Crisis

The UN passed twelve resolutions between August 2, 1990 Iraq invasion of Kuwait and January 15, 1991 deadline given to Iraq to withdraw her troops from Kuwait territories (Aja, 1999: 222-225).

- a. In August 2, 1990, UN Security Council (UNSC) resolution 660 was passed condemning Iraq invasion of Kuwait. The vote was 14 against 0, with Yemen abstaining, sponsored by Canada, Cote de Ivorie, Ethiopia, Finland, France, Malaysia, United Kingdom and USA.
- b. UNSC, Resolution 661 (1990) called all countries to stop importing all commodities and products from Iraq and Kuwait including exportations to both countries. Medical supplies and humanitarian export of food stuff were exempted. The resolution was passed by 13 against 0, Cuba and Yemen abstaining.
- c. In August 9, UNSC Resolution 662 was passed. The resolution declared annexation of Kuwait as 19th province of Iraq illegal. The UN advised all nations to refrain from indirect recognition of annexation.

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- d. UNSC, Resolution 664 was adopted on August 18, 1990 which demanded that Iraq should permit foreign nationals to leave Kuwait and Iraq. The resolution was passed when Saddam Hussein declared that citizens of other countries are not permitted to leave. The resolution was unanimous vote, reaffirms UNSC Resolution 662.
 - e. UNSC, Resolution 665 was issued on August 25, 1990 which authorized member states cooperating with government of Kuwait to use measures commensurate with specific circumstances to ensure that sanctions against Iraq was implemented. The resolution was adopted by 13 against 0, Cuba and Yemen abstaining. Co-sponsored by Canada, Cote de Ivorie, Finland, United Kingdom, USA and Zaire.
 - f. UNSC, Resolution 666, 667, and 669 were passed on September, 13, 16 and 24 respectively in 1990. Resolution 666 was voted to establish procedure for determining the humanitarian needs for food supplies to civilian populations in Kuwait and Iraq due to suffering from trade embargo. Resolution 667 was adopted condemning Iraq violation of diplomatic premises in Kuwait and abduction of diplomatic personnel and other foreign nationals. While resolution 669 was adopted for UN to examine request for assistance and aid to Kuwait under Article 50 of the UN Charter and to make recommendations concerning action.
 - g. UNSC, Resolution 670 was adopted on September 25, 1990 to impose air transport embargo against Iraq. The resolution required that each member state to take necessary action to ensure aircraft registered in its territory comply with the UN economic sanction against Iraq.
 - h. UNSC, Resolution 674 was adopted on October 22, 1990 calling all states to collect evidences of Iraq human right abuses in Kuwait and financial losses caused by invasion. The resolution reminded Iraq that under international law, it is responsible for any loss, damage or injury of Kuwaiti's and foreign nationals as a result of occupation of Kuwait.
 - i. UNSC, Resolution 676 was passed on November 28, 1990 which condemned Iraq attempt to alter the demographic composition of the population of Kuwait, history and civil records as maintained by legitimate government of Kuwait. The resolution mandated the then UN General Secretary Javier Perez de Culler to take inventory of Kuwait population register which covers up to August 1, 1990, a day before invasion.

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- j. UNSC, Resolution 678 was the final resolution against Iraq invasion. It was adopted on November 29, 1990 with 12 votes against 2 with China abstaining. The resolution stated that unless Iraq fully complies by January 15th January 1991 deadline unconditionally, the UN members might use all necessary means to restore international peace and security in the Gulf state.

Aja (1999) maintained that on January 16, 1991 the UN began operations against Iraq. First, Iraq responded by firing some shots of Scud- missiles against Israel as a counter measure to escalate the crisis; but US cautioned Israel to use anti – nuclear mask instead of revenge. The UN left enforcement of the resolutions to countries that contributed troops. So, USA which has largest troops to the coalition of forces took the lead and timings, even decided when Iraq was weak enough for cease-fire. Iraq only fired some harmless far-sighted shots against the Allied Forces. On 27th February 1991, Iraq surrendered and the US – led coalition forces suspended the military action against Iraq (Iwobi, 1991).

UN's Response to Ukraine–Russia Conflicts, and the Challenges

- a. In 2022, the General Assembly adopted a resolution condemning Russia attempted annexation of four Ukraine cities – Donetsk, Kherson, Luhansk and Zaporizhzhia. The resolution was sustained by 143 votes, 5 against and 35 absented.
- b. The UN set up high level human rights monitoring group to collate evidences of human rights violations and abuses in Ukraine for accountability, and
- c. The General Assembly of UN approved Commission to investigate war crime in Ukraine with documented evidences of Russian war crimes, torture, rape and deportation of children to Russia.

Challenges

UN responses to investigate Russia action and to take decisive action was limited by Russian veto power in UN Security Council. Daniel (2025) Wall Street Journal (WSJ), reported that NATO troops carried out drills in February 2025 from Ukraine border to test a quick reaction force over increasing dimensions of Russian attacks. The NATO's military muscle was unusual because European nations carried out the exercise without USA. But US President, Donald Trump said a lot of work had to be done ahead of

his planned talk with Russian leader in terms of ending the conflict in Ukraine. The conflict has decimated Ukrainian environment, causing great floods, wildfires and pollutions. The New York Times (4th April 2025), reported execution of prisoners of war near Novoivanovka in Kursk regions of Russia. New York Times also reported on (5th April 2025), that Zelensky home town Kryvyi Rih was attacked, 16 people were killed by Russian drones. The Magazine noted that the attack targeted Western military instructors in Ukraine. Nineteen were killed on 7th April 2025 in central Kyiv while at Sumy northeastern Ukraine thirty – two people were killed on 12th April 2025, New York Times 13th April 2025 reported.

This research discovered that liberalism policies of Mikhail Gorbachev has completely vanished from Russian policy. Vladimir Putin is determined to superintend its former empires. Georgi & Lytvynenko (2025) WSJ reported that Russian Foreign Minister Sergei Lavrov demanded international recognition of Russian control over Crimea and four other Ukrainian regions. The Russian president, Vladimir Putin had in 2024 rejected an immediate cease – fire with Ukraine, accusing USA as acting on the interest of Ukraine. Example, New York Times (30th March, 2025) reported untold stories of American hidden roles in Ukraine against Russian invading armies. According to the report, the secret partnership was based out of U.S military garrison command in Wiesbaden, Germany. The Magazine noted that the command is guiding big picture battle strategy and precision targeting information down to soldiers in the field.

Key Differences and Similarities on UN's Roles

Differences:

- a. The UN's response to Gulf Crisis was marked by quick resolutions. There was deadline to unconditionally withdrawal of troops from Kuwait and eventual deployment of Allied forces. However, UN's response to Russia-Ukraine conflict has been on negotiations and appeals.
- b. The two conflicts took place in difference geopolitical setting and era. For example, Gulf Crisis took place immediately after Cold War, while Russia-Ukraine conflicts are happening in multi-polar era.
- c. Russia as a belligerent state is a permanent member of the UN Security Council and she has a power of veto, while Iraq as aggressor had no veto power and she was not a member of the Security Council.

Similarities:

- a. The Gulf Crisis and Russian – Ukraine conflicts both had evidences of annexations. Therefore, Iraq and Russia are all belligerent state which was an act against UN Charter.
- b. Both Iraq and Russia rejected UN's resolutions to pull out from the occupied territories of another sovereign states.

Discussion of Findings

The UN is stuck in dealing with veto power states, therefore its effectiveness in combating future conflicts involving multi-polar and veto power States is bleak. In other words, the inability of UN to muzzle its power against Russian annexation of some parts of Ukraine has become a subject of debate in the ability of UN combating global peace in international relations. The research observed that States without power is at the mercy of superpower states in the world. Iraq was a victim of recalcitrant state without power. Indeed, the research illuminated some lessons to states that are indifference to power possession.

The study also highlighted lessons learned from the Gulf Crisis that may be applied in line with Carl Von Clausewitz theory to the Russia – Ukraine conflicts in order to eliminate threat to world peace and making UN effective as a global peace organization. Lastly, the research threw lights on major differences and perhaps some areas of similarities in both conflicts that might be useful to UN in combating global peace and security.

Conclusion

The UN was built on normative order to exercise influence in conflict resolutions, and to prevent excess of states globally. In the Gulf Crisis, the UN achieved that through coalition of forces, regrettably Russia- Ukraine conflict have dampened the trust on UN conflict resolution approach. Russia's possession of veto has made the UN toothless and subject of debate on its effectiveness to realize world peace.

Recommendations

1. UN should explore peaceful engagement with sub –regional and continental organizations of affected State before deployment of coalition forces.

2. UN should re-structure the Permanent Security Council to reflect democratic setting among all continents; Africa had none, Europe three, Asia one and America one is statistically undemocratic; and use of veto should be $\frac{2}{3}$.
3. UN should endeavour to conduct plebiscite after annexation to the State affected to determine the validity of claims over territory before intervention can take place.
4. UN should mandate US to pull down its buffer zone in Ukraine to guarantee Russian trust on peace – building in the region.

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Reimagining Democracy: The Role of Youth Resistance in Democratic Futures

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Abstract

The role of young people in shaping democratic societies has become increasingly clear in recent years. Across continents, youth-led protests, social movements, and political campaigns have raised important questions about justice, freedom, inclusion, and governance. This paper explores the future of youth resistance in relation to democracy, considering how young people are challenging the status quo, building new communities, and imagining better political futures. Using both theoretical and qualitative frameworks, the study examines youth movements in Africa, Asia, Europe, and Latin America, analysing how digital tools, education, and global solidarity networks are reshaping democratic engagement. This paper explores how social media, civic education, and institutional gaps have influenced youth resistance. It also looks at how democracy is being reshaped through the active participation of younger generations. considers how democracy is being redefined through the participation of younger generations. The findings reveal that while youth resistance faces many challenges such as repression, misinformation, and political exclusion, it also carries strong potential for positive change. The paper concludes by offering recommendations for policy, education, and civil society to support youth inclusion and leadership in democratic

development. The future of democracy will likely depend on how societies engage with the power and voices of young people.

Keywords: Youth Resistance, Democracy, Social Movements, Protest, #EndSARS, Digital Activism.

Introduction

Throughout history, young people have been central to political transformation. From students marching against wars in earlier decades to today's teenage climate activists, youth have consistently stood at the forefront of struggles for justice and change. In the 21st century, their involvement in resisting unjust systems and promoting democracy has become even more visible (Ojo & Afolaranmi, 2024). Movements such as the Arab Spring, #EndSARS in Nigeria, Fridays for Future, and Hong Kong's Umbrella Movement demonstrate how young voices have brought pressing democratic concerns to the global stage (Afolaranmi, 2022). Unlike in the past, when youth were often seen merely as reactive forces, today they are also solution-bearers—organisers, writers, digital influencers, artists, and even political leaders. Through tools like social media, grassroots mobilisation, and education, they are shaping new ways of engaging democracy, even as they encounter resistance from governments and older generations. Arrests, suppression, and social labelling as “troublemakers” have not silenced them; rather, such challenges highlight their resilience and determination.

At the heart of democracy lies the right of people to choose their leaders and influence decisions, yet many young people still feel excluded from this process. Despite being one of the largest demographic groups, their participation is often constrained by voter age restrictions, lack of resources, and widespread mistrust of politicians. This exclusion has not led to apathy, but to innovation. Youth across the world are resisting exclusion through public protests, creative arts, digital activism, and informal community networks. Reports such as that of the African Union Youth Envoy (2022) affirm that young Africans are demanding greater political space and accountability, while Kaur and Silva (2023) show how Asian youth movements are constructing “small democracies” in their communities where national institutions fail. These examples reveal that democracy is not simply about elections, but about everyday participation, fairness, and dignity.

This paper, therefore, seeks to explore how young people’s acts of resistance are shaping the future of democracy. It examines the diverse forms of youth resistance—whether through protests, music, art, online platforms, or grassroots organising—and probes the motivations behind these efforts, particularly how young people respond to injustice, exclusion, and the shortcomings of democratic institutions. It further investigates the impact of youth movements on political change, public opinion, and policy reforms in both democratic and authoritarian contexts, while also identifying the tools and platforms which are digital media, education, and global networks as channels through which young people are mobilising. In doing so, the study aims to present a clearer picture of how today’s youth are actively imagining and constructing the democratic futures they wish to inhabit.

Ultimately, this research is not simply about observing youth protests but about listening to their deep concerns over inequality, corruption, climate change, gender justice, and human dignity. It seeks to highlight their creativity, resilience, and leadership, affirming, in the words of Dlamini (2024), that “young people are not tomorrow’s leaders, they are today’s conscience.” By placing youth at the centre of democratic inquiry and drawing on global examples alongside academic perspectives, the paper argues that the trajectory of democracy in the years ahead will depend significantly on how societies choose either to support or suppress youth resistance.

Understanding youth resistance and democracy requires engagement with ideas from political science, sociology, and youth studies. This study is primarily informed by Critical Youth Theory, but it also draws comparative insights from Critical Theory and Democratic Theory in order to situate young people’s struggles within wider debates about power, participation, and social change.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative research approach designed to explore the voices, actions, and impacts of youth resistance on democracy. The emphasis is not on quantifiable outcomes but on understanding the meanings young people attach to their resistance, the strategies they employ, and the implications of their actions for democratic futures.

Research Design

A comparative case study design was employed to provide depth and context. Four regions were purposively selected—Nigeria (#EndSARS), Hong Kong (Umbrella Movement), Chile (student protests), and South Africa (Fees Must Fall). These cases were chosen for three key reasons:

- a. **Relevance:** Each represents a prominent youth-led movement that challenged established political, economic, or social systems.
- b. **Diversity:** The cases reflect different cultural, political, and economic contexts (Africa, Asia, and Latin America), enabling cross-regional comparison.
- c. **Impact:** These movements gained both local and international attention, making them rich for analysis of youth-democracy dynamics.

This purposive selection ensures the study focuses on cases with strong illustrative value, while acknowledging that findings are not intended for broad statistical generalisation.

Data Collection

Data were drawn from multiple sources to strengthen reliability through triangulation:

- a. **Academic Literature:** Peer-reviewed articles published between 2018 and 2025 were reviewed to capture the latest scholarly debates.
- b. **Institutional Reports:** Documents from the African Union Youth Envoy, UNDP Youth Strategy (2022), and Accord's 2023 report on youth participation provided policy-oriented perspectives.
- c. **Media Sources:** International and regional newspapers, online news outlets, and broadcast interviews with youth activists were examined for first-hand accounts and narrative framing.
- d. **Social Media Content:** Publicly available digital artefacts such as tweets, campaign videos, hashtags, and online petitions were included to analyse grassroots mobilisation strategies.

All data sources were verified for authenticity and credibility. For academic and institutional documents, peer-review and publisher reputation served as validation criteria. For media and social media content, triangulation was applied by cross-checking events across multiple outlets and platforms. Only material publicly available and legally accessible was used, with ethical care taken to ensure that no confidential or personal information was exploited.

Data Analysis

A thematic analysis method was applied, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework:

- a. ***Familiarisation***: All documents and digital texts were read and re-read to gain contextual understanding.
- b. ***Initial Coding***: Segments of text were coded manually and digitally (using NVivo software) to capture recurring ideas.
- c. ***Theme Development***: Codes were clustered into broader themes such as causes of resistance (e.g., injustice, corruption, poverty, exclusion), forms of resistance (e.g., protest, digital activism, artistic expression), state and institutional responses, and democratic impacts.
- d. ***Reviewing Themes***: Themes were tested against the data to ensure coherence and to check for overlaps or contradictions.
- e. ***Defining and Naming Themes***: Clear definitions were created for each theme to maintain analytic consistency.
- f. ***Reporting***: Themes were contextualised within each case study while also allowing cross-case comparisons.

The analysis paid attention to both shared global patterns (such as the use of social media in mobilisation) and context-specific differences (e.g., the banning of social media during Hong Kong protests versus its central role in Nigeria's #EndSARS movement).

Limitations

This study recognises several methodological limitations. First, the focus on prominent, largely urban movements may underrepresent rural or less-visible youth resistance. Second, reliance on publicly available data excludes insights from closed or informal networks where key strategies may be shaped. Third, because youth movements are dynamic and rapidly evolving, some findings may not capture current realities. Despite these constraints, triangulation of sources and systematic thematic coding increase the validity and depth of the findings, providing a credible picture of how youth resistance is shaping democratic futures.

Theoretical Framework

Critical Youth Theory provides the central lens for this research. As articulated by Pineda and Driskill (2018), the theory challenges dominant views that portray young people as incomplete citizens or passive actors who

must wait until adulthood to participate fully in society. Instead, it recognises youth as capable political agents whose voices and actions have intrinsic value. It questions adult-centric power structures that often silence young people or limit their contributions to symbolic participation. Dlamini (2024) extends this framework by describing South African youth as “truth tellers in a tired democracy,” emphasising their role in revitalising political spaces that have become unresponsive. In this light, Critical Youth Theory helps to explain why young people resist not only authoritarianism or injustice, but also the paternalistic expectation that they should be seen rather than heard.

However, Critical Youth Theory alone does not fully capture the complexity of youth resistance across different cultural and political contexts. For this reason, the study also engages with Critical Theory more broadly, particularly its concern with unveiling structures of domination and exclusion. This wider perspective enables an understanding of youth resistance as part of a broader struggle for emancipation, connecting their actions to historical movements for justice and equality. By situating youth activism within these longer traditions, the analysis highlights how their resistance is both generationally distinctive and historically continuous.

Furthermore, insights from Democratic Theory provide a comparative framework for analysing how youth movements reshape democratic practice. Classical democratic theory often emphasises formal institutions such as elections, parties, and legislatures, but youth resistance highlights alternative forms of democratic participation. Kaur and Silva (2023) describe these as “small democracies” that emerge in local communities, digital spaces, and informal networks. By bringing these perspectives together, the theoretical framework shows that democracy is not only maintained through institutional procedures but is also reimagined and renewed through everyday practices of resistance, creativity, and solidarity. Taken together, these frameworks allow for a more comprehensive understanding of youth resistance. Critical Youth Theory foregrounds the agency of young people and critiques adultism, Critical Theory situates youth struggles within broader patterns of social domination, and Democratic Theory provides the language to analyse how such struggles expand or challenge democratic practices. This combined approach clarifies why youth resistance sometimes leads to systemic reform, while at other times it is suppressed or co-opted. It also highlights the dual nature of youth

activism: as both a response to democratic deficits and a generative force for democratic renewal. By applying these interconnected theories, this paper will analyse real-world cases with a deeper appreciation of youth power, the challenges they face, and the democratic futures they imagine.

Discussion of Findings

This section analyses the key findings from the case studies and data sources, focusing on how youth resistance is shaping democratic futures globally. The analysis considers the causes, forms, challenges, and impacts of youth resistance, while engaging with Critical Youth Theory, Critical Theory, and Democratic Theory to provide deeper understanding.

1. Causes of Youth Resistance

Across all cases, a central driver of resistance is dissatisfaction with governance, exclusion, and injustice. In Nigeria, the #EndSARS movement began as opposition to police brutality but evolved into a wider critique of governance failures (Afolaranmi, 2022). As Adebayo and Durotoye (2023) observe, young Nigerians rejected a democracy that excluded and endangered them. In Hong Kong, resistance emerged in response to the erosion of civil liberties, showing how youth may mobilise to defend democratic space even in semi-authoritarian contexts. In Chile, student protests revealed long-standing exclusion and inequality, culminating in constitutional reform. In South Africa, the Fees Must Fall movement revealed deep frustrations about unfulfilled post-apartheid promises and the persistence of structural inequality.

Critical Youth Theory helps explain these diverse causes. It recognises young people not as passive recipients of policy but as active agents confronting systemic exclusion. From this perspective, dissatisfaction with leadership is not mere disobedience but a claim to agency in spaces where youth have been marginalised. Comparative insights from Critical Theory further reveal that youth resistance often emerges at the intersection of structural injustices—such as economic exclusion, corruption, and historical inequalities—that limit opportunities for full democratic participation. Yet the causes are not identical. While economic inequality drives resistance in Chile and South Africa, in Hong Kong resistance is rooted more in identity and political autonomy. These divergent causes suggest that youth

resistance cannot be reduced to a single universal explanation but must be understood within the cultural and political histories of each context.

2. Forms of Youth Resistance

The findings reveal how youth resistance has diversified beyond traditional protest marches. Digital activism, artistic expression, and symbolic gestures have become central. Hashtags such as #EndSARS and #FeesMustFall mobilised global solidarity. Protest music and performance art in South Africa helped sustain morale and generate empathy. In Hong Kong, umbrellas became symbols of resilience. Critical Youth Theory provides insight here: youth movements often use creativity and digital platforms to subvert adult-dominated systems and to construct alternative democratic spaces. Democratic Theory further clarifies that such actions expand the meaning of democracy beyond electoral institutions toward everyday participation. However, the findings also reveal tensions. Digital tools empower mobilisation but expose activists to surveillance, repression, and co-optation. This dual reality challenges overly celebratory narratives of digital activism, suggesting a need for cautious, context-specific analysis.

3. State and Society Responses

The findings show that government responses to youth resistance are often repressive. Nigeria's Lekki Toll Gate shooting, Hong Kong's National Security Law, and Chile's police violence illustrate how states frequently prioritise order over dialogue. These responses reinforce Critical Theory's view of the state as a defender of entrenched power structures rather than a neutral arbiter. At the same time, there are divergent outcomes. In Chile, sustained youth resistance achieved constitutional reform, while in Hong Kong, repression curtailed most political gains. These contrasts demonstrate that state response is a key variable in determining whether youth resistance strengthens or weakens democracy. Civil society responses also differ: churches and NGOs in South Africa and Chile often supported student movements, while in Hong Kong, some institutions distanced themselves from youth resistance to avoid state retaliation.

4. Impact on Democratic Thinking and Action

Despite repression, youth resistance has left lasting legacies. In Nigeria, #EndSARS fostered civic consciousness and inspired youth political

ambition. In South Africa, student leaders transitioned into formal politics, broadening representation. In Chile, youth activism catalysed constitutional reform, a rare instance where grassroots pressure reshaped national institutions. In Hong Kong, while political space narrowed, cultural identity and democratic aspirations deepened. Here, Democratic Theory helps interpret the findings: democracy is not confined to electoral outcomes but includes everyday practices of participation, identity formation, and claims to justice. Critical Youth Theory underscores that even when youth resistance fails to achieve immediate structural change, it reshapes democratic imagination by asserting the legitimacy of youth agency. The divergent impacts reveal a tension: in some contexts, youth resistance produces institutional reform, while in others it produces cultural but not political change. This raises critical questions about the durability of democratic gains and the vulnerability of youth agency in authoritarian settings.

5. Challenges and Dangers

The study highlights significant challenges facing youth resistance, including burnout, repression, internal divisions, and the danger of co-optation. The co-optation of youth leaders by political elites is particularly concerning. Critical Youth Theory warns against tokenistic inclusion that silences youth voices rather than empowering them. The UN Youth Report (2025) similarly cautions that youth inclusion must be ethical and substantive rather than cosmetic. This finding underscores a contradiction: while states often exclude youth, they sometimes strategically include them in order to neutralise movements. This paradox reveals the fragility of youth power within existing political systems and suggests the need for movements to develop strategies that safeguard their integrity and autonomy.

6. Futures of Youth Resistance and Democracy

The findings suggest that youth resistance will remain central to democratic futures. Youth are unlikely to abandon the pursuit of justice and equality, even when states attempt suppression. The future of democracy therefore depends on how institutions respond. Where youth are genuinely included, democracy is likely to deepen. Where youth are silenced, resistance will re-emerge in new forms, sometimes disruptively. Critical Youth Theory

suggests that the future will be shaped not only by formal institutions but also by the imaginative spaces youth create through culture, art, and digital networks. Democratic Theory reinforces this view by highlighting that democracy is an evolving practice rather than a fixed system. In sum, the findings reveal both shared global patterns and critical divergences. Youth resistance consistently emerges from exclusion and injustice, employs creative and digital tools, and shapes democratic consciousness. Yet outcomes vary sharply depending on state responses, cultural contexts, and the ability of youth to resist co-optation. These complexities affirm that youth are not merely future leaders but present-day agents of democratic transformation.

Conclusion

This paper has explored how youth resistance is not only a response to failed systems but also a significant force in shaping democratic futures. The study has shown that across various countries namely Nigeria, Hong Kong, Chile, and South Africa—youth have mobilised against injustice, inequality, state violence, and exclusion. They have used both traditional and digital methods to voice their demands, creating new ways of participating in the democratic process. Despite the different contexts, one unifying theme stands out: young people are refusing to remain silent in the face of oppression. Their actions, whether on the streets or on social media, are challenging long-standing systems of power. They demand more than political inclusion; they want fairness, truth, and the ability to shape the societies they live in.

However, the road has not been easy. Youth resistance often attracts harsh responses, ranging from state violence to imprisonment. Some movements have lost momentum due to burnout, fear, or internal divisions. Others have been co-opted or silenced. Yet, many continue to rise—learning, adjusting, and moving forward with renewed strength. The evidence presented in this paper shows that the future of democracy is closely tied to how societies treat their youth. If governments continue to shut out young voices, they risk deeper unrest. But if youth are genuinely included and empowered, democratic systems will become more just, inclusive, and resilient. The conclusion is clear: youth are not just the future of democracy—they are its present force. As governments, institutions, and societies think about the future, they must recognise and respect the political intelligence, creativity, and courage of young people.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to support both youth resistance and democratic growth:

- a. **Promote Youth Inclusion in Governance:** Governments and political parties should create real pathways for youth participation, not just through youth wings but also through candidacy, appointments, and decision-making positions. National Youth Parliaments and quotas for young candidates can be effective.
- b. **Protect the Right to Protest:** Legal and institutional frameworks must protect peaceful protest. States should end the use of excessive force against young protestors and punish security personnel who abuse power.
- c. **Civic Education and Political Literacy:** Schools, communities, and religious institutions should prioritise civic education to help young people understand their rights and responsibilities in democratic societies.
- d. **Digital Safety and Expression:** As youth increasingly use online platforms for resistance, governments and tech companies should work together to protect freedom of expression while ensuring online safety.
- e. **Support Mental Health for Activists:** Youth involved in resistance often face emotional and psychological stress. Civil society organisations and mental health professionals should offer support and care services tailored to young activists.

By taking these steps, societies can turn youth resistance from an act of desperation into a constructive force for democratic renewal. It is time to stop seeing youth as problems to be managed, and start seeing them as partners in building a better, more just world.

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**Philosophy of Religion and Theology in
the 21st Century: Relevance and
Challenges**

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Abstract

The twenty-first century presents both opportunities and challenges for the study and practice of philosophy of religion and theology. In an era marked by globalization, technological advancement, secularism, and religious pluralism, questions about the role of faith, reason, and ultimate reality remain highly relevant. Philosophy of religion provides a rational framework for exploring issues such as the existence of God, the problem of evil, and the coherence of religious belief in the light of scientific and philosophical critiques. Theology, on the other hand, interprets divine revelation, doctrines, and traditions in ways that address the existential concerns of individuals and societies. Both disciplines together engage with pressing issues such as morality, human dignity, social justice, interreligious dialogue, and the quest

for peace in conflict-ridden contexts. However, they also face challenges, including increasing skepticism toward religion, the dominance of materialistic worldviews, and the struggle to communicate faith meaningfully in a rapidly changing cultural environment. By critically examining these issues, philosophy of religion and theology can provide intellectual depth, ethical guidance, and a platform for dialogue between diverse worldviews. Their continuing relevance lies in their ability to engage tradition and modernity, reason and faith, and local and global contexts to promote human flourishing in the twenty-first century.

Keywords: Dialogue, Modernity, Philosophy of Religion, Theology, Worldview

Introduction

The twenty-first century has witnessed profound transformations in human thought, culture, and social interaction. Globalization, scientific advancement, secularization, and religious pluralism have reshaped how people engage with questions of ultimate reality, morality, and human destiny (McGrath, 2012). Within this context, philosophy of religion and theology remain essential disciplines for critically exploring the meaning of faith, the nature of God, and the relationship between religion and contemporary society. Philosophy of religion, as a rational inquiry into religious belief, addresses questions such as the existence of God, the problem of evil, and the rationality of religious experience (Taliaferro, 2013). Theology, in turn, interprets divine revelation and religious traditions, seeking to provide frameworks of meaning that guide personal and communal life (Grenz & Olson, 1996).

Despite their enduring significance, these fields face serious challenges in the twenty-first century. The rise of secularism has reduced the influence of traditional religious authority in public discourse (Taylor, 2007). Scientific naturalism and materialism often dismiss metaphysical claims as irrelevant or unverifiable (Plantinga, 2011). At the same time, religious extremism and intolerance highlight the urgent need for dialogue, tolerance, and critical reflection (Hick, 2004). Engaging these realities requires philosophy of religion and theology not only to defend the relevance of faith but also to address moral, social, and existential issues in ways that resonate with contemporary culture.

Thus, this paper explores the continuing relevance of philosophy of religion and theology in the twenty-first century while critically analyzing the challenges they encounter. It argues that these disciplines are indispensable

for fostering interreligious dialogue, guiding ethical reflection, and promoting holistic human development in a rapidly changing world.

Conceptual Clarification of Terms

Before examining the relevance and challenges of philosophy of religion and theology in the twenty-first century, it is important to clarify the key terms used in this study.

Philosophy of Religion: Philosophy of religion is a branch of philosophy that critically examines the central themes and concepts involved in religious traditions. It seeks to analyze questions concerning the existence and nature of God, the rationality of faith, the problem of evil, religious language, and the relationship between religion and science (Peterson et al., 2020). Unlike theology, which is grounded in the claims of a particular religious tradition, philosophy of religion adopts a critical, rational, and often comparative approach to religious beliefs and practices (Taliaferro & Harrison, 2010).

Theology: Theology is the systematic and critical study of the divine, religious beliefs, and the practice of faith within a particular tradition. Grenz and Olson (1996) define theology as the task of “reflecting on the God of the Christian faith and His relation to the world” (p. 13). Theology seeks to interpret revelation and tradition in ways that are meaningful to contemporary believers, offering frameworks for understanding faith, ethics, and communal life (McGrath, 2012).

Relevance: In academic discourse, relevance refers to the significance or applicability of a discipline or concept within a given context. When applied to philosophy of religion and theology, relevance implies their ability to address contemporary issues such as secularism, moral dilemmas, religious pluralism, and interfaith relations (Stenmark, 2006).

Challenges: Challenges denote the difficulties, obstacles, or critical questions that hinder the effectiveness of a discipline in addressing its aims. For philosophy of religion and theology, these challenges include the rise of secularization, the dominance of scientific naturalism, religious intolerance, and the difficulty of communicating religious truths in an increasingly pluralistic and skeptical society (Taylor, 2007; Plantinga, 2011).

By clarifying these concepts, the discussion that follows situates philosophy of religion and theology within their proper academic and practical contexts, providing a foundation for assessing their relevance and challenges in the twenty-first century.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework provides the conceptual lens through which this study examines the relevance and challenges of philosophy of religion and theology in the twenty-first century. This paper adopts three complementary perspectives: rational-critical theory, hermeneutical theory, and theology of engagement.

Rational-Critical Theory: Rooted in the Enlightenment tradition, rational-critical theory emphasizes the use of reason and critical reflection in assessing religious claims. Habermas (1984) argues that rational discourse provides a foundation for understanding truth and meaning in a pluralistic society. Within the philosophy of religion, this framework allows for the examination of arguments for and against God's existence, the coherence of religious doctrines, and the rationality of belief systems (Plantinga, 2000).

Hermeneutical Theory: Hermeneutics highlights the role of interpretation in understanding religious texts, traditions, and experiences. Gadamer (2004) stresses the importance of dialogue and historical consciousness in interpretation. Applied to theology, hermeneutics enables believers to reinterpret doctrines and practices in ways that speak to contemporary cultural and existential contexts (Thiselton, 2009).

Theology of Engagement: In the twenty-first century, theology is not confined to abstract reflection but is actively engaged in addressing societal issues such as justice, peace, human dignity, and interreligious dialogue. Bevans and Schroeder (2011) describe this as a "prophetic dialogue," where theology enters into conversation with cultures, religions, and social realities while remaining rooted in faith. This framework underscores the practical relevance of theology for ethical decision-making and social transformation.

Taken together, these perspectives provide a robust theoretical grounding for assessing both the enduring significance and the contemporary challenges of philosophy of religion and theology. They enable this study to approach the disciplines not merely as abstract intellectual exercises but as dynamic tools for dialogue, interpretation, and transformative engagement in today's complex world.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative, analytical, and interpretive methodology that is most suitable for philosophical and theological inquiry. Unlike

empirical research, philosophy of religion and theology rely primarily on critical reasoning, conceptual analysis, and interpretive engagement with texts and traditions (Evans, 2009). The aim of this methodology is to explore the enduring relevance and challenges of these disciplines in the twenty-first century through a rigorous examination of ideas, arguments, and contexts.

The research employs three interrelated methods:

1. **Historical-Contextual Method:** This involves situating philosophical and theological thought within its historical development while relating it to contemporary contexts. By examining the works of classical and modern thinkers such as Augustine, Aquinas, Kant, and contemporary scholars, this study highlights how enduring questions of faith and reason continue to evolve (McGrath, 2012).
2. **Comparative Method:** Philosophy of religion and theology are increasingly global and interreligious disciplines. This study employs a comparative lens to analyze how different traditions and worldviews—Christianity, secular humanism, and pluralist perspectives—approach questions of truth, meaning, and ethics (Hick, 2004).
3. **Critical-Analytical Method.** At the core of philosophical and theological reflection is the task of analysis and critique. This study evaluates arguments concerning the rationality of belief, the challenges of secularism, and the relevance of theology in public discourse. Critical reasoning is used to assess the strengths and weaknesses of various positions (Taliaferro & Harrison, 2010).

These methods are complemented by hermeneutical interpretation, which recognizes that theology in particular requires ongoing re-interpretation of faith traditions in light of changing cultural realities (Thiselton, 2009). Together, they provide a comprehensive approach that is both faithful to the intellectual heritage of philosophy and theology and responsive to contemporary challenges.

The Relevance of Philosophy of Religion and Theology in the 21st Century

In a world increasingly shaped by secularism, globalization, and scientific advancement, the relevance of philosophy of religion and theology remains profound. These disciplines provide intellectual, moral, and spiritual resources for engaging some of the most pressing issues of the modern era. Their significance can be discussed under several dimensions.

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1. ***Addressing Ultimate Questions:*** Despite the rise of scientific naturalism and secular ideologies, questions concerning the existence of God, the meaning of life, the problem of evil, and the destiny of humanity continue to preoccupy human thought. Philosophy of religion provides rational frameworks for exploring these questions, ensuring that they are not dismissed as irrational or irrelevant (Peterson et al., 2020). Theology complements this by interpreting divine revelation and articulating responses that offer hope and coherence for believers in contemporary contexts (McGrath, 2012).
 2. ***Ethical and Moral Guidance:*** Modern society faces complex ethical dilemmas ranging from bioethics and environmental justice to political corruption and human rights. Philosophy of religion and theology contribute to moral reasoning by grounding ethical values in transcendent principles rather than mere relativism (Evans, 2009). For instance, the theological emphasis on human dignity provides a strong foundation for defending justice, equality, and the sanctity of life (Volf, 2011).
 3. ***Fostering Interreligious and Intercultural Dialogue:*** The twenty-first century is marked by religious pluralism and cultural diversity. Philosophy of religion creates space for dialogue by critically comparing different religious claims, while theology—when open and dialogical—promotes mutual understanding and peaceful coexistence (Hick, 2004). These contributions are crucial in societies where religious misunderstanding often leads to conflict and violence.
 4. ***Engaging Science and Technology:*** The rapid growth of science and technology raises questions about human identity, morality, and the possibility of transcendence. Philosophy of religion examines whether scientific explanations eliminate the need for God, while theology reflects on how faith can coexist with scientific discoveries (Plantinga, 2011). Such dialogue is vital in bridging the perceived gap between faith and reason.
 5. ***Promoting Human Flourishing and Social Transformation:*** Theology and philosophy of religion are not only academic exercises but also contribute to practical life. They encourage active participation in addressing poverty, injustice, violence, and environmental crises (Bevans & Schroeder, 2011). By integrating spiritual vision with social

responsibility, these disciplines shape communities toward holistic human flourishing.

In summary, philosophy of religion and theology remain deeply relevant in the twenty-first century. They offer critical reflection on ultimate questions, ethical guidance, interreligious dialogue, engagement with science, and contributions to human development. Their continued relevance lies in their ability to adapt to changing contexts while remaining rooted in the search for truth and meaning.

The Challenges of Philosophy of Religion and Theology in the 21st Century

While philosophy of religion and theology continue to demonstrate their importance, both disciplines face significant challenges in the twenty-first century. These challenges arise from intellectual, cultural, social, and political developments that affect how religious thought is perceived and practiced in the modern world.

- 1. *The Rise of Secularism and Religious Skepticism:*** One of the major challenges is the dominance of secular ideologies that marginalize religion in public life. Taylor (2007) describes this as the “secular age,” where belief in God is no longer taken for granted but exists as one option among many. This environment has fueled skepticism about religious claims, leading to the perception that theology and philosophy of religion are outdated or irrelevant in addressing contemporary issues.
- 2. *Scientific Naturalism and Materialism:*** The growing authority of science has created an intellectual climate where naturalistic explanations are often viewed as sufficient for understanding reality. Plantinga (2011) notes that this scientific naturalism tends to dismiss metaphysical or theological explanations as unscientific. Consequently, philosophy of religion faces the challenge of defending the rationality of belief in God, while theology struggles to communicate faith in ways that are credible to scientifically minded audiences.
- 3. *Religious Pluralism and Relativism:*** The twenty-first century is marked by cultural and religious diversity. While this pluralism can enrich dialogue, it also challenges theology’s claims to truth and universality. Hick (2004) argues that the coexistence of multiple religions raises questions about the exclusivity of any one tradition. This can lead to relativism, where all beliefs are considered equally valid, undermining the distinctiveness of theological claims.

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- 4. *Extremism and Misuse of Religion:*** Another pressing challenge is the misuse of religion to justify violence, extremism, and intolerance. Armstrong (2014) emphasizes that religious traditions, when interpreted narrowly or politically, can become sources of division rather than peace. This undermines the constructive role of theology and philosophy of religion in promoting dialogue and social harmony.
 - 5. *Communication and Relevance in a Changing Culture:*** Finally, both disciplines face the challenge of engaging meaningfully with contemporary culture. Theological language often appears abstract and inaccessible to ordinary people, while philosophical discourse may seem detached from practical life (McGrath, 2012). Bridging the gap between academic reflection and lived experience remains a critical challenge.

In sum, philosophy of religion and theology confront a range of challenges in the twenty-first century, including secularism, scientific naturalism, religious pluralism, extremism, and communication barriers. These difficulties, however, do not diminish their value; rather, they invite renewed creativity, dialogue, and contextual engagement to ensure their continuing relevance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Philosophy of religion and theology remain essential disciplines in the twenty-first century. They help humanity wrestle with the deepest questions of meaning, existence, morality, and transcendence. They also provide intellectual resources for addressing ethical dilemmas, fostering dialogue among diverse faith traditions, and engaging with contemporary issues such as science, technology, and social justice. While they face challenges from secularism, skepticism, religious pluralism, and rapid cultural change, these obstacles present opportunities for renewal and deeper reflection. Far from being outdated, philosophy of religion and theology continue to shape the moral and spiritual imagination of society.

To strengthen their relevance in the present age, the following recommendations are suggested:

- 1. *Contextual Engagement:*** The disciplines must continue to respond to the realities of culture, society, and science in ways that remain meaningful to diverse audiences.
- 2. *Dialogue and Collaboration:*** There is a need for philosophy and theology to work hand in hand with other fields of knowledge, particularly the

sciences and social sciences, in order to provide holistic responses to modern problems.

3. **Public Relevance:** Theology especially should not remain confined to academic or ecclesiastical circles but must contribute to public debates on morality, governance, and justice.
4. **Critical and Constructive Reflection:** Philosophy of religion should continue to sharpen the intellectual foundations of belief, while theology should provide constructive visions that inspire faith and responsible living.

In conclusion, philosophy of religion and theology are not relics of a bygone era. They are living disciplines that, when pursued with openness and commitment, can illuminate the human search for meaning, nurture ethical responsibility, and contribute to the transformation of society.

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**Critical Review of the Boko Haram
Insurgency and Its Implications for
Human Security in Northern Part of
Nigeria: A Study of Borno State**

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Abstract

The Boko Haram insurgency has severely undermined human security in Borno State, Nigeria, causing widespread displacement, loss of lives and economic collapse. This study critically examined existing literature on the insurgency, identifying key gaps and emerging perspectives while assessing its implications for human security across dimensions such as personal safety, food security, healthcare, education, environment and livelihoods. It also examined existing literature relating to Boko Haram insurgency origin, causes and tactics as well as government's counter-insurgency strategies. While much has been written on the insurgency, many studies relied on secondary sources and broad generalisations, often failing to capture the real experiences of those directly affected. Anchored on Human Security

Theory and the Political Economy of Conflict framework, this study provided a comprehensive understanding of the crisis and its implications for the well-being and stability of affected communities. Methodologically, the research adopted a qualitative approach, relying on secondary data from academic works, government reports, and publications from international organizations. The findings revealed that Boko Haram has severely disrupted livelihoods, weakened state institutions, and intensified poverty, displacement, and psychological trauma among residents. The study concluded that the insurgency has deeply eroded social cohesion and long-term development in Borno State. It also highlighted the importance of conducting primary field research, gathering empirical evidence from people who have directly experienced the impacts of the insurgency. This will help in shaping more effective policies, contributing to knowledge and developing sustainable solutions for affected communities in Borno state. Ultimately, the study recommended holistic interventions that combine security stabilization, livelihood restoration and institutional rebuilding as well as enhanced humanitarian aid.

Keywords: Insurgency, Human security, Boko haram, Borno State, Nigeria

Introduction

The Boko Haram insurgency has been one of the deadliest conflicts in modern African history, with Borno State at the heart of the crisis. What began as an ideological movement escalated into a prolonged conflict, leaving thousands dead, communities uprooted and infrastructure in ruins. Schools have been burned, livelihoods destroyed, and millions forced to flee their homes (Abubakar, 2021). At the heart of this crisis is human security, which extends beyond physical safety to include economic stability, education, healthcare and social cohesion. The insurgency has triggered a severe humanitarian crisis, with many living in displacement camps under dire conditions. (UNHCR, 2021). Despite military efforts and counter-insurgency measures, Boko Haram and its splinter group, ISWAP, continue to pose a serious threat, highlighting unresolved issues such as poverty, radicalisation and weak governance (Ahmed and Suleiman, 2021). This study critically examines the impact of Boko Haram on human security in Borno State, Nigeria reviewing existing literature to identify key research gaps. Analysing scholarly works, reports and empirical studies provides insights into how the conflict has reshaped life in Borno and what is needed for lasting peace and stability.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the extensive academic and policy attention the Boko Haram insurgency has received, critical gaps remain in understanding its full impact on human security, particularly in Borno State. Much of the existing literature relies on generalised statistics and quantitative national-level data, often overlooking the nuanced and multidimensional effects of the conflict on local populations. Issues such as personal safety, access to healthcare, food security and the erosion of livelihoods are frequently treated in isolation rather than as interconnected elements of human security. Furthermore, secondary research has often failed to adequately capture the lived experiences and long-term socio-economic and psychological consequences endured by communities in Maiduguri, Bama and Gwoza, areas most affected by the insurgency. While military responses and counter-insurgency strategies have been widely discussed, their effectiveness in addressing the broader human security needs remains underexplored.

Objectives of the study

1. To critically examine existing literature on the Boko Haram insurgency;
2. To identify gaps and emerging perspectives in the literature
3. To assess the implications of Boko Haram insurgency for human security in Borno State.

Conceptual Clarifications

Historical Background of Boko Haram insurgency

Boko Haram, officially known as Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati wal-Jihad, which translates to "People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's Teachings and Jihad," was founded by Mohammed Yusuf in Maiduguri, Borno State, in the early 2000s. Onapajo (2020) note that tensions between Boko Haram and the Nigerian government escalated due to socio-economic grievances, government crackdowns, and internal power struggles within the group. The government's heavy-handed response, including arrests and extra-judicial killings, worsened the conflict. Zenn (2021) identified the 2009 crackdown by Nigerian security forces, which resulted in the death of Mohammed Yusuf and the arrest of his followers, as the turning point that triggered Boko Haram's violent insurgency, marked by bombings, assassinations and attacks on government and civilian

targets. After Yusuf's death, Abubakar Shekau became the leader, escalating Boko Haram tactics to include suicide bombings, kidnappings and village raids, causing displacement and humanitarian crises. According to Campbell (2022), a major split occurred in 2016, leading to the formation of Islamic State in West Africa Province (ISWAP) under Abu Musab al-Barnawi, which aligned with ISIS and focused on military and government targets. Despite the split, both factions continued violent activities, with Shekau's leadership ending in 2021 after his death in a confrontation with ISWAP forces.

Conceptual Reality of Insurgency and Security

Neil, (2005) describes insurgency as a struggle between a non-state group and an established authority, where the insurgent group seeks to challenge, undermine, or overthrow the existing constitutional government of a country or its policies through various means, including violence, propaganda and social disruption. According to Kilcullen (2010), insurgencies are often marked by their use of irregular warfare tactics, aiming to erode the legitimacy of the state and gain the support of the local population. This definition is particularly relevant to Boko Haram, which employs unconventional tactics such as bombings, kidnappings and assassinations to destabilise the region and undermine the authority of the Nigerian government.

1. **Human Security:** Acharya (2001) describes human security as the protection of individuals and communities from threats that can undermine their survival and daily life. The concept emerged in the post-Cold War era, challenging the conventional notion of security, which was primarily concerned with national defense and territorial integrity. Human security, as defined by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 1994), encompasses economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community and political security.
2. **Economic Security:** Higazi (2020) defines economic security as the ability of individuals and communities to sustain livelihoods and access resources. He noted that Boko Haram's insurgency has devastated Borno's local economies especially agriculture, trade, and small businesses through village attacks, farm burnings, and looting, leaving many without stable income.

3. **Personal Security:** Personal security is the protection of individuals from violence, threats, and harm. Boko Haram's killings, kidnappings and sexual violence have created widespread fear, especially among women and children. Many have been forced into slavery or recruited as child soldiers. (Zenn, 2021)
4. **Food security:** Food security refers to a situation where all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (FAO, 1996). It encompasses four key dimensions: food availability, food access, food utilisation and stability of these factors over time (World Food Programme, 2020).
5. **Environmental Security:** Environmental security involves safeguarding natural resources and ecosystems from degradation and conflict-related harm. In Borno State, the Boko Haram insurgency has worsened environmental challenges, as mass displacement has led to deforestation, soil degradation, and pressure on scarce water resources (Adamu & Bello, 2022).
6. **Community Security:** Community security concerns the protection of people from violence, displacement, and instability. Boko Haram's activities have severely eroded traditional structures, displaced populations, and disrupted social cohesion (Akpan & Ering, 2023).
7. **Political Security:** Political security involves the protection of political institutions, governance structures, and the rule of law. Boko Haram insurgency has significantly weakened state authority in Borno State, challenging the Nigerian government's ability to maintain order and provide essential services. (Adebayo and Yusuf, 2021).
8. **Health Security:** Health security involves access to healthcare, disease prevention, and emergency response. The Boko Haram insurgency has severely undermined this in Borno, as attacks on hospitals and the displacement of health workers have left many without medical care. Consequently, malnutrition, disease, and mental health challenges are widespread (WHO, 2021).

Critical Review of the Boko Haram Literature

Origins and Causes of Boko Haram

According to Barkindo, (2023), the origins and causes of Boko Haram have been the subject of extensive empirical research, with scholars identifying a

confluence of economic, religious, historical, political and educational factors contributing to the group's emergence and persistence of violent extremism. Agbiboa (2023) found that poverty, unemployment, and inequality fuel radicalisation in Northern Nigeria, with Boko Haram exploiting these frustrations by offering financial incentives and belonging. Similarly, Onuoha (2021), in "Boko Haram: Islamism, Politics, Security and the State in Nigeria," found that Boko Haram's rigid interpretation of Islam and rejection of Western values appeal to marginalised communities.

Barkindo (2023), in "Boko Haram-ISWAP and the Growing Footprint of Islamic State (IS) in Africa," examined how historical grievances fuel Boko Haram's emergence and persistence. Using interviews with former militants, security experts, and displaced persons, the study found that colonial injustices, marginalisation, and post-colonial neglect created deep resentment that Boko Haram exploits. The author recommended promoting political inclusion, equitable resource distribution and grassroots peacebuilding to address these root causes.

In relation to education, Sampson (2020), in "Education and Boko Haram Insurgency in Northern Nigeria," found that Boko Haram exploited low literacy levels and poor educational access to recruit vulnerable youths. The destruction of schools and attacks on teachers further weakened the education system. The study recommended rebuilding schools, expanding access to education, and introducing vocational training to reduce youth susceptibility to radicalisation.

Regarding political manipulation and ethnic divisions, Maiangwa (2021), in "The Political Economy of Boko Haram Insurgency," found that political elites in Nigeria have exploited religion and ethnicity to maintain power, deepening divisions that enable extremism. Boko Haram has capitalised on these fractures to justify its actions and recruit members. The study recommended stronger political accountability, anti-corruption measures and inclusive governance to curb such manipulation.

Boko Haram Strategies and Tactics

Boko Haram has adopted diverse and evolving tactics to sustain its insurgency in Northeastern Nigeria. It began with hit-and-run attacks, assassinations and bombings targeting officials, security forces, and opposing religious leaders. By 2011, the group escalated to suicide bombings, including the UN headquarters attack in Abuja (Zenn, 2021).

Between 2014 and 2015, it shifted to guerrilla warfare and territorial control, capturing several towns and committing large-scale atrocities such as the Baga massacre and the Chibok schoolgirls' abduction. Boko Haram has also exploited propaganda, social media and forced recruitment to expand its influence (Campbell, 2022).

One notable study by Omenma et al. (2020), in "A Decade of Boko Haram Activities: The Attacks, Responses and Challenges Ahead," analysed the group's violent strategies using a mixed-methods approach. Their findings show that Boko Haram effectively employs guerrilla tactics, ambushes and kidnappings to destabilize security forces and instill fear. They recommended improved intelligence gathering and stronger community engagement to counter such asymmetric warfare.

Varin (2021), in her book "Boko Haram and the War on Terror," examined Boko Haram recruitment and radicalisation strategies within the framework of global jihadist movements. Using case studies and an analysis of Boko Haram propaganda materials, the study found that Boko Haram alignment with global jihadist narratives has enhanced its recruitment efforts, attracting fighters both locally and regionally. A major observation from this study was that Boko Haram ability to align global extremist ideologies with local grievances increases its appeal among the vulnerable.

Al-Tamimi (2021), in "The Defeat of Abu Bakr Shekau's Group in Sambisa Forest," analyzed primary sources such as internal communications and battlefield reports to examine the factional conflict between Shekau's Boko Haram faction and ISWAP. The study found that ISWAP's strategy of gaining local support contrasted with Shekau's brutality, creating internal divisions that led to his group's downfall.

Sidi (2020), in "Boko Haram et la Juxtaposition des Contextes," examined the group's communication strategies and adaptation of global jihadist media tactics to the Sub-Saharan context. Using qualitative content analysis of propaganda materials and social media posts, the study found that Boko Haram effectively uses digital platforms like Twitter and Instagram to spread its ideology and target youth audiences.

Government Counter-insurgency Strategies

The Nigerian government has employed military, political, and social strategies to counter Boko Haram, with mixed results. Initially, its response was military, marked by the deployment of the Joint Task Force (JTF) in

2011. However, as Boko Haram's strength grew, a state of emergency was declared in 2013, leading to the creation of the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF) comprising troops from Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon, and Niger. According to Musa and Audu (2023), the government also introduced de-radicalisation and reintegration programmes such as Operation Safe Corridor to rehabilitate former insurgents.

Musa and Ibrahim (2020), in their study "The Role of Military and Non-Military Strategies in Countering Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria," used surveys and interviews with 120 security personnel, officials, and community leaders. They found that while military operations weakened territorial control, the group adapted with suicide bombings and guerrilla tactics. Non-military efforts, including deradicalisation, peace dialogues and economic programs, had limited success due to public skepticism and resistance to reintegrating ex-militants. The authors recommended structured reintegration, increased public awareness and stronger psychological rehabilitation

Mohammed and Lawal (2021), in their work: "The Nigerian Military's Counter-Insurgency Strategy against Boko Haram: An Assessment from the Field," surveyed 150 respondents, including military personnel, security experts, and displaced persons in Borno State. The study found that joint military operations and the MNJTF weakened Boko Haram's territorial control, but the group adapted through guerrilla tactics and attacks on civilians. The conventional military approach proved ineffective against asymmetric threats, and reported human rights abuses strained relations with local communities. The authors recommended improved intelligence, coordination with vigilante groups, and strict adherence to human rights.

Okonkwo (2020) examined "Community-based Security Approaches in Counterinsurgency: The Role of Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) in Borno State" through structured interviews with 100 CJTF members and security officials. Findings showed that the CJTF played a crucial role in gathering intelligence, securing local communities, and complementing military efforts. However, the study also revealed concerns over the lack of proper training, accountability and occasional abuses by some CJTF members. The study recommended formalising the CJTF structure, providing training in human rights and counter-terrorism and integrating CJTF members into official security agencies where possible.

Okoye and Williams (2020), in their study “The Role of International Intelligence Cooperation in Countering Boko Haram: A Case Study of US-Nigeria Security Relations,” used secondary data from security reports, policy documents and intelligence briefings. They found that intelligence-sharing between Nigeria and the United States helped track Boko Haram’s financial networks and foreign recruits. However, U.S. arms restrictions on Nigeria, due to human rights concerns, limited the full potential of military support.

Johnson and Aliyu (2022), in their study “Soft Power Approaches to Countering Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria: The Role of Education, Media and Religious Leaders,” examined non-kinetic strategies for combating extremism. Drawing on interviews with 100 educators, media practitioners and religious leaders, they found that misinformation and extremist ideologies spread through local networks fueled radicalisation. Initiatives such as counter-narratives, peace education, and interfaith dialogue showed promise but were hindered by poor funding, political interference and low public trust.

Similarly, Ibrahim and Adeola (2022), in their study “De-radicalisation and Re-integration of Ex-Boko Haram Fighters in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects,” used interviews with security officials, community leaders, and former insurgents to assess Nigeria’s Operation Safe Corridor Programme. The study found that while the program aided rehabilitation, societal resistance to reintegration remained strong due to fear of re-radicalisation. It also noted flaws in the screening process, with some individuals reportedly posing as ex-fighters to benefit from the program. The authors recommended stronger community engagement, improved monitoring and better vocational training to ensure sustainable reintegration.

Theoretical Framework

Human Security Theory

The human security theory shifts the focus of security from state sovereignty and military defense to the protection of individuals and communities. It emphasizes that true security lies in freedom from fear and want ensuring people are safe from threats to their survival, livelihoods, and dignity (UNDP, 1994; Acharya, 2001). Human security encompasses economic stability, food access, healthcare, education, environmental protection, and political freedom. This framework is most relevant for

examining the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on human security in Borno State.

Activities of Boko haram have severely undermined these dimensions of security by destroying livelihoods, displacing communities and creating food shortages. Women and children have been disproportionately affected through abductions, killings, and forced displacement (UNICEF, 2023). The destruction of schools and healthcare facilities has further deepened insecurity, leaving residents struggling to rebuild. In essence, the human security approach underscores the need to eliminate fear, deprivation and vulnerability by ensuring access to basic human needs and freedoms.

Human Security Theory helps explain why a purely military approach has failed to restore stability in Borno. As Sen (1999) notes in his capability approach, security extends beyond the absence of violence to include access to opportunities that enable individuals to live meaningful lives free from fear and want. This view aligns with Akinyemi and Olaniyan (2021), who argue that lasting solutions to insurgency require not only counterinsurgency efforts but also investments in economic empowerment, education, and good governance.

Political economy of conflict

The political economy of conflict provides a valuable framework for understanding the persistence and dynamics of armed conflict, particularly in fragile regions like northeastern Nigeria. It posits that conflicts are sustained not only by grievances such as poverty or marginalisation but also by the economic opportunities they create for various actors. Violence thus becomes both a symptom of breakdown and a means of accessing power, wealth, and resources (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004; Duffield, 2001).

In the case of Boko Haram, this framework helps explain how the insurgency is intertwined with local and transnational economies. The group finances its operations through kidnapping, smuggling, extortion, looting, and control of local markets and trade routes. This “war economy” thrives amid weak state presence and collapsed governance, providing precarious livelihoods for unemployed and disillusioned youth (Zenn, 2021). The theory also highlights how political elites may sustain violence for personal or electoral gain. In Nigeria, corruption, impunity, and mismanagement of security funds have made conflict profitable for some political and military actors. Additionally, while humanitarian aid in Borno

provides vital relief, it has also created a parallel economy that encourages rent-seeking, resource diversion, and dependency, weakening local resilience and long-term peacebuilding (Mshelizah et al., 2021).

Methodology

The study adopted a qualitative research approach, relying on secondary data from scholarly articles, academic journals, policy reports, research papers and publications from international organisations to analyse the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on human security in Nigeria, with particular emphasis on Borno State. A systematic literature review is conducted to examine existing studies, highlighting key findings, gaps and areas needing further investigation. The paper critically engaged with secondary sources to highlight key themes, gaps and emerging perspectives in Boko Haram studies. The study also critiques existing literature emphasising the need for empirical studies to provide a clearer, firsthand account of the situation.

The Implications of the Study for Human Security In Borno State

Impact on Personal and Community Security

1. ***General Atmosphere of Fear and Restricted Movement:*** Usman and Garba (2021), in their study "The Psychological Impact of Insecurity in Conflict-Affected Regions" conducted surveys in Maiduguri and IDP camps. Their findings show that the insurgency has created an environment of fear, where civilians constantly worry about attacks, abductions, and bombings. Many people avoid traveling between towns, limiting economic activities and social interactions. The study found that curfews, military checkpoints and restricted movement have also contributed to the loss of personal freedoms. The authors recommended community-based policing, trust-building between civilians and security forces
2. ***Increased Fatalities and Violent Attacks:*** Adebayo and Yusuf (2021), in "Trends in Fatalities and Violent Attacks in Boko Haram-Affected Areas," analyzed security and mortality data from 2009 to 2020 and found that Boko Haram was responsible for over 35,000 deaths in Borno State. Major attacks occurred in Maiduguri, Baga and Bama, primarily through suicide bombings, mass shootings and village raids. The authors note the severe psychological toll on survivors and

recommended improved early warning systems and stronger military presence.

3. ***Kidnappings and Forced Recruitment:*** Ali and Ibrahim (2020), in their study "Boko Haram's Kidnapping Strategy and Its Impact on Personal Security" conducted interviews with former captives and security officials. Their findings reveal that Boko Haram has systematically used abductions as a terror tactic, with over 10,000 people kidnapped since the insurgency began. The 2014 Chibok schoolgirls abduction remains the most infamous case, but similar incidents have occurred in Gamboru Ngala and Kukawa. Many abductees are forced into labor, sexual slavery or indoctrination. The study recommended strengthening border security, enhancing intelligence operations, and providing rehabilitation programs for rescued victims.
4. ***Gender-Based Violence and Exploitation:*** Okonkwo and Suleiman (2024), in their study "Conflict, Gender-Based Violence, and the Boko Haram Insurgency," analysed humanitarian reports and found that Boko Haram frequently targets women and girls through sexual violence, forced marriages and exploitation. Many survivors face stigmatization and community rejection, while female IDPs remain highly vulnerable to abuse by insurgents, security forces and aid workers. The authors call for enhanced psychological support, stronger legal protections and community sensitization to address gender-based violence and survivor stigma.
5. ***Disruption of Social Structures:*** Adebayo and Yusuf (2021), in their study "Forced Displacement and Community Disintegration in Borno State," found that over 2.1 million people have been displaced in Borno, with major IDP camps in Maiduguri, Bama, and Monguno. Displacement has fractured community bonds, weakened traditional leadership, and eroded social norms, heightening tensions between host communities and IDPs. The authors advocated for reintegration programs, land resettlement policies and strengthened local governance to rebuild social cohesion.
6. ***Mass Displacement and Humanitarian Crisis:*** Olajide and Nwosu (2020), in their study "Forced Displacement and Human Security in Borno State: An Analysis of Boko Haram Activities," employed demographic data analysis and interviews with internally displaced persons (IDPs). They found that over 2 million people had been

displaced by Boko Haram's attacks, with most seeking refuge in IDP camps in Maiduguri, Monguno, and Bama. The study highlighted overcrowding, poor sanitation and inadequate food supply in the camps, drawing on reports from the International Organization for Migration (IOM).

Effects on Health and environmental security

1. ***Healthcare disruption:*** Adeyemi and Hassan (2021), in their study on Boko Haram's impact on healthcare in Borno State, used a qualitative case study approach with health reports and interviews. They found that attacks led to the closure of over 40% of healthcare facilities, especially in rural areas, and that displacement increased pressure on urban health services. They recommended enhanced security for health workers, mobile medical outreach to IDP camps and reconstruction of destroyed facilities.
2. ***Social and Psychological Effects:*** Adebayo and Yusuf (2021), in their study "Boko Haram Insurgency and Social Disintegration in Borno State," found that the insurgency has fractured social bonds, displaced over two million people and weakened traditional leadership structures in communities such as Gwoza, Bama and Dikwa. Survivors often struggle with loss of identity and community support, while abducted women and children face stigmatisation upon return. The authors recommended reconciliation and peacebuilding programs to rebuild social cohesion. Futhermore, Bello and Ali (2020), in "Psychological Effects of Boko Haram Insurgency on Victims and Survivors," reported that over 60% of respondents exhibited PTSD, depression and anxiety symptoms. .
3. ***Deforestation and Land Degradation:*** Adamu and Bello (2021), in their study "Environmental Consequences of Boko Haram Insurgency in Borno State: A Satellite Imagery Analysis," used remote sensing to assess forest loss and soil degradation in conflict-affected areas. They found that between 2009 and 2020, Borno lost over 35% of its forest cover, especially around Sambisa Forest, Gwoza and Konduga, where Boko Haram operates from forest hideouts. The insurgents' involvement in illegal logging and charcoal production has accelerated deforestation, leading to soil erosion and declining agricultural yields, thereby worsening food insecurity. The authors recommended reforestation and

stricter regulation of forest resources to curb further environmental damage.

Economic Instability and Loss of Livelihoods:

Ali and Ibrahim (2020), in their study "The Impact of Boko Haram Insurgency on Rural Livelihoods in Borno State" conducted surveys in affected villages and found that Boko Haram attacks have decimated farming, fishing, and trade the primary sources of income for rural communities. The study notes that 70% of farmers abandoned their lands due to insecurity, leading to food shortages. The destruction of market centers in towns like Gwoza, Damboa and Kukawa further collapsed local economies. The authors recommended livelihood recovery programs, microfinance support for displaced entrepreneurs, and security backed agricultural initiatives to rebuild economic stability.

Impact on Agriculture and Food Security

Abdullahi, Musa and Ibrahim (2022), in their study "The Impact of Boko Haram Insurgency on Agricultural Productivity in Northeast Nigeria," used a mixed-methods approach combining surveys of 250 farmers with secondary data analysis. Their findings revealed a 60% decline in agricultural output between 2010 and 2020 due to Boko Haram attacks. Fear and displacement forced many farmers to abandon their lands, causing food shortages and inflation. Displaced farmers in IDP camps also lacked access to tools and inputs, worsening food insecurity. The authors recommended enhanced rural security to enable farmers' safe return and agricultural recovery.

Ijirshar (2020), in the study "Livestock Farming and Boko Haram Insurgency in Borno State," examined how the conflict affected livestock production through field visits and interviews with pastoralists and veterinary officials in Monguno, Konduga, and Damboa. The findings revealed frequent cattle raids by insurgents, forcing herders to flee or sell animals at low prices, leading to a sharp decline in meat and dairy supply and worsening food insecurity. The study recommended livestock restocking programs and the creation of secure grazing zones to support affected pastoralists.

Political and Governance Challenges

Governance and State Legitimacy: Adebayo and Yusuf (2021), in their study “Boko Haram Insurgency and the Crisis of Governance in Borno State,” found that the insurgency severely weakened state authority, especially in rural areas once controlled by Boko Haram, such as Bama, Gwoza, and Dikwa. The collapse of state institutions and failure to deliver basic services eroded public trust and created a governance vacuum. The authors recommended strengthening grassroots governance and improving coordination between federal, state and local authorities to restore legitimacy.

Impact on Electoral Processes and Political Participation: Ali and Ibrahim (2020), in their study “Insurgency and Electoral Violence in North-East Nigeria,” analyzed election reports and voter surveys in Borno State. They found that Boko Haram’s threats and attacks sharply reduced voter turnout during the 2015 and 2019 elections, as many polling stations in conflict areas remained closed and thousands of IDPs could not vote. The authors argue that fear and displacement undermined political participation and election credibility. They recommended alternative voting mechanisms, such as electronic and IDP voting systems, to improve participation.

Disruption of Education

Akpan and Ering (2023), in their study “Boko Haram Insurgency and the Right to Education in Northern Nigeria: Implications for National Development,” examined how Boko Haram’s violence has undermined children’s access to education. They found that persistent attacks and insecurity caused widespread school closures and reduced enrolment, threatening human capital development. Citing UNICEF (2020), the authors noted that over 3,600 schools were closed, affecting more than 1.2 million children. They emphasized the need for urgent government action to protect schools and uphold the right to education, highlighting that continued disruption perpetuates poverty and vulnerability.

Bukar and Ali (2023), in their study “Boko Haram and the Crisis in Education in Borno State,” assessed school attendance, destruction of infrastructure and teacher displacement. Using UNICEF data, they found that over 1,400 schools had been destroyed and more than 1,000 teachers killed or displaced since the start of the insurgency. The 2014 Chibok schoolgirls abduction, in which 276 girls were kidnapped, was highlighted

as a pivotal event escalating fears about school safety. The authors recommended enhancing security in schools.

Destruction of Infrastructure and Public Services

Okonkwo and (2022), in their study "Infrastructure Destruction and Its Impact on Development in Borno State" analyzed government damage assessment reports and found that over 60% of public infrastructure in Borno has been damaged or destroyed. The study cites the 2015 Baga Massacre, where Boko Haram burned down entire villages, as well as attacks on major towns like Maiduguri, Konduga and Damboa, where government buildings and bridges were destroyed. Roads linking rural communities to urban centers have been severely damaged, restricting access to markets, healthcare and humanitarian aid.

Gaps and Emerging Perspectives from the Literature Reviewed

During the review of the existing literature on the Boko Haram insurgency and its impact on human security in Borno State, it became clear that while much has been written on the topic, significant issues remain. One notable issue is that several scholars tend to make blanket statements about the situation without sufficiently backing them up with concrete data from the field. For example, many studies provided broad generalisations about the impact of the insurgency on economic stability, education and displacement, but they often lacked detailed facts and figures on the ground evidences that would give a clearer picture of the true situation. This tendency to rely on secondary data or broad assumptions limited the depth of understanding necessary information to address the complex realities in Borno State. Furthermore, some of the studies reviewed do not involve field research, instead drawing conclusions based solely on existing reports. This raises questions about the accuracy and reliability of the findings, as they may not fully captured the lived experiences of people directly affected by the insurgency. It is crucial for any research on such a volatile and evolving issue to involve fieldwork, where empirical data can be gathered directly from affected communities. Without this, there is a risk of overlooking or misinterpreting critical aspects of the human security crisis.

Okoli & Lenshie (2022) also contributed to an ongoing debate over the effectiveness of military versus non-military interventions. While some scholars argued that, military force is necessary to dismantle Boko Haram

operational capacity, others stressed that heavy handed tactics have worsened grievances, pushing more people toward radicalisation (Okoli & Lenshie, 2022). Humanitarian and development focused approaches, such as education, economic empowerment and de-radicalisation programmes have gained traction in recent years, but there is still no clear consensus on the best strategy for long-term stability.

One of the key gaps in the existing literature on Boko Haram literature is the under-representation of grassroots and community narratives. Much of the research focused on high level security responses, political decisions and military strategies, while the voices of those directly affected local communities, displaced persons and survivors are often missing. Many studies relied on secondary data without engaging directly with those on the ground, leaving a significant gap in understanding how the insurgency has reshaped daily life in Borno State.

Economic recovery remains understudied. While existing research highlights the destruction of businesses, agriculture, and trade, little is known about how communities are rebuilding and adapting. Further studies should assess the effectiveness of government and NGO efforts in restoring livelihoods and their actual impact on affected populations.

There is also limited empirical data on the long-term psychological effects of the insurgency, particularly among children and young people. Reports highlighted cases of post-traumatic stress and depression, but there is a need for deeper research into how years of exposure to violence and displacement have shaped the mindset and future prospects of the younger generation. Without this, interventions may fail to address the root causes of radicalisation and trauma.

Lastly, there is a noticeable gap in assessing the role of traditional and religious leaders in peacebuilding efforts. Boko Haram's ideology thrives on distorting religious beliefs, yet studies rarely explore how local leaders and clerics could counter radical narratives and help re-integrate former insurgents into society.

Therefore, there is a need to bridge these gaps by conducting field research to gather real, first-hand accounts from the people directly affected. Through engaging with displaced persons, local leaders, security operatives and survivors, a more grounded, accurate understanding of the human security crisis in Borno will be provided. This approach will greatly contribute to knowledge as well as bring fresh insights that are essential for

creating better policies and interventions to support those most affected by the insurgency.

Findings

The study found that the Boko Haram insurgency has severely undermined human security in Borno State, particularly in Maiduguri, Bama and Gwoza. Personal security remains threatened by persistent violence, abductions and forced displacement. Many communities have been uprooted, with residents living in overcrowded and insecure IDP camps. Livelihoods have collapsed due to restricted access to farmland, destroyed markets, and disrupted trade routes. Economic activities such as farming and small-scale trading have declined sharply, worsening poverty and food insecurity. Healthcare access has deteriorated as insurgents have targeted hospitals and displaced medical personnel. IDP populations faced growing health risks, including malnutrition and disease outbreaks, with limited medical support. The education sector has been deeply affected. Schools have been destroyed or shut down, teachers displaced and thousands of children denied access to learning. This disruption threatens long-term development and stability. Political and governance systems have been weakened in many affected areas of the state. Government institutions have lost presence in insurgent-held zones, eroding public trust and limiting state capacity. Infrastructure - including roads, bridges and public buildings have been destroyed, hindering both humanitarian aid and reconstruction efforts.

Conclusion

The Boko Haram insurgency has severely impacted destroyed human security in Borno, causing violence, displacement, economic collapse, and psychological trauma. While military efforts have weakened the group, the effects on education, livelihoods, and mental health remain profound. Despite extensive research, gaps persist in understanding how survivors rebuilt their lives and how children affected by the conflict will re-integrate. Bridging the gap between academic research and policy implementation is crucial to ensuring that findings translate into practical solutions. A human security centered approach in addressing Boko Haram is essential, focusing not just on military action but also on protecting individuals and communities from economic, social and psychological harm. Lasting recovery requires more than security measures; it demands investment in

education, economic stability and psychological support. Real progress will only come when those affected can move beyond survival and start rebuilding their lives with hope and dignity.

A key limitation of this study is its reliance on secondary sources, which may not fully reflect the lived experiences or changing realities in affected communities. Field-based research engaging directly with victims, displaced persons and local institutions would yield deeper insights into the human aspects of the crisis.

Further research should examine long-term recovery, psychosocial rehabilitation, and community resilience in post-insurgency reconstruction. It should also explore gendered impacts and assess the effectiveness of government and NGO interventions in restoring human security.

Overall, bridging the gap between academic research and policy implementation remains crucial to ensuring that insights translate into tangible improvements in people's lives. A human security-centered approach beyond mere military solutions is essential, emphasizing protection, empowerment, and social rebuilding. Lasting peace and recovery in Borno will require sustained investment in education, economic revitalization, and psychological support so that those affected can move beyond survival toward rebuilding their lives with hope and dignity.

Recommendations

The recommendations of the study are stated below:

1. ***Boost Economic Recovery and Livelihood Support:*** Providing job opportunities, skills training and financial support for small businesses is crucial for economic stability. Agricultural recovery programmes should also be prioritised, as farming communities in Borno have been devastated by the insurgency.
2. ***Strengthen Security and Intelligence Efforts:*** While military action has weakened Boko Haram, community policing, intelligence gathering and early warning mechanism must be improved to prevent further attacks. The government should also work with local leaders to counter extremist narratives and prevent recruitment into the insurgent group.
4. ***Enhance Humanitarian Aid and Infrastructure Development:*** International organizations and the Nigerian government must work together to improve living conditions in IDP camps, rebuild essential

infrastructure, and ensure access to clean water, healthcare and food security.

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Leadership Programmes and Organisational Performance in Public Administration in Akinyele Local Government, Oyo State Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the *impact of leadership programmes on organisational performance in public administration*, with a focus on Akinyele Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria. Its specific objectives were to assess existing leadership development programmes, evaluate their effects on performance indicators, identify key success factors, and analyse challenges to implementation. The study filled an existing empirical gap in Nigerian public administration literature by linking leadership development with organisational performance, anchored on the *Transformational Leadership Theory*. The research adopted a *descriptive survey research design*. The population comprised 3027 public officials in Akinyele Local Government. Using *Taro Yamane's formula*, a sample size of 110 was drawn through a random purposive sampling technique and 94 questionnaire responses was used for the study. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The regression results showed that *leadership development programmes significantly predicted organisational performance* ($\beta = 0.782$; $R^2 = 0.612$; $p < 0.05$). Findings also revealed strong correlations between leadership competency models and employee satisfaction ($r = 0.694$), and between mentoring programmes and organisational effectiveness ($r = 0.711$). The study concluded that effective leadership development programmes improve organisational performance in local public administration. It recommends that government should institutionalise leadership mentoring, continuous professional development, and performance-based evaluation systems to sustain high organisational performance levels.

Keywords: leadership programmes, organisational performance, public administration, *Akinyele Local Government*

Introduction

Public administration plays a crucial role in government and public service delivery. It encompasses the management and implementation of policies,

programmes, and services that serve the interests of the public (Shafritz, Russell, Borick & Hyde, 2022). Effective public administration is essential for ensuring efficient and transparent governance, promoting public trust, and achieving societal goals. Leadership development programmes have gained significant attention in public administration to enhance organisational performance and drive positive change (Clausen, Demircioglu, & Alsos, 2020). Public administration refers to the activities and processes involved in implementing government policies and programmes (Rosenbloom, Kravchuk, & Clerkin, 2022). It encompasses various functions, such as planning, organising, coordinating, and controlling public resources to achieve public objectives and meet the needs of citizens (Schwarz, Eva, & Newman, 2020).

Leadership plays a critical role in public administration. Influential leaders provide direction, inspire employees, and foster a positive work culture. They are responsible for making important decisions, managing change, and driving organisational performance. Leadership in the public sector requires unique skills and competencies due to the complex nature of public service and the need to balance diverse stakeholder interests (Miao, Newman, Schwarz & Cooper, 2018). Leadership development programmes enhance individuals' leadership skills, knowledge, and abilities. These programmes provide training, mentoring, and experiential learning opportunities to develop leadership competencies and promote effective leadership practices (Schiuma, Schettini, Santarsiero, & Carlucci, 2022).

In the context of public administration, leadership development programmes aim to cultivate capable leaders who can navigate the complexities of the public sector and drive organisational success. Leadership development programmes in public administration refer to structured initiatives aimed at developing leadership capabilities and enhancing the effectiveness of leaders within public organisations (Mone, London, & Mone, 2018). These programmes focus on developing strategic thinking, decision-making, communication, and team-building skills. Leadership is essential in public administration as it influences public organisations' direction, performance, and outcomes. Effective leadership in the public sector involves understanding and addressing societal needs, engaging stakeholders, managing resources efficiently, and promoting ethical behaviour and accountability (Mau, 2019). Leadership development programmes have gained increasing prominence in the public sector due to

the recognition of the importance of capable leaders in driving organisational performance and achieving public objectives. Public organisations invest in leadership development initiatives to attract, retain, and develop talented leaders who can navigate complex challenges and deliver effective public services (Masenya, 2022).

Statement of the Problem

Previous studies have examined the role of leadership development in Nigeria's public sector. For instance, a qualitative multiple case study explored strategies and tools used to measure the effectiveness of LDPs in improving frontline leadership and service delivery in public sector organisations in Owerri, Imo State. The findings highlighted the necessity for senior executives to implement evaluation strategies to enhance leadership and service delivery (Osuagwu, 2022). Another study assessed the role of effective leadership in enhancing organisational performance in Nigeria's public organisations, emphasizing the importance of leadership in achieving organisational goals (Njoku, 2014).

There is limited empirical evidence on the extent to which leadership development programmes influence key performance indicators such as transparency, responsiveness, productivity, and citizen satisfaction in public administration. Additionally, while some programmes may exist, the components that make them successful such as strategic planning, mentorship, continuous assessment, and follow-up are often not clearly defined or systematically implemented. The study also seeks to address the challenges faced in implementing effective leadership development programmes, which may include inadequate funding, lack of political will, poor institutional frameworks, and resistance to change among public officials. Therefore, this study seeks to critically examine the nature, implementation, and impact of leadership development programmes on organisational performance in public administration, using Akinyele Local Government as a case study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This research aims to evaluate leadership programmes and organisational performance in public administration in Akinyele Local Government, Oyo State Nigeria. The specific objectives are:

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1. To identify leadership development programmes in the public administration and their impact on organisational performance.
 2. To evaluate the effect of leadership development programmes on key performance indicators in public administration in Akinyele, Oyo State.
 3. To identify the key components and characteristics of successful leadership development programmes in the public administration sector in Oyo State.
 4. To examine the challenges faced in implementing effective leadership development programmes in the public administration sector in Oyo State.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to public administrators, policymakers, and practitioners in Oyo State. It evaluates the impact of leadership development programmes on organisational performance, offering evidence-based insights for effective policy and decision-making. By addressing the gap in research specific to Oyo State, it contributes valuable knowledge to the field of public administration. The study highlights best practices, identifies challenges in implementing leadership initiatives, and provides strategies for improvement.

Literature Review

Leadership development programmes play a crucial role in enhancing organisational performance, particularly in the public administration sector. Effective leadership fosters employee productivity, satisfaction, and overall institutional efficiency. This conceptual review explores the concept of leadership development and organisational performance, examining key variables related to support leadership growth. It also identifies essential components of successful leadership programmes. By analysing existing literature, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of leadership development effectiveness in public administration (Kouzes, & Posner, 2023).

Leadership Development in Public Administration

Leadership remains one of the most intricate and multifaceted concepts, having attracted considerable scholarly attention over the years, especially within today's rapidly evolving and interconnected global environment.

Despite this extensive exploration, leadership continues to provoke both interest and confusion due to its inherent complexity. As Bennis observes, leadership remains "the most studied and least understood topic of any in the social sciences" and "never have so many laboured so long to say so little" (Silva, 2021). Numerous scholars have proposed varied definitions and theories to explain leadership.

Public administration is a multifaceted concept that can be understood from several perspectives. When viewed as an institution, public administration refers to the formal structures and entities established by government to execute laws, policies, and public programmes (Kouzes, & Posner, 2023). These include ministries, departments, agencies, commissions, and parastatals across federal, state, and local levels. They serve as the government's machinery for managing public affairs and delivering essential services. For instance, the Ministry of Education, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), and local government councils exemplify such institutions of public administration. When regarded as a discipline, public administration constitutes an academic field that examines both the theory and practice of managing public organisations. Drawing upon political science, management, law, sociology, and economics, this discipline explores how governments function and how public policies are developed and implemented (CEML, 2002).

Lastly, when considered as an output, public administration pertains to the services and outcomes produced by government institutions through these administrative processes (Meaklim, & Sims, 2011). These outputs address public needs and contribute to societal welfare, taking the form of both tangible outcomes (such as roads, schools, and healthcare facilities) and intangible results (including policy outcomes, regulations, and social services). For example, public housing schemes, health insurance initiatives, and environmental protection policies exemplify outputs of public administration. In essence, without effective leadership development programmes, optimal functioning of public administration cannot be fully realised (Alimo-Metcalf et al, 2002).

Organisational Performance

Organisational performance refers to the ability of an organisation to achieve its goals and objectives effectively and efficiently. In public administration, organisational performance is often measured by the extent

to which public sector organisations can deliver services that meet the needs and expectations of citizens (Cox III, Buck & Morgan, 2019). A scholar defines organisational performance as a multidimensional construct that includes financial performance, operational performance, and stakeholder satisfaction (Phillips, Thai, & Halim, 2019). In the public sector, organisational performance is not only about achieving financial targets but also about delivering high-quality services, ensuring accountability, and fostering public trust. The importance of organisational performance in public administration cannot be overstated. High-performing public sector organisations are essential for the effective implementation of government policies, the efficient use of public resources, and the achievement of socio-economic development goals (Gallagher & Thordarson, 2018).

Theoretical Review

Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational Leadership Theory, initially introduced by James MacGregor Burns and later expanded by Bernard Bass, emphasises the role of leaders in inspiring and motivating their followers to achieve exceptional outcomes (Ohemeng, Amoako & Obuobisa-Darko, 2018). Transformational leaders are characterised by their ability to create a vision for the future, stimulate intellectual curiosity, and foster an environment of trust and commitment. These leaders engage with their followers on an emotional level, encouraging them to transcend their self-interests for the greater good of the organisation¹⁴. The relevance of Transformational Leadership Theory to leadership development lies in its focus on enhancing leader-follower relationships and fostering a culture of continuous improvement. In the public sector, including Oyo State, transformational leadership can drive significant changes in organisational performance. For example, leaders who embody transformational qualities are likely to inspire public sector employees to embrace innovative approaches and improve service delivery (Kouzes, & Posner, 2023).

Development of the Conceptual Model

Figure 1: Conceptual model for the study
 Source: Authors’ Construct, 2025

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The design enabled the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data from a large and diverse group, facilitating a comprehensive exploration of the relationship between leadership development and performance outcomes. The population comprised 3,027 employees across all staff levels, including senior, middle, and junior staff. A sample of 110 employees was selected using a random purposive sampling technique, Data were collected using a structured questionnaire divided into two sections. Section A gathered demographic data, while Section B, based on a 5-point Likert scale, was aligned with the study’s four objectives. To ensure validity, the questionnaire was built on existing literature and validated scales, and reviewed by experts in leadership and organisational development. For reliability, a pilot study was conducted with 30 staff from Ibadan South-West Local Government. Feedback helped refine the

instrument, and statistical techniques, including Cronbach’s alpha, were used to ensure internal consistency.

The analysis of quantitative data was conducted using Excel and SPSS software to ensure accuracy and efficiency. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages was generated to summarise participants’ demographic characteristics and survey responses.

Data Analysis

Demographic Analysis of Data

The demographic profile of respondents from Akinyele Local Government reveals a diverse and representative administrative workforce. Females slightly outnumber males (50.0% vs. 42.6%), with 2.1% identifying outside the binary and 5.3% undisclosed. Most respondents fall within the 26–45 age range, indicating active mid-career professionals, while others represent junior staff and senior-level personnel. Educationally, 39.2% hold HND or bachelor’s degrees, 30.9% have master’s degrees, and 9.6% possess PhDs, suggesting a highly qualified workforce. In terms of job roles, 34.0% are in middle management, 30.9% at entry level, 21.3% in senior roles, and 10.6% as executives. This diverse composition across age, gender, education, and hierarchy strengthens the study’s reliability in evaluating the impact of leadership development on organisational performance.

Research Question 1: What leadership development programmes exist in the public administration sector, and how do they impact organisational performance?

Table 1: Summary Statistics

	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Leadership development programmes in Oyo State public administration have clearly defined goals and objectives.	19 (20.2%)	65 (69.1%)	5 (5.3%)	3 (3.2%)	2 (2.1%)

The leadership development programmes in Oyo State are effectively aligned with the strategic goals of public administration.	11 (11.7%)	58 (61.7%)	19 (20.2%)	5 (5.3%)	1 (1.1%)
Leadership development programmes have led to noticeable improvements in organisational performance in Oyo State's public sector.	16 (17.0%)	44 (46.8%)	23 (24.5%)	10 (10.6%)	1 (1.1%)
Sufficient support and resources have been allocated to Oyo State's public administration's leadership development programmes.	16 (17.0%)	38 (40.4%)	27 (28.7%)	9 (9.6%)	4 (4.3%)
Public sector leaders in Oyo State actively participate in and benefit from leadership development programmes.	14 (14.9%)	50 (53.2%)	19 (20.2%)	8 (8.5%)	3 (3.2%)

The effectiveness of leadership development programmes in Oyo State is regularly evaluated to ensure continuous improvement.

14	40	28	9	3
(14.9%)	(42.6%)	(29.8%)	(9.6%)	(3.2%)

Source: Authors' Construct, 2025

The data shows a generally positive perception of leadership development programmes in Oyo State's public administration. Most respondents (89.3%) believe the programmes have clear goals, and 73.4% agree they align with strategic objectives. While 63.8% acknowledged improvements in organisational performance, 24.5% were undecided. Regarding resources, 57.4% agreed they were adequate, but 28.7% remained uncertain, highlighting some concern. Leadership participation was seen as high (68.1%), though some gaps may exist. Evaluation of these programmes received moderate support, with 57.5% agreeing they are regularly assessed, but nearly 30% were unsure. Overall, respondents view the programmes as structured and impactful, but areas like resource allocation and continuous evaluation need enhancement to ensure long-term effectiveness in the public sector.

Research Question 2: How do leadership development programmes affect key performance indicators such as employee productivity, employee satisfaction, and organisational effectiveness in the public administration sector?

Table 2: Summary Statistics

	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Leadership development programmes have significantly increased employee productivity in Oyo State's public administration.	17 (18.1%)	48 (51.1%)	21 (22.3%)	5 (5.3%)	3 (3.2%)
Leadership development programmes in the Oyo State public sector have significantly improved employee satisfaction.	15 (16.0%)	37 (39.4%)	32 (34.0%)	8 (8.5%)	2 (2.1%)
Organisational effectiveness in Oyo State's public administration has improved due to the implementation of leadership development programmes.	14 (14.9%)	41 (43.6%)	27 (28.7%)	9 (9.6%)	3 (3.2%)

Leadership development programmes are directly linked to better management of crucial Oyo State public sector performance indicators.	15 (16.0%)	37 (39.4%)	22 (23.4%)	16 (17.0%)	4 (4.3%)
Increased employee engagement and morale can be attributed to the leadership development initiatives in Oyo State's public administration.	11 (11.7%)	39 (41.5%)	29 (30.9%)	10 (10.6%)	5 (5.3%)
The leadership development programmes in Oyo State contribute to improved decision-making processes within public administration.	16 (17.0%)	30 (31.9%)	31 (33.0%)	13 (13.8%)	4 (4.3%)

Source: Authors' Construct, 2025

The findings indicate that leadership development programmes in Oyo State's public administration are perceived to positively impact key performance indicators. A majority of respondents agreed the programmes

enhance employee productivity (69.2%) and satisfaction (55.4%), though many remained undecided, indicating room for improved visibility and communication of outcomes. Similarly, 58.5% affirmed improved organisational effectiveness, while 29% were uncertain. Views on alignment with performance indicators were mixed, with 55.4% in agreement but over 21% expressing doubt. Regarding employee engagement and decision-making, responses were moderately positive but showed notable levels of neutrality. Overall, while leadership development efforts are generally viewed as beneficial, inconsistencies in implementation and impact awareness highlight the need for stronger evaluation systems and better alignment with measurable outcomes.

Research Question 3: What are the key components and characteristics of successful leadership development programmes in the public administration sector?

Table 3: Summary Statistics

	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Successful leadership development programmes in Oyo State include regular and comprehensive training sessions.	14 (14.9%)	44 (46.8%)	24 (25.5%)	8 (8.5%)	4 (4.3%)
Effective mentorship and coaching are integral to successful leadership development	16 (17.0%)	38 (40.4%)	28 (29.8%)	8 (8.5%)	4 (4.3%)

programmes in
Oyo State.

Leadership
development
programmes in
Oyo State utilise
well-defined
competency
models to guide
development
efforts.

15 (16.0%)	39 (41.5%)	22 (23.4%)	18 (19.1%)	0 (0.0%)
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Continuous
professional
development is a
crucial feature
of successful
leadership
development
programmes in
Oyo State.

16 (17.0%)	38 (40.4%)	24 (25.5%)	14 (14.9%)	2 (2.1%)
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Performance
evaluation and
feedback
mechanisms are
effectively
incorporated
into leadership
development
programmes in
Oyo State.

16 (17.0%)	32 (34.0%)	29 (30.9%)	12 (12.8%)	5 (5.3%)
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E-learning and digital tools are widely used in leadership development programmes in Oyo State to enhance learning outcomes.

16	30	23	19	6
(17.0%)	(31.9%)	(24.5%)	(20.2%)	(6.4%)

Source: Authors' Construct, 2025

The data highlights key features of effective leadership development programmes in Oyo State's public administration. Most respondents affirmed that regular training (61.7%), mentorship (57.4%), and competency models (57.5%) are essential components of successful programmes. While support for these features is strong, a significant number remained neutral, indicating inconsistent implementation or awareness across departments. Continuous professional development was endorsed by 57.4%, though 42.5% expressed uncertainty or disagreement, suggesting gaps in delivery. Performance feedback mechanisms received moderate support (51%), with high neutrality reflecting limited visibility or transparency. Views on e-learning tools were mixed, with only 48.9% in agreement and 26.6% in disagreement, pointing to challenges in digital integration. Overall, respondents emphasised structured training and mentoring as critical for effective leadership development.

Research Question 4: What challenges and barriers are encountered in implementing effective leadership development programmes in the public administration sector?

Table 4: Summary Statistics

	LEVEL OF AGREEMENT				
	SA	A	U	D	SD
Bureaucratic inefficiencies are a significant challenge in implementing leadership development programmes in Oyo State’s public administration.	13 (13.8%)	48 (51.1%)	25 (26.6%)	5 (5.3%)	3 (3.2%)
Limited financial resources hinder the effective implementation of leadership development programmes in Oyo State.	17 (18.1%)	47 (50.0%)	16 (17.0%)	13 (13.8%)	1 (1.1%)
Corruption and governance issues negatively impact the success of leadership development initiatives in Oyo State.	21 (22.3%)	35 (37.2%)	24 (25.5%)	13 (13.8%)	1 (1.1%)

There is a lack of adequate infrastructure and facilities to support leadership development programmes in Oyo State.	17 (18.1%)	45 (47.9%)	14 (14.9%)	16 (17.0%)	2 (2.1%)
Resistance to change within public administration poses significant barriers to implementing leadership development programmes in Oyo State.	25 (26.6%)	32 (34.0%)	22 (23.4%)	11 (11.7%)	4 (4.3%)
Insufficient top management support limits leadership development programmes' effectiveness in Oyo State's public sector.	21 (22.3%)	44 (46.8%)	15 (16.0%)	10 (10.6%)	4 (4.3%)

Source: Authors' Construct, 2025

The study reveals that public administrators in Oyo State widely recognise several institutional and systemic barriers hindering effective leadership development. Bureaucratic inefficiencies were cited by 64.9% as major obstacles, reflecting frustrations with red tape and procedural delays. Financial constraints topped the list, with 68.1% agreeing that insufficient funding limits programme quality and reach. Corruption and poor

governance were also noted by 59.5%, highlighting ethical issues like nepotism and fund mismanagement. Infrastructure inadequacies were identified by 66.0%, suggesting disparities in access to training resources. Resistance to organisational change (60.6%) and lack of executive support (69.1%) were seen as key barriers to implementation and sustainability. These findings emphasise the urgent need for reform and strategic investment to overcome systemic challenges.

Discussion of Findings

The first research question examined the availability and structure of leadership development programmes in the public administration sector, as well as their effect on organisational performance. Most respondents confirmed that such programmes in Oyo State are well-structured, have clear goals, and align with the strategic objectives of public organisations. Prior research supports this and emphasises the value of integrating leadership development into governance structures to promote accountability, service quality, and institutional efficiency (Olowu, 2024). Studies have shown that public organisations with goal-oriented leadership training experience enhanced administrative coordination and improved service delivery (Kouzes, & Posner, 2023).

A large portion of respondents indicated that participation in these programmes improved their engagement, task clarity, and motivation. These outcomes are consistent with studies demonstrating that investment in leadership training results in improved work output, increased morale, and better alignment with organisational objectives (Okafor, 2023). This aligns with the human capital theory, which posits that investment in employee development yields tangible returns in performance. Research has also shown that leadership training positively impacts employee retention, workplace collaboration, and innovation (Day, 2000). Enhanced employee engagement is known to be a strong predictor of organisational success, especially in the public sector, where bureaucratic inertia can be a limiting factor (Pitts, Hicklin, Hawes, & Melton, 2010).

The data also revealed a positive relationship between leadership training and decision-making efficiency, though some respondents were neutral on this point. Prior findings suggest that structured leadership programmes improve analytical capacity and leadership judgment, especially when embedded with cognitive and strategic development modules (Creta &

Gross, 2020). However, as other studies have noted, the effectiveness of such programmes may vary across departments depending on leadership commitment, visibility, and institutional support (Ujuagu, 2020).

Respondents highlighted regular training, mentorship, use of competency frameworks, continuous professional development (CPD), performance feedback, and digital learning tools as key components. These findings align with research emphasising that structured, ongoing training contributes to long-term leadership capacity (Osei, 2020). Mentorship and coaching were also seen as crucial components, echoing previous studies which found that guided learning improves leadership adaptability and emotional intelligence in managerial roles. Competency-based models are widely recognised for their utility in benchmarking leadership skills and tracking growth over time (Okorie & Onwe, 2016).

Respondents identified several obstacles, including bureaucratic inefficiencies, limited funding, corruption, lack of infrastructure, resistance to change, and insufficient executive support. These issues reflect long-standing challenges in public sector reform and training implementation. Bureaucracy was recognised as a major constraint, consistent with prior findings that procedural bottlenecks often stifle innovation and delay programme execution¹⁰. Financial limitations were also widely cited, and research confirms that many local governments struggle with consistent budget allocations for capacity-building programmes (Kosack & Fung, 2014).

Conclusion

The study concludes that leadership development initiatives play a vital role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of public sector administration. In Akinyele Local Government, well-structured leadership programmes have significantly contributed to the achievement of strategic goals and improved operational performance. These programmes are not only clearly defined but are also closely aligned with the broader objectives of public administration, resulting in measurable improvements in employee productivity, job satisfaction, morale, decision-making, and overall organisational effectiveness. Bureaucratic bottlenecks, inadequate funding, governance issues such as corruption, infrastructural deficiencies, managerial resistance to change, and lack of top-level support pose significant obstacles to successful implementation. Addressing these issues

will not only enhance the effectiveness of leadership programmes but also contribute to the long-term success of public administration in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

1. Leadership development should be formally integrated into the strategic framework of public administration in Akinyele Local Government.
2. The study recommends that leadership programmes be subject to periodic assessment using performance indicators such as employee productivity, decision-making quality, and citizen satisfaction.
3. The government should commit more financial and logistical resources to the planning and implementation of leadership development programmes.

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